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DEVELOPMENT. IMPACT OF TOURISM IN THIS PROCESS”**

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ECONOMICS

The Impact of Monetary Policy on Tourism Sector. The Case of Albania

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Abstract

Albania has a great tourist potential. This is due to the geographical position, high natural values, and special historical and cultural aspects. For this reason, the development of tourism is an important factor for the country's economic development. The impact that tourism development has on the country economy is widely analyzed in the tourism literature. However, the impact of the monetary policy of Bank of Albania on the development of tourism in our country has hardly been addressed in the tourism literature. The purpose of this work is precisely to highlight the way and the degree of influence of the monetary policy of Bank of Albania in the development of tourism, for the period 2008-2023. After the crisis of 2008, Bank of Albania changed the direction of the monetary policy by reducing the interest rate, so it followed an expansionary monetary policy with the aim of influencing the economic growth of the country. In 2022, Bank of Albania increases the interest rate, so it follows a restrictive monetary policy with the aim of reducing the inflation rate. In this paper, will be presented the impact of policy monetary of Bank of Albania on the development of tourism. The method that will be used is the statistical data analysis of relevant institutions for the period 2008-2023, mainly of Bank of Albania, INSTAT and General Directorate of Taxes

Keywords: Tourism, Monetary policy, Interest rate.

The Impact of Monetary and Fiscal Policies on Tourism

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Abstract

Monetary policies, like interest rate adjustments, affect consumer spending and investment, influencing tourism demand. Fiscal policies, such as tax changes or government spending, can impact infrastructure development and tourism-related services. Both policies shape the economic environment, affecting tourists' decisions and industry growth. The main aim of this work is to analyze the impact of tourism on the economy but, more importantly, how the two key macroeconomic policies in the country, monetary and fiscal policies can stimulate tourism and consequently impact the economic development of the country, and furthermore help in economic restructuring for sustainable development. In this sense, the analysis will initially concentrate on the practical importance and benefits that this industry has brought to the country's development, mainly in GDP and employment, but not only. It will explore the steps taken by fiscal policies and whether they have yielded results in terms of the efficiency of this sector. In addition, in the end, the impact of monetary policy will be assessed through Vector Autoregressive Analysis (VAR), for the period 2008Q1-2023Q2, examining the impulse response functions (IRF) and variance decomposition for the three transmission channels of monetary policy in the economy: interest rate channel, inflation, and exchange rate. The study concludes that fiscal policy has been effective in providing stimuli through its fiscal and administrative policies in the tourism sector however, there are opportunities to work together with the tourism organizations to assess and rejuvenate different tourism lines, considering the concept of a 'life cycle', while monetary policy reaffirms its stability, yet with more room to contribute to the tourism sector. Therefore, the main recommendation is that monetary policy can further engage in supporting this sector, aligning with fiscal policy to optimize/maximize the economic benefits of tourism, among other considerations. This paper suggests that two policies cannot have an immediate impact with short-term policies, especially in the specific case of tourism, due to the risk presented by monetary policy and tourism. Therefore, in the assessment of this work, these two policies should already establish structural policies supporting the tourism industry.

Keywords: Monetary policy; Fiscal policy; Tourism development; Economic Restructuring for Sustainable Development, VAR.

JEL classification: E4, E6, C31.

1. Introduction

In the last 15 years, tourism in Albania has experienced continuous growth. In 2019, which is recognized as the year when the tourism sector experienced a significant development boom, the share of this sector's contribution to GDP was 20.5%. Meanwhile, in 2022, its total contribution is estimated to be approximately 25% of the GDP. These figures not only indicate the growth this sector has undergone but also highlight its vital importance to our country's GDP.

The main aim of this work is to present a clear picture not only from the perspective of the impact of tourism on the economy but, more importantly, how the two key macroeconomic policies in the country, monetary and fiscal policies - which have the decision-making authority

to formulate policies in favor of the overall well-being of the economy and society - can stimulate tourism and consequently impact the economic development of the country.

In the coming days, the issue is not merely about figures, statistics, or GDP, or to be more specific it's not all about GDP! The battle many developed nations are undertaking is for societal well-being. In this context, we endeavor to establish an approach towards structuring the economy for sustainable development, particularly in analyzing policy spaces and all structures enabling the functioning of this industry. The focus extends beyond just boosting GDP to enhancing societal welfare. The critical analysis, grounded in macroeconomics and econometrics, aims to address:

- 1) The impact of monetary and fiscal policies on the development of the tourism sector.
- 2) Identification of the more effective policy between the two.
- 3) Exploration of intervention areas for improvement across economic structures and sectors.
- 4) Assessment of the current state and typologies of tourism, identifying their needs for maturity.
- 5) Evaluation of Albania's readiness to change its economic structure.

The goal is to delve into these aspects and provide insights into the transformative potential for a sustainable future.

Following Camilleri, M. A. (2018) logic and advancing its theoretical treatment, the demand curve in tourism, from a microeconomic perspective, would be conceptualized in two divisions, both considering the income targets of visitors. According to data from INSTAT, the Ministry of Finance and Economy, and other institutions, Albania attracts a diverse range of tourists, with the majority coming from Europe and neighboring countries. Taking this into account, all tourism structures should create and operate in a demand curve that prioritizes the sector's benefits, while also maximizing the tourists' utility.

Returning to the two divisions, all of this in microeconomic conceptualization can be interpreted in the context of Giffen and Veblen goods. Both of these share a common phrase that offers a solution, well-known in international trade, especially when discussing open, developing, and competitive economies like Albania: "Creating relative and absolute advantages." How will these advantages be created? This then involves precisely restructuring and the two macroeconomic policies, monetary and fiscal, whose authorities are the Central Bank and the government, respectively. It is within the authority of these institutions to prepare, assess, and implement effective policies and strategies to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of this sector so that it generates even more positive contributions to the country's economy.

Figure 1: Giffen Good

Source: The concept of the demand curve for tourism from a microeconomic perspective, presented by the author

This is the concept of Giffen goods, which if we parallelize with what the development and growth of the tourism sector require, would be conceptualized as prestigious normal goods. Demand for Giffen goods rises when the price rises and falls when the price falls. In econometrics, this is known as an upward-sloping demand curve, which goes contrary to the fundamental laws of demand.

Figure 2: Veblen good's demand curve

Source: V. Thorstein (1899). Authors' adaption

In the above figure, Veblen's concept of goods has been presented in the context of the tourism sector. This theory represents a category of products for which demand increases with the rise in price, otherwise known as Veblen goods or luxury products. In this context, a remodeling of this theory has been done to fit the tourism industry. In both cases, it would be the optimal solution for this sector to operate against the laws of demand, as microeconomic theory suggests that for these product groups, consumers are indifferent. They will pay the price set,

regardless of the amount. How is this done? By creating relative and absolute advantages. In other words, offering what others do not!

2. Economic treatment

As stated at the beginning of the paper, this work does not merely aim at data analysis and speaking solely in numbers but rather seeks to go beyond that, to understand and evaluate the possibilities and spaces that economic agents have to act and create added value. With this in mind, fiscal and monetary policies, along with all the entities directly and indirectly involved in this industry, can leverage their opportunities and capacities to establish a beneficial and sustainable sector for society as a whole. To return to economic analysis, in fact, one of the ways to achieve a sustainable economic restructuring for development is through macroeconomics policies. That being said, their coordination is essential.

Figure 3: Fiscal and monetary cooperation
 Source: Blinder. A (1982)

As seen the graph contains the component of fiscal policy, which is the gap between actual and potential output ($y-y^*$), which through Okun's law serves as a proxy for unemployment. On the other hand, there is also the component of monetary policy, which is inflation through the short-term Phillips curve, as well as the weight of investments in GNP (I/Y). In this context, there are two instruments: fiscal and monetary policies. Assuming that the origin point would be global optimality, then at point A - which implies the situation where it is predicted the economy would go if none of the policies change - real output will be very high, and the weight of investments very low. Vectors F and M, emerging from point A, show the effect on the economy as a result of the change in fiscal and monetary instruments, respectively. Thus, by moving in line with what was analyzed in the IS-LM model, an expansive fiscal and monetary policy would lead to an output increase. However, monetary expansion would increase investments (as shown in the above model), while fiscal expansion would decrease them. The line from A to O shows that under conditions of full coordination, global optimum would be achieved. In other words, lines AB and BO reflect a different behavior of policies, specifically a restrictive fiscal policy that takes the economy from A to B and an expansive monetary policy that takes the economy from B to O, thus achieving overall welfare. In the case of a floating

exchange rate regime, monetary policy is usually more effective than fiscal policy in stimulating the economy (Gordon, 2014).

One of the ways in which monetary policy can influence the economy, involving the interest rate, is precisely through financial development, which can directly impact not only economic growth but also the development of the tourism sector. When discussing economic growth, two models come to mind: the Neoclassical growth model and the endogenous growth model.

Let's begin the analysis with the macroeconomic production function $Y = AK + F(K, L)$, which exhibits constant returns to scale and diminishing marginal products of capital and labor in $F(K, L)$.

In terms of per capita, the above equation can be written as:

$$y = Ak + f(k)$$

where A represents the technological process, introducing the concept of endogeneity into the model. The capital intensity k evolves depending on investment activity I , population growth rate n , and the depreciation of the existing capital stock δK according to:

$$\frac{\dot{k}}{k} := \hat{k} = \frac{\dot{K}}{K} - n = \frac{I - \delta K}{K} - n = \frac{I}{K} - (\delta + n)$$

The financial sector determines which portion of savings is channeled into investments, i.e., the accumulation of the economy's capital stock; $\lambda S = \lambda sY = I$. What we know is that only a portion of total savings goes into investment activity, while the remaining part $(1 - \lambda)$ is eliminated in the banking sector.

According to Markus (2003), the financial component in the growth model can be described, for example, by the difference between loan and deposit interest rates. Therefore, a reduction in this difference, e.g., due to increased competition pressure, leads to channeling a growing portion of savings into investment.

$$\hat{k} = \frac{\lambda s Y}{K} - (\delta + n) = \lambda s (A + f(k) / k) - (\delta + n)$$

$$\hat{k} = \underbrace{[\lambda s A - (n + \delta)]}_{\text{long-term component}} + \underbrace{\lambda s \frac{f(k)}{k}}_{\text{convergence component}}$$

Financial markets impact both the long-term component of income and the transitory component of growth. The level of λ is crucially determined by the development level of the financial services sector. In sustainable growth, all terms increase uniformly. In other words, k can be written as y . This means that a shift in the λ parameter, directing more savings into investments, would increase y . Graphically, this is illustrated below:

Figure 4: The impact of financial development on economic growth
 Source: Paganos (1993)

Thus, this is just one of the channels and ways in which the monetary authority can find room to positively influence the development of the tourism sector through the proper assessment and implementation of policies.

The biggest challenge that accompanies the tourism sector, and the question posed in this case, revolves around how sustainable and reliable this sector is. In fact, to address this question, Butler precisely formulated the theory of the “lifecycle”.

Figure 5: The Concept of a Tourist Area Cycle of Evolution
 Source: Butler, R. W. (1980)

Butler's Lifecycle Theory is a model developed to explain how tourist destinations go through changes over time. This theory comprises five main phases: (1) exploration, (2) development, (3) consolidation, (4) crisis, and (5) rejuvenation or re-creation.

Exploration: In this phase, a tourist destination starts attracting the attention of initial visitors and creates a positive image.

Development: The number of tourists increases, and tourist infrastructure is developed to cope with the growing demand.

Consolidation: At this stage, the tourist destination reaches its peak with a high number of tourists and well-developed infrastructure.

Crisis: A situation occurs where the destination faces challenges and issues, including a decline in tourists, infrastructure problems, or negative events.

Rejuvenation or Recreation: The destination works to improve the situation, change its image, and regain tourist interest.

3. Methodology

The focus of this paper is not only on the statistical and econometric analysis to assess the impact of the tourism sector on the Albanian economy or the evaluation of the impact of macroeconomic policies, but also on theoretical treatment from the perspective of strategies, spaces, and challenges posed by this sector in our country. In this sense, the analysis will initially concentrate on the practical importance and benefits that this industry has brought to the country's development, mainly in GDP and employment, but not only. It will explore the steps taken by fiscal policies and whether they have yielded results in terms of the efficiency of this sector. Finally, an assessment of the impact of monetary policy will be conducted through VAR analysis, particularly because evaluating the direct impact effect of this policy on tourism is challenging and cannot be done a priori based on data, unlike what can be concluded for fiscal policy. Data is sourced from INSTAT, the Bank of Albania, the Ministry of Tourism and Environment, and other institutions involved in researching this sector.

The econometric analysis has a quarterly basis, covering the period from 2008q1 to 2023Q2. The variables under consideration include tourist income in our country as a proxy for measuring the development of this sector (reported by Bank of Albania), inflation (Instat), exchange rate (Bank of Albania), and the interest rate called Repo from the Central Bank. It is evident that the analysis addresses three of the transmission channels of monetary policy in the economy, specifically the inflation channel, the exchange rate channel, and the interest rate channel, respectively.

Figure 6: Flow chart of research methodology

3.1 Sector background and Fiscal policy evaluation

The development that the tourism sector has undergone in the past decade has been significant, directly impacting GDP and employment. This has led the government to implement a series of measures to transform this sector into a priority for the economy through fiscal and administrative incentives. As seen in the graph below, the number of employed individuals and the contribution to GDP, whether direct or indirect, has been satisfactory.

Figure 7: Contribution of tourism

Source: INSTAT

In 2019, a year considered the peak of tourism in Albania, the sector's total contribution to the economy was 20.5%. However, in 2020, due to the global COVID-19 crisis, there was a decline. Nevertheless, this situation did not persist, and a rising trend resumed after 2020. Tourism in total constitutes around 250'000 jobs in 2022, compared to 244'000 jobs in 2019 before the pandemic.

For the period 2017-2022, it is estimated that a total of 282 construction permits have been issued for accommodation structures, with a total investment of 263 million euros. The year 2019 set a record for investments in hotel infrastructure, reaching a total value of 110 million euros.

Figure 8: Investments (million ALL) and construction permits

Source: Tourism and Hospitality in Albania 2022, UNDP

The increase in tourism accommodations in Albania has had several impacts on the country's economy and society. On the one hand, the growth of the tourism industry has created new jobs and generated revenue for the government through taxes. The coastal regions of Albania have experienced a significant increase in the number of hotel rooms. This growth in accommodation options has contributed to the country's thriving tourism industry. On the other hand, the increase of accommodations has also had negative impacts such as overcrowding and environmental degradation. These include efforts to diversify the tourism industry beyond the coastal regions and to promote eco-tourism and cultural tourism.

Therefore, the Albanian government has developed policies and strategies to promote sustainable tourism development and to ensure that the industry contributes to the country's economic growth while also protecting its natural and cultural assets (Ilollari, O. et al. (2023)., Palazzo, M., Gigauri, I., Panait, M. C., et al.,2022).

In addition, there have been other government-approved incentives to encourage and support tourism, such as:

- Profit tax exemption for all 4-5 star hotels;
- Reducing VAT to 6% for the entire accommodation sector;
- Reducing VAT to 6% for all services provided in 5-star hotels;
- Exemption from infrastructure impact taxes for 4 and 5-star hotels holding an internationally recognized trademark.

Figure 9: Contribution by categories
Source: INSTAT

According to UNWTO, in 2022, Albania was ranked 55th in the global ranking, as tourism and travel revenues reached 2.84 billion euros, a 48% increase compared to 2021. According to the balance of payments published by the Bank of Albania, travel revenues in 2022 experienced a 36% increase compared to the pre-pandemic situation.

Figure 10: Revenues - Inflow streams from travels and Expenditures - Outflow streams from travels
 Source: Bank of Albania

Moreover, the net balance, indicating the difference between inbound and outbound flows, has been consistently positive, as depicted in the above graph. It is noteworthy that the inbound flows are consistently higher in the third quarter, implying a higher demand for summer tourism. At this point, it is crucial for policymakers and stakeholders in this sector to create alternatives for sustainable tourism throughout the year. In fact, recent data from the Central Bank indicates that Albania has experienced significant inbound flows throughout the year in recent years, providing a positive signal for the economy and offering a potential response to the conference theme.

Figure 11: Hotel taxes, 9-month comparative revenues of major municipalities
 Source: Open Data

As shown in the above graph, returning to the impact of fiscal policy through the mentioned fiscal stimuli, it is understood that year by year, the total revenue collected from hotel taxes has been increasing. This means that despite their reduction, the value they have generated through sector development, improving services, and increasing capacities has provided direct stimulus, resulting in even more revenue. Typically, government fiscal stimulus has not been opposed by any author regarding the development of the tourism sector in terms of revenue generation. Therefore, the evaluation of this policy is easier and more apparent without the

need for advanced econometric analyses. However, another insight from this graph is precisely the regional division within this economic sector. As indicated, municipalities that have experienced the greatest growth are in the southern region, implying that the policies undertaken may not have been suitable for stimulation throughout the entire country or may not have been at the right level.

3.2 Econometric analysis

The logic of processing the econometric model.

- 1) Specify the model
- 2) Stationarity
- 3) Optimal lags selection
- 4) Estimate VAR
- 5) Perform diagnostic: normality, autocorrelation, stability, etc.
- 6) Perform impulse responses
- 7) Interpret the results

VARs in this study can be written in the following equation:

$$Y_t = A_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p A_i Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t$$

where:

$$Y_t = \begin{bmatrix} y_{1,t} \\ y_{2,t} \\ \vdots \\ y_{4,t} \end{bmatrix}, A_0 = \begin{bmatrix} a_{10} \\ a_{20} \\ \vdots \\ a_{40} \end{bmatrix}, A_i = \begin{bmatrix} a_{t11}(L) & a_{t21}(L) & \cdots & a_{i41}(L) \\ a_{t12}(L) & a_{t22}(L) & \cdots & a_{i42}(L) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{t14}(L) & a_{t24}(L) & \cdots & a_{i44}(L) \end{bmatrix}, \varepsilon_t = \begin{bmatrix} e_{1,t} \\ e_{2,t} \\ \vdots \\ e_{4,t} \end{bmatrix};$$

$Y_{1,t}$ is quarterly Tourism Income

$Y_{2,t}$ is quarter interest rate

$Y_{3,t}$ is quarter exchange rate

$Y_{4,t}$ is quarter inflation rate

In order to make the equation of the model accurate, the specification of appropriate Lags is to select a number of Lags for the VARs model by selecting the model that has Lags causing the lowest index of information criteria. In this study, the selected index of information criteria is Swartz Information Criteria and in our case is 2 lags;

$$SIC(p) = \log(\det(\hat{A}_p)) + \log(n) \frac{pm^2}{n}$$

According to the stationarity of variables, only Tourism income is I(0)

4. Conclusions

In the foremost consideration, it is essential to articulate that there exists no definitive formula, especially not for a specific economic policy. This is because the economy, in its entirety, is intricate, shaped not only by the nature of its economic mechanism but also by political nuances, and in this specific case, it depends entirely on the nature of the sector. In other words, there is no unique solution because assessments must be made based on the market segment, both on the demand and supply sides.

It is imperative to bear in mind that when the market is analyzed, on the one hand, there is demand, and on the other hand, there must be careful consideration of supply. The demand for tourism in Albania, for instance, cannot yield maximum benefits unless there is an enticing and compelling offer in place. This is how the market economy functions!

The study concludes that fiscal policy has been effective in providing stimuli through its fiscal and administrative policies in the tourism sector however, there are opportunities to work together with the tourism organizations to assess and rejuvenate different tourism lines, considering the concept of a 'life cycle', while monetary policy reaffirms its stability, yet with

more room to contribute to the tourism sector. Therefore, the main recommendation is that monetary policy can further engage in supporting this sector, aligning with fiscal policy to optimize/maximize the economic benefits of tourism. Fiscal policies from the other side, although they have undertaken projects to support the tourism sector and have been effective, still need investments in various types of tourism. In our assessment, following the logic of the life cycle theory, tourism should create both relative and absolute advantages to operate in the elastic part of demand where, as in the case of Giffen and Veblen goods, the law of demand is broken. In the tourism sector, there is a need for such tactics because it no longer is spoken about normal products, as long as tourism depends on individuals' preferences for differences rather than similarities. Furthermore, there are many spaces where different policies such as monetary and fiscal interventions can be implemented in various segments to create an industry, not only to mature profits but also to avoid risks in a renaissance curve as predicted by the economic theory of 'life cycle'. The sector must focus a lot on this point by showing flexibility and adaptation to the needs of tourists, also following the logic of Holton's model. This paper suggests that two policies cannot have an immediate impact with short-term policies, especially in the specific case of tourism, due to the risk presented by monetary policy and tourism. Therefore, in the assessment of this work, these two policies should already establish structural policies supporting the tourism industry.

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Tourism Effects in The Real Exchange Rate of Albania, Focusing only on the Euro as the Country-Specific Dominant Currency

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Abstract

This paper explores the significant influence of tourism on Albania's real exchange rate, particularly focusing on the Euro/Albanian Lek (ALL) exchange rate. Drawing from Albania's National Tourism Strategy, this study emphasizes the country's strategic objectives to enhance the tourism sector's impact on the economy and employment. The increase in tourist accommodation and service enterprises from Q1 2016 – Q3 2023 highlights this growth trajectory. Albania's position in the Tourism Dependence Index and the substantial tourist arrivals in recent years further exemplify the sector's growth.

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) has noted Albania's economic growth, attributing it partly to robust tourism inflows. This study adopts a focused approach, examining trimester tourism arrival data from INSTAT and its correlation with exchange rates from the Bank of Albania, centering specifically on the Euro due to the predominant European tourist demographic.

A narrative aspect of this study is the comparison between tourism dynamics and agricultural methodologies, using the strategic application of plant fertilizers as a metaphor for tourism interpretation and relation with the economy growth. This analogy extends to exploring the concept of over-tourism and its sustainability implications. The study also examines the challenges of sustainable tourism and waste management in tourist cities, citing Italy's achievements in waste recycling as a model for sustainable tourism practices.

The paper discusses the critical role of real exchange rate management in economic strategy for developing countries, as emphasized by Sebastian Edwards's research. It also delves into the work of Ding Ding and Yannick Timmer on the impact of exchange rate movements on tourism flows, exploring the concept of dominant currency pricing and its implications for countries like Albania.

This research uniquely focuses on the effects of tourist numbers on the exchange rate, particularly the depreciation of the Euro against the ALL. It challenges the notion of tourism as a standalone economic driver, advocating for an integrative approach combining tourism with capital accumulation, R&D, and education, as suggested by economic theories from Solow and Romer and contemporary researchers like Ding Du, Pin Ng, and Alan A. Lew. Additionally, the paper highlights the importance of considering other factors influencing tourism, such as destination image and visitor safety. It also discusses the impact of exchange rate stability on foreign investment, exports, and trade balance, citing studies from Edwards (1988) and Berka & Devereux (2010). The interconnected nature of tourist behaviors across different nations and the importance of early warning mechanisms for tourism managers are also explored.

In terms of methodology, the paper utilizes the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, examining the interrelationship between variables such as GDP, real exchange rate, and foreign tourist numbers.

The VAR model, with variables including the logarithms of the Real Exchange Rate (RER), tourist numbers from Euro-Country Currency regions, and Real GDP, offers a multifaceted view of the interrelationships and the impact of lags between these variables.

Using the STL Decomposition method and adhering to the Hannan-Quinn criterion for lag selection, the model reveals an inverse and long-term relationship between tourism growth shocks and exchange rate growth. The study identified a 23% impact on the exchange rate growth in the immediate term and a 37% influence over the long term from tourism growth shocks, signifying a persistent trend. This impact manifests initially as a devaluation of the Euro, stabilizing after five trimesters without reverting to the original level, thus suggesting a sustained overvaluation of the local currency.

The robustness of the model is affirmed by passing the normality test in a variation using data from 2002-2023. Stability tests validate the model's viability, with heteroskedasticity checks indicating no significant issues. The correlation between tourism and the exchange rate is negatively established at - 0.31, reinforcing the inverse dynamics observed. The dataset used straddles the minimum threshold for robust analysis, spanning from Q1 2016 to Q3 2023, providing a comprehensive period for evaluation.

For the standard errors, the Monte Carlo test with 100 repetitions was employed. The impulse responses demonstrate that an initial increase in tourist numbers—for example, in August 2023—leads to an immediate decline in the exchange rate. A more pronounced continuation is seen in the second trimester, followed by a reinforcement of the foreign currency (Euro in this case and in this model) in the third and fourth trimester. After the fifth trimester, the exchange rate level stabilizes, and the impact of the change in tourist growth rates remains negative. These findings also corroborate the correlation shown in the table above in this research paper. The impact of the change in tourist growth rates appears small in the alteration of the exchange rate level, but the relationship between them is inverse and long-term.

The Granger Causality test does not show strong evidence for causation from the number of tourists to the exchange rate level, presenting a complex scenario where the influence of tourism on the exchange rate is significant but not unidirectional. The extended analysis encapsulates a nuanced understanding that the relationship between tourism growth and exchange rate stability is intricate and multifactorial, with implications for policymakers to devise sustainable and balanced economic strategies.

This model allows for a simultaneous examination of the impact of each variable on the others, demonstrating a persistent and negative influence of tourism on the real exchange rate, both in the short and long term. The findings, based on Cholesky Decomposition, reveal that 23% of changes in the exchange rate growth in the short term and 37% in the long term are attributable to changes in tourist numbers growth.

In conclusion, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the multifaceted relationship between tourism and economic factors in Albania, offering insights for policymakers to develop more effective and sustainable tourism strategies.

Fiscal Incentives to Promote Sustainable Regional Tourism: Case of Albania

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Abstract

This paper investigated the impact of fiscal incentives to promote sustainable regional tourism in Albania. This examination used the primary and secondary research related to the dynamic of taxation policy in Albanian tourism sector, particularly recently. We demonstrate the static and dynamic analysis the tourism growth in Albania supporting by diverse fiscal instruments. Additionally, we examine empirically the effectiveness of tax ratio over the years according to the tourism growth through primary and secondary data. The government should encourage the tourism growth through promotion an intra-regional tourism in the short run and long run. The policymakers should impose the appropriate tourism taxation in order to boost the sustainable tourism investments in future.

Keywords: Fiscal incentives, regional tourism, sustainable tourism

JEL codes: Z32, Z38, R5

Public Policies for a New Model of Tourism in Albania: Agrotourism

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Abstract

This paper will deal with one of the latest models of tourism development in Albania, such as agrotourism. The purpose of treating this form of tourism is precisely the range of economic and social problems that it treats and not only the aspect of tourism development in the country. Albania has an agricultural tradition, where in addition to the high weight that this sector contributes to the GDP, specifically about one fifth of it, it has also created a culture over the years and features of the social mentality, among others. Therefore, public policies that deal with such a sector as well as intend to interfere with the development of another strategic or priority sector, such as tourism in recent years, constitute a new development model in a country that has high potential to provide a sustainable development in place. The combination of these sectors is seen as the genesis of a new industry that is growing rapidly, such as agritourism. Through official government data on budget support as well as specific policies undertaken in recent years, this study will examine the capacity for development of this industry, the expected results, possible benefits and contribution to economic development, as well as the needed support to boost it.

Keywords: agrotourism, 100 villages, public policies, economic development.

JEL codes: Q10, L83, O13

1. Introduction

In recent years, Albania has started working on a new model of tourism development, which will serve as a promoter for the economic development of the whole country. The government has identified various rural areas which are being treated as tourist locations and are being piloted as a source of development by mixing agriculture and tourism. Working with these rural areas aims to implement several public policies, including dimensions such as: infrastructure, tourism, agriculture and livestock, employment, preservation of traditions and values, etc. On the other hand, these policies would address some of the problems of our country, such as the migration of young people from the country, the neglect of agriculture and animal husbandry, working in villages, etc. From 2018, the Government of Albania has launched a new model of rural development based on the tourism potential of our country, through a Public Policy Program for the development of tourism '100 Villages', covering 12 districts and 61 municipalities.

Several potential financing channels have been identified for the megaproject, such as: the state budget (through specific programs of 4 ministries - the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development, the Minister of Tourism and the Environment, the Minister of Infrastructure and Energy and the Minister of Culture), funds from the European Union and the private sector (potential businesses in agrotourism). The purpose of this analysis is to deal with new models of tourism that serve as a catalyst for development and economic prosperity and well-being, since the objectives of this program are several dimensional: the development of public

infrastructure, economic development and the development of social capital capacities and human.

The channels for the development of tourism can be many, and a comprehensive tourism strategy must jointly exhaust these forms. In the case of this program, most of these elements are handled in a coordinated manner, thus increasing the likelihood of a successful development process, such as: *marketing and promotion* - which are the first to identify the locations; *tourist infrastructure* - since the construction and maintenance of roads are part of the development plan as a prerequisite for further progress; *cultural, sports and natural tourism* - in this project, all possible forms of tourism are identified, dealing with the historical one of heritage values; *cooperation with the private sector* - invitations to entrepreneurship and private businesses has been communicated since the beginning with the announcement of this project to invest in agritourism along with others. But on the other hand, 2 very important channels for which there is no main plan of involvement are: *International cooperation*, so how will it cooperate with international organizations, with embassies, or participation in international exhibitions of tourism for the promotion of these villages as tourist destinations, as well as *education and training* - how will the education system be adapted to offer education and training programs for the personnel of the tourism sector to gain knowledge and improve their service in order to offer the most quality packages.

One of the forms of tourism that has development potential in Albania and would have an advantage compared to the countries of the region is Agrotourism, which will be treated in more detail in this paper, to see the capacity of the country, always relying on the program I government. Agritourism, otherwise known as Agricultural Tourism, where citizens can visit a farm for educational, recreational or retail purposes. The reasons why we should invest in Agrotourism are precisely the benefits it brings, such as: green employment opportunities, increases the quality of life of farmers and consumers, while improving the environment and enriching the local culture. By 2021, there are registered 19 agrotourism entities and 8 are in the certification process. Agritourism is seen as an innovation model for the development of the green economy, tourism and the generation of new jobs in developed countries, thus the agri hub was created in Dubai, a tourist destination in the Dubai desert.

Albania as a country with a high development potential in agriculture, the sector which generates the largest part of the gross domestic product shows premises for development and for agricultural tourism, as this form is seen as a fast-growing industry that diversifies the agricultural economy of producers with tourism, attracting visitors for entertainment, entertainment, shopping and education purposes and thus contributing to the growth of their economy.

2. Methodology

The working methodology will be based on secondary research using official data on public finances related to the budget dedicated supporting respective policies. The data for this study will be obtained from official sources of the institutions responsible, such as the Ministry of Finance and Economy, High State Control, Institute of Statistics and other related institutions. The statistical method combined with the descriptive method, through review, analysis of data, interpretation and summarizing main findings will be techniques for conducting this research.

3. Excepted results

In this paper, the potentials of our country, government support through policies, and cooperation with the private sector will be addressed. Also, part of the study will be the treatment of the expectations of this new growing industry, be it in employment, education and growth of well-being and economy.

Analyzing the objectives of the 100 villages program and the new model of tourism that is being presented will be included, and the government's support for the development of these villages with the aim of promoting agro tourism. The study consists of clarifying the model that is applied through this policy, the forms of intervention, the expected results, the development channels and a special feature for the budgeting and funding sources of this policy. In particular, the benefits of agritourism in the country, the problems that this new industry addresses, as well as its contribution to economic development will be highlighted.

Active Labor Market Programs and Employment: Case of Albania

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Abstract

Active labour market policies (ALMPs) are publicly financed interventions intended to improve the functioning of the labour market by inducing changes in labour demand and labour supply, as well as their matching process. (Ernst, Merola, & Reljic, (2022)). These policies are tailored to the country's needs. Due to the financial crisis and the increase in the unemployment rate, active labour market policies (ALMP) inevitably returned to the forefront with their "activation strategy" (Godec and Benčina (2018)).

Since pre COVID period, these policies and their efficiency are not studied for Albania. In order to do this is necessary to review the experience of the other countries and the models and practices that they use.

This paper focuses on the ALMPs, as an instrument to bring to employment unemployed jobseekers, especially those belonging to vulnerable categories. The purpose of this paper is to present the main findings of the existing literature, on the relationship between active labour market policies and employment focusing in Albania.

This paper presents the review of many articles and working papers in this field. The main findings indicate that there are many factors determining the effectiveness of the interventions (through ALMPs) like type of program, monetary incentives, program duration, target group etc. Many studies conducted in different countries suggest a positive effect of ALMPs in employment in general. The results of an impact assessment conducted in Albania show that being treated in one of the programs, increases the probability of being employed but the probability ratio differs among the different programs.

This paper contributes to the increase in knowledge regarding the effectiveness of ALMPs in general and especially in Albania, focusing on the recent literature and data regarding ALMPs implementation in this country.

Keywords: active labour market policy, employment, impact evaluation

JEL codes: E24, E62, H61

1. Introduction

Creating jobs and reducing unemployment remains one of the most challenging problems in both developed and developing countries. According to Kluge (2016) policymakers worldwide struggle to find effective programs that can help the jobless find jobs and that increase workers' productivity and labour income. Since the 1990s, there has been an increased acceptance in the developed countries of the need for ALMPs to strengthen the link between social protection, labour market policies and employment. Today, these policies are widely regarded as an important tool in fighting unemployment (Escudero, 2018).

Active labour market policies (ALMPs) are state budget financed interventions intended to improve the functioning of the labour market by inducing changes in labour demand and labour supply, as well as their matching process. (Ernst, Merola, and Reljic, 2022).

According to ILO (2016), there are five main categories of ALMPs: (1) Training, (2) Public employment programs, (3) Employment subsidies, (4) Support for the creation of microenterprises and (5) Employment intermediation services.

This paper presents the review of many articles and working papers in this field. Many observational evaluation studies have been published. Many studies conducted in different countries suggest a positive effect of ALMPs in employment in general.

In Albania, pursuant to the Program of the Government and the Ministry of Finance and Economy for supporting unemployed jobseekers, the National Employment and Skills Agency has implemented the legal package according to the approved law and the respective subsequent DCMs. Currently Albania is implementing 5 different ALMPs stipulated in 4 different DCMs. An impact assessment was conducted in Albania for the previous generation programs before 2019. This assessment shows that being treated in one of the programs increases the probability of being employed but the probability ratio differs among the different programs.

2. Methodology

As stipulated by most researchers, the key outcome of ALMPs should be the employment of the participating individual. The most important question that evaluations of active labour market measures should answer, is whether a person participating in a measure gets a higher chance to find a job as a result of it (European Training Foundation, 2022).

The methodology used in this paper consists of the review of the existing studies conducted in the field of ALMPs from different authors in different countries. Several journal articles and reports have been used in order to formulate and point out the main findings regarding the ALMPs effect on employment. The analysis for Albania has been based on the reports published by National Employment and Skills Agency, mainly on the Impact Evaluation Report for the Employment Promotion Programs until 2019. Usually, an impact assessment is done 4 years after the end of a certain program with the purpose of assessing the employability of the program participants 1 year after the end of the program. Also, this paper has used many findings from the statistics reports published by NAES,

3. Literature review

The effectiveness of active labour market policies – including subsidized employment, training and job search assistance – has been a matter of vigorous debate over the past half century (Card, Kluve, & Weber (2010)). According to Crepon & Van den Berg (2016) active labour market policies are massively used with the objective being to improve labour market outcomes of individuals out of work.

Kluve and Schmidt (2002) analyzed 20 OECD countries between 1985 and 1999 and found that training measures have a positive impact on the employment rate. The Nordic countries have a relatively long tradition of active labour market programs. Sweden has long been seen as a pioneer of active labour market interventions with policies dating back to the late 1930s. From a review of the evaluation literature on ALMPs in the Nordic countries conducted by Nekby (2008) it comes out that programs that more closely approximate regular employment such as those provided by wage subsidized employment programs, yield positive results for subsequent employment outcomes. Meanwhile intensive contact and counselling with Public Employment Service (PES) caseworkers is found to be effective for vulnerable groups.

Godec and Benčina (2018) conclude that training programs retain their proactiveness across time. According to Card et al. (2018) targeting the long-term unemployed people in particular yields even bigger effects on employment. According to Dangler (2019), who conducted a study on the effectiveness of active labour market programs on the job quality of welfare recipients in Germany, all the four types of programs increased the probability of holding a

high-quality job. Participation in an ALMP helps to obtain a high-quality job compared with non-participation. The effects differ among programs and the dimensions of job quality.

According to a study conducted by Escudero (2018) through an extended pooled cross-country and time series database for 31 advanced countries during the period 1985–2010, it results that ALMPs matter at the aggregate level but mostly through appropriate implementation aspects. Start-up incentives and measures aimed at vulnerable populations are more effective than other ALMPs in terms of reducing unemployment and increasing employment. The positive effects of these policies seem to be particularly beneficial for the low skilled.

Card, Kluve, & Weber (2010) conducted a meta-analysis study of recent micro econometric evaluations of active labour market policies. They categorized 199 program impacts from 97 studies conducted between 1995 and 2007. According to this analysis, job search assistance programs yield relatively favourable program impacts, whereas public sector employment programs are less effective. Training programs are associated with positive medium-term impacts.

4. Results and discussion

In 2019, there was a reform in the employment promotion programs in Albania, by designing new ALMPs. The main aim of the reform was to design active labor market programs, standard in frame, but individualized in terms of addressing different vulnerabilities. All the programs rely on the principle of subsidizing the employer, different from the design prior to 2019, where the subsidy went directly to the jobseeker/employee.

Usually, an impact evaluation report on the programs is prepared four years after the program implementation in order to analyze the employability rate of the program beneficiaries. For the programs implemented through 2014-2018, the Impact Evaluation of Employment Promotion Programs in Albania, has been done in 2019. According to this report prepared by UNDP (2019) in collaboration with the Albania institutions, Ministry of Finance and National Employment Service, Active labor market measures in the form of employment promotion programs (EPPs) in Albania, are put in place with the aim of increasing employment, reducing unemployment, decreasing informality, supporting vulnerable groups, and paving the way to sustainable and formal employment.

This assessment shows that being treated in one of the programs increases the probability of being employed but the probability ratio differs among the different programs. The largest impact on the probability of being employed is found for the employment promotion program of unemployed jobseekers in difficulty. The results for the employment promotion program of unemployed jobseekers in difficulty show that being treated in this program increases the probability of being employed by 33.8%.

The results for the impact of on-the-job training employment promotion program show that relative to the control group, being on-the-job training program increases the probability of employment by 27.9%.

5. Conclusions

The effectiveness of ALMPs depends on the type of program itself. Subsidy programs are more effective compared to public works and training. Training programs tend to show more positive effects several years after the end of the program. In general, ALMPs appear to be more effective in the long term.

In Albania, the result of the Impact Evaluation conducted in 2019 show that being treated in one of the programs, increases the probability of being employed but the probability ratio differs among the different programs.

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Tourism-Led Employment: The case for Albania

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Abstract

Albania being a small developing country with advantageous features for tourism, has prioritized the tourism sector in recent years. As a result, the total contribution of travel and tourism constituted 20.5% of the Albanian GDP before the pandemic. Given that tourism relies heavily on labour, investigating its influence on employment becomes a crucial research focus especially for developing countries. Nevertheless, the universality of this impact across all nations remains a subject of debate. This study aims to investigate the effect of the tourism sector on employment in Albania. In addition, the impact of economic growth and inflation rate, which are included in the analysis as control variables, on the employment rate are investigated. This research gains significance by addressing this pressing issue and proposing an innovative econometric approach, the ARDL Bounds Test with time Breaks.

By using quarterly data for the period 2012-2023, the study reveals the existence of a cointegration connection between the employment rate and international tourism demand, economic growth, and inflation rate in Albania. The investigation establishes that growth in tourism demand by 1% correlates positively with a 0.2% increase in the employment rate.

Keywords: Employment, Tourism, Tourism-Led Employment, ARDL model.

JEL codes: J20, Z3,

1. Introduction

As the world economy transitions from a production to a service economy, one of the most significant industries is the tourist industry. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, tourism was the largest service industry globally. According to WTTC (2018) report, tourism not only exceeded global economic growth (from 2011 to 2019) but was ranked in first place as the world's fastest-growing industry leaving behind important sectors such as Information and Communication. The direct global contribution of tourism on GDP was estimated to be 3.2% but if the indirect and induced effect is included the wider and total contribution amounts to 10.4% of the world GDP.

Travel and tourism took the largest hit in the two decades after the COVID-19 pandemic and the global limitations. The industry saw a decline of -49.1% (total contribution to the world's GDP fell to 5.5%) in 2020, an amount that is estimated to be about twelve times the decline that occurred during the global crisis of 2009 (WTTC, 2021). The growth of the sector was rapid in 2022, by 21.7%, considering the sharp decline two years before. Predictions are that tourism will be affected in the following years by the economic situation and the price crisis. Before the pandemic period, the World Bank (2020) estimated a growth of 3.8% on average every year in the following 10 years. In 2033, after the pandemic and the price crisis, the total contribution of tourism is estimated to reach 11.6% of the world's GDP (World Bank, 2023). The tourism sector, in addition to its impact on economic growth, also has a significant effect on employment and the creation of new jobs. Among the three main sectors of the economy, the researchers estimate that tourism has the potential to create more employment opportunities and income from labour (Fletcher, 1989); (Mescon, T.S. & Vozikis, G.S, 1985); (Liu, 1984); (Kim, H. & Kim, BG, 2015) (Roldán, n.d.). Tourism employment can have also important

social implications. Studies show that employment in tourism tends to improve income inequality and gender inequality in the labour market. The WTTC studies show that in the tourism sector, women make up about 54% of the workforce in the tourist industry. The tourism sector also employs a higher number of young people than the general economy (WTTC, 2019a); (WTTC, 2019b).

In the WTTC (2020) report, it is estimated that before the pandemic, employment related to the tourism sector, which includes direct, indirect, and induced employment amounted up to 10.3% of the total global employment or 330 million jobs. What makes the tourism sector even more important for employment is that globally 25% of new jobs created for the period 2014-2019 were made possible by tourism. The covid-19 pandemic was responsible for 62 million jobs lost in 2020. Only 1/3 of the lost jobs were able to recover in 2021, when tourism employment constituted 9.1% of the overall employment. Predictions are that in 2024, tourism statistics will reach pre-pandemic values and that tourism will create 126 million new jobs by 2033 (WTTC, 2022); (World Bank, 2023).

Tourism is estimated to be very important, especially for small and developing economies compared to other sectors. In these economies, employment in tourism can reach up to 50% of total employment (Zhao, J., Yang, D., Zhao, X & Lei, M, 2023).

Albania being a small developing country with advantageous features for tourism, has prioritized the tourism sector in recent years. Noteworthy investments have been made not just in air and sea infrastructure, but also in various other aspects such as favourable public policies. As a result, the total contribution of travel and tourism constituted 20.5% of the Albanian GDP before the pandemic. Due to the restrictions imposed during the pandemic, there was a significant drop of nearly 60% in the volume of international arrivals, resulting in a reduction of the overall contribution of tourism to 10.3% of GDP in 2020. The recovery was swift in 2021 in which GDP total contribution of tourism reached 17.4%. While the contribution for 2022 was 18% (WTTC, 2023).

The share of employment in travel and tourism-related activities was 25.2% or 243,800 employees before the pandemic. In 2022, the share of employment marked 21.2% after reaching record low levels of 15.8% in 2020 in the last 15 years. According to the WTTC (2023), in 2033, one in four people will be employed in activities related to tourism in Albania.

2. Methodology

For this study, quarterly data from 2012 to the second quarter of 2023 of the employment rate, the number of international tourist arrivals, growth rate of gross domestic product (GDP) and the Consumer Price Index (CPI) were used. First, the study investigates the relationship between variables using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Bounds Test with time break. Then, after determining the significant cointegration relationship, the long-term and short-term coefficients are estimated. The study uses the following model to investigate the effect of tourism on the employment rate:

$$Lemp_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Ltr_t + \beta_2 GDP_t + \beta_3 Inf_t$$

where EMP shows the ratio of the employed population of a country to the total population and computed considering the people at the age of 15 to 64, TR is the number of international arrivals, GDP indicates the quarterly growth rate of real GDP and INF is the quarterly percentage change in CPI. Employment rate and tourism are used in logarithmic forms for empirical purposes and obtained the data from the Instat Database.

3. Results and Discussion

Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF), Philips Perron and Zivot–Andrews unit root tests are used to test the stationarity of the series. The findings of the unit root tests are similar. The series are mixed. GDP growth rate is I (0) while all three other series are I (1). As a consequence, the ARDL model is employed. The bound test shows co-integration among the variables and the study proceeds with the ARDL Error Correction model. The variables are significant both in short run and in long run period. Tourism has important implications for employment in Albania.

In order to complete the econometric analysis, diagnostic tests are run for the model. The test of normality Jarque-Berra shows that the normality holds, and the result of Skewness shows that the residuals are normally distributed while the White test refutes the assumption of heteroskedasticity. The Durbin-Watson test was used to test for autocorrelation and the test for stability shows that the coefficients are stable and lie between the lower and upper values.

4. Conclusions

According to the ARDL Bounds test results, there is a cointegration relationship between the employment rate and international tourism demand, economic growth, and inflation rate in Albania. This finding coincides with previous studies. The study determines that an increase in tourism demand (1%) positively affects the employment rate (0.2%).

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Migration and Tourism Nexus: A Viewpoint Based on the VFR Trend in Albania

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Abstract

Migration and tourism are two important phenomena, with a high socio-economic impact for developed and developing countries, both related to people mobility. Nowadays, Albania is still experiencing high emigration levels, as well as a significant internal migration, directed mainly towards the areas with better job opportunities, a better education quality, and a high quality of life. On the other hand, in recent years, there has been a very high interest in visiting Albania, both from Albanians who reside abroad and from citizens with a foreign background. The development of tourism has a very positive impact not only on the country's economy, but also on social and cultural aspects. We analyse in this basic study the relation between migration and tourism through the "Visiting Friends and Relatives" (VFR) indicator. The considered time period is from 2016 to 2022.

Keywords: migration, tourism, VFR travel

JEL codes: F22, Z32, L83

1. Introduction

The nexus between migration and tourism is a significant topic in the tourism-related research. According to William and Hall (2000), there are several causal relationships in the link between tourism and migration. One such cause is that tourism inflows generate labor migration to meet the employment needs of tourism industries, which depend on special skills from overseas countries. Many approaches explain the relation between the considered variables by qualifying tourism itself as the cause of international migration. The tourism sector (in developed and developing countries) positively affects economic growth, as it can create jobs and new economic opportunities. From the latest Eurostat data, VFR is the second main purpose of travel in the EU-27 countries, with an average of 39.5% in the last decade; the highest value obviously belongs to traveling for holidays and leisure purposes. This paper highlights and determines some new insights into the relationship between migration and tourism, through the VFR indicator. We also consider some statistics related to the situation of VFR tourism in Albania, and to the emigration phenomena during the period from 2016 to 2022.

2. Literature review

Migration and tourism are both related to the movement of people and monetary sources. We define in this section two distinct concepts, 'tourism-led migration' (TLM) and 'migration-led tourism' (MLT), respectively. TLM describes the tourism-migration nexus for socio-economic reasons. According to Gössling and Schulz (2005), tourism may lead to the movement of temporary, seasonal, or permanent work migrants. The MLT relationship is closely related to the VFR purposes, as well as to holiday trips or professional and business purposes.

Many authors have studied the MLT and TLM phenomena in different geographical areas of interest, such as in the United States, Canada, Belgium, France, Italy, Australia, etc. (see for

example, Kim et al., 2014; Lehto et al., 2001; Basu, 2007; Boyne et al., 2002; Massidda & Piras, 2015; Massidda et al., 2015; Backer, 2012; Seetaram & Dwyer, 2009).

3. Some key statistics

The following analysis is based on secondary data, which have been collected from the database of the (Albanian) Institute of Statistics (Survey on Tourism - "Holiday and Trips") and other official statistical databases.

Albania has historically experienced mass migrations, at different stages of its development. The long history of Albanian emigration is also related to the strong connection between family members and friends. In the period 2016-2022, net migration in Albania has deteriorated (except for the year 2020, when the entire world was hit by the COVID-19 pandemic).

Figure 1 shows the number of tourists for visiting friends and relatives purposes during 2016-2022.

Figure 1. Number of tourists for visiting friends and relatives' purposes
Source: General Directorate of State's Police

According to a World Tourism Organization (WTO, 2009) report, migration has led directly and indirectly to a significant growth in tourism, for both home and host countries, through increased visibility, particularly in the VFR sector.

Table 1 shows the trips distribution by purpose (percentage) in Albania and abroad, for the period from 2017 to 2022.

Table 1. Trips distribution by purpose in Albania and abroad, in (%)

Purpose	2017		2018		2019		2020		2021		2022	
	*	**	*	**	*	**	*	**	*	**	*	**
Holiday and leisure	24.2	30.9	31.7	30.3	34.0	37.6	50.9	51.3	51.3	37.3	49.7	49.8
Visiting relatives and friends	58.2	46.6	61.3	47.2	56.1	46.2	39.5	33.9	42.4	42.5	42.6	38.1
Business	9.6	13.8	1.8	15.2	4.1	8.1	1.2	2.6	2.1	10.5	2.0	5.0
Other	8.0	8.7	5.1	7.2	5.8	8.1	8.4	12.2	4.2	9.7	5.7	7.1

Source: INSTAT, Survey on Tourism "Holiday and Trips"
*Albania **Abroad

4. Preliminary conclusions

VFR tourism is closely related to the trend and history of international migration flows; VFR tourism represents a significant aspect of migration patterns. The primary motivation for VFR tourism is the desire to spend time with family and friends. Migrants often engage in VFR tourism to visit their home country or community. Besides the social and cultural aspects, VFR tourism can have significant economic implications. VFR tourists contribute to the local economy by spending on accommodation, dining, transportation, and other services during their stay.

Reduction of Poverty through Tourism in Albania

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic underscored the crucial role and positive contributions made by the tourism industry. Tourism facilitates the advancement of socio-economic growth, the generation of employment opportunities, and the alleviation of poverty. Tourism development is seen as a powerful source of economic advancement in developing countries, yet there remains a dearth of comprehensive studies investigating its nuanced relationship with poverty reduction in Albania. Existing literature reveals limited exploration into the intricate interplay between poverty alleviation and the burgeoning tourism sector in Albania. This paper aims to bridge this gap by delving into the under-examined terrain of how international tourism impacts the at-risk-of-poverty rate and GDP in Albania. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the direct economic impact of tourism in Albania. The study relies mainly on secondary data obtained from INSTAT from 2017 to 2021. By examining the linkage between GDP and International Tourism, At-Risk –Poverty Rate, and International Tourism this study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of tourism as a tool for poverty reduction.

Keywords: GDP, At risk of poverty rate, international tourism, number of arrivals

JEL codes: I32, Q01, Z32

1. Introduction

In 2022, the World Travel & Tourism Council reported that the pandemic resulted in a staggering loss of 62 million jobs, reducing the global workforce in the sector to 271 million. Before the pandemic, tourism was of the world's largest sectors accounting for 1 in 4 of all new jobs created in the world. Located in the Western Balkans, Albania is a country that has undergone a profound transformation coincided with the rapid growth of the tourism sector. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the direct economic impact of tourism and assess how tourism contributes to the overall economic development of Albania. The question arises: can the tourism industry in Albania be a key driver in the ongoing fight against poverty? Albania, much like many countries in the region, has faced economic disparities, and the potential of tourism to bridge these divides is a subject of great interest. The nation's tourism initiatives have aimed not only at boosting economic growth but also at addressing social inequalities and reducing poverty. The journey of Kukes region, one of the poorest areas of Albania, in harnessing the power of tourism to uplift the living standards of its people presents a compelling case study. It is in this context that this paper delves into a detailed examination of specific tourism-related initiatives, their outcomes, and the overall impact on poverty alleviation. Section 2 describes the methodology of the study, section 3 delves into the current state of poverty in Albania, shedding light on key indicators and contextual factors that shape the socio-economic landscape. Following this, section 4 offers a comprehensive overview of the tourism sector in Albania, detailing its growth, dynamics, and impact on local communities. Specifically, section 5 narrows its focus to the Kukes Region, exploring the potential of tourism as a catalyst for poverty reduction. By synthesizing findings from these sections, the study aims to contribute valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on sustainable development and the

role of tourism in fostering economic well-being. Finally, section 6 presents a succinct conclusion, summarizing key findings and implications derived from the research, thus paving the way for informed policy recommendations and future avenues of exploration.

2. Methodology

This study relied on accessible quantitative data, statistics, and information sourced from secondary sources. The search encompassed aggregating data and reports sourced from diverse public sources, including governmental institutions like the Ministry of Tourism and Environment's Annual Reports. Additionally, non-governmental sources such as the Institute of Statistics Albania (INSTAT) were consulted. The study also referred to reports from esteemed international organizations like the World Bank and World Travel & Tourism Council.

3. Results

Table 1 presents a summary of the financial commitment of the Albanian government to poverty reduction and social support over the specified years, highlighting the progressive increase in resources allocated to these critical endeavours.

Table 1. Spending on SDG 1 (2017 – 2021) per Capita and as % of GDP

SDG 1	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
GDP per capita (ALL)	540	571	593	581	660
Per capita spending (ALL)	24 033	25 298	26 256	27 412	29 062
Measured in terms of GDP %	2,4%	2,5%	2,6%	2,7%	2,9%

Source: Braho A., Ymeri S., (2021) , INSTAT

Table 2. Insights into Social Exclusion Between 2017 and 2021

Variables	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
At risk of poverty rate (%)	23.4	23	21.8	22	22.2
At risk of poverty before social transfers	38.5	39.0	38.1	37.9	39
At risk of poverty after social transfers	26.5	26.3	26.1	24.8	25.2
Gini index (%)	33.1	30.1	30.1	29.4	30.0

Source: INSTAT 2020,2021

In 2021, the at-risk-of-poverty threshold for a one-member household was established at 191.791 ALL, slightly higher than the 186.242 ALL recorded in 2020. An estimated 622.705 individuals were living below this threshold in 2021, only marginally higher than the 621.504 estimated in 2020. The estimated at-risk-of-poverty rate for 2021 is 25.2%. However, if income levels exclude certain social transfers, the estimated at-risk-of-poverty rate rises significantly to 39.0%.

Table 3. Indicators of Tourism 2017-2021

Variables	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
International tourism, number of arrivals ('000)	5118	5927	6406	2658	3429
Contribution of Tourism to GDP	17.6%	18.7%	20.5%	10.3%	17.4%
Job created	165,800	171,200	224,000	178,600	226,000

Source: World Travel and Tourism Council 2023

International tourism arrivals increased to 3,429,000, indicating a recovery from the pandemic's impact. The poverty headcount ratio remained relatively stable at 22.2%. The tourism sector emerged as a pivotal driver of the nation's economy, with its contribution to GDP consistently rising. Starting at 17.6% in 2017, the contribution of tourism to GDP increased to 20.5% in 2019, then experienced a decline in 2020, likely due to the COVID-19 pandemic, before rebounding to 17.4% in 2021.

4. Discussion

4.1 The potential of tourism-Kukes Region

According to Instat the Kukës Region is economically the poorest country of Albania, with a population of 80,428, grapples with a notable economic challenge as it emerges as the most impoverished region in Albania. This is underscored by a substantial poverty rate of 21.8%, reflecting a significant proportion of its inhabitants living below the poverty line. The Gini Coefficient, a metric measuring income inequality, stands at 25.6%, indicative of a relatively unequal distribution of economic resources within the region.

Table 4. International tourism, number of arrivals and GDP per capita 2017-2021

Year	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
International tourism, number of arrivals	280,452	291,011	327,752	227,129	328,683
GDP per capita	337	363	359	N/A	N/A

Source: INSTAT 2021

In 2017, international tourism in the region saw 280,452 arrivals, which increased marginally to 291,011 in 2018 and further rose to 327,752 in 2019. On the economic front, the GDP per capita in Kukës exhibited a positive trajectory from 2017 to 2019, rising from 337 to 359. However, data for 2020 and 2021 are not available (N/A), preventing a comprehensive analysis of recent economic performance.

5. Conclusions

Despite the substantial downturn caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, the tourism sector emerged as a crucial economic driver. These findings underscore the importance of continued efforts to sustain economic growth, reduce income inequality, and support the tourism sector's resilience, while maintaining the positive trajectory in poverty alleviation. One in five jobs in Albania is linked to tourism, travel, and related activities.

Identifying the effects of tourism development on poverty reduction in the Kukes region proves challenging due to its current limited scale. Meaningful impacts may not manifest until tourism experiences more substantial development in the area. The study emphasizes the need for a forward-looking approach, acknowledging that the positive effects of tourism on local communities and economies may materialize progressively over time. The findings suggest that a sustainable approach to tourism, supported by effective policies and community engagement, will be pivotal in realizing the envisioned positive impacts on poverty reduction in Albania and in the Kukes region. This study examined only some components of tourism and poverty reduction, future research should focus on the use of new techniques measuring tourism impacts on poverty reduction and pro-poor tourism in Albania. Conducting longitudinal studies tracking the development of the tourism sector and its impacts on poverty over time could provide a clearer understanding of the trajectory and long-term effects of tourism growth.

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Factors Influencing Tourist Arrivals: A Comparative Analysis on Western Balkan Countries.

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Abstract

This study employs time series analysis to examine the factors influencing fluctuations in tourist arrivals within a certain timeframe (2005-2021) across a chosen set of Western Balkan nations. The countries that have been chosen for this study are Albania, Croatia, Montenegro, and Greece. These nations exhibit distinct attributes in terms of their socio-economic development patterns; nonetheless, they share commonalities in terms of their coastal topography and cultural heritage influences. The empirical literature indicates that factors such as income and prices play a crucial role in determining the demand for tourism arrivals. According to prevailing theories, tourism is predominantly regarded as a luxury item or service.

In this study, two distinct autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models will be employed to analyze the relationship between the number of tourist arrivals and international tourism receipts. The models will incorporate various independent variables, including GDP growth rate, consumer price index, exchange rate, transportation costs, and other pertinent factors associated with tourism infrastructure.

Based on our estimation results, we have observed small variations among countries, indicating a relatively low amount of price elasticity. Nevertheless, when considering Balkan countries, it is shown that income level and currency rates hold greater significance.

Keywords: Tourism, Price level, ARDL models

JEL codes: Z32, P22, C32

1. Introduction

The current body of literature related to tourism economics has placed significant emphasis on the subject of tourism demand modelling. The primary focus of empirical applications has mainly focused on methodological concerns and the examination of certain causes. Nevertheless, it is very astonishing that there has been limited debate regarding the ramifications of the selected dependent variable in terms of both theoretical and empirical outcomes. Furthermore, the implications stemming from the selection of the measure for tourism demand have received scant attention.

The present investigation makes use of time series analysis in order to investigate the factors that influence changes in tourist arrivals over a specific period of time (2005-2021) across a selected group of Western Balkan countries. For the purpose of this investigation, the countries of Albania, Croatia, Montenegro, and Greece have been selected.

These economies exhibit diverse characteristics in terms of the patterns of socioeconomic growth that they have experienced; nonetheless, they share similarities in terms of the coastal geography and cultural heritage influences that they have experienced. When it comes to determining the demand for tourism arrivals, the empirical literature suggests that factors such as income and prices play a significant part in the evaluation process (Cvetkoska & Barisic, 2017; Selimi et al., 2018; Malaj, 2020). Generally speaking, travel is considered to be a luxury good or service, because of the prevalent notions.

2. Methodology

This investigation will make use of two different autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models in order to examine the connection that exists between the quantity of tourists who visit a country and the amount of money that is earned from tourism on a global scale. There will be a number of independent variables that will be incorporated into the models. These variables will include the rate of growth of the GDP, the consumer price index, the currency rate, the costs of transportation, and other pertinent factors linked with tourist infrastructure.

The World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank are used to determine the total amount of money spent by international tourists in each country as well as the total number of tourists who visit each country from other countries.

3. Results and Discussion

The findings of the estimation demonstrate that the income in the destination country (GDP per capita), which is employed as a proxy for the level of development, has an upward relationship with tourism demand, regardless of which dependent variable is chosen. This is in line with what was predicted. It is appropriate to draw the conclusion, based on the estimated parameters, that a one percent rise in the GDP per capita at the destination is associated with a growth of 0.988% in tourism expenditure. This growth is the result of a 0.566% increase in tourist arrivals and a 0.442% increase in average expenditure.

4. Conclusions

The findings from the empirical application section suggest that the variables that explain in the final demand models exhibit consistency. This suggests that these variables possess significant impacts on tourism demand, regardless of whether it is assessed by tourist arrivals, expenditure, or average expenditure. Theoretical arguments suggest that the main factors influencing tourism have a significant impact on average expenditure in the Western Balkan economies.

From a practical perspective, our findings help define tourism development strategies at destinations by highlighting the ways in which factors might impact tourism flows and expenditures to varying degrees. Tourism destination managers will thus be better equipped to determine whether the goal is to optimize tourism flows or tourist expenditures, as they will have a better understanding of how various policies and factors can have differing effects on visitor expenditures and arrivals.

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The New EPBD Directive: How Can Albania Respond to this Objective? A Case Study of Albanian Agrotourism Renovation

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Abstract

With the new EPBD directive, the European Union has announced the way forward for the construction of new buildings and the renovation of old ones. Albania's goal for years has been to be part of the European Union and certainly parameterizing itself with the needs of European directives in terms of energy transition is certainly an essential point of social economic integration.

In this article, a ZEB model building will be presented, consisting of an excellent passive system (well-insulated walls and windows) combined with a heat pump hybrid, with radiant floor heating, integrated with a photovoltaic system and batteries. This article presents a project carried out in Italy in the beautiful Val d'Orcia, Tuscany, where a building was renovated, bringing it to zero consumption.

In particular, the heat losses of the building were eliminated by isolating the perimeter walls from the inside and replacing the fixtures, thus eliminating the problems of thermal bridges. All this was accompanied by the complete renovation of the systems, bringing the heating to low temperatures with underfloor radiant modules, powered by an electric heat pump and all powered by a photovoltaic system made up of 3 generators. Electric vehicle charging has been integrated to provide a greater service linked to tourist hospitality and increasingly widespread electric mobility.

What will be achieved is to transport this hotel structure to the Albanian tourist areas, in particular in Korca to see beyond the technical feasibility of the project, its economic weight and evaluate whether today it is possible to make investments in this sector (energy efficiency) without the contribution of European grants.

To do this, simulation software in BIM, FEM and Trnsys was used to understand how through hourly dynamic simulation, it is possible to have an overview of the energy consumption of the building in the Albanian area.

Keywords: Energy Saving, Energy Efficiency, Photovoltaics, NZEB, Storage Systems, Sustainable Economy, Energy Independence, Renewable Energy.

The Symbiosis between Tourism and the Environment for Sustainable Economic Development

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Abstract

Climate change is widely acknowledged as the world's most pressing and consequential environmental catastrophe, commanding the highest level of focus and concern at present. Tourism is one of the sectors which is particularly affected by environmental changes: while favourable climate conditions are seen as an enticing feature, unfavourable climate circumstances work as a catalyst for the growth of the tourism industry. Likewise, literature also offers different viewpoints on the impacts, both positive and negative, of tourism on the environment. Current literature explains the negative effect of tourism on carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions through different channels, mainly based on energy use. On the other hand, the transition from dirty to clean sectors, well-managed tourism, sustainable tourism policies, sustainable investments in tourism show that they positively affect the improvement of the quality of the environment. The magnitude of the impact that tourism has on environmental quality varies significantly between developed and developing economies.

This paper studies various aspects of the symbiotic relationship between tourism development and the environment. The study focuses on the impact that tourism has on environmental degradation, also presenting an empirical analysis of the link between CO₂, tourism development and primary energy supply for the Albanian case.

Keywords: Environment, Carbon Dioxide, Tourism, Energy, Sustainable Development

JEL codes: O11, L83, Q41, Q53, Q56

1. Introduction

Concerns over the rising amounts of CO₂ in the atmosphere have been voiced for years. Scientists broadly recognize that the primary cause of climate change and global warming is the rapid increase in CO₂ emissions caused by human activity during the past 50 years (Anderson, T. R., et al., 2016; Mossler, M. V., et al., 2017). According to Pieter Tans (Global CO₂ Monitoring Laboratory), every year, we excavate a mountain of carbon, burn it, and release the carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. The industry that accounts for almost 8% of global CO₂ emissions caused by human activity is tourism. The environmental impact of tourism will rise in line with the number of people who can afford to travel (Nature Climate Change, 2018). Travel and tourism have grown at one of the world's quickest rates for the last 20 years, outpacing exports of food, energy, and vehicles (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2023). Albania emits 0.013% of the total amount of CO₂ in the world (for the year 2020), while Albania's GDP constitutes 0.019% of the world's (for the year 2022) (World Bank, 2023). For 2021, the direct contribution of the tourism sector generated 7.5% of Albania's GDP, while its total contribution generated about 17.5% of Albania's GDP (Ministry of Finance and Economy of Albania, 2022).

A large amount of research shows that there is a significant relationship between environment and the tourism, with most studies concentrating on the detrimental consequences of climate change and global warming on the travel and tourism industry (Scott et al., 2012). The literature

claims that while favourable climate conditions are considered as an attractive factor, unfavourable climate circumstances are considered as a pushing factor for the growth of the tourism industry (Amelung, B., et al., 2007). On the other hand, in a theoretical framework, Bach and Gössling (1996) first addressed the role of tourism in global greenhouse gas emissions. This study found that the aviation industry has a major contribution to greenhouse gas emissions. The debate's multidisciplinary character contributed to a steady increase in the number of new and innovative research in the 2000s (Scott, D., et al., 2012). Tourism revenues (Lee and Brahmašreene, 2013; Gamage et al., 2017; Zhang and Gao, 2016) and tourist number (entries) (Akadiri et al., 2018; Sghaier et al., 2018; Solarin, 2014) are the two indicators used in the literature to test the potential effects of tourism developments on CO₂ emissions.

The literature describes how tourism affects CO₂ emissions mainly through energy use as the most important channel. According to Gössling et al. (2015), traveling internationally for tourists uses the most amount of energy. Fossil fuels including coal, natural gas, and oil are used by the tourism industry to meet nearly all of its energy needs. Fossil energy resources are mostly used by the tourist industry for travel, lodging, and destination-related activities. The aviation industry's share of worldwide CO₂ emissions has increased as a result of airline travel growing faster than other modes of transportation, particularly in recent years. According to Dwyer et al. (2010), the transportation of water, the importation of food and other material items, and the disposal of trash all need a substantial amount of energy in tourist areas. Similar to this, because they involve mechanical activities, theme parks, ski resorts, and attractions are high energy intensity areas.

In this paper, it is intended to analyse the impact that tourism has on environmental degradation, evaluating the empirical impact of the international tourism receipts as one of the two main indicators of tourism development and primary energy supply as the main channel through which tourism affects the environment in CO₂ emissions for the case of Albania.

2. Methodology

The data utilized in this study's analysis are at the macroeconomic level, and the approach is based on quantitative indicators. For the case of Albania, annual data are gathered from the World Bank between 2000 and 2020 and published in 2023. The data are used by authors to recalculate the variables in different measures than those used by World Bank. Data include CO₂ emissions (*CO₂*) measured in kg per capita; International tourism receipts (*Receipts*) measured in current U.S. dollars per capita; Primary Energy supply (*Energy*) measured in MJ per capita.

Emissions of carbon dioxide are generated when fossil fuels are burned, and cement is produced. International tourism receipts are expenditures by international inbound visitors, including payments to national carriers for international transport. Primary energy supply is defined as energy production plus energy imports, minus energy exports, minus international bunkers, then plus or minus stock changes. Data for primary energy supply is derived by data of energy intensity, which is the ratio between energy supply of primary energy and gross domestic product measured in MJ/\$ 2017 PPP GDP. The variable of energy intensity is multiplied with PPP GDP measured in constant 2017 international dollars.

The collected data were first transformed into natural logarithms before the empirical analysis was carried out. The program Stata 15.0 was used to make all of the estimates. The econometric model that is employed is the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model. Under specific conditions, the OLS model allows for the assessment of the extent to which other independent variables explain the dependent variable over a given time period. These assumptions are checked by statistical tests. More precisely, the tests of heteroskedasticity, normality, partial correlation, and multicollinearity are the statistical tests that were employed in this analysis. The dependent

variable and each of the independent variables in this analysis are time series that do not have unit roots.

Based on the aforementioned approach and conceptualization of the model to be employed for the empirical analysis, the econometric model intended for evaluation is:

$$lCO2 = C + \beta_1 * lReceipts + \beta_2 * lEnergy + \mu \quad [1]$$

3. Results and Discussion

The following model is the outcome of the econometric analysis of the data collected for the Albanian economy:

$$lCO2 = -4.311449 + 0.0944228 * lReceipts + 1.070557 * lEnergy \quad [2]$$

The empirical model implies that with the increasement of receipts from tourism per capita and that of primary energy supply per capita, the CO₂ emissions per capita will increase as well. The model results to have an R-squared of 0.9070, which means that 90.71% of the variance in the CO₂ variable is explained by the independent variables included in this regression. Additionally, according to the regression analysis, the model results jointly statistically significant, as indicated by the value F=87.77 (p-value=0.0000). As well, each of the independent variables statistically significantly explains CO₂ emissions in Albania.

The diagnostic tests have been successfully completed by the empirical model. It turns out that the model's residuals are homoscedastic, or that the assumption of consistency of coefficients for the estimated OLS regression is met, based on the results of the Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity. In reference to the normality test, the residuals' histogram indicates a normal distribution, and the Jarque-Bera test confirms that the requirement for residual normality in order to have consistent regression coefficients is satisfied. There are statistically significant relationships between CO₂ emissions and each of the other two variables in the model separately, even after controlling for a third variable that is related to them, according to the significance values of the partial and semi-partial correlations of CO₂ emissions with other independent variables. The assumption of consistency of coefficients for the OLS regression is satisfied by the estimated model since multicollinearity between independent variables is not present.

The results of the diagnostic tests and the empirical model itself are appended in the Appendix at the end of the study.

4. Conclusions

The findings of the empirical investigation supporting the Albanian case in point for the years 2000–2020 confirm the significant relationship between tourism and the environment. Increasement in the international tourism receipts and primary energy supply as the main channel through which tourism affects the environment cause the environmental degradation. Therefore, policymakers should not only focus their policies and strategies to just further the amount of international tourist and their expenditures. They should focus their policies in making the tourism more sustainable. By encouraging the use of ecologically friendly equipment and tools, the tourism industry may help safeguard the environment through effective management.

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The Influence of Energy Prosumers in Shaping a Sustainable Future

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Abstract

As the energy landscape is undergoing transformative changes, navigating towards net-zero emissions becomes crucial in the face of escalating environmental challenges. Central to this change is the shift towards green technology- renewable energy sources and the reshaping of consumer behaviour to harmonize energy supply and demand dynamics. The catalyst for this transition lies in the formulation of strategic energy policies that empower consumers to actively participate in fostering of sustainable energy practice. In this framework, more consumers are becoming prosumers—actively involved in producing, storing, consuming, and managing energy. This paper focuses on energy prosumers, examining aspects such as energy efficiency, net-zero emissions, Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG 7), and energy electricity market models. This paper is designed with twofold goals: firstly, to untangle the shared models inherent in energy prosumer systems; secondly, to gain insights the context of energy prosumer dynamics. The findings highlight the progress made in energy prosumer systems models, challenges, and efficient adaptation to the new renewable energy business model. Addressing these challenges is crucial for fostering a sustainable and resilient energy future.

Keywords: Net zero emissions, Renewable energy, Energy Prosumers, Energy Policies

1. Introduction

The definition of consumer in economics is a person who uses goods and services to satisfies their needs. Energy prosumer is a new term which describes those who are energy producers and energy consumers at the same time. According to (Rodriguez et.al, 2014) the energy prosumer needs the development of new energy business models as well as effectively helps promoting the circular economy. (Pieńkowski, 2021) analysis four types of energy prosumers: residential, community/co-op, commercial, and public prosumers. These energy prosumers provide electricity, which is fed into the grid, while they also consume electricity supplied from the grid but generated by other suppliers. According to the European Environment Agency in Europe, there are different types of presuming including individual investment (on-site), collective prosumers in one building, community investment, and the creation of the Energy Community Cooperatives. Many developed countries have already set ambition targets which. For turning prosumers one of the key contributors with a large market share. Taking Finland as an example, (Child et.al, 2020) pointed out that by 2050, prosumers could self-generate up to 26% of the electricity consumed. Both individuals and groups can choose to become energy prosumers, contributing their efforts to achieving the goal of RE100. The 7th Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) by the UN focuses on providing universal access to affordable and clean energy sources. Energy prosumer model, a practice enabling individuals, communities, small and medium enterprises (SMEs), and others to generate electricity, particularly from renewable sources, stands out as a crucial and effective strategy in realizing this goal. Achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 necessitates a fundamental transformation in the energy power sector. This transformation involves a growing reliance on renewable sources s, facilitating both the consumption and production of renewable energy. Nevertheless, these developments will trigger the well-functioning of day a-head and intraday market enhancing the broad participation of all type of customers in the electricity market.

2. Methodology

Theoretical and energy prosumer modelling analysing.

3. Conclusions

The journey towards achieving net-zero emissions demands a contributing to the power sector evolution with a clear target, of power sector reformation towards reduction of emissions and boosting of technology and economy development. economic transformation, marked by both extensive scale and intricate execution. This research serves as a descriptive analytic modelling, for setting the ground for the model implementation in practice.

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Analysing the Relationship between Infrastructure and Tourism: Case of Albania

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Abstract

Infrastructure impacts on tourism and vice versa are more visible than ever. Tourism impacts the infrastructure in various ways such as: construction and modernization of the roads and encourages the constructions of new hotels, restaurants and other facilities in order to better accomplish the needs and desires of the tourists. Another important aspect through which tourism influences the infrastructure are the communications means as well as continuous investments in the framework of the latest technology. On the other side, a better transport infrastructure lowers the transportation costs and shortens the distance between origin and destination countries, which can stimulate international tourism flows. Having said that, the development of tourism sector depends on the infrastructure system, because if the opportunity of tourists to travel to a selected destination is impeded by inefficiencies in the transport system, they will seek alternative destinations. In this regard, a developed tourism must be preceded by a developed infrastructure, in order for the destination to become easier to access, better organized and more attractive. This study aims to analyse the relationship between tourism sector and infrastructure investment, by pointing out their interdependence. It highlights the significance of infrastructure in the tourism development and reveals the impact of tourism on the need for development of infrastructure components. This paper uses the VECM (Vector Error – Correction Model) and finds that infrastructure investments in Albania has been contributing positively to revenues generated from tourism sector.

Keywords: tourism development, infrastructure, investment, transport, communication.

JEL code: Z32, H54, E22, L91.

1. Introduction

Tourism is considered as the mainstay of economic development, because its social, political, cultural and economic implications are becoming bigger and bigger. For its development, infrastructure and investment improvement are considered essential needs, because the availability of tourism infrastructure within a destination will determine the amount and structure of tourist movement within it. A number of authors have cited the infrastructure base of a country as a potential determinant of the attractiveness of a destination. Investments in roads, railroads and airports reduce transportation costs for products and people and ensure access throughout the places. In this regard, in order for tourism industry to continue generating revenue, it is needed efficient and effective tourism infrastructure in place.

Tourist arrivals in Albania have increased at a growth rate of about 33% during 2022, compared to the previous year. Tourism revenues amounted to about 17% of gross domestic product, confirming that it is indeed a pillar of the economy. The cultural diversity, racial harmony, and natural beauty of Albania, make it an attractive destination. Despite this, the quality of infrastructures (transport and communication), can be an obstacle for successful tourism development. The subject of this paper is the assessment of the relationship of infrastructure investment and tourism development and points to the need of investment in infrastructure, as an important driver of improving the tourism sector. Based on these, is suggested the following

hypothesis: There is a positive relationship between the tourist's receipts and investment in infrastructure.

2. Literature Review

The relationship between infrastructure and tourism is emphasized in various studies, which underline two directions: the first one is the special role of tourism development in the infrastructure's modernizing, and the second is the reverse direction, the generation of multiplication effects of infrastructure development upon tourism (Mowforth and Munt 2003; Gunn 1994; Gunn and Var 2002; Eagles and McCool 2002). Efficient infrastructure is a factor which ensures the efficient functioning of the economy (Bookman and Bookman 2007). On the other side, if the infrastructure is weak, it can disrupt a country's economic development and international competitiveness (Tribe 2004; Hope 2010). Nguyen (2021) examined the impact of investment in tourism infrastructure development on attracting international visitors. Further, Lim et al. (2019, p. 187) emphasizes that "tourism infrastructure increases tourism demand trends".

Transport plays a big part of the tourist equation, and it is undeniable that transport infrastructure directly impacts the tourism infrastructure that attracts visitors. Kaul (1985) is among the first to recognize the importance of transport infrastructure as an essential component of successful development in tourism industry. Michniak et al. (2014), by using the potential accessibility approach, studied the impact of investments in road infrastructure on tourism development in terms of intensification of stays. Jou et al. (2012) focused on the influence of new road infrastructure on tourism behaviour. Communications infrastructure also plays a crucial role in attracting tourists. As such, good communication infrastructure provides quick and cheap communication between the origin and destination country. It also gives information on the destination and other tourism products and services, make informed decisions about where to go, by reducing uncertainty, fear and asymmetric information.

3. Methodology

This paper uses international tourism receipts per annum as the dependent variable, considered a measure for tourism revenue in Albania. In the focus are two main components of touristic infrastructure such as transport (Total inland transport infrastructure investment) and communication (internet user), which refers to individuals who have used the Internet in the last 3 months. Sandra Ajimotokin, Alexandra Haskins and Zach Wade (2015) conducted the effect of unemployment rate on crime condition from Federal Bureau, showing that there is a positive correlation between violent crime and unemployment rate. In this regard, this paper is using the unemployment rate as a proxy variable for crime rate of Albania. Another variable that has been considered important is GDP, where the expectation is that GDP and infrastructure investments are positively related. All variables are primary data from World Bank and OECD. Since the data set of this research is constructed in different kind of units, the gap between each variable are too large. In this regard, each variable is transformed to natural log. The following equation is going to be used: $\ln TR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln_III + \beta_2 \ln_GDP + \beta_3 \ln_Un + \beta_4 \ln_Int + u$.

First of all, both the Augmented Dickey and Fuller (ADF) unit root test (Dickey & Fuller, 1979; Dickey & Fuller, 1981) and Phillips and Perron (PP) unit root test (Phillips & Perron, 1988) are applied to test the stationarity of the series though the hypothesis: H_0 : time series is not stationary; H_a : time series is stationary. If the variables are integrated of order one $I(1)$, the Johansen cointegration test is applied to check if the series are cointegrated or not. In the case of cointegration presence between the variables under study, a subsequent analysis is performed by estimating a VECM.

4. Results and Discussion

In order to get the result of empirical estimation is used Statistic software (Stata) 17. The ADF and PP unit root results for all the variables indicate that, aa variables are non-stationary, in level, since the absolute value of the test statistic is smaller than the critical value at 1%, 5%, and 10%. Therefore, the null hypothesis for unit root cannot be rejected (the series are non-stationary). In this regard, were taken the first difference and the ADF and PP tests were again applied. At first difference, the absolute value of the test statistic is higher than the critical value at 1%, so the null hypothesis for unit root can be rejected. So, all the variables are stationary at the first difference, then integrated of order 1.

After confirming that the variables tested for unit root are integrated in the same order, the cointegration test is applied. The results of both trace statistics and maximum eigenvalue suggest the presence of 1 cointegrated vector among the time series variables at a 5% significance level. The findings suggest that there is a long-run relationship between the variables, which means that the variables move together closely to achieve the long-run equilibrium. And a long-run model, VECM, is applied. According to its results, all the independent variables are significant. Total inland transport infrastructure investment and Internet user carry positive coefficient, implying that they are important factors in accounting for tourism revenues. Also, Internet user and GDP have positive coefficients, while unemployment rate carries a negative one.

5. Conclusion

Tourism industry can support the country's economy as a main income generation source. Attracting international tourists is very important as they bring significant income, foreign currency, and jobs to countries. Therefore, for successful tourism growth, are needed more intensive investments in the development and maintenance of tourism infrastructure to make the destination more competitive and attractive are critical measures. Otherwise, if infrastructure is poor, it will lead to problems with its functionality and the tourist will be dissatisfied, so consequently the destination will be considered as uncompetitive. In this regard, should be taken into consideration the relationship between transport and tourism policy, since their coordination can improve visitor mobility to and within destinations, enhance visitor satisfaction, and help to secure the economic viability of local transport systems.

The main problem with transport in today's world is pollution. In this regard, it is of crucial importance to find the solution to making travelling more environment friendly in the future, in order to keep the air and water quality good for living.

Investment in infrastructure must represent a priority for national and local policies, since this sector represents the engine of local and national economies' development. Also, public investment in tourism infrastructure will encourage private sector investment. Therefore, this paper recommends:

- Identify factors that affect tourist travel demand and develop strategies that take such factors into account.
- The destination marketing and government agencies should work together to create the right conditions and physical infrastructure in order to achieve greater coherence of the destination experience.
- Encourage tourism and transport policymakers to work closer together to design transport services and infrastructure that respond to the needs of all travelers.
- Encourage international investment in tourism assets, as well as increase foreign direct investment in tourism and enhance sustainable infrastructure for tourism.
- Get feedback from tourists through existing mechanisms to better understand the problems they encounter and potential ways to enhance their experience.

6. Limitations

This study still has some limitations. Due to data limitations, it only takes in consideration 21 observation, consisting in the period 2001 - 2021. Also, in this study are taken in consideration two aspects of infrastructure: transport and communication. It would be of great interest to study how investment in the accommodation infrastructure would affect the tourism revenues. These issues may provide opportunities for further study.

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Tourism as a Transformative Tool Toward a Balanced Socio-Economic and Environmental Model of Development

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Abstract

The considerable literature and the experience of society tell us that the tourism sector directly contributes to a country's economic and social development models. At the same time, it has a noticeable impact on the natural environment and the heritage of society. Meanwhile, under the rhythms of advanced communication and information technologies, the role of the mission in question is growing. This paper will address the possibility of our country's Development under the indicators of sustainable Development, answering the following research question: How much and how the activity in the tourism sector can be designed and developed towards a development model that, while offering economic Development, considers and takes care of society and nature and simultaneously contributes to the recognition, preservation, and cultivation of the heritage of society and nature? Mainly using secondary sources, empirical, descriptive, and analysis, as well as other research study instruments, will provide opportunities to identify, compare, analyze, evaluate, and offer recommendations.

The paper's main conclusion is that reforming the country's development model under a balanced approach of economic, social, and environmental indicators is necessary to improve society's economic growth and well-being while preserving and caring for the societal and natural environment. This paper also recommends that the activity in the field of tourism become an essential instrument to reform and transform our country's development model towards the keyword of the contemporary global development model of sustainable Development.

Keywords: development model, sustainable model of Development, sustainable tourism;

1. Introduction and literature review

Sustainable tourism is a growing area of interest within the tourism industry, as it seeks to balance economic growth with environmental protection and social responsibility (World Tourism Organization, 2003). Several studies have examined the concept of sustainable tourism and its various dimensions. While domestic tourism, which proved to be an essential lifeline for many jobs and businesses during the pandemic, is projected to recover to pre-pandemic levels by 2023, the full recovery of international tourism is now expected to take up until 2025 or beyond (OECD, 2022). Countries with a sizeable tourism sector pre-COVID-19, such as Iceland (8.1% of GDP), Mexico (8.0%), and Portugal (8.1%), have experienced some of the most significant declines in the sector's direct contribution to GDP and in overall GDP (OECD, 2022).

This paper will address the possibility of our country's development under the indicators of sustainable development, answering the following research question: How much and how the activity in the tourism sector can be designed and developed towards a development model that, while offering economic development, considers and takes care of society and nature and simultaneously contributes to the recognition, preservation, and cultivation of the heritage of society and nature? The main hypothesis suggests that sustainable tourism in Albania and the WB region is positively associated with economic growth, environmental protection and social

responsibility practices. Measuring the sustainable tourism means measuring the environmental, social and economic costs of the model of development that we apply in daily life.

While tourism can generate significant revenue for local economies, it can also lead to economic leakage through the concentration of businesses and jobs in the tourism sector rather than another sectors Cohen, M. D., & Vorn, P. (2017). Different states are a primary concern in the tourism industry, as rapid growth has led to significant habitat destruction, pollution, and climate change Becken S, Hay J. (2007). Also, tourism activities also contribute to the overconsumption of natural resources, such as water and energy. To mitigate these impacts, sustainable tourism practices such as ecotourism and responsible travel have been developed (Lemelin & Gagnon, 2017). These approaches prioritize the conservation of natural environments and cultural heritage while promoting local economic Development and benefiting local communities. Social impacts are another essential aspect of sustainable tourism (UNWTO, 2023). Local people may feel marginalized or excluded from decision-making processes related to tourism development. To address these issues, community-based tourism (CBT) has emerged as an alternative approach involving local communities in planning and managing tourism activities Cohen et al., 2017). CBT can help ensure that benefits are shared more equitably among stakeholders and promote greater social inclusivity within host countries UN Environment (2017).

2. Methodology

As we discuss sustainable tourism, the question is raised: How to measure sustainable tourism? Tourism has become a significant economic driver in many sectors (D'Amore, 1988) with benefits for job creation, economic growth J.J. Liburd and D. Edwards (2010) and improved citizen well-being. However, there is also a risk of natural resource exploitation and damage when tourism is concentrated in one area. It is crucial to balance economic growth and the preservation of regional natural resources to maintain a high quality of life and promote sustainable development R. Harris, G. Tony, P. Williams (2002). Sustainable Development aims to achieve economic, social, and environmental sustainability, which coincides with three pillars of the triple-bottom-line approach. The triple bottom approach is a comprehensive framework that integrates these three pillars into business activities for private and public sector organizations (F.J. et al. (2016). It facilitates planning, reporting, and decision-making toward achieving Sustainable Development. This approach sets performance standards for economic, social, and environmental activities (J. Elkington, 1998). The benefits of implementing the triple bottom approach include increasing market position, cost savings, and improved stakeholder relations. It also leads to better strategic decision-making and benefits the wider community and destination.

To ensure the sustainability of tourism, the European Commission has created the 'European Tourism Indicators System' (ETIS) to help measure their performance. In Albania, sustainable tourism can be measured through different indicators that assess its environmental, social, and economic impacts.

To measure competitiveness in tourism, the measurement framework includes three indicators: core, supplementary, and future Development. Dupeyras et al., (2013). The authors suggest that comparing tourism's Direct Gross Domestic Product (GDP) over the years is crucial in determining tourism competitiveness and will strengthen the use of the TSA. The focus is on direct impacts, such as domestic and inbound tourism consumption. However, the future challenge lies in measuring the indirect and induced impacts. Comparing the change in Tourist Direct Gross Development Product over the years is the most commonly cited statistic for tourism competitiveness. Returning to Albania, the measurement of sustainable tourism can be done through various indicators assessing tourism's environmental, social, and economic

impacts. Various indicators can be used to measure sustainable tourism in Albania and the region, assessing its environmental, social, and economic impacts. Here are some key indicators: Among the environmental impacts, the author brings to attention the following indicators in this paper. Carbon emissions calculate the carbon footprint of tourists and businesses in the sector. Recent studies over the past 10 years have estimated that tourism's contribution to global GHG emissions ranged between 5% (UNWTO and UNEP, 2008; OECD/UNEP, 2011; UNWTO and ITF, 2019), and closer to 8% (Lenzen, M., et al. 2018). including transportation, accommodation, and activities. Based on data from the United Nations Environment Programme (2021), air and water pollution, overconsumption of natural resources, and increasing greenhouse gases (GHG) threaten people and the planet. "Air pollution accounts for an estimated seven million premature deaths each year" and "rising global greenhouse gas emissions are resulting in record-breaking temperatures and more extreme weather" (UNWTO, 2022).

The economic Impacts of the tourist activity may be measured through revenue generation, which shows the total revenue generated by tourism in the country. All these arguments contribute directly to the SDG 3 on good health and wellbeing's. The following graph is presented if I refer to the Tourism Working Group survey results (2023).

Figure 1. Employment (in1000) in tourism. **Figure 2.** Top Sustainable Development Goals that tourism contributes to.

Source: WTO, 2023 (2023)

Source: G20 Tourism Working Group survey results

In 2020, the tourism sector generated 42 thousand employees in Albania. In 2023 there is a significant growth on tourism sector. Gov AI (2023). Tourism is one of the top four export earners globally and currently provides one in ten jobs worldwide. As a services trade, it can help achieve SDG 8 on decent work and economic growth. Providing decent work opportunities in tourism, particularly for youth and women, and policies encouraging better diversification through tourism value chains can enhance tourism's positive socio-economic impacts.

Figure 1 and 2. Compare of the tourism indicators in Albania and Serbia
Source: WTO, 2022

If we compare indicators across countries in the Western Balkans, it is visible that Albania has significant positive indicators compared to Serbia.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the G20 Tourism Working Group survey results (2023), Green Tourism is the top priority ranking for tourism activity, followed by digitalization, destination management, skills, and tourism SMEs. Tourism can also contribute to sustainable cities and communities, as stated in SDG 11. It can promote urban infrastructure and accessibility, preserve cultural and natural heritage, and support regeneration. Investment in green infrastructure, such as more efficient transport and reduced air pollution, can lead to more innovative and greener cities that benefit residents and tourists. In order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal 12, which focuses on responsible consumption and production, the tourism sector needs to adopt sustainable consumption and production methods. By keeping track of sustainable development impacts in tourism, such as energy, water, waste, biodiversity, and job creation, the tourism industry can achieve better economic, social, and environmental outcomes. Tourism is a crucial contributor to economic growth, employment, and other social dimensions, as evidenced by the Sustainable Development Goals 2030. As one of the largest and fastest-growing economic sectors globally, tourism can help foster economic growth and Development at all levels by creating jobs and providing income. It directly impacts SDG 1, no poverty, and its sub-goals. Sustainable tourism development can be linked with national poverty reduction goals, promoting entrepreneurship and small businesses, and empowering less favored groups, particularly youth and women, at the community level.

4. Conclusion

The main conclusion of the paper is that the country's development model needs to be reformed under the concept of a balanced approach to economic, social, and environmental indicators. As the 17 SDGs and the corresponding 169 SDG targets offer the world a new direction, tourism can and must play a significant role in delivering sustainable solutions for people, the planet, prosperity, and peace. This is necessary to enable economic growth and well-being for society while preserving and caring for the natural environment. Tourism has the potential to contribute, directly or indirectly, to all of the SD goals. In particular, Goals 8, 12, and 14 have been included as targets for inclusive and sustainable economic growth, sustainable consumption and production (SCP), and the sustainable use of oceans and marine resources, respectively. The paper also recommends that the field of tourism can become an important instrument to reform and transform the development Albanian model of the country towards sustainable Development, which is the keyword of the global development model. The advancements in society's knowledge and technology provide great opportunities to achieve these objectives.

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The Energy-Growth Nexus Revisited: An International Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

This paper undertakes a comprehensive review of the rapidly expanding literature of energy consumption-economic growth nexus. The analysis includes three categories of energy consumption: total energy consumption, aggregate renewable energy consumption, and disaggregate renewable energy consumption. The study also discusses various hypotheses related to the causal interaction between these variables, providing an overview of the empirical literature. Notably, the survey highlights that most empirical studies predominantly concentrate on either investigating the direction of causality between energy consumption and economic growth or assessing the role of energy consumption in stimulating economic growth. A general observation drawn from these studies is that the existing literature lacks consensus on the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth, primarily due to variations in the structural features of analysed countries, their developmental stages, the diverse econometric methods employed, and the disparate time frames under examination. The authors should prioritize exploring new approaches and perspectives in their research, by utilizing multivariate models, rather than relying on a common set of variables across diverse countries and time intervals, for a deeper understanding of the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth.

Keywords: Energy Consumption, Economic Growth, Renewable Energy Consumption

JEL codes: O4, Q43, Q48

1. Introduction

Energy is widely recognized as a pivotal factor in driving economic development. In recent years the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth has emerged as a major area of scientific research and policy consideration. The complex interplay between energy resources and economic activities has far-reaching implications for both developed and developing countries, affecting economic stability, environmental sustainability and societal well-being. Understanding this nexus is paramount in designing and implementing environmental and energy policies.

Despite decades of extensive study within energy economics literature, the causal relationship between energy consumption and economic growth remains elusive and empirical research has failed to provide a consensus on this relationship. The absence of agreement on the link between energy consumption and economic growth in the literature is due to the structural differences among analysed countries, variations in their development stage, diverse econometric methods used, different proxy variables used, and different time periods analyzed. The outcomes seem to be different in terms of the direction of causality and its long-term versus short-term effect on energy policy.

The literature on the causal relationship between energy type variables and economic growth could be synthesized into four testable hypotheses: neutrality, growth, conservation, and feedback hypothesis. (i) First, the neutrality hypothesis or “non-causality hypothesis” suggests that there is no econometrically valid relationship between energy consumption and economic growth; (ii) Second, the growth hypothesis or the “uni-directional causality from energy consumption” suggests that there is unidirectional causal relationship running from energy consumption to economic growth; (iii) Third, the conservation hypothesis or the “uni-directional causality from economic growth” assumes that real GDP growth influences the consumption of energy; (iv) Finally, the feedback hypothesis or the “bi-directional causality” suggests that energy consumption and economic growth are interdependent.

The aim of this study is to synthesize the existing literature on the causal relationship between energy consumption and economic growth nexus. The literature is classified into three strands. The first strand comprises studies which investigate the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth without making any qualitative discrimination. The second strand is composed of studies which analyse the relationship between aggregate renewable energy consumption and economic growth. Meanwhile the third strand includes studies which investigate the relationship between disaggregate renewable energy consumption and economic growth. Through the combination of key findings, methodological approaches, and theoretical frameworks, this literature survey seeks to shed light on the causal relationships, feedback mechanisms, and policy implications inherent in the energy-economic growth paradigm.

2. Methodology

The concept of a causal relationship between energy consumption and economic growth was initially introduced in the seminal paper by Kraft and Kraft (1978), who investigated this relationship in the context of the United States. Consequently, numerous studies have attempted to establish and understand the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth. The methodology employed in this study involves the synthesis and analysis of empirical studies, that explain this relationship. A common observation from these studies is the variability in results: some indicate causality running from economic growth to energy consumption, others suggest causality from energy consumption to economic growth, and there are instances where no causality or bi-directional causality between these variables is found. The analysis of the literature is structured into three sections. The first section provides a literature review for total energy consumption-growth nexus, the second section analyses aggregate renewable energy consumption-economic growth relationship, while third section analyses the disaggregate renewable energy consumption-economic growth relationship. A chronological list of the empirical literature on the causality between energy consumption and economic growth by author, time frame, country, methodology, and empirical results is provided in this literature survey.

3. Results and Discussion

The first category of literature encompasses studies analyzing the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth. A general conclusion from these studies is that, with respect to the conclusions related to the conservation, growth, neutrality, and feedback hypotheses, the results exhibit significant variability across the 25 reported studies. Since all types of causality results (uni-directional causality, bi-directional causality and no causality) have been reported in the literature, it is difficult to reach a conclusion on the relationship between energy and economic growth. The results for each hypothesis are given by percentage in Figure 1. The findings from the surveyed studies reveal a distribution of support among hypotheses, with 24% confirming the conservation hypothesis, 24% the growth hypothesis,

37% the feedback hypothesis, and 15% the neutrality hypothesis. Notably, when considering the cumulative findings from 61% of the surveyed countries supporting either the feedback or growth hypotheses, it suggests that energy conservation policies which could negatively impact on energy consumption might consequently have adverse effects on economic growth.

Figure 1. Hypotheses for Total Energy Consumption-Economic Growth Nexus
Source: Own research

The second strand of literature consists of studies exploring the relationship between aggregate renewable energy consumption and economic growth. The findings across the 10 reported studies show a diverse range of outcomes. Illustrated in Figure 2, the results for each hypothesis are presented as percentages. The results for surveyed studies show that 57% supported the feedback hypothesis; 22% supported the neutrality hypothesis; 14% supported the growth hypothesis, and only 7% the conservation hypothesis. In this context, energy conservation policies may have an adverse effect on economic growth and changes in economic growth are reflected back in energy consumption.

Figure 2. Hypotheses for Aggregate Renewable Energy Consumption-Economic Growth Nexus
Source: Own research

The third strand of literature includes studies examining the relationship between individual renewable energy sources and economic growth. The findings across the 7 reported studies are illustrated in Figure 3, where the results for each hypothesis are presented as percentages. The results for surveyed studies show that 46% supported the feedback hypothesis; 23% supported the growth hypothesis, and 31% supported the conservation hypothesis.

Figure 3. Hypotheses for Disaggregate Renewable Energy Consumption-Economic Growth Nexus

Source: Own research

4. Conclusions

The main objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive survey of the literature focused on the causal relationship between energy consumption and economic growth. Additionally, this survey provides researchers with an overview of the literature on the causality between total energy and renewable energy consumption and economic growth, particularly in the context of country-specific studies. Understanding this nexus is very important in designing and implementing effective environmental and energy policies.

A general conclusion derived from these studies is the absence of consensus regarding both the existence and the direction of causality between these variables in the literature. The conflicting results, concerning the four hypotheses (neutrality, growth, conservation, and feedback), can be attributed to the different data set, selected countries, proxy variables and econometric techniques employed across different studies. This review analysis indicates that 24% of the studies confirm the conservation hypothesis, 24% confirm the growth hypothesis, 37% confirm the feedback hypothesis, and 15% confirm the neutrality hypothesis for total energy consumption-economic growth relationship. For aggregate renewable energy consumption-economic growth nexus, our finding reveals that 57% supported the feedback hypothesis; 22% supported the neutrality hypothesis; 14% supported the growth hypothesis, and only 7% supported the conservation hypothesis. While for the disaggregate renewable energy consumption-economic growth nexus, our finding reveals that 46% supported the feedback hypothesis; 23% supported the growth hypothesis, and 31% supported the conservation hypothesis. Since most of the studies included in the analysis support the feedback hypothesis, then energy conservation policies will reduce the performance of economic growth and changes in economic growth will be reflected back in energy consumption.

According to Ozturk (2010), to avoid these conflicting and unreliable results and to get a better understanding of energy consumption-economic growth relationship, the authors should focus

more on the new methods, employ multivariate models including new variables and consider the unrecorded economy, especially in developing countries in which the size of unrecorded economy is large. Using the same methods with the same variables, just by changing the time period examined, will not have more potential to contribute to the existing energy–growth literature (Karanfil, 2009).

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Tourism in Global South: Shaping Sustainable Ecotourism in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study examines the current tourism development in one of the highly fragile remote mountain regions aswdain Pakistan and to emphasis the need to develop an ecotourism model. It examines the preference and activities of tourists and the environmental issues associated with the current mass tourism in Hunza Valley. The study collected data from 1046 tourists between 2021 and 2022 through field surveys and analyzed it using descriptive statistical tools. The findings highlight a prevalent trend of group travel and a diverse range of tourist activities in Hunza valley. The study asserts that the growing number of tourists has led to environmental challenges, including pollution, waste accumulation, and disturbances to wildlife and vegetation and addressing these issues requires immediate adoption of sustainable practices, proactive management, and collaboration among stakeholders. The study strongly advocates for promoting tourism development in the region based on an ecotourism model, which emphasizes responsible and nature-focused travel. The study also underscores the significant economic contributions of tourists in the Hunza Valley to the local economy and thus, policymakers are advised to provide support to local businesses, invest in accommodations, encourage sustainability, engage with communities, and diversify attractions. These measures aim to maximize the positive impacts of tourism for sustainable development. This study argues that tourism is reshaping the region's economy and thus, it is crucial to ensure tourism development on the basis of ecotourism principles.

Keywords: Mountain Tourism, Sustainable Tourism Model, Local Economies

JEL codes: Z32, L83, Z38, R11

1. Introduction

Tourism is one of the fastest growing sectors in developing countries and such rapid growth in tourism has raised the prospects that tourism is the main agent of socio-economic development (Tapper 2001). Traveling from developed countries to developing countries and from urban to rural areas is an emerging segment of leisure market (Rinzin et. al. 2007). The major forces behind the increasing growth of the traveling and tourism sector in developing countries are the pristine natural beauty and cultural diversity in the exotic destinations. Changing in lifestyles of developed countries where people tend to spend more time on leisure activities is also one of forcing factors of traveling to developing countries (Veenhoven 1999).

Gilgit-Baltistan is a mountainous region located the northern part of Pakistan. It provides tremendous recreational opportunities to national and international tourists Ali and Shedayi (2023). The most prominent purposes are recreational activities, adventure activities and culture tourism (Shedayi et al. 2022). However, the flow of tourist arrivals remains changed with the passage of seasons as most recreational and cultural tourists visit during summer season of the year whereas, adventure tourists visit throughout the year. Since the weather in Winter season remains very cold in most of the tourists' destination, therefore, the flow of

tourists in the region remains low comparatively. In the case of recreational activities, visitors enjoy the natural landscape, mighty mountains, and grasp of the nuanced dynamics of tourism development in the region. While scholars have dissected various dimensions of tourism in isolated studies, there exists a crucial requirement to synthesize and integrate these findings. Such a comprehensive understanding is essential to paint a holistic picture of tourism's evolution in this region. Consequently, the dividends of such endeavors can be equitably distributed across the entire region and to the visiting tourists. This study thus seeks to offer an encompassing analysis of the ongoing tourism development in Gilgit-Baltistan, with a specific focus on the case of Hunza Valley. The insights derived from this research endeavor can subsequently serve as a foundational cornerstone for the formulation of an effective ecotourism model.

2. Methodology

This study is based on a quantitative research approach where data were collected through an on-site survey conducted over the span of 2021 to 2022. To facilitate this endeavor, a meticulously designed questionnaire was formulated, informed by a comprehensive review of existing literature and expert insights from seasoned tourism professionals. This questionnaire was subsequently subjected to a pilot test, engaging 40 tourists, the valuable feedback from which prompted necessary refinements before the final survey was administered. The survey itself was a comprehensive undertaking, reaching out to a diverse array of tourists across various tourist destinations within the captivating expanse of Hunza Valley. This enabled to capture the breadth of experiences and preferences that encompass the region's unique tourism landscape. Upon the culmination of the survey, a total of 1046 valid responses were collated and used as the dataset for meticulous analysis, lending robustness to the subsequent findings. The survey was done through enumerators. To ensure the quality and ethical conduct of the survey, a team of five university graduates was hired and these enumerators were selected based on their proficiency and understanding of the research process and such training equipped them to navigate potential challenges and maintain consistency in data collection.

3. Results and Discussion

The data analysis is mainly done by using descriptive statistical tools as table 1 depicts a prevailing trend among tourists visiting Hunza valley, where a substantial majority opt for private arrangements, often involving their own vehicles, to explore the region collectively. Group travel is the predominant mode of exploration, with distinct patterns emerging. Specifically, journeys undertaken with family members (n=490) hold the foremost position, closely followed by group visits that encompass both relatives and friends (n=430). This analysis underscores the substantial prevalence of group travel experiences in the region. Considering these findings, it becomes evident that the region's tourism policies could be strategically aligned with the prevalent group travel trend. Recognizing the popularity of group excursions, the local authorities could prioritize the development of amenities and services tailored to accommodate larger parties. For instance, facilitating well-equipped rest areas, ample parking spaces, and enhanced guidance for larger groups could significantly enhance the overall tourist experience. Moreover, considering that group travel often involves multiple generations, the creation of age-friendly facilities and accessible paths would contribute to a more inclusive and enjoyable visit for all. Collaboration with private tour operators and guides specialized in handling group visits could further elevate the quality of these experiences. By fostering partnerships with local businesses, the region can ensure that the unique cultural and natural heritage is showcased responsibly to larger groups of visitors. Ultimately, these insights provide a foundation for targeted policy adjustments that not only align with the preferences of tourists but also promote sustainable tourism practices.

Table 1: Trip arrangements

	Trip Arrangement				Total
	On a package(via tour company)	Private arrangement (self/with friend/relative)	Institutional Arrangement	educational Trip/visit	
single	5	18	1	1	25
Group with family members	68	420	1	1	490
Group with relatives and friends	43	379	6	2	430
Group official visit with staff	10	17	6	1	34
Group-with tour company travelers	3	0	0	0	3
Group trip	53	10	0	0	63
Total	182	844	14	5	1045

Source: Authors' own calculation based on survey data

Analyzing the travel preferences of the respondents reveals a consistent pattern this study reveals that a majority of visitors arrive in groups regardless of the season. This trend can be attributed to the considerable distance to the valley, making group travel a more practical and enjoyable option for many. Further exploration of group dynamics uncovers that, across all seasons, the largest portion of visitors consists of families. This emphasizes the familial nature of the visits. Additionally, a substantial number of visitors opt to explore the valley with both relatives and friends, indicating a preference for shared experiences. This insight is visually depicted in Table 1, providing a clear representation of the distribution of group characteristics among the respondents. These results help tourism managers plan and manage the utilization of local resources such as accommodation, transportation, and attractions more effectively. It will also help policymakers to ensure that the local infrastructure can handle the influx of visitors without compromising the environment or visitor experience.

Table 2: Tourists activities in Hunza valley

	Culture	Hiking/trekking	Boating	Wildlife	Glacier	Lake	Nature
Spring	57.8	76.4	28.5	29.3	39.9	41.1	75.3
Summer	65.5	59.6	31.5	24.5	62	53.9	78.2
Autumn	68.6	1.8	6.3	16.6	24.2	33.6	74.3
Winter	70.9	2.1	1.6	19	26.5	36	76.5
	65.7	34.975	16.975	22.35	38.15	41.15	76.075

Source: Authors' own calculation based on survey data

This study underscores the diverse range of activities that tourists actively engage in while exploring Hunza Valley, revealing a multifaceted tourism landscape. From the survey data, this

study highlights the following activities and their corresponding percentages: hiking/trekking (34.97%), boating (16.9%), wildlife viewing (22.35%), glacier exploration (38.15%), lake visits (41.15%), and a general interest in experiencing the natural allure of the region (76%). Moreover, cultural site visits also emerge as substantial (65.7%). The implications of these findings have policy applications for sustainable tourism development. For instance, the substantial interest in hiking and trekking necessitates policies that establish well-marked trails, promote responsible trekking behavior, and ensure proper waste disposal to preserve the pristine landscapes. Similarly, the appeal of boating and wildlife viewing emphasizes the importance of establishing guidelines to regulate water-based activities and wildlife encounters, ensuring minimal ecological disruption. The pronounced desire to explore glaciers and lakes calls for policies focused on preserving these fragile ecosystems through controlled access and promoting educational initiatives that underscore their significance. The overwhelming interest in experiencing the natural charm of the region underscores the necessity of implementing policies that emphasize conservation and minimize the environmental impact of tourism activities.

The average duration of visitors' stays in Hunza Valley across different seasons is shown in table 3 and it is found that the majority of visitors tend to stay for an average of 3.9 days during the spring, 3.3 days in the summer, 3.2 days in the autumn, and 3.1 days in the winter. This indicates that visitors are inclined to spend a substantial portion of their time exploring the valley's offerings throughout the year. The calculated overall average stay period of 3.4 days provides a valuable insight for policy formulation in the realm of sustainable tourism. It implies the importance of efficient transportation, quality accommodations, and a diverse range of experiences that cater to different seasons. Through strategically aligning tourism offerings with visitors' typical stay periods, policymakers can enhance both the economic impact of tourism and the overall satisfaction of visitors while ensuring that natural and cultural resources are conserved for future generations.

Table 3: Stay Period

Days	Spring		Summer		Autumn		Winter	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1-2	53	20.15	152	40.97	90	40.36	72	38.10
3-4	124	47.15	156	42.05	99	44.39	87	46.03
5-6	63	23.95	40	10.78	31	13.90	27	14.29
Above 6	23	8.75	23	6.20	3	1.35	3	1.59
Total	263	100	371	100	223	100	189	100
Average	3.9		3.3		3.2		3.1	
Overall Average	3.4							

Source: Authors' own calculation based on survey data

Mountain tourist destinations face significant vulnerability due to the escalating number of visitors as Hillery et al. (2001) asserted that the more appealing a tourist spot, the greater its renown, subsequently increasing the risk of degradation due to the surge in visitor numbers. As a result, this can diminish the overall quality of visitors' experiences. A comprehensive grasp of tourists' perceptions regarding the impact of tourism is pivotal for formulating effective management and promotional strategies. In the context of understanding tourist perceptions about the environmental impact of tourism in the valley, respondents were asked to identify the issues they observed. According to Table 4, a majority of participants indicated that the current state of tourism in Hunza valley leads to issues such as air pollution, accumulation of solid waste and litter, intensified pressure on land use, including the

conversion of cultivated and uncultivated land into developed areas, amplified noise pollution, disruptions to wildlife, and damage to vegetation. These critical concerns underscore the unsustainability of the current tourism practices. This analysis underscores the necessity to proactively address all the aforementioned consequences of tourism in a timely manner, in order to establish a foundation for sustainable nature-based tourism in the valley. The high mountain tourist destinations in Pakistan are already exceptionally susceptible to the impacts of climate change, necessitating a robust destination plan that effectively mitigates the ramifications of both climatic shifts and human-induced activities within these sites.

Table 4: Respondents' perception on environmental concerns of Tourism

Rating	Air Pollution	Solid Waste and Littering	Pressure on land use change	Noise Pollution	disturbance to wildlife	Current tourism seems unsustainable
Disagree	0.0	2.9	1.7	3.8	8.0	12.0
Don't know	12.1	16.9	11.8	20.7	28.6	25.0
Agree	47.0	66.3	54.8	62.6	56.0	52.5
Strongly Agree	40.8	14.0	31.7	12.9	7.3	10.4

Source: Authors' own calculation based on survey data

The expenditure pattern of tourists in Hunza Valley, as shown in Table 5, demonstrates that visitors spend on average PKR 15,440 on food, PKR 21,278 on accommodation, PKR 5,233 on handicrafts, PKR 3,952 on dry fruits, and PKR 2,486 on local traditional food during their stay. This insightful breakdown reveals the economic avenues that contribute significantly to the local economy and to capitalize on these findings, policymakers can adopt a multi-faceted approach. This includes promoting local businesses by enhancing handicraft production and traditional food experiences. Investing in accommodation facilities would not only attract more tourists but also generate employment opportunities. By fostering sustainable tourism practices and encouraging engagement with local communities, the valley can preserve its natural beauty and cultural heritage. The support for artisans, agri-tourism initiatives, and diverse attractions can collectively extend tourists' stays, thereby maximizing the economic and socio-cultural benefits of tourism for Hunza Valley's sustainable development.

Table 5: Tourism Spending Pattern

Expenditures	Average Spending in PKR	Per Day Spending In PKR
Food	15440	4541
Accommodation	21278	6258
Handicrafts	5223	1536
Dry Fruits	3952	1162
Local Traditional Food	2486	731

Source: Authors' own calculation based on survey data

The results of this study serve as a foundational framework for the development of an eco-tourism model tailored specifically to the unique characteristics and challenges of the Hunza Valley of Pakistan. It argues that leveraging the predominant trend of group travel, the model prioritizes the enhancement of amenities and services to accommodate larger parties, aligning

tourism policies with the prevalent group travel dynamics and recognizing the diverse range of activities that tourists engage in, the model integrates policies focused on sustainable tourism development, emphasizing responsible trekking, regulated water-based activities, and controlled access to fragile ecosystems like glaciers and lakes. The model addresses the average duration of visitors' stays, emphasizing the importance of well-designed itineraries and a diverse range of experiences that cater to different seasons. In response to tourists' perceptions of environmental impact, the eco-tourism model includes proactive measures to address issues such as air and noise pollution, waste accumulation, and disruptions to wildlife and vegetation. Finally, the model capitalizes on the expenditure pattern of tourists, promoting local businesses through initiatives such as handicraft production and traditional food experiences, contributing to the economic and socio-cultural sustainability of Hunza Valley. Overall, the eco-tourism model integrates these insights into a holistic approach that not only enhances the visitor experience but also prioritizes the conservation of natural and cultural resources, fostering sustainable development in the high mountain tourist destination of Hunza Valley. This analysis leads to the development of the following framework for sustainable eco-tourism in the study which is aligned with the indicator framework of Batta (2006)

Figure 1: Framework for Sustainable Eco-tourism

The framework explained in figure 1 shows the critical role of Gilgit-Baltistan's economy in recognizing and valuing the natural resources and assets inherent to the region as it underscores the importance of allocating adequate funds for the conservation of these natural attractions, which serve as the primary catalysts for tourism development in the area. As these resources contribute significantly to the local economy, it becomes imperative for the local community to actively advocate for their conservation. In this symbiotic relationship, the local community becomes a valuable human resource, contributing to the overall economic vitality.

4. Conclusion

The understanding of interplay between tourism development and environmental preservation is essential to safeguard the region's future prosperity in Gilgit-Baltistan Pakistan. This study

shows that the majority of visitors embark on their journeys collectively, often with family members or a combination of relatives and friends and this collective exploration trend holds potential for strategic policy alignment. Tourism managers and policymakers should capitalize on this penchant for group travel by offering amenities and services tailored to accommodate larger parties and for this purpose, the establishment of environmentally friendly guest houses along with tour guiding facilities for the nearby destinations can significantly enhance the overall visitor experience. Collaborative ventures with private tour operators specializing in group visits would further enrich these experiences, ensuring responsible and immersive encounters with the region's natural and cultural heritage. The study further unveils the multifaceted tapestry of activities tourists take part in while exploring Hunza Valley. From hiking to glacier exploration, wildlife viewing to cultural site visits, the region offers a diverse array of experiences that cater to varied interests. This array of activities emphasizes the need for targeted policy formulation that fosters sustainable tourism practices and guidelines for responsible trekking, regulations for water-based activities, and strategies for conserving fragile ecosystems—such as glaciers and lakes—can all contribute to a harmonious blend of exploration and preservation. These policies could extend to waste reduction initiatives, reforestation efforts, and sustainable transportation options, collectively striving to minimize the environmental footprint of tourism. This argues that through offering well-designed itineraries, activities, and attractions within these durations, policymakers can optimize visitors' experiences while conserving the region's natural and cultural resources. This study concludes that for better management of tourism and to develop an ecotourism model for the region, it is essential to understand the linkages among the natural attractions (natural resources), local economy and the local communities of the region. Creating synergy among these sectors is demand of the time and policymakers and tourism manager should pay more attention to such linkages to ensure sustainable tourism in the region.

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Investigating the Relationship between FDI and Tourism Growth in Albania

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Abstract

This research paper explores the relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) stock in tourism industry growth. Realizing the importance of tourism industry in their economy, many governments decide to take concrete to invest or attract foreign investment to improve the infrastructure of tourist destinations, in order to create a competitive offer for tourists. The study uses Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to assess the nature and significance of this relationship, using quarterly time series data from 2014Q1 to 2023Q2. The results indicate that there is a long run cointegration between the international tourist arrivals and the foreign direct investment in Albania.

Keywords: *Tourism, Foreign Direct Investment, ARDL*

JEL codes: Z31, Z32, E22, P45

1. Introduction

For many countries, tourism sector has become an important source of income and economic growth. According to the UNWTO (1980, p.2), tourism has been described as “an activity essential to the life of nations because of its direct impacts on the social, cultural, educational and economic fields of national societies, as well as on their international relations”.

Realizing the importance of this sector in their economy, many governments decide to take concrete actions for the promotion and development of tourism. They invest or attract foreign investment to improve the infrastructure of tourist destinations, in order to create a competitive offer for tourists. These investments have contributed to the development of transport, accommodation, and service infrastructure (Sukhanova, 2019). The development of the tourism sector can lead to increased export earnings, the creation of new employment opportunities, bringing about direct or indirect advances, and providing employment opportunities for unemployed youth and women. (Fauzel et al., 2017).

Foreign direct investment (FDI) is one of the engines through which developing countries can develop their tourism sector; but the dynamics of FDI and its implications in this growing sector have been relatively little studied. (UNCTAD, 2007). FDI plays an important role in the development of industry, especially in developing countries. It provides capital and infrastructure, such as international airports, highways, hotels, and modern technologies, which are key elements of tourism development (UNCTAD, 2000; Selvanathan et al 2012; Samimi et al.,2013 Khoshnevis, 2017).

In Albania, the tourism sector is one of the biggest contributors to the economy. Only for the year 2022, WTTC (2023) has estimated that the impact of this sector on the Gross Domestic Product is about 21.6% or 444.3 million Euros, while it is predicted to increase to 22% of the GDP in 2023.

Since the Covid-19 pandemic, Albania has been considered one of the countries with the fastest recovery in the tourism sector. (UNDP,2022; WTTC, 2023). Specifically, there has been an

increase in the number of tourists. In 2022, the country welcomed around 7.5 million international tourists, marking a significant growth of 32.6% compared to the previous year, despite the insecurities from the Russia-Ukraine aggression and inflation.

On the other hand, in the last decade, Albania has also noticed an increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) flows. According to the data of the Bank of Albania (2023), the direction of FDI inflow has been oriented by sectors such as extractive and processing industry, energy, hydrocarbons, and the financial sector. Meanwhile, in the last 5 years, there is an increasing trend of flows in sectors such as real estate, transport, accommodation and food services, agriculture, forests, and fishing, which are sectors assessed as priority for the development of the country. (Bank of Albania, 2023).

In the last Tourism Strategy 2019-2023, the government policies are intended to prioritize public investments, encourage private investments with the aim of attracting a greater number of tourists the return of the tourism industry, as one of the three main pillars of the Albanian economy.

Despite the attention given to the growth of private investments in the tourism sector through the absorption of foreign capital in Albania, to the authors' knowledge, there is no empirical evidence of this relationship. Therefore, the main purpose of this research paper is to assess whether there is an impact of foreign direct investments in the growth of the tourism sector in Albania.

2. Methodology

In this research paper is used quarterly time series data for the period 2014Q1 to 2023Q2 for the variables in natural log form.

The interested variable (used as proxy for tourism growth) is the number of international tourist arrivals (ITA) from Albanian Institute of Statistics, which is seasonally adjusted by authors in Eviews10, by CensusX-13 model, to take consistent results. The second variable is the amount of transport and accommodation FDI stock (TFDIs) in million Euro from Bank of Albania, used as a proxy for FDI in tourism. The authors have chosen to work with stock data, because it is preferable and suggested for many analytical purposes and use of the data in this way is consistent with FDI theory. (UNCTAD,2007; Ford et al,2008; Peric,2016).

First it is tested for unit root presence in each variable to find the order of integration of variables using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test and Zivot-Andrew's test which is suggested to identify the unit root presence in structural breaks. Due to Covid-19 pandemic presence, we expect the ITA series to have a structural break during 2020, as there was a total shutdown of the country. After the unit root test, it is used the bound cointegration test to assess if there is a long run cointegration between the variables.

Since the variables results integrated in different order $I(0)$ and $I(1)$, an ARDL model (Pesaran et al.,2001) will be evaluated to see the connection in the long-term and short-term period of the variables. To measure the effect of the Covid-19 pandemic, a dummy variable for the second quarter of 2020 is included in the model.

In the end, the diagnostic tests were conducted to ensure that the model was specified correctly.

3. Results and Discussion

To study the order of integration of series, the Augmented Dickey Fuller unit root is used, as well as Zivot-Andrews unit root test for structural breaks. Zivot and Andrew's unit root test conclude that $\ln ITA$ and $\ln GDP$ variables are stationary in level [$I(0)$], while $\ln TFDIs$ is stationary in first differences [$I(1)$], with structural break on 2020Q2 and 2021Q2 specifically. Since the variables of interest are of mixed order of integration, to estimate the long run and short run effect within variables an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model is used.

First, it is tested if the variables are related in the long term through the ARDL bound test. The null hypothesis indicates that there is no cointegration between the variables and is rejected if the F statistic is greater than the critical values.

The bound test results shows that the null hypothesis rejects, confirming a long-term relationship between the variables of interest, which means that even if there is a shock in the short-term period which can affect the movement of the individual series, they will converge in time, in the long-term.

Since there is cointegration, then the error correction model is followed. It results that FDI stock in accommodation and transport has a positive and significant impact on international tourism arrivals in short and long run. In the model, the error correction term has a negative sign and is significant, indicating how much of adjustment from short run to long run takes place each quarter. The negative effect of Covid 19 pandemic is shown by the dummy variable, which is an exogenous variable in this model. The coefficient is negative and significant at 5%.

4. Conclusions

This research paper is an attempt to examine the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI stock in accommodation and transportation is used as proxy) on the tourism growth (international tourist arrivals is used as proxy) of Albania over the period 2014Q1 to 2023Q2. It adapted the autoregressive distributed lagged model, and the estimation results support the existence of the long-run equilibrium relationship between them.

The error correction coefficient is negative and significant indicating that the causality runs from the explanatory variables to international tourist arrivals, and, in addition, the magnitude of the coefficient shows how many quarters takes to restore the long-run equilibrium after a short-run shock, such as Covid-19 pandemic.

This research paper results emphasise the importance of foreign direct investment in the tourism sector. Since FDI have a positive and significant impact in tourism sector, the government should take appropriate policies to attract investment from multinational corporations, to help tourism industry growth and to make Albania more attractive and competitive compering to other regional countries.

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Albanian Startup Ecosystem: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

This paper examines the Albanian startup ecosystem, highlighting challenges, opportunities, and offering actionable recommendations. Challenges encompass funding limitations, regulatory hurdles, and a nascent venture capital industry. Opportunities include market potential, a skilled workforce, and government support. Recommendations focus on capital access, regulatory reform, cross-sector collaboration, entrepreneurship culture, and mentorship programs. This study informs stakeholders, guiding the growth of a vibrant Albanian startup ecosystem.

Keywords: startups, ecosystem in Albania, challenges, opportunities

JEL codes: H80, H81

1. Introduction

The startup ecosystem in Albania is still in its early stages of development, but it has the potential to become a major driver of economic growth and innovation in the country. Albania has a young population, a growing tech sector, and a number of government initiatives aimed at supporting startups. However, there are still a number of challenges that need to be addressed in order for the startup ecosystem to thrive.

The Quintuple Innovation Helix model is a framework for understanding innovation that recognizes the role of five key stakeholders:

- **Government:** The government plays a key role in creating a supportive environment for innovation, through policies and programs that promote entrepreneurship, research and development, and access to finance.
- **Industry:** Businesses are the primary drivers of innovation, as they are constantly looking for new ways to improve their products and services and gain a competitive advantage.
- **Universities:** Universities play an important role in generating new knowledge and training future innovators.
- **Financial institutions:** Financial institutions provide the funding that startups and businesses need to grow and innovate.
- **Intermediary organizations:** Intermediary organizations, such as incubators, accelerators, and venture capital firms, play a vital role in supporting startups and helping them to bring their products and services to market.

2. Methodology

Analysing existing literature on startup ecosystems, innovation models, and economic development, particularly focusing on the Albanian context. Examination of successful startups in Albania, such as Publer, Kreatx, and SkaiTech, to understand factors contributing to their success. Evaluation of Albanian government policies and programs that support startups, such as various funding and support schemes. Identifying and examining the roles of different stakeholders in the startup ecosystem, using the Quintuple Innovation Helix model, which

includes government, industry, universities, financial institutions, and intermediary organizations.

3. Challenges

The startup ecosystem in Albania is still in its early stages of development, and there are several challenges that startups face. Here are some of the most common challenges:

- **Access to finance:** It can be difficult for startups to raise the capital they need to grow and scale their businesses. There is a lack of angel investors and venture capital funds in the country, and banks are often reluctant to lend to startups.
- **Lack of experienced mentors and advisors:** Many Albanian entrepreneurs do not have access to the advice and guidance they need to succeed. This can be a major disadvantage, especially for first-time entrepreneurs.
- **Fragmented startup ecosystem:** The Albanian startup ecosystem is still relatively fragmented. There is a lack of coordination between the different stakeholders, such as government agencies, universities, and businesses. This can make it difficult for startups to navigate the ecosystem and find the resources and support they need.
- **Small domestic market:** The Albanian domestic market is relatively small, which can make it difficult for startups to grow their businesses beyond Albania.
- **Brain drain:** Many talented young Albanians leave the country to seek better opportunities abroad. This can deprive the startup ecosystem of the talent it needs to thrive.

According to "The Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI, 2019), Switzerland ranks 2nd among other countries, with a score of 80.4, higher than in 2018. Israel ranks 12th among the top 15 countries good and scores 67.9.

Figure 1: The Global Entrepreneurship Index

Source: The StartupBlink

4. Opportunities

The Albanian Startup ecosystem is still in its early stages of development, but it presents a number of opportunities for entrepreneurs and investors. Here are some of the key opportunities:

- *Growing domestic market:* Albania's domestic market is growing rapidly, which provides startups with a large and growing customer base.
- *Young and talented population:* Albania has a young and talented population, which provides startups with a pool of potential employees and customers.

- *Low costs:* The cost of living and doing business in Albania is relatively low, which can give startups a competitive advantage.
- *Access to the EU market:* Albania is a candidate for EU membership, which gives startups access to the EU single market.

5. Conclusion

The Albanian startup ecosystem has the potential to become a major driver of economic growth and innovation in the country. However, there are still a number of challenges that need to be addressed in order for the ecosystem to thrive. The Albanian government, universities, and businesses need to work together to create a more supportive environment for startups.

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Crisis Management in Tourism Industry: Gaps and Opportunities in Albania

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Abstract

During the last few years humanity has been facing many global challenges which have changed the way in which humans see the world. These challenges provide new opportunities for businesses operating in different areas of the economy but can also bring new risks which have to be addressed in a timely manner. One of the main risks associated with major events is the business continuity risk that can arise when economic agents are faced with external threats. These events are unpredictable and can be destructive for organizations if they are not managed properly. The aim of this paper is to shed some light on the readiness of economic agents which operate in the tourism industry to face unexpected events and their perceptions of the crisis management strategy. The evidence collected will consider the experience from the latest situations which emerged after two recent crises which were evident in Albania: the earthquake of November 26, 2019, and the outbreak of COVID-19. Within this context, an overview of other potential crises that can affect the tourism industry in the short term and the response plans from tour operators will be drawn.

Keywords: Crises Management, Tourism Industry

JEL codes: H12, Z320

1. Introduction

Crises can hit when least expected. For this reason, it is very important for economic agents to be prepared for facing these situations and the risks associated with them and have in place the necessary means for minimizing their consequences. The nature of these tools can vary from one organization to another, but their objective should be the same: keep the business running. The Institute for Risk Management considers business continuity an important component of risk management function (Institute of Risk Management, 2002). According to the published standard, the role of risk management function should include, among other things, developing risk response processes, including contingency and business continuity programs. The process of business continuity planning and its formalization started life as an information technology function that focused on ensuring that the technology of the firm would continue to function in case of a disaster.

A lot of qualitative work toward BCP came out of the response of companies to the 9/11 terrorist attack, period during which BCP plans were significantly enhanced as a result of lessons learned at that time (Girling, 2013). This specific event was a starting point for many significant changes that affected the operating environment for tourism. In the forthcoming years, terrorist attacks became one of the predominant external threats to international travel (O'Connor, Stafford, & Gallagher, 2008).

Despite the fact the initial roots of BCP were strongly related to IT function, it would not be effective to consider the effectiveness of these plans only in this area. For a better explanation, the concept of Business Continuity Management (BCM) can be of use. As per the definition given from Business Continuity Management Institute, Business Continuity Management does not only include Business Continuity, but it also encompasses Crisis Management (CM), Crisis

Communication (CC), IT Disaster Recovery Planning and Operational Resilience (OR) (BCM Institute, 2018). It is considered a powerful tool that can be implemented to provide greater confidence that the output of processes and services can be delivered when risks are faced (Gibb & Buchanan, 2006).

2. Literature review

i. Nature of crisis in tourism industry

Crises can affect in a significant way any industry. Natural disasters and those caused by humans cannot be predicted or avoided. Furthermore, while disasters are, fortunately, relatively rare occurrences and they are to some extent random, it is also true that no destination is immune from such events (Faulkner, 2001). Despite the uniqueness of the crises, there are three major characteristics that appear most of them – unexpectedness, urgency, and danger (Hermann, 1972). The characteristics of these events make it necessary the existence of well-established crisis management plans that define the appropriate strategies and guidelines to prevent, prepare and mitigate – when possible - the damage caused by unexpected events with the aim of facilitating recovery of tourism from negative occurrences via protecting and rebuilding a positive destination image, reassuring potential visitors of the safety of the area, and re-developing the functionality of the destination to help local travel and tourism industries recover their business and get back to business as usual (Huang, Tseng, & Petric, 2007).

The link between tourism and risk reduction and management is particularly important in countries that rely heavily on tourism and are at the same time vulnerable to natural hazards. Furthermore, several characteristics of tourism industry expose it to risks whose impacts are disproportionate to its ability to bear the consequences (Becken & Hughey, 2013). Based on this fact and on historical events, we have grounds to believe that natural disasters will have an important impact on the tourism industry in the future, especially considering climate crisis the consequences it brings. To minimize these impacts, a more collaborative and integrated framework of disaster and destination management should be developed by tourism stakeholders. Its success will depend on the willingness and readiness of these stakeholders to collaborate across specific businesses (Bhaskara, Filimonau, Wijaya, Suryasih, & Ayu, 2021). In his book “Managing Tourism Crises”, Joan C. Henderson looks for the roots of tourism crises in the developments in the economic, political, socio-cultural, and environmental domains, which are assumed to affect demand and supply in countries where tourism takes place. Furthermore, technology is considered an additional domain in which crises are initiated (Henderson, 2006). These domains are not considered as separate and often they may overlap since major crises tend to be related to several factors.

ii. Requirements for a successful crisis management plan

Preparing for a crisis is a time-consuming process that requires efforts from several areas of competence. Even though there are no practices which are set in stone, the process should follow some steps which are similar despite the nature of the business that is preparing the plan. Of course, it is important that the plan(s) is (are) fully prepared and validated before the crisis starts, since time is an important factor when a crisis hits, and the situation can escalate very quickly.

Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC), a standard setter for sustainable travel and tourism, has developed two sets of criteria serving as a benchmark for tourism sustainability – Destination Criteria useful for public policymakers and destination managers and Industry Criteria useful for hotels and tour operators. The first group of criteria represent the minimum standards that any tourism destination should aspire to reach, and which are applicable to the entire tourism sector. It also contains a sub-section related with pressure and change management that draws the attention into risk and crisis management and gives a general overview of the requirements needed for a successful outcome (Global Sustainable Tourism

Council, 2019). As per the respective criteria, the destination should have a risk reduction, crisis management and emergency response plan that is appropriate to the destination itself. Key elements of the framework are communicated to residents, visitors and enterprises and procedures and resources are established for implementing the plan which is regularly updated. The framework should contain, among other: a) a documented risk reduction and crisis management response plan for tourism in the destination, b) the preparation of the plan should consider a wide range of potential risks that the destination may face, including natural catastrophes, terrorist attack, health, resource depletion and other risks specific to the destination, c) communication procedures identified for use during and after an emergency, and d) program for local delivery of information and training on risk and crisis management.

3. Methodology

To draw conclusions about the issues that tourism industry in Albania faced when real crises hit, a case study strategy will be used. This method is considered effective as it provides a real context for the development and implementation of crisis management plans. This will enable us to better understand the current state of readiness to face unexpected events and the gaps identified which need to be addressed.

i. Crisis response in the aftermath of the earthquake of November 26, 2019

On 26th of November 2019, Albania was hit by a 6.4 magnitude earthquake in which fifty-one lives were lost. A high number of buildings (estimated to be more than 14,000) suffered severe damage or were fully destroyed, and more than 10,000 citizens had to move out of their current homes. Although this event occurred outside the tourist season, its impacts were visible in the tourist infrastructure.

In the aftermath of the event, a study was carried out at the request of the Ministry of Tourism and Environment by the United Nations Development Program. The research was focused on the immediate response of hotel accommodation as a temporary solution for citizens who had lost their homes. As per the data published on this study, a high number of hotels were involved in this initiative to show solidarity with those affected by opening the doors to them, even before the government authorities launched an appeal in this regard (United Nations Development Program, 2020). Even though in the center of this study was the accommodation of Albanian citizens located in affected areas, the study also identified three elements considered as success factor in creating the potential for resilience: 1) Integrated basic services, 2) Creation of a positive social atmosphere by hotel staffs, 3) An inherent tendency displayed by the citizens to engage and interact with others, as a result of being faced with the same adversity. Despite the importance of these three elements, a missing

ii. Crisis response in the aftermath of the outbreak of COVID-19

On March 8, 2020, first cases of coronavirus were identified in Albania. On the same day, the government put a ban on all the incoming flights and ships coming from the northern Italy until April 3, 2020. As additional measures, the schools were closed for two weeks, and all the sport activities were suspended. On March 10, 2020, all the citizens received messages on their phones to raise awareness of the situation. All the above-mentioned measures (and others which are not subject to this study) were taken in the immediate response to the situation. The presented restrictions inevitably affected the movement of people, increasing the insecurities for future travel.

4. Results and Discussion

Based on the experience drawn by the management of two consecutive crisis that occurred in Albania during 2019-2020, several points of intervention can be identified. They can be further elaborated to provide a more accurate crisis management strategy and increase the resilience of the tourism industry in the face of unexpected events.

First, what is observed in both crises is the immediate response followed by measures taken to take control of the situation. These measures were decided on an ad-hoc basis and were not part of a well-developed crisis management strategy. An appropriate crisis management strategy should be developed by keeping in mind several extreme scenarios and the immediate measures taken should vary depending on the characteristics of the occurring situation.

Secondly, a business impact analysis should be performed to evaluate the potential impact of crises in different areas of the tourism industry. This will help different stakeholders to prioritize their internal processes and services offered. Based on this prioritization, the service providers can decide whether there are services that must be offered to the customers, no matter what, services that must be offered with some limitations and services that will not be offered for an (un)defined period.

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Towards Tourism Driven Growth Model for Albania

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Abstract

This paper provides a deep view on tourism¹ related figures in Albania, exploring their impact on main economic variables. The effect of tourism on economic growth, employment, foreign currency inflows, is evaluated based on disposable data and is also empirically tested using simple regression equations. The empirical evidence supports real data, demonstrating a positive relationship between tourism related income and GDP growth in Albania. It is also empirically tested that the value added of tourism sector in economy increases, as public investments expand and there is a surge in tourist arrivals.

Keywords: Economic growth; Tourism; Employment; Tourist arrivals; Regression equation

1. Introduction

Albania witnessed a boom of tourist figures and a substantial quantity of foreign currency inflows related to tourism, as well, in the last couple of years. The weight of tourism sector counts for approximately 8% of nominal GDP in the last year. Economic data, as well as empirical evidence confirms the positive relationship between tourism generated revenues and economic growth in Albania.

As showed in the Table 1, tourism sector contribution to growth is also notable compared to other sectors of economy. Tourism contributed to *nominal growth* by 1.4 pp in the last couple of years, while this contribution in the last decade was approximately by 0.2 pp.

Table 1. Nominal GDP growth based on main sectors contribution

Average	Agriculture	Industry	Construction	Trade	Tourism*	Others	Net taxes	Nominal GDP growth
2009-2019	0.9	0.7	- 0.2	0.4	0.2	1.7	0.5	4.2
2017-2023	1.2	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.6	1.9	0.9	6.8
2021-2023	2.4	1.6	1.7	1.4	1.4	2.9	1.7	13.0
2022-2023	3.0	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.4	2.7	1.2	13.1

Source: INSTAT, authors own calculations.

Having a look on the path of *real economic growth* by its main contributors, the growing contribution of tourism sector to real economic growth is distinctive. After pandemics tourism sector has supported economic growth by 1.1 pp, compared to 0.3 pp in the years before pandemics.

Employment in tourism sector accounts for 10% of employment in the private sector², on average during 2010 – 2023. Employment in total economy, as well as employment in tourism

¹ Tourism sector in this paper is approximated by the activity of the group “Hotels, restaurants, bars, coffee shops, transport and telecommunication.

² Labour market data refer to administrative data published by INSTAT. Detailed data on employment according to firms’ size are available up to 2021. Quarterly data on total employment for economy and the tourism sector are available up to 2023Q2.

sector kept growing after the pandemics, with the latter growing at a slower pace. On average, employment grew by 3.2% during 2021Q2 – 2023Q2, and employment in tourism grew by 2% for the same period. It seems a little bit counterintuitive that employment increase in tourism sector, especially after pandemics, wasn't at the same pace with the total employment in economy, or even faster, taking into the consideration the fact that tourism sector, is one of the sectors labour intensive. Two factors might explain the sluggish employment growth in this sector: (i) we refer to the administrative data published by INSTAT, which to some extent may differ from those provided by Labour Force Survey; (ii) there has been a large labour force migration abroad during the last years, which in turn might have affected a fraction of workers employed on the tourism sector previously. Contribution of tourism sector to the total employment of economy has been marginal, as tourism sector largely relies on small to medium enterprises. On average, during 2011 - 2021 the vast majority of employment in tourism sector, 92%, was provided by the firms with a number of employees up to 49³.

The boom in tourism growth in the last couple of years is explained by the substantial increase in *tourist arrivals*. During first 9 months of 2023 approximately 8.3 million tourists visited Albania, recording an increase by 29% on annual basis. The last two years tourist inflows average annual increase, by 40%⁴, is outstanding compared with the pre-pandemic period '18-'19, averaging 11% annually.

Foreign currency inflows marked a considerable increase in the last years. For the first half of the year 2023, tourism related FX inflows were 1.5 billion Euro, marking an increase by more than 37%, on annual terms. On average, tourism related income increased by 54%, annually, after pandemics, compared to an average of 9%, during 2012-2019. High inflows from tourism activity have been reflected also in a substantial rise of foreign currency deposits during the last years. Foreign currency deposits at the end of Q3 2023 reached a level of 7.8 bln Euro, 16% higher than a year ago. The upsurge in FX deposits in the last two years is 10 pp higher, compared to the growth experienced during 2012-2019.

There have been some *measures undertaken by the government* in order to encourage the tourism sector development in Albania. Most important ones include the reduction in VAT ratio to 6% (from 20% flat rate) for: (i) the accommodation structures (2016); (ii) all the services provided in luxury and brand resorts (2017); (iii) agritourism services, ie restaurants and accommodation (2019). Several promotional advertisements in the most known international travel journals were another important measure in boosting tourism during the last couple of years.

2. Methodology

In this paper, our focus is to test for the presence of positive effects of tourism on economic growth. The purpose of this paper is not to follow the conventional growth literature, exploring all the factors that back the economic growth. Therefore, the equations used in this this paper go beyond the conventional ones, such as those initially proposed by Solow (1956), and all the series of literature following Solow.

A broad literature overview on tourism and sustainable development nexus is provided in Destek et al. (2021). They give a summary of existing literature on tourism positive and negative externalities. The vast majority of the exiting literature find a positive relationship between tourism related activities and GDP. There are studies, such as Sequera and Campos

³ Following the definition of SMEs according to EU Recommendation 2003/361, SMEs are defined the firms with a number of employees up to 249 an annual turnover less than 5.1 billion lekë. Throughout this paper we will refer to these firms as small and medium enterprises, SMEs, despite their annual turnover to be eligible as a SME.

⁴ Latest quarterly data available for 2023 comprise 9- months period. For comparability purposes we have referred to the same period during 2017 – 2019 and 2022 – 2023.

(2005) and Mohapatra (2018) that find a negative correlation between tourism receipts and GDP growth.

The sample used for this purpose includes quarterly data 2010Q1 – 2023Q2. The explanatory variables include: (i) *tourism revenues* (*tour_revenues*)⁵ in Euro; (ii) *trade openness indicator* (*trade_op*) which denotes the sum of imports and exports as a ratio of GDP; (iii) GDP' prior values expressed in Euro and adjusted for seasonality. GDP values in euro were computed taking the average quarterly values for Eur/Lekë exchange rate, as published by BoA. Trade openness indicator is calculated based on the publications of BoA for import and exports of goods and services, and INSTAT publications for GDP data. It enters into equation with one time lag (-1). All the variables are used on their logs. We have used seasonally adjusted data for GDP and Tourism revenues data, since the seasonal adjustment test using census X-12 method shows the existence of seasonality.

The estimation equation has the form:

$$\log GDP_{nom_EUR_SA} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \log tour_{revenues_SA} + \beta_3 \log trade_{op(-1)} + \beta_4 \log GDP_{nom_EUR_SA(-4)} + \beta_5 HP_trend_GDP + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

The substituted coefficients:

$$\log GDP_{nom_EUR_SA} = 2.84 + 0.07 \log tour_{revenues_SA} + (-0.07) \log trade_{op(-1)} + 0.51 \log GDP_{nom_EUR_SA(-4)} + 1.68 HP_trend_GDP \quad (1.1)$$

In this paper we have also tried to explore the main factors behind the value added of tourism sector, using quarterly data from 2017Q1 – 2023Q2. The main purpose is to find out the main elements that support tourism sector development, backing in turn the overall economic growth. In a simple regression equation, the change in the value added of tourism sector is explained by the change in: (i) *tourist arrivals* and (ii) *gross fixed capital formation of government*⁶, *GFCF*.

The estimation equation has the form:

$$\log VA_{tourism} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \log tourist_arrival + \log GFCF_{gov} + AR(1) + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

The substituted coefficients:

$$\log VA_{tourism} = 6.7 + 0.2 \log tourist_arrival + 0.1 GFCF_{gov} \quad (2.1)$$

3. Results and Discussion

The equation (1) explains the economic growth depending on tourism revenues, trade openness and its past values. While explaining the changes in economic growth other variables rather than the explanatory variables in the equation 1 were included in this model, such as foreign direct investment inflows, but it turned out to be statistically insignificant at the 1%, 5% and 10% level. Public investments were also one of the explanatory variables used in the equation, but it was omitted since it posed a negative correlation with GDP growth, despite being a statistically significant parameter at 99% confidence level.

The coefficient of trade openness estimated by OLS is found to be negative and statistically significant at 10% level. The negative correlation between trade openness and economic growth, as evidenced by Vehapi et.al (2015) in analysing the empirical effects of trade openness in SEE countries, might be attributable to the low level of initial economic development of Albania⁷.

⁵ We have used only the travel related foreign currency inflows, not the balance of travel, as published by BoA, because the latter is netted for the travel related spending of Albanians abroad.

⁶ Since no data of GSCF of government is published by INSTAT, we have approximated this variable by capital expenditures of local and central government plus all fiscal transfers having investment features.

⁷ In their study they have found trade openness doesn't exert significant effect on growth of SEE, but including other explanatory variables into the model, the coefficient of trade openness become positive and statistically significant. This means that the positive effects of trade on growth are conditioned by other factors, such as the human capital, physical capital, FDI and the initial income per capita.

In the equation (1.1) the positive relationship between tourism receipts and economic growth is evidenced, being also statistically significant.

The equation (2) explains the value added of tourism sector, depended on tourist arrivals and public GFCF. The regression equation finds a positive and statistically significant relationship between the number of tourist arrivals, GFCF of government and the value added of tourism sector at a 99% confidence level. Higher public investments tends give a rise in value added of tourism sector, implying that government policies and strategies are an important factor for the tourism perspective in particular and for the economic perspective in general.

4. Conclusions

Tourism sector had a prompt upsurge during the last couple of years in Albania. Its contribution to the economic growth more than three folded compared to the pre-pandemics period. Tourism sector contribution to growth, was notable not only compared to its historical averages values, but also compared to the other sectors of economy. During the last couple of years as tourist arrivals and tourist nights of stay increased rapidly, there was a substantial upsurge in the foreign currency inflows, as well as in the foreign currency deposits in the banking system. All these developments point out that tourism sector is enhancing considerably its impact on economic growth, compared to its historical behaviour.

Empirical evidence also supports the real data developments, pointing out at a positive and statistically significant relationship between tourism receipts and economic growth. The contribution of tourism sector itself in economic growth is positively correlated to tourist arrivals, as well as to public investments, implying that government policies play a significant role in tourism development. Nevertheless, the results should be taken into consideration with caution, since they are highly dependent on the reliability of economic data, which might be subject for a frequent revision. A strand of tourism related research is highly focused on the negative externalities of tourism growth, such as energy use or CO₂ emission increase, but in case of Albania this might be a subject for further work, since no reliable data is available in the meantime.

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Abbreviations

BoA: Bank of Albania
EU: European Union
FX: Foreign currency
GDP: Gross Domestic Product
GFCF: Gross Fixed Capital Formation
INSTAT: Institute of Statistics
LFS: Labour Force Survey
SEE: Southeastern Europe
SME: Small Medium Enterprises

Tourism as a Strategic Sector in Sustainable Development: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

Only in the last years, tourism as a strategic sector has been awarded increased attention from the authorities and the local media. A large wave of international marketing and the development of successful traveling agencies have placed Albania as a recently discovered “Balkan gem”. Although the general impression is that the tourism industry has yielded positive impacts on the country’s economy through the years, a lack of evidence is detected from developing countries, more specifically for Albania and its neighboring counterparts. This study aims to present a comparative analysis of the tourism industry in Albania, Croatia, and Montenegro. The main objective is to understand the factors influencing the contribution of tourism to the economy. This comparison is made by understanding the evolution of the industry through the years and aspects from the neighboring countries that can help Albania in increasing the impact of tourism on the economy. The study reveals findings including the focus on the promotion of the country to extend tourists’ average nights and become recognizable in new markets. These findings can assist mainly policymakers and tourism organizations, in addition to researchers who want to expand on this topic.

Keywords: Tourism, Albania, Croatia, Montenegro, comparative analysis, economic impact

JEL codes: L83

The Economic Dimensions of Sustainable Tourism. Reflections from a Mediterranean Community of Projects

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Abstract

Sustainable tourism encompasses various economic dimensions that aim to balance economic growth with environmental and social responsibility. The economic dimensions of sustainable tourism aim to create a positive impact on local economies while minimizing negative consequences for the environment and local communities. Sustainable tourism practices strive for a balance that ensures long-term economic benefits without compromising the well-being of the destination. This article presents the contribution of the projects selected under the Interreg-MED Thematic Objective of Sustainable Tourism during the 2014-2020 period in re-thinking and re-focusing tourism development in Mediterranean coastal destinations in relation to their socioeconomic objectives. Taking into account the cross-cutting nature of the tourism sector, the analysis revealed that the integration of the socioeconomic dimension is an integral part of any effective strategies and actions.

Keywords: sustainable tourism, Interreg-MED, Mediterranean

1. Introduction

Tourism and its interconnections with other sectors is placed amongst the highest income generators in the Mediterranean, especially in terms of generating gross value added and employment. However, the emerging global sustainability challenges demand for re-thinking and re-positioning the tourism model to meet the demands for differentiation, innovation, cost optimization and the tourists' growing sustainability expectations (Economic Commission for Europe, 2022, UNECE & ESCAP, 2021). It has become widely acknowledged by policymakers, developers and tourism corporations, that policies and planning for the development of tourism should take into account the concepts of "sustainability" or "sustainable development" (Bianchi, 2010). In both developed and developing countries, sustainable tourism strives to achieve a balance between preserving the environment, upholding cultural integrity, establishing social justice, and promoting economic benefits (Mitchell & Hall, 2005). In the meantime, the growing acceptance of the notion of sustainable development as a means of resolving economic-environmental conflict has significant consequences for the form and trajectory of economic restructuring (Gibbs, 1996). Encouraging sustainable consumption principles, offering new tourism services and achieving a competitive advantage by meeting the needs and welfare of local communities and addressing the sustainable development priorities of tourism destinations can be the means to resolve potential implications and address the issues related to re-orienting the tourism industry towards sustainability (Streimikiene et al., 2020).

2. Methodology

In this light, the present paper focuses on the INTERREG MED Community of projects under the *Sustainable Tourism* Thematic Objective (TO). During the course of the 2014-2020 programming period, 30 projects were selected under the Sustainable Tourism TO, focusing

on enhancing the development of a sustainable and responsible coastal and maritime tourism in Mediterranean coastal areas. Although the thematic focus of the projects is clearly on tourism issues, the projects tackle a wide range of socioeconomic, environmental and governance dimensions through their thematic objectives and related activities. Niavis et al. (2022) identified the most common 12 thematic objectives targeted by the projects, covering all four dimensions of tourism sustainability. For the needs of this paper, 6 out of the 12 thematic objectives that are classified under the socioeconomic dimension are taken into account. More specifically, the thematic objectives under the socioeconomic dimension are:

- Generating employment
- Increasing Gross Value Added (GVA)
- Diversifying & differentiating the tourism product
- Promoting clustering/innovation
- Improving social well-being
- Improving accessibility

Taking into account the average funds invested by the projects on the 12 policy objectives, the results show that 41% of the total budget was allocated to the 6 socioeconomic objectives while 59% was allocated to environmental and governance priorities. Most resources were invested in activities related to the diversification and differentiation of the tourism product and the improvement of social well-being.

Figure 1: Average funds invested by the projects in socioeconomic objectives

Source: Own elaboration

Moreover, out of the 60 eligible Mediterranean coastal areas, the objective to diversify and differentiate the tourism product was counted in 46 regions, followed by the objective to improve social well-being (44 regions), to increase the gross value added (39 regions), to promote clustering and innovation and improve accessibility (33 regions) and, finally, to generate employment (32 regions).

3. Results and Discussion

The results clearly highlight that the socioeconomic dimension is an integral part for effective sustainable tourism strategies and actions. To this end, all 30 projects of the Sustainable Tourism Community directly or indirectly take into account and plan for restructuring local economies and societies towards sustainable tourism development. Their activities take the form of strategies to promote alternative tourism products, action plans and tools to valorise and monitor water and energy usage in public and private sector, circular tourism tools applying

the principles of circular economy in the tourism industry, business models to enhance the sustainability of the cruise value chain etc.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the linkages between tourism and economic development is evident and versatile, either directly in the form of generating employment or indirectly in the form of stimulating the development of basic infrastructure to improve accessibility. The results of the Interreg MED Sustainable Tourism Community highlighted that tourism development needs to be approached in an innovative and sustainable way so that the local communities can take full advantage of its potential while preserving the natural and cultural heritage resources.

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Analysis of Green Growth Performance in the Western Balkans Countries

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Abstract

Green growth aims to use natural assets in order to promote economic growth and development without harming nature. To do this, investments that support sustainable growth without harming nature must be encouraged. Green growth aims to reduce CO2 emissions and reduce environmental degradation.

The main purpose of this paper is to present green growth through some indicators in the Western Balkans Countries. In the study, 5 countries were taken (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia), leaving Kosovo out of the analysis due to the lack of data. The indicators taken in the study are indicators that give us an idea of the progress of these countries towards green growth. The indicators that have been analyzed are: production-based CO2 productivity, renewable energy supply, renewable electricity, mean population exposure to PM2.5.

Through these indicators, we will be able to see the progress or regression made by each of the analyzed countries in terms of green growth. These indicators are reflected for a period of 10 years (2010-2020) in order to make a comparison between years and between countries. The data is obtained from OECD Stat which provides us with an accurate and reliable database.

At the end of the paper, based on the progress of the indicators, we drew some conclusions and recommendations regarding the policies that should be undertaken for the best possible progress towards the green growth.

Keywords: Green growth, Production-based CO2 productivity, Renewable energy supply, Renewable electricity, PM2.5

JEL codes: F64, F43, Q20

1. Introduction

The Western Balkans are gaining prominence for their green growth as they strive for sustainable development and less environmental effect. The Western Balkans' green growth can be summed up as follows: Renewable Energy: Renewable energy sources like sun, wind, and hydropower have a lot of potential in the Western Balkans. Energy Efficiency: Achieving green growth requires increasing energy efficiency. Reducing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions can be achieved through improving energy efficiency in buildings, industry, and the transportation sector.

The adoption of a circular economy model encourages waste reduction and resource efficiency. Sustainable Tourism: The Western Balkans may experience green growth by using sustainable tourism techniques. Putting an emphasis on eco-tourism, ethical tourism management, and the preservation of cultural heritage can draw eco-aware tourists and boost regional economies. Green Investments and Funding: It's critical to promote green investments and make it easier for sustainable projects to obtain funding. Initiatives for green growth are implemented in the region with financial and technical help from international organizations like the European Union Policy and Regulatory Framework. Green growth indicators are important measurements that are used to gauge how well sustainable development and the shift to a

greener economy are going as well as their impact. Typical green growth indicators include the following: Measurement of greenhouse gas emissions: This is one of the most significant indicators. Monitoring emissions from several industries, including transportation, energy, and manufacturing, is part of this. A greener economy is being achieved as emissions are gradually reduced.

The tracking of the expansion and proportion of renewable energy capacity within the overall energy blend is an additional crucial metric. It illustrates the shift in energy sources from fossil fuels to cleaner, renewable alternatives. Economic Growth: It's critical to evaluate how green industries and sectors are growing economically in relation to more established ones. It assists in determining whether green growth tactics are producing financial gains while reducing their negative effects on the environment.

These indicators offer a thorough grasp of the developments and results of green growth projects. They support decision-making, progress monitoring, and strategy adjustment by policymakers to ensure environmentally responsible and sustainable development.

2. Methodology

The content makes this paper's main goal is to provide a broad overview of green growth for the non-EU Balkan countries and to assess the indicators that show where these economies have performed better and where improvement requires intervention. Production-based CO₂ productivity, renewable energy supply, renewable electricity, and mean population exposure to PM_{2.5}, are the variables that we have selected for the analyses. The green economy, according to various international organizations, is based on three main objectives: the efficient use of resources, the protection of the environment and the increase of social equality. The green economy is considered as a tool and prerequisite for sustainable development (European Commission, 2020). It improves human well-being and social equity and reduces environmental risks and ecological insufficiency (UNEP, February 2018). This economy promotes economic development and preserves the natural resources necessary for social well-being (OECD, May 2011). Use of OECD-generated data in order to accomplish the goal. Selected indicators are available in the OECD.Stat Green Growth database to track advancements in green growth. Five non-EU Balkan nations are included in the database we chose (Albania, Serbia, Montenegro, Bosnia-Herzegovina, North Macedonia). The variables that we have chosen for the analyses are: Production-based CO₂ productivity (GDP per unit of energy-related CO₂ emissions), Renewable energy supply (% total energy supply), Renewable electricity (% total electricity generation), and Mean population exposure to PM_{2.5}. Values of variables are compared between countries using graphical methods. Graphs are used because they are ideal for comparing one or more value sets and because they make it simple to display both the high and low values found in data sets. Using a line graph, we will make a comparison chart.

3. Results and Discussion

Production-based CO₂ productivity, according to the OECD, measures the economic value produced (in terms of real GDP) per unit of CO₂ emitted. Gross direct CO₂ emissions from the burning of fossil fuels that occur within a country's borders are referred to as production-based emissions. It is clear from Graph. (1) that Bosnia-Herzegovina has the lowest production-based CO₂ productivity, while Albania has the highest. Over an extended period, Albania's values for this variable are significantly higher than those of other countries. In Albania, this variable is trending upward; in other nations, it is trending downward or remains constant.

Graph.1 Production-based CO₂ productivity: GDP per unit of energy-related CO₂ emissions
Source: OECD, Authors Calculations

4. Conclusions

We used data for a select Balkan Countries as well as certain green growth indicators in our paper. The proposed indicators are a subset of those that have been employed and examined in research to assist nations in enhancing their environmental and economic policy frameworks. This study suggests that all of the countries under consideration need to make improvements in the indicators examined in the paper. The use of renewable energy sources and carbon dioxide emissions from human productivity are two of the primary indicators that are looked at.

The phenomenon of carbon dioxide emission affects not only the nation releasing the gas but also those who are impacted by its atmospheric distribution. Taxation is one of the political tools that should be used to lower carbon dioxide emissions from cars. Tax increases would push the economy toward technological advancements that reduce carbon emissions. This would lessen the effects of greenhouse gases on the planet by helping nations have cleaner air and environments.

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The Movement and the Stay of the EU and Non-EU Citizens and their Relatives in Albania

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Abstract

This scientific article delves into the legal intricacies surrounding the movement and stay of European Union (EU) citizens and their relatives in the Republic of Albania. Against the backdrop of Albania's ongoing efforts towards European integration, the regulation of the entry, residence, and mobility of EU citizens within its borders represents a focal point of analysis.

The study explores the legal framework governing the rights and obligations of EU citizens and their family members in Albania. Emphasis is placed on Albania's alignment with EU directives and regulations, examining how the nation has adapted its legal infrastructure to accommodate the principles of free movement and residence enshrined in European Union law.

Key components of the analysis include the examination of entry requirements, the issuance of residence permits, and the conditions under which EU citizens and their relatives may stay in Albania. Moreover, the study investigates any specific rights conferred upon EU citizens and their family members during their residence in the country, as well as the mechanisms in place for addressing legal challenges that may arise.

As Albania progresses on its path toward European integration, understanding the legal dynamics governing the movement and stay of EU citizens and their relatives becomes paramount. This article aims to contribute to the scholarly discourse on the evolving legal landscape in Albania concerning EU citizens, shedding light on the implications of these regulations for both the nation and the European Union.

Keywords: Republic of Albania, the Law “On foreigners”, family reunification, international law.

1. Introduction

The treatment of foreigners entering or seeking to enter, stay or work in the territory of the Republic of Albania, according to the criteria and norms of EU legislation, is subject of the Law nr. 108 “On Foreigners” of 28.03.2013.

This law specifies in detail the type of residence permits, and for the first time a residence permit is foreseen for highly skilled workers, and the recognition of this type of residence permits by other countries, based on possible agreements.

The purpose of this specific law is to follow the steps of the European Union countries related to the respect of the fundamental right of the free movement and the family reunification.

The right to be accompanied by their family members, was and continues to be a right that regardless the nationality of the family members itself.

The provisions on family reunification permits, in the law provide the possibility of family reunification and cohabiting foreigners and provides the possibility for any foreigner who is registered as a resident in Albania to seek family reunification, as it happens in the European Union.

The law provides clear provisions on autonomous residence permits, as well as legal definitions of fictitious marriages, which lead to the annulment of residence permits issued for motives of family reunification, without leaving this to a subjective assessment of employees of the police.

For the first time, the law "On Foreigners" "erases" an old obligation to citizens of the United States of America.

Family reunification, according to Albanian national law, is considered the entry and stay in the Republic of Albania of members of the family of an Albanian citizen resident in the Republic of Albania who do not have Albanian citizenship or are stateless.

It aims to preserve the family, regardless of the fact that the family relationship is established before or after the entry of a foreigner into the Republic of Albania. When in Albania, individuals enter with the family, those who are over the age of 18 should apply for a residence permit each. Juveniles are included in parents' applications, however, when they reach the age of 18 and are still in Albania, they must apply for a residence permit for themselves.

Family reunion is allowed only for certain categories of persons who enjoy the status of a family member. The Albanian legislature accorded the status of family member to spouses, cohabitants, first-line ancestors, and descendants.

As spouses will be considered those persons who have entered into a regular marriage under Albanian legislation. Those legal prohibitions that are imposed by Albanian legislation aggravate also on the marriage of a foreign citizen when he asks for family reunification in the Republic of Albania.

Thus, a person who has entered a regular marriage in his country of origin with a same-sex person can not apply for family reunification in Albania. This is derived from the Albanian legal provisions under which marriage is related between a man and a woman, so of the principle of heterosexuality and monogamy.

In the category of cohabitants are included persons whose cohabitation has a stable and proven character. This is a category that is already foreseen in all national legislations. Also for this category is the same assertion as for the case of marriage.

I should point out that when people are involved in a registered partnership, they are unable to seek family reunification with family members in Albania. This is because this institute is not recognized by Albanian family law but they can seek family reunification by verifying their coexistence. So, they can seek the family reunification with the cohabiting status, and it will only be adopted if their cohabitation has a stable, continuous character, is monogamous and above all, be among the persons of different sexes.

The family members of Albanian or foreign nationals, to stay in the territory of the Republic of Albania is granted a "D / BF" permit, with a one-year validity, 90 days stay, with one, two or more entry- exit.

This visa entitles the holder to apply for a residence permit after entering the Republic of Albania. This is the visa initially issued. The residence permit is then renewed for a two-year period.

The documentation required to apply for family reunification under the Law "On Foreigners" is:

1. a copy of the identity document of the Albanian citizen or the foreigner (active subjects), in this last case together with a photocopy of the residence permit;
2. the certificate issued by the foreign authorities certifying the relationship with the person seeking family reunification in Albania (in any case the document must be accompanied by the Apostille stamp);
3. 4 photographs of the person seeking family reunification, in the concrete case of the passive subject;
4. documentation that certifies that the subject has an appropriate residence in Albania, such as the certificate of ownership of the apartment, or, in the case of a foreign national, the lease contract;
5. A notarial declaration by both subjects, passive and active, expressing the will to live together if there is no marriage relationship;
6. confirmation that the active subject has sufficient income to secure the livelihood of the passive subject;
7. the health insurance according to the duration of the residence permit for family reunification.

Regarding to the maintenance of the family reunification after the marriage is resolved, the Albanian legislature has maintained an opposite attitude from European jurisprudence.

In Albania, if the foreigner has obtained a residence permit due to family reunification and the marriage from which he has received the status of a family member, in the capacity of his spouse, has been solved, his permit may be refused to renewal or even canceled.

On this point, Article 57 point 2 states that, in case of termination of the family relationship (marriage or coexistence), in the period of five years from the acquisition of the first residence permit, for the effect of family reunification, this right is lost.

Family reunification aims to preserve the family, regardless of whether the family relationship is established before or after the entry of a foreigner into the Republic of Albania.

As I specified before, for the first time, the law "On Foreigners" "erases" an old obligation to citizens of the United States of America.

American citizens do not need a visa to enter the Republic of Albania, they must only be provided with a passport valid for at least 3 months before the date of its expiration.

In addition to the passport, the border and migration officer may also ask the latter to also submit some of the following documents:

- a) Invitation of the guarantor / invitee in Albania;
- b) Return ticket / reservation;
- c) Proof of evidence-based accommodation;
- d) Work permit if you enter Albania for employment purposes;

- e) Financial assets, Albanian or foreign currency, that can be exchanged in one exchange agency in the Republic of Albania, or other forms of payment accepted in commercial transactions in the Republic of Albania, such as checks, credit cards, etc. (currently it is 30 (thirty) Euros per day stay and 15 (fifteen) Euros for the minor;
- f) The original international vaccination card, when a foreigner comes from countries affected by the epidemic or illnesses for which Albanian legislation requires.

US citizens do not need to register with the regional border office and migration for stays in less than a year, but if they plan to stay for more than a year then they must apply for a residence permit explained below.

It is important that the border and migration officer has correctly stamped the passport with the entry stamp.

When we talk about the family law protection with regard to freedom of movement, we tend to differentiate between the family of the EU citizen and the the family of the non-EU citizens.

For both EU and non-EU citizens, in the Republic of Albania, is the Law nr. 108 “On Foreigners” of 28.03.2013 that defines the limits to the right to free movement, and as a result to the right of family reunification.

The Law "On Foreigners" has reflected the suggestions of EU experts, the most positive experiences of legislation and administrative practices of some EU member states, such as Slovenia, Finland, Norway, Romania, but also Croatia.

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Civil Responsibility and Class Action on the Environmental Damages

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Abstract

Issues related to the protection of the environment are among the most acute problems which societies face today. This paper aims to present the efforts made by Albanian legislators to improve the legal framework in the domain of environmental protection. The European legal framework has significantly influenced our internal legislation and enforcement of preventive and protective mechanisms and methods. It is worth studying the content of our domestic environmental legal framework on preservation and the impact focus on conservation through the prevention, reduction, and compensation of damages from proposed projects. Civil liability in environmental damages is an issue that deserves a particular explication due to the problems found in the lack of accountability. NGOs play a fundamental role in enforcing of the environment protection legal acts. Regardless, the Albanian environmental legislation does not have rules for collective lawsuits or class action. Lack of this procedural instrument makes access to courts difficult. NGO's lack of legitimacy, put them in a situation where they could not require the rights of the group of interest. The paper seeks to find problems by exposing it. Although, it tries recommending solutions about the environmental damage. The legislator must approve a legal framework in supplying the collective lawsuit. As a civil mechanism, they are complementary to one each other. Their mission is to compensate the environmental damage.

Keywords: Class actions, civil liability environmental, damage, collective initiative, legal mechanism,

1. Introduction

The damage to the environment can cause health disease and destruction of properties. Consistently, we need a legal instrument specialized in supporting the right of living healthily, and in a suitable environment. Every physical person has the right to sue for the cause of the damage that has come to them personally. For example, let's suppose that the actions which have destroyed the environment have produced consequences for the community. We are not talking about pecuniary or non-pecuniary damage toward only one person but toward a community. What are the solutions to this situation? In this paper, I seek to highlight environmental damage as a phenomenon that must be fought with collective claims to prevent and compensate for the damage caused to the environment. Environmental damage is a phenomenon that affects many aspects of life. Preservation of human life and health is a complex issue which affects food safety, consumer protection, public health, and the right to have a clean and convenient environment. Tourism, agriculture, light industries, and service sectors, make up the majority of the GDP of Albania. These sectors improve their performance if we would protect the environmental conditions.

That affects the economic indicators and quality of life. Collective lawsuits are necessary, where the problems extend to a mass of people (society, quarter, or community). Surely, this conclusion follows the guidance of the tort system itself. "For instance, one defendant can owe a tort duty of repair to many plaintiffs, as with a class action suit, and, on the other hand, one plaintiff could sue multiple defendants who share responsibility for the same wrong. (Bronsther, 2021, p.256). To achieve goals, we need a combined legal framework. The

institutional framework must be solid and responsible in its obligations, with well-defined competencies. Lack of measures taken by the state authorities, individuals, alone or as a community, have the right to protect the environment by seeking compensation for the damage caused because of illegal actions against nature and resources. The collective lawsuit is one of them that can start a trial process for the Court to review and oppose the forbidden activity of subjects that have caused damage to the environment. There are too many international conventions that can be used as reference for enhancing the domestic environmental legal framework. The Aarhus Convention, the European Union Directive regarding the prevention and remedying of environmental damage, the Albanian legal framework in civil law, specifically the Civil Code and The Civil Procedure Code, scientific articles, national and foreign literature, reports, studies and manuals, particularly dealing with the issue of the environment and collective actions as the mechanism for finding the violation of the law, and the restoration of violated rights and oppressed rights. Ultimately, we bring to the reader's attention some conclusions and recommendations related to the findings of the Albanian legislation concerning the issue of the legitimacy of non-profit organizations and interest groups as a function of environmental protection.

2. Methodology

To achieve the goals of this study, I have tried to conduct selective research within the field of environmental law and the Albanian domestic law on it. Pecuniary damages, and non-pecuniary damages studies, are concepts of civil responsibility. We have to find and show the elements of civil responsibility, and the causal relationship, from one side and the other legal provisions due to environmental preservation. The observational method, orienting itself in the existing literature, particularly on the procedure of protecting the environment referring to the collective initiatives, refers to the positions held by national courts and foreign courts in relation to the engagement of NGOs in matters of building repair and building compensation. The analytical method consists of an analysis of the international legal framework and its effect on the internal legislation in each field. Descriptive, and comparative, aims to bring to attention the best practices used for guaranteeing the right of access to the courts of interest groups in the repair and compensation of out-of-contract buildings when we have them in an environment. These methods are applied in paper combined with one another throughout the work.

3. Results and Discussion

This paper raises many issues for discussion, the result of which will be alive when the goals are achieved, according to the analysis and analysis carried out:

- The environmental issues that pass an exclusive responsibility only to the state authorities or to a wider community.
- What are the challenges of collective actions in the future?
- What criteria must be completed, by the interest groups to be legitimized in a class action?
- How effective is the role of state authorities, interest groups, and experts in environmental impact assessment?
- How does this affect tourism as an especially dominating sector of the country's economy?

These issues raised for discussion will be part of this paper, for giving recommendations and proposals for solutions.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we reflect on some problems concerning environmental protection. We found that the law addresses the claims of public institutions rather than private subjects. The lack of

implementation and enforcement of the law on collective lawsuits has created delays and problems in addressing case law concerning environmental damages to the court by groups of interest. This law is a draft. If it had been entered into force it would set up material and procedural provisions to give access to all non-profit organizations. Groups of interest, which are specialized in cases linked to the environment would be legitimized in seeking the rights of the community. It can be the community, which seeks the addition and imposition of civil liability, by restoring the damages and seeking compensation and reparation from all the entities that have caused damages. Collective action (class actions) is a legal instrument affirmed by the directive of the European Union, but Albania has not yet received the proper response. Judicial practice is scarce about any issues that have to do with opposing the procedures of collective lawsuits. Also, cases are very few. Another problem is related to the process of informing the public about decision-making in the field of the environment.

In addition, concerning the analyses and the studies made, the approval and entry into force of the law for "Collective Lawsuits" is recommended. The entry into force of this law is not a matter of carrying out and enriching the legislation. These have to do with the right to access in courts. The community has the right to represent itself, in case of problems which worry many people. On the one hand, NGOs founded to protect the interest of the community can express their opinions and recommendations against the decisions of state authorities. Also, they can represent the whole community to the court for compensation and repairing damages by the guilty subject. On the other hand, we must emphasize that the entry into force of the collective action law is a challenge for Albanian legislators. That is because it must find a stable legal structure. This can make easier the process of implementation. Apart from that, the law could be excluded and inapplicable. I think we must update the Albanian legislation, especially in civil liability and environmental damage, because it is very weak.

The participation of free initiative strengthens the position of civil society against the decisions of the state authorities putting forward the responsibility of each subject whose actions, bring profound consequences to the environment. It improves living standards and economic indicators. In addition, society inherits a cleaner environment, reflecting an improvement to the economic sector supported by tertiary services and the sustainable development of tourism and other sectors.

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The Impact of Industry 4.0 on Human Capital Dynamics and Sustainable Economic Restructuring

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Abstract

The emergence of Industry 4.0 is characterized by the integration of digital technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), robotics, and big data analytics. This revolution is transforming industrial and service sectors and playing a crucial role in economic restructuring for sustainable development. This paper examines the complex effects of Industry 4.0 on human capital within the context of sustainable economic transformation.

The analysis begins by tracing the revolutionary nature of Industry 4.0 and its implications for traditional industrial practices. A key focus is the transition in human capital, which is integral to achieving sustainable economic goals. This transition, marked by a shift from manual to cognitive skills and the need for continual learning, is critical in promoting an adaptable and innovative workforce.

Furthermore, the emergence of new job roles demanding advanced digital skills is discussed, along with the challenges in workforce transformation, such as the digital divide and the requirement for extensive skill development. The paper proposes strategies for human capital development, emphasizing the need for organizational and governmental initiatives in education, training, and lifelong learning policies, aligned with sustainable economic objectives.

In conclusion, the paper offers a future perspective on the role of human capital within the framework of sustainable economic development in an automated world. Recommendations are provided for all interested actors and key stakeholders to effectively navigate the challenges and opportunities of human capital management in the era of Industry 4.0, contributing to sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: Industry 4.0, Human Capital Transformation, Sustainable Economic Development, Workforce Adaptation, Digital Skills Advancement.

JEL codes: O33 (Technological Change), J24 (Human Capital; Skills), O14 (Industrialization; Choice of Technology), Q01 (Sustainable Development), J21 (Labor Force and Employment).

1. Introduction

Industry 4.0, first identified in Germany in 2011, marks the onset of the fourth industrial revolution, characterized by a blend of technologies that merge physical, digital, and biological domains. Key to this revolution is the development of cyber-physical systems, driven by advances in the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), robotics, and big data analytics. What sets Industry 4.0 apart is its ability to create interconnected and adaptable manufacturing environments, integrating cutting-edge technologies to make production processes highly customizable and efficient. This marks a significant departure from earlier industrial revolutions focused on mechanization, mass production, and automation. The impact of Industry 4.0 extends beyond technological advancements; it represents a fundamental shift in how industries function and collaborate, enhancing productivity, creating new business models, and generating novel market opportunities. Notably, it transforms data into a crucial resource for real-time decisions and forward-looking analysis, revolutionizing traditional

business operations. Furthermore, Industry 4.0 is reshaping labor markets and the dynamics of human capital, with a growing need for new skills, particularly those related to digital technology. This era presents both challenges and opportunities in employment, necessitating a rethinking of labor policies and training programs to match the new technological context.

2. Methodology

This research paper employs a mixed-method approach to analyze the impact of Industry 4.0 on human capital. The qualitative component explores the industry's effects on various sectors and the new skills required for human capital. Quantitatively, the paper uses a questionnaire based on the DIGICOMP framework, completed by 513 students assessing their digital skills. These results are used to support the argument that education and training in digital skills are critical strategies for current and future needs, highlighting the importance of equipping the workforce for the challenges posed by Industry 4.0. Additionally, quantitative analysis through Confirmatory Factor Analyses, based on interviews with 200 businesses, explores the critical role of employee training in adapting to Industry 4.0. This comprehensive approach ensures a nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities in skill development and workforce transformation as industries evolve with technological advancements.

3. Results and Discussion

The research reveals key findings on the impact of Industry 4.0. It shows significant changes in job roles and labor markets due to Industry 4.0, emphasizing the creation of new job types. The study underscores the essential role of human capital training, supported by data analysis including means, standard deviations, and T statistics. It discusses the evolution of skill requirements from manual to cognitive skills, emphasizing the need for problem-solving, analytical thinking, adaptability, and digital literacy in the new industrial era. The need for digital competencies, as evidenced by DigiComp assessments, and the role of government and organizations in skill development are also outlined. Additionally, the study identifies challenges like skill gaps and job displacement, alongside opportunities for new job creation and workforce diversification.

4. Conclusions

The paper concludes that in the Industry 4.0 era, human capital must adapt and continually learn to meet technological advancements. It emphasizes the need for both technical and soft skills like creativity and critical thinking. The future of human capital requires dynamic workforce development, cross-disciplinary learning, and continuous upskilling. Collaboration between public and private sectors is crucial for aligning education and training with industry needs, ensuring human capital drives sustainable growth and competitiveness in a technologically advanced economy.

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FINANCE

Sustainable Banking in Albania and its Impact on Bank Profitability

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Abstract

This paper gives an overview of the sustainable approach of the banking sector in Albania, by analyzing green practices applied by banks and the level of awareness of bank employees towards this matter. During recent years, banks in Albania have made steps forward regarding green practices by offering green loans, carbon footprint reports for their customers, policies, public commitments, and company goals on environmental protection, etc. In this study, to give an objective conclusion regarding the sustainable approach and its impact on bank profitability, primary data was collected by a questionnaire targeting bank employees and then was used to analyze the level of employees' go-green perception and the effect on bank profitability regarding environmental and sustainable matters. From this analysis, it was concluded that the bank's sustainable approach (regarding policies, strategies, action plans, etc.) has a positive impact on bank profitability, which can also be explained by the positive reputation that these banks can have.

Keywords: sustainable banking, awareness, environment, profitability.

JEL codes: G21, Q56.

1. Introduction

Sustainable banking is defined as the delivery of “financial products and services, which are developed to meet the needs of people and safeguard the environment while generating profit” (Yip and Bocken, 2018). International Finance Corporation (2005) encompasses four dimensions of good business performance: financial, economic, environment, and social sustainability. Although the nature of the banking sector, as the backbone of the finance industry, requires fewer natural resources and may have less negative impact on the environment in comparison with the manufacturing companies, there is much evidence that sustainability and going green will lead the service sectors toward profitability (Zahra and Garvis, 2000).

In our country, the banking system has undergone radical transformations since 1992 moving from few state-owned traditional banks to modern banks that offer many products and services, even sustainable ones. Moreover, when analyzing the banking sector in Albania, especially the largest banks, it is observed a recent approach oriented towards sustainability and green banking by offering products and services that contribute towards environmental/social improvement. As one of the largest banks, Raiffeisen Bank has undertaken policies that include: environmental, social, and governance (ESG) housing loans for living premises equipped with energy efficiency certificates; business loans from the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, combined with a 15% grant financed by the IPA funds of the European Union, while also offering technical assistance that enables SMEs to optimize their investment needs to achieve compliance with EU Priority Directives; financing and supporting agreements between investors and companies that are increasingly taking ESG into account by financing the production of solar panels with a payback period of up to 5 years in EUR and 7 years in ALL; eco-friendly recycled debit/credit cards; using digital platforms that

significantly reduce the use of paper, reduce carbon emissions and minimize the need for travelling; digital wallet; individual carbon footprint report as a monthly overview for customers to better understand how their monthly expenses affect the environment. Also, National Commercial Bank has drafted action plans, policies, public commitments and company goals on environmental protection; offering green loans which are energy efficiency loans for individuals that want to use the loan for improvements that will lead to energy savings and CO2 emission reduction for their living premises; using digital channels for transactions and reducing paperwork in branches; and implementing a new project in their headquarters consisting in solar control and energy savings.

As observed from above mentioned practices, considerable steps have been taken to contribute towards sustainable and green banking. As so, aiming a better understanding of these policies and measures on the employee’s awareness, bank reputation and profitability, a questionnaire was drafted, targeting employees of all 11 banks in Albania, where it was concluded that these practices have a positive impact on bank profitability.

2. Methodology

To meet the objectives of this study, a questionnaire was drafted regarding sustainable bank policies and employees related practice. The target population consisted of all employees working in all 11 banks that operate in cities of Tirana, Durrës, Vlora and Elbasan. Considering the digital convenience, the questionnaire was conducted online. The questionnaire itself consisted in three parts. The first part presented a brief introduction and the study’s aim, while requesting to the respondent to share the questionnaire with other colleagues. In the second part, were given questions regarding employee’s demographic data. The final part consisted of questions related to sustainable bank strategies, policies, and daily activities (5 variables in total: intranet, online meetings, online approvals, eco-friendly paper and cards, green loans, financing and supporting agreements for companies that take ESG in consideration), while also indicating the Return on Assets (ROA) for 2022 for the corresponding bank where the respondent worked. ROA was used as the profitability indicator for the hypothesis H1: Bank sustainable practices have a positive impact on bank profitability.

Certain limitations were taken in consideration during drafting of the questionnaire and study analysis. The generalizability of the conclusions may be limited by the use of a single time primary data given by employees that have participated in this study. Also, data collection and sampling size present their own limitations. The responses recorded from the questionnaire did not take in consideration experts’ opinion regarding these issues. The reputation of banks was measured according to employees’ perception, and not international ratings. Moreover, sustainable or green banking practices were more present in the Albanian banking industry during recent years; as so, these practices do not have a long history and their impact may be more obvious on the future years.

3. Results and Discussion

The questionnaire was filled by 179 employees, mainly females of age 26-30 years old. Most respondents had a master’s degree, and 3 years of work experience in the banking industry. The answers collected were analyzed regarding: the presence of common method biased (CMB), reliability, correlation, and structural model, and results are presented below.

Table 1. Results regarding variables of the analysis

CMB	VIF	Cronbach’s	Correlation	Structural model
Harman’s single-factor test – no concern for CMB	1.31-1.83 No multicollinearity	$\alpha > 0.5$	Goodness of fit	57% (R ²)

Source: Authors’ calculations

The main hypothesis was also found significant for $\beta = 0.33$; $p < 0.05$. The banks' daily sustainable operations (intranet, online meetings, online approvals, eco-friendly paper/cards), and also sustainable policies (such as green loans, financing and supporting agreements for companies that take ESG in consideration) had a positive impact on profitability. This may be explained also with the fact that the largest banks, which also have a higher profitability than smaller banks, are more sustainable-oriented, and have more capacities in investing towards sustainable policies, as well as in the short-term and long-term.

4. Conclusions

The main objective of this study was to give an overview on sustainable banking practices in the Albanian economy, by offering concrete examples on these sustainable policies and action plans, while also concluding if this approach has an impact on bank profitability. As derived from the analysis of the primary data collected by the drafted questionnaire, bank sustainable approach (regarding policies, strategies, action plans, etc.) has a positive impact on bank profitability. More than ever, also by taking in consideration environmental climate changes and the importance of a sustainable environment for future generations, banks are orienting their policies towards sustainable alternatives. In this regard, they contribute positively to the bank reputation, which can attract new customers and retain current costumers.

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Investigating the Determinants of Albanian Agritourism Prices

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Abstract

This paper aims to investigate the price determinants of Albanian agritourism. The agritourism sector in Albania has developed strongly in recent years and has attracted the interest of various stakeholders. Agritourism businesses have the opportunity to become sustainable and contribute to the revitalization of life in rural areas. This paper aims to create a model based on the hedonic pricing model to show the factors that have a significant impact on the price of accommodation. The dependent variable in this model is the price of the agritourism accommodation, while the independent variables are as follows: Distance from the center, Staff service, Facilities, Cleanliness, and Comfort. The data of the variables analyzed are secondary data obtained from the Booking platform for all agritourism establishments that also offer accommodation services, except the restaurant. The results of the econometric model indicate that cleanliness, facilities, and comfort are significant variables for the pricing of accommodation. On the other hand, distance from the center is not significant as tourists seek agritourism to connect with nature and the external environment.

Keywords: Agritourism, hedonic price model, tourism, agriculture, rural tourism.

JEL codes: Q10, Q13 and Z32

1. Introduction

Sustainable agriculture and sustainable rural tourism live in harmony and close connection with each other as a function of sustainable economic development. This solid relationship can be traced back to a common denominator: the environment. Both sectors are fundamentally dependent on the environment for their development. According to Westlund and Nilsson (2022), rural tourism is based on the rural environment in general whereas farm tourism is based on the farm and farmer. The development of rural tourism contributes to the enrichment of tourism supply and the enhancement of sustainable development of rural zones (Chi & Han, 2021). The rural natural environment, farming activities, and local culture are important rural resources and elements of rural landscapes. The cultural and physical environment of the countryside is a fundamental motivation for tourists to engage in rural tourism (Kastenholz et al., 2017).

Rural tourism has undergone significant development in recent years. The awareness of the population for ecological products and the strong connection with the environment seem to be reflected in positive figures for rural tourism. The global rural tourism market is expected to reach USD 102.7 billion in 2023 (Future Market Insights, 2023). Between 2023 and 2033, a steady annual growth rate of 6.8% would further accelerate the market (Future Market Insights, 2023). This would lead to a market valuation of US\$ 198.3 billion in 2033. Meanwhile, agritourism is estimated to increase by 5.79% (US\$ 89.86 billion) (Future Market Insights, 2023).

In Albania, agritourism has experienced unprecedented development in recent years. They are increasingly meeting tourists' demands for organic products, peaceful nature, reasonable costs,

and quality food. Agritourism offers better prospects for Albania's small farmers (Times, 2023).

The development of agritourism was promoted by the Albanian government in 2018 through financial support such as IPARD (94 million euros) and the National Programme (115 million euros), prioritizing the development of agriculture and tourism (AZHBR, 2023). According to the farmer's portal, there are 256 agritourisms in Albania (Portal, 2023). The largest number of agritourism is in the region of Kukës – Tropojë and in the region of Korça. These two regions have a wonderful natural environment. This is confirmed by the study of (Sulaj et al., 2022), which found that the most attractive factor for visiting farms in agritourism is the natural environment of the land.

Figure 1. Number of agritourism according to the regions of the country (October 2023)

Source: The farmer's portal, 2023

2. Methodology

The main objective of this paper is to investigate the determinants of prices in Albanian agritourism. The literature shows that the hedonic price method is the most appropriate model. The hedonic pricing method determines the price based on the internal and external characteristics that influence the product. The hedonic pricing technique was originally developed by Griliches (1971) to estimate the value of quality changes in consumer goods. How much visitors value the presence of a working farm can be investigated using hedonic price analysis (Fleischer and Tchetchik, 2005).

For the analysis, secondary data were obtained from Booking platforms on the prices of agritourism that offer accommodation and the evaluations by customers of these accommodations to understand the importance of intrinsic, locational, and environmental attributes.

The econometric model used in this study is a multiple regression, which has the following form:

$$y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 * x_1 + \beta_2 * x_2 + \dots + \beta_n * x_n + \epsilon_t \quad [1]$$

y_t = the dependent variable;

α = the intercept of the equation;

β_t = sensitivity of the dependent variable – a change of the dependent variable for each unit change in the independent variable $X_{i,n}$;

X_n = independent variables;

ε_t = error term.

The dependent variable in this model is the price of agritourism accommodation, while the following indicators are used as independent variables:

- Distance from the center;
- Staff service;
- Facilities;
- Cleanliness;
- Comfort of the accommodation;
- Value for money;
- Location;
- Number of reviews.

Before analyzing and interpreting the results of the econometric model, we will first test the importance of the model. Then, we will check and verify if the model is valid and correct, by performing tests for the several assumptions (the functional form of the model is appropriate, the model does not suffer from autocorrelation, heteroskedasticity and multicollinearity and the residuals of the model have a normal distribution), which should be fulfilled for a good regression analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

The benefits that sustainable rural tourism can derive from sustainable agriculture can consist of several elements: Food quality, biodiversity conservation, preservation of natural beauty, and authentic community experiences. For these reasons, the development of agritourism in Albania has increased significantly in recent years. There are some studies on agritourism in Albania, which is a new alternative for rural tourism development and is supported by the government to revitalize life in villages, but there is no previous study on the determinants of Albanian agritourism price. The literature suggests that cleanliness, staff service, facilities, and comfort are significant variables in accommodation pricing (Gordan et al., 2023) (Zhang et al., 2011). While the distance from the center is expected to be insignificant since tourists look for agritourism to connect with nature and the external environment. Results of our econometric model show that cleanliness, facilities and comfort are significant variables in accommodation pricing, results which are in accordance with the conclusions drawn by Gordan et al (2023) and Zhang et al (2011).

4. Conclusions

Rural tourism is an important factor that determines the economic progress of the regional economy and influences the economic and social development of rural areas. It creates benefits by increasing the income of the local community, improving employment opportunities for the inhabitants of the region, and minimizing the risk of environmental pollution or destruction of cultural heritage. In Albania, investments in agritourism are growing rapidly. However, accommodation prices are still relatively low. Most of them have prices that do not fluctuate regardless of the region. In the study, the certified agritourism businesses published on the official website of agritourism in Albania (Agritourism, 2023) were considered, which, in addition to the farm and restaurant, also offer the possibility of accommodation. The rating of these agritourism by local and foreign visitors is very high. According to Booking.com, the ratings for all agritourism are more than 8.7/10. From the literature review of previous studies, many factors influence the price of agritourism accommodation, such as internal characteristics, environment, population density, attitude toward sustainability, and local products. Results of the econometric model using secondary data about Albanian agritourism

that offer accommodation show that cleanliness, facilities and comfort are significant variables in accommodation pricing.

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An EU Approach Towards Sustainable Tourism in Albania

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Abstract

With the number of foreign visitors arriving to Albania in September 2023 increasing by 45% compared to September 2022 (INSTAT), and trade openness increasing due to a surge in exports of (tourism) services (SWD, 2023), Albania's tourism sector was faced with a boom during 2023 and clearly showed recovery from the COVID-19 consequences. Moreover, this sector is a major driver of economic growth, contributing directly up to 8.5 – 8.7% of GDP and indirectly to more than 20% of GDP (UNDP, 2022). Looking at European Union (EU) level, tourism showed almost a full recovery compared to pre-pandemic levels in 2019, but as the EU strives for full recovery it is also striving for a “green” tourism.

The objective of this paper is to conduct a comprehensive review of policies and challenges towards sustainable tourism development at EU level and use this understanding to provide recommendations for future tourism policies in Albania. The literature review will be followed by a SWOT analysis while taking into consideration the interconnectedness between tourism and environment and the role that tourism small and medium size enterprise (SMEs) play, and a comparative analysis between any EU Members State good practices and Albania.

A tourism boom is associated with challenges and requires particular attention to sustainable tourism policies. Considering EU's pledges for a twin transition - green and digital - tourism and environment policies should be intertwined and digital transformation can be used at the benefit of sustainable tourism development.

Keywords: Sustainable tourism, EU, Albania, environment, SMEs.

JEL codes: D02, F63, F64, F68, L52, L83, L88, O19, O25

1. Introduction

Tourism represents an important part of the EU economy, and it has been identified as one of the fourteen (14) industrial ecosystems in the EU's updated 2020 New Industrial Strategy (SWD, 2021). Similarly, tourism in Albania constitutes an important sector. According to the National Strategy for Sustainable Development of Tourism of Albania 2019 – 2023, tourism contributes up to 8.5% of the country's GDP directly and up to 26.2% of GDP indirectly. Additionally, it was defined as one of the strategic industrial sectors in the Common Regional Market Action Plan 2021 – 2024, adopted by the Western Balkans' countries.

The objective of this work is to raise awareness on sustainable tourism, which has gained widespread acceptance at EU level, and provide recommendations for a sustainable approach in tourism policies in Albania.

Booming tourism is often associated with challenges and raises questions about the environmental and socio-economic impact. According to UNWTO, sustainable tourism principles should ensure a balance between environmental, socio-cultural and economic aspects. Tourism has long been considered an important sector in the EU - to name some key strategic documents - as defined in the “*new political framework for tourism*” (COM, 2010) in 2010, where a number of challenges to tourism sector were recognized in efforts to make Europe, the world's number one tourist destination. This was followed by the update on the

2020 European Industrial Strategy, where tourism was defined as one of the key industrial ecosystems and pathways for recovery of these ecosystems were set forth.

These frameworks are followed by numerous thematic strategic documents that aim to contribute to sustainable tourism, such as the traveler's package directive – currently being revised; promoting greener tourism through supporting green SMEs (e.g. the EU Ecolabel and EU eco-management and audit scheme); improving the data collection for tourism; digital transition for tourism, etc.

2. Methodology

A qualitative analysis of tourism policies at EU level and in Albania is undertaken to identify best practices, gaps and ways forward towards sustainable tourism, taking into account current challenges and priorities.

The analysis reveals several important EU tools that support sustainable tourism. The EU Tourism Dashboard monitors the green and digital transition; the Tourism Business Portal is dedicated to tourism SMEs supporting their need for information on the industry; a dedicated guide on tourism funding provides information on financing opportunities for various tourism sectors, etc.

Looking at a few best practices, Paphos, Greece and Seville, Spain are proud holders of the title “European Capital of Smart Tourism 2023”, awarded for their smart and sustainable tourism practices. Seville for example is a very good example of using cooperation with the private sector to develop Tourism Sustainability Indices to measure various tourism indicators and identify areas for improvement (WEF, 2023).

3. Results and Discussion

Tourism growth poses major challenges to sustainability, but EU shows how incorporating tourism across key industrial ecosystems and within the efforts towards the twin transition – green and digital – can lead to positive outcomes. Hence, at EU level, tourism policies have been reflected across digital transition, European Green Deal, various agendas that support SMEs, and back by funding opportunities.

Similarly in Albania, two important documents – the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans (GAWB) and the Common Regional Market Action Plan (CRM AP) – consist of actions related to the green transition and sustainable tourism, in line with EU standards and practices and enhancing regional cooperation and knowledge sharing. However, at national level, the key document for the development of sustainable tourism lacks elements related to the green transition or supporting tourism SMEs through tailor made actions.

Therefore, relevant institutions in Albania can take several steps to enhance actions towards sustainable tourism in line with EU standards and approach:

Improve governance:

- Ensure that the new National Tourism Strategy includes the necessary measures aiming to enhance tourism development in line with environmental protection; support to tourism SMEs; support education and skilling, etc;
- Consider the cross-cutting aspects of tourism by ensuring closer coordination and coherence between institutions. Albania has already taken a positive step recognizing the interconnectedness between tourism and environment and putting both sectors under one roof (Ministry of Tourism and Environment);
- Establish a tourism network that engages all tourism stakeholders (public and private sector, academia and CSOs) through open dialogue and transparency to address challenges jointly and share best practices.

Improve data collection and statistics:

- Assess the impact of the sector and improve statistical reporting aiming to provide more insights into the gaps and needs to further address sustainability of the tourism sector, as well as of the businesses operating in this sector. Tourism Satellite Accounts (TSAs) used in the EU are a good tool to gather insights into sustainability of tourism SMEs and more thorough impact assessments of the tourism sector.

Encourage investments:

- Investing in infrastructure goes in parallel with tourism development, including transport, digital infrastructure etc., as it supports not only tourists but more importantly, SMEs which can access larger markets, supply chains and more modern payment systems;
- Investing in education and tourism skills is another important step that requires multistakeholder collaboration to update curricula, integrate business needs and enhance education opportunities.

4. Conclusions

The importance of tourism sector in the Albanian economy highlights the need for sustainable development. In fact, Albania has recognized the importance of sustainable tourism already in the National Strategy for a Sustainable Tourism Development 2019 – 2023. But, as the Strategy comes to an end, it is the right time to consider gaps from the current strategy, emerging needs and obligations deriving from various regional cooperation documents, EU integration process and global political and economic developments.

Hence, the new National Strategy should have more elements and indicators related to sustainability of the sector and to promote the competitiveness of tourism SMEs in line with best practices and EU standards. To achieve this, there is a need to focus on better statistical reporting on sustainability, closer cooperation among tourism stakeholders, closer coordination among various institutions given the cross-cutting and complex nature of the tourism sector and encourage investments in both, infrastructure and skills.

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The Nexus between Influencing Variables and Tourism Receipts in Albania

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Abstract

Tourism is quite a recently developed contributor in Albanian economy and it is growing progressively. This sector is contributing with acceleration in Albanian economy, and it is being seen as an important sector for future sustainability of our economy. Latest figures of the previous year demonstrate that 17.4% of the total Albanian GDP is generated by tourism economic activities and transactions related to it. This paper aims to analyze these factors and their effects in tourism receipts in Albania for the last 26 years (1995 – 2021). Secondary data from the World Bank database are used in form of time series. Multivariable linear regression model is used to create a generalized framework to understand the relation between tourist receipts and other variables. Regarding the multiple regression in the research and methodology section, number of tourists, gross fixed capital formation, foreign direct investments and political stability are seen as the principal factors affecting tourism receipts in Albania. As tourism is analyzed as a long-term tributary in Albanian economy, policymaking institutions should produce sustainable policies to support the growth of the sector.

Keywords: Tourism receipts, macroeconomic variables, multiple regression model, etc.

JEL codes: Z32, C32, C51

1. Introduction

Tourism is quite a recently developed contributor in Albanian economy, and it is growing progressively. The commencement of tourism in Albania dates back to '60, when first tourists from Eastern Europe Block came to visit limited touristic destinations of the country. The modern tourism concept began to develop in the first years of the new millennium. Tourism is contributing with acceleration in Albanian economy, and it is being seen as an important sector for future sustainability of our economy. Latest figures of the previous year demonstrate that 17.4% of the total Albanian GDP is generated by tourism economic activities and transactions related to it. Yet, there are various macroeconomic and political factors that have a direct impact on tourism. As these factors change, tourism receipts are being impacted. The number of tourists, gross fixed capital formation, net migration, foreign direct investments, remittances, political stability, and government effectiveness are contemplated as foremost factors impacting revenues coming from tourism. This paper aims to analyze these factors and their effects in tourism receipts in Albania for the last 26 years (1995 – 2021). Multivariable linear regression model is used to create a generalized framework to understand the relation between tourist receipts and other variables. Since the tourism is a vigorous sector, covering several economic activities like traveling, accommodation and other facilities, there are a lot of components affecting it. The overall analysis of these factors can create a microframework to analyze the major top indicators impacting tourism receipts. In this context, the adequate analysis of demographic, socio – economic and political factors can lead into a sustainable growth of revenues coming from tourism. As suggested by literature, foreign direct

investments, gross fixed capital formation, net migration indicator, remittances, and political stability are seen as the main factors that impact tourism receipts in Albania.

In developing countries, late studies prove that there is a positive relation between foreign direct investments and tourism receipts (Samimi, Sadeghi, & Sadeghi, 2015). In the context of economic growth, Sokhanvar have found that foreign direct investments in tourism sector should be considered as highly important for economic growth and development, from the policymaking viewpoint, especially in long run (Sokhanvar, 2019). The development of this sector is also linked with all three mentioned dimensions of sustainability (Streimikiene, Svagzdiene, & Jasinskis, 2021). Sustainable actions are also related with demographic and social indicators like aging, life expectancy, etc. There is a significative negative correlation between remittances and tourism receipts, implying that those families receiving remittances do not spend them on tourism activities, but more on daily consume products, or rarely saving (Hasan, Hashmi, & Sajid, 2022). Provenzano affirms that there is no statistical correlation between tourism and migration phenomenon (Provenzano, 2020). Balli and Jean Louis also emphasize that there is no direct correlation, however, migrants that are residents in foreign countries of OECD can bring indirect tourism receipts, due to their promotion activity for their homeland (Balli, Balli, & Louis, 2016). Ghalia et. al. suggest that institutional reform can help boost the economies of countries with low-quality institutions, and it can also have important additional economic benefits for countries that are highly dependent on tourism (Ghalia, Samargandi, & Sohag, 2019). Akadiri and Uzunel also affirm that there is a causal relationship between tourism policies and political stability in general (Akadiri, Alola, & Uzuner, 2021). Furthermore, political (in)stability and destination image have a strong effect on tourist satisfaction and intention to recommend (Eid, El-Kassrawy, & Agag, 2019). Athari et. al. proves that employing the Pooled OLS (Ordinary Least Square) and the Generalized Moment of Methods (GMM), the estimation results suggest that the political risk is a significant impediment to the growth of total tourism arrivals in the panel countries. (Athari, Alola, Ghasemi, & Alola, 2020).

2. Research methodology

In this paper, secondary data are used to create time series of the variables, and all of them are quantitative variables. In general, macro indicators like remittances, foreign direct investments, gross fixed capital formation, net migration [in cumulative effect], the government effectiveness, political stability, etc. are taken into analysis. As suggested by the literature review and other papers [see: Literature review], these are the most important factors that contribute to the fluctuation of tourism receipts in developing countries. As a very important notation, all these variables are being deflated. Inflation adjusting is made to remove the effect of inflation, as most of the variables are impacted by inflation. Multiple linear regression is chosen to describe the impact of the independent variables in the tourism receipts in Albania. Then, all the statistical tests are described in the Analysis section, to affirm the stability of the model used.

The general equation of the multiple linear regression can be as below:

$$y_i = \lambda_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + \beta_6 x_6 + \varepsilon_i$$

where,

y_i – Δ Rec., the level of tourism receipts in Albania.

x_1 – Δ FDI (-1) (foreign direct investments with 1 lag term delay),

x_2 – Δ remittances,

x_3 – Δ^2 number of tourists,

x_4 – Δ GFCF, the level of gross fixed capital formation

x_5 – Δ PStab., the index of political stability

x_6 – Net Migration (-1) (with 1 lag term delay)

ε_i – error term of residuals.

As a result, from data processing of the variables time series, the econometric model is presented as in the **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 1: General multiple regression model of tourism receipts in Albania

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.01E+08	45850857	2.199254	0.0420
D (FDI (-1))	0.591626	0.147984	3.997892	0.0009
D(REM)	-0.448774	0.244669	-1.834206	0.0842
D(D(TOURISTS))	290.7965	24.90482	11.67631	0.0000
D(GFCFDEF)	0.597245	0.110618	5.399149	0.0000
D(PSTAB)	3.69E+08	1.60E+08	2.300102	0.0344
NETMIG (-1)	-2462.993	1080.162	2.280207	0.0358
R-squared	0.921470	Mean dependent var		47491055
Adjusted R-squared	0.893754	S.D. dependent var		3.12E+08
Log likelihood	-472.4117	Hannan-Quinn criteria		40.04213
F-statistic	33.24629	Durbin-Watson stat		2.117944
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Processed by authors in EViews10.

The general model used in this paper has successfully passed all the statistical tests related to its significance, and the multiple regression is presented as:

$$\Delta \text{Receipts} = 0.0001 + 0.592\Delta\text{FDI} (-1) - 0.449\Delta\text{Rem.} + 290\Delta 2\text{Tourists} + 0.597\Delta\text{GFCF} + 0.00037\Delta\text{PStab} - 2462.99\text{NetMig.} (-1)$$

As variables change throughout time, econometrical models need to adapt or improve. However, long-term stability of model is required to use it as a sustainable instrument. CUSUM test (or CUSUM of squares) is used to affirm the usability of a certain model. Regarding our data series, CUSUM of squares [the most precise test] confirms that our model has stable parameters and can be used in long-term analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

It is clearly shown that foreign direct investments, the number of tourists, gross fixed capital formation and political stability have a positive correlation with the receipts coming from tourism. Meanwhile, the net migration of individuals and the level of remittances have a negative impact on tourism flows. Furthermore:

If foreign direct investments increase with 1%, this will expand the tourism receipts of the next year by 0.592%.

If the gross fixed capital formation (the level of public investments in infrastructure and other sectors) is enlarged with 1%, this will increase the tourism receipts of the actual period by 0.597%.

If the political stability index is increase by 1%, it causes a 0.0037% more tourism flows.

If remittances get larger by 1%, this will cause a shrinkage by 0.449% in tourism receipts.

These results present the influence of these variables directly in tourism receipts in Albania. Despite that, tourism is also impacted by other micro and macro factors, but they are not in the focus of this paper. Net migration and foreign direct investments are being analyzed in the context of one lag term delay, due to their impact in economy. Foreign direct investments require at least 1 year to prepare the investment, the contractual and juridical aspects, etc., and then to have a measurable impact in an economy. The same logic stands for net migration, since the habituation and accommodation process in another country require at least 8 – 12 months, to have impact in economy.

4. Conclusions

Nowadays, tourism is one of the top contributors in Albanian economy, directly responsible for more than 17% of the total gross domestic product. The tourism sector in Albania is also impacted by some macroeconomic variables that influence the level of revenues coming from tourism. As the most important ones, factors like the foreign direct investments, remittances, net migration, political stability, and the gross fixed capital formation have a considerable impact on tourism. In conclusion, foreign direct investments, the number of tourists arriving in Albania, gross fixed capital formation and political stability tend to have a relatively strong positive correlation with the tourism flows in the last 26 years in Albania. In contrary, the number of net migrants leaving the country (with one lag term delay) and the level of remittances are negatively correlated with the tourism receipts. Furthermore, if foreign direct investments increase with 1%, this will expand the tourism receipts of the next year by 0.592%. In addition, the gross fixed capital formation (the level of public investments in infrastructure and other sectors) is enlarged with 1%, this will increase the tourism receipts of the actual period by 0.597%. If the political stability index is increase by 1%, it causes a 0.0037% more tourism flows. Lastly, if remittances get larger by 1%, this will cause a shrinkage by 0.449% in tourism receipts. The authors recommend that tourism should also be considered in the context of sustainable economic growth, because several activities related to tourism potentially cause negative externalities. Moreover, government and other policymaking institutions should make long-term strategic investments and fiscal policies in support of tourism.

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Data Analytics in Fintech: A Tool for Assessing and Responding to COVID-19 Economic Challenges

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Abstract

The unprecedented challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic have compelled industries worldwide to reassess their strategies and adapt to a rapidly evolving landscape. This paper aims to analyze in detail the complex interaction between the Covid-19 pandemic and the Fintech landscape in Albania. In a period where global economies underwent unimaginable transformations due to the pandemic, questions arise regarding the extent to which the Fintech sector in Albania has been affected by this dynamic. The analysis focuses on whether the challenges presented by the pandemic have acted as a catalyst for innovation and development in the Fintech field or conversely, whether the sector has largely remained unchanged. Through an in-depth analysis primarily based on literature review, key indicators, case studies, and regulatory dynamics analysis, the abstract aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between the health crisis and the evolution of Fintech in Albania. By emphasizing this connection, the analysis contributes to the ongoing debate on the adaptability and resilience of financial technology in the face of external influences, offering valuable perspectives for industry actors, decision-makers, and researchers. The exploration not only unveils the specific impact of Covid-19 on the Fintech sector in Albania but also serves as a broader reflection on the sector's ability to withstand and thrive in unexpected challenge contexts, thus outlining the foundations for sustainable growth in the future and suggesting actionable steps to be taken.

Keywords: covid-19 pandemic, fintech, landscape, innovation and development, adaptability and resilience, sustainable growth

1. Introduction

In recent years, we have witnessed a remarkable surge in the field of financial technology, commonly known as fintech. This domain encompasses a wide range of technological applications that have revolutionized conventional financial services. Fintech is characterized by its diverse ecosystem comprising startups, established companies, and platform-based businesses all working towards transforming the landscape of financial markets and institutions. One key driving force behind this transformation is the integration of data analytics—an immensely powerful tool that harnesses vast amounts of data to extract valuable insights.

Against the backdrop of unprecedented economic hardships caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the convergence between fintech and data analytics has assumed even greater significance. The objective of this study is to delve into how data analytics plays an instrumental role within the realm of fintech—specifically in evaluating and responding to the economic repercussions stemming from this ongoing global health crisis. By exploring these interconnected domains comprehensively, our aim is to illuminate an evolving terrain where finance intersects with technology while navigating through intricate economic challenges triggered by this pandemic situation.

2. Methodology

To fully explore the relationship between the Covid-19 pandemic and the Fintech sector in Albania, we will adopt a phased approach. We will begin with a comprehensive literature review to contextualize the global transformations in the financial sector caused by the pandemic. Subsequently, we will proceed with data collection, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. This will involve in-depth interviews with industry experts, analysis of business financial data, and the use of relevant government reports.

To gain a comprehensive view of the pandemic's impacts, we will examine specific cases of Albanian Fintech companies, assessing their responses and adaptations during the critical period. Augmenting the investigation with qualitative interviews will enable us to glean invaluable insights from key industry players, including regulators and market actors.

The application of statistical methods will allow us to quantitatively assess key performance indicators, providing a robust foundation for analyzing trends and variations in the industry. Furthermore, we will conduct a comparative analysis with other international contexts to further contextualize the findings. This integrated methodology is designed to offer a comprehensive perspective on the pandemic's influence on the dynamics of the Fintech sector in Albania, encouraging a profound understanding of the changes and developmental opportunities.

3. Conclusions

Given the impact that fintech has had globally during the pandemic period, we anticipate drawing significant conclusions. Firstly, our plan is to identify how the challenges presented by the pandemic have influenced the adaptation strategies and innovation within Albanian fintech companies. It will be intriguing to explore whether the crisis has acted as a catalyst for the accelerated adoption of digital solutions and advanced financial technologies.

Secondly, we expect to understand the role of regulators in facilitating or impeding the sector's evolution. The flexibility of policies and regulatory support might emerge as crucial factors shaping the fintech sector's response during the pandemic.

Furthermore, we aim to highlight the opportunities that have emerged within the pandemic context. We anticipate identifying specific sectors within fintech that have experienced considerable growth and evaluating how these opportunities might shape the future of the Albanian financial sector.

Lastly, our goal is to emphasize the importance of lessons learned and best practices derived from the experiences of the fintech sector in Albania during the pandemic. These findings could offer valuable guidance for future strategic developments, policies, and initiatives aimed at ensuring the continuous elasticity and innovation of the fintech sector during times of crisis.

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The Role of Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations and Fiscal Decentralization Progress in Albania

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Abstract

Fiscal decentralization, coupled with effective intergovernmental fiscal relations, stands as a cornerstone in the evolution of modern governance structures. This paper investigates the intricate dynamics between intergovernmental fiscal relations and the progress of fiscal decentralization initiatives across diverse socio-economic and political contexts, with a special focus on Albanian case. By analyzing the progress made in fiscal decentralization efforts worldwide, this research identifies key drivers, challenges, and best practices that have shaped successful outcomes.

Through a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, this study evaluates the real level of fiscal decentralization made in Albania. By identify all source of intergovernmental relations in Albania and making a scientific evaluation of these sources, paper will provide real conclusions and strong recommendations on following next years.

In the context of Albania, the interplay between intergovernmental fiscal relations and the progress of fiscal decentralization stands as a testament to the country's commitment to effective governance and regional development. The paper delves into case studies from various countries, offering a comparative analysis of fiscal decentralization models. Over recent years, Albania has embarked on ambitious fiscal decentralization initiatives, aiming to empower local governments and enhance their capacities to meet the diverse needs of their communities. Lessons learned from Albania's journey serve as a rich source of knowledge, providing practical implications and recommendations for other nations striving to achieve similar fiscal decentralization goals, making a significant contribution to the global discourse on decentralized governance.

Keywords: Local Government, Public Finance Management, Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations, Fiscal Decentralization

JEL codes: H72; H73; H77

1. Introduction

Decentralized governance, underpinned by the intricate interplay of intergovernmental fiscal relations and fiscal decentralization progress, has garnered increasing attention in the discourse of contemporary public administration and governance. This paper delves these interrelated concepts, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of their roles, challenges, and outcomes within evolving governance frameworks. The evolution of governance paradigms in recent decades has underscored the importance of fiscal decentralization as a catalyst for local development, efficient resource allocation, and responsive public service delivery.

Fiscal decentralization and the increase in the autonomy of the local government has progressed at a satisfactory and stable rate during the last years. After territorial administrative reform in Albania, the growing responsibilities of local government has brought the need to increase the share of local revenues and expenditures to GDP and general government expenditures, in

particular the increase of revenues from unconditional transfers, own revenues, and allocated taxes. The reforms developed over the years for the modernization of local finances have yielded results in terms of macroeconomic stability, predictability, and transparency of disciplined use of budget funds.

Based on international literature, the level of decentralization represents an important developmental stage of public policies. Different countries have created general mechanisms such as the unconditional transfer formula or specific forms of transfers linked to the country's specific characteristics. According to the literature, even though financing mechanisms can be identified, their implementation requires adaptation and assessment to the country's context. By defining the boundaries and goals of these concepts, we aim to establish a robust foundation for our analysis. The scope encompasses the diverse mechanisms through which financial resources are allocated, shared, and utilized across central and local government levels. Our objective is to discern how these mechanisms influence the overall governance landscape, affecting local autonomy, accountability, and service quality.

2. Methodology

Rigorous empirical analysis forms is used on the evidence of level of transfers from central to local government in Albania. Through quantitative methods, we delve into datasets spanning diverse nations, exploring trends, patterns, and correlations related to fiscal decentralization progress. Concurrently, qualitative methods, including in-depth case studies, allow us to unpack context-specific nuances, providing depth to our quantitative findings. This methodological triangulation enhances the robustness of our analysis, offering a holistic view of intergovernmental fiscal relations and fiscal decentralization progress.

The study is based on primary data on intergovernmental transfers collected by authors in official sources of the Ministry of Finance and Economy for 61 Municipalities in the Government Financial Information System (AGFIS Treasury System). Official information on decentralization progress and macroeconomic indicators for local units is provided by local self-government units and by INSTAT for the period 2016-2023. All the data are processed by the authors of the paper to be used in the right format for the analysis of intergovernmental relations and decentralization progress in Albania.

3. Results and Discussion

As the result, this study is presented a succinct overview from comprehensive analysis. Local government in Albania has made reforms to push forward the fiscal decentralization process, but based on the nature of the transfers, the comparison with the local budget and sustainability of the fiscal decentralization reforms, has demonstrate that the progress has not reached strategic expectations.

The local budget expenditures for the year 2024 are projected at 71.1 billion lek, with an increase of 10.4% compared to the 2023 budget. These expenditures for the year 2024 account for 3% of GDP, up from 2.4% in 2015. Additionally, an extra amount of 15.3 billion lek is allocated as conditioned transfers from line ministries and central institutions for investment projects benefiting municipalities, making the local budget as a percentage of GDP 3.5%. **Local government takes around 22% of the budget in the form of transfers at the full discretion of central government decisions.** Unconditional transfers for 2024 are 12% higher than in 2023 and 92% higher compared to 2015 (the year before the administrative-territorial reform). The unconditional transfer projected for 2024 is 24.3 billion lek, and it will be increased by 10.7

billion lek for new sectoral functions and 1.5 billion lek for salary increases, bringing the total transfer from the state budget to local authorities to 36.5 billion lek.

For the funding own functions of local government, various funds are allocated from the budgets of line ministries or budgetary institutions through different forms of unconditional transfers, without being subject to the phases and cycles of budgetary discussions between central and local authorities. The distribution of these transfers is carried out without a transparent criterion or an approved formula in cooperation with local governments, with a goal to create a developmental mechanism. On this research results that, such as water supply function that have been recentralized. The recentralized functions does this harm just intergovernmental fiscal relations, but it is also not in line with the national policies of the decentralization strategy.

In this study results a low impact of fiscal autonomy on local governance structures and was an implicated situation of fiscal decentralization on economic development and social equity in local government. As distilling complex analyses into concise findings, we provide valuable takeaways for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers, fostering evidence-based decision-making in the realm of public administration and fiscal policy. In summary, this paper represents a significant contribution to the evolving field of decentralized governance based on the literature cases and the real measure on Albanian intergovernmental relations. Through this research, with a concrete result we have evaluated the policy formulation, inspired further scholarly inquiry, and catalyzed effective governance practices worldwide.

4. Conclusions

Through this study we have identified the toric forms of handling intergovernmental fiscal relations and the way of handling them in the case of Albania. ***The intergovernmental relations built and developed over the years have been finalized with the approval of the local finance law. These mechanisms need to be preserved and guaranteed through technical mechanisms within the budget drafting and implementation system.*** Considering the current financial situation of the local government in Albania, the level of fiscal decentralization has been measured, resulting in the need for intervention:

Increasing local revenue capacity, through increasing the level of financial autonomy of local government, especially by increasing the levels of financing of local functions.

Fiscal consolidation and sustainability of local government finances during 2024 will be an important indicator of strengthening the ability of local government to provide public services. Strengthening the rules and procedures for the management of public finances at the local level, ensuring more fiscal discipline in the management of financial difficulties.

In cooperation with other institutions, revision of salaries for all levels of local government.

Analysis and revision of the scheme (if necessary) of the distribution of the unconditional transfer impacted by the 2023 Census for local self-government units.

The size of funds with the local government's decision-making discretion (transfers and local taxes) does not correspond to the level of responsibilities and real competencies that local government has by law. It is necessary to ensure an increase in the quality of public services that the size of these funds for local government should be increased.

Based on the results of this research is necessary that central government needs to put in transparent legal framework all the intergovernmental transfers from line ministries, and to have a special focus on decentralization new tax source of revenues. Budgetary transfers should

be based on more transparent mechanisms according to the legal distribution criteria, in order to avoid political influence on these funds. By encouraging the fiscal capacity of local government by new source of revenues on local level, will strength not just the responsibility on public finance management but and in quality of public services delivered by municipalities.

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Exploring the Impact of Blockchain on the Financial Dynamics of Travel and Tourism Companies

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Abstract

Blockchain technology is revolutionizing various sectors worldwide. It's a logical step that blockchain has extended its reach to the travel and tourism industry, an area already experiencing rapid digital advancement. As with other industries, tourism is also undergoing significant change due to blockchain technology. This research aimed to analyse the impact that blockchain has on companies in this sector. It focused particularly on the impact that blockchain has on the financials of these companies. The research is exploratory and interpretative. The information was collected from various sources, including research papers, industry reports, and organisations.

The research found that tourism companies can have several benefits from blockchain, like fraud prevention, cost efficiency, enhanced customer experience, improved competitiveness, creation of new revenue models, increased efficiency in inventory management, and industry collaboration. Blockchain technology, by fostering transparency, security, and efficiency, has the potential to drive significant positive transformations in the travel and tourism industry, which could lead to better financial management and economic outcomes. Among the positive benefits, the risks that are associated with blockchain in tourism are also be considered.

Keywords: blockchain, tourism, transparency, cost efficiency, financial management

JEL codes: G30, O33, Q01

1. Introduction

Blockchain technology is playing a key role in economic development. As difficult as it was when it was first introduced as easy, it has now spread its impact in many areas. Similar to other sectors, blockchain is also contributing to transforming the travel and tourism sector. Different stakeholders related to these sectors are enjoying the benefits that are related to the use of blockchain, including customers, travel and tourism companies, and the country. Together with the many benefits that relate to the use of blockchain in this sector, there are also some risks. What are these benefits? Who is reaping these benefits? Do companies have any financial benefit from using blockchain? What are the risks that come with the use of blockchain in the travel and tourism industry?

The aim of this research was to answer all these questions. The ways blockchain can affect the travel and tourism sector can be many. This research saw things more from the perspective of the companies that operate in this industry. Among different areas of a company that blockchain can affect, the research focused more on the financial impact that blockchain had on these companies. The aim was to see the potential of blockchain to affect the financials of the company in the short and long term. This includes its potential to increase revenues, reduce costs, and promote the growth of companies in this industry.

Blockchain has attracted a lot of attention from different stakeholders. Regarding the travel and tourism industry, there also is a growing interest in using blockchain in different areas. Blockchain is showing a significant potential to transform companies in this industry and also

the whole industry, by offering different mechanisms that can promote sustainable tourism. The adoption of blockchain in tourism companies can positively affect service quality. It can also improve service planning for tourism companies, which can lead to a reduction of the costs and time needed to offer the service (Rana et al. 2023). This technology serves as an innovative way of financing innovative tourism projects, and it can contribute to increasing the company's competitiveness and efficiency. It can have a significant impact on improving the financial management of tourism companies (Castillos et al. 2023).

The research is exploratory and interpretative. Considering the fact that the adoption of blockchain in the travel and tourism industry is relatively new, it made it difficult to access quantitative information on the impact that this technology has on the financials of travel and tourism companies. This explains why the research is qualitative more than quantitative. The basis for the research was secondary information collected from various sources. Some key findings about ways through which blockchain can affect travel and tourism companies included increased efficiency in inventory management, enhanced customer privacy, creation of new revenue models, and reduced costs (Gupta, 2019). Besides the benefits, using blockchain has some technical, legal and financial risks that should consider.

2. Methodology

This research aimed to make an analysis of the impact of blockchain on tourism companies. The focus was on how blockchain can affect these companies, considering what its advantages and disadvantages are. Its primary focus was on the impact of blockchain on their financials. The research was exploratory and interpretative. It is mainly based on secondary information that was collected from various sources, including research papers, blockchain organisations, and industry reports. The information was collected initially and then processed to remove the one that did not relate to the research. Some key objectives of the research were:

To analyse the advantages and disadvantages of using blockchain in travel and tourism companies.

To find ways in which the financials of travel and tourism companies can improve from the use of blockchain.

To create a guide for companies in this sector that are not taking advantage of the benefits that blockchain offers.

To highlight some key risks that related to blockchain that travel and tourism companies should consider.

3. Results and Discussion

Blockchain has a high potential to affect the travel and tourism industry. This research focuses more on the way it can affect the financials of companies that operate in this industry. The research does not include only companies that offer a blockchain-based solution, but also a company that may indirectly benefit by using blockchain services offered by other companies. Some key benefits that blockchain adoption in travel and tourism has are (Gupta, 2019), (Joshi, 2019):

Cost efficiency. By eliminating middlemen and streamlining various processes, blockchain can significantly reduce operational costs for companies in the travel and tourism sector.

Increased efficiency in inventory management. Blockchain can solve the problem of poor visibility on the inventory, which results in overbooking, cancellations, or refunds. A confirmed booking in the blockchain can take the form of a direct sale or a booking made by an agent, which is added as a transaction block.

Fraud prevention. Blockchain's immutable and transparent nature can help combat fraud and data theft, which is particularly beneficial in payment processing and identity verification.

Enhanced customer experience. Faster transactions, quicker check-ins, and more secure data management enhance the overall customer experience, potentially leading to higher customer retention and positive reviews.

New revenue models. Blockchain facilitates the creation of new business models, like decentralized marketplaces and loyalty programs, which can generate additional revenue streams for businesses.

Industry collaboration. Consortium blockchains like Camino can foster greater collaboration and trust among industry stakeholders, promoting a more cooperative and innovative industry ecosystem.

Increased competitiveness. Considering that blockchain is relatively new in the travel and tourism industry, companies that take the risk of adopting it first will be one step ahead of the competitors, which will lead to higher profits.

Using blockchain in travel and tourism companies has several benefits that are reflected in the financials of the company. Overall, we can say that blockchain has the potential to improve the financial management of these companies. The application of blockchain technology in the travel and tourism industry hinges on several fundamental and generalizable ideas, including decentralization, transparency and trust, data security and privacy, identity verification, real-time data management, cost efficiency, smart contracts, tokenization and loyalty programs, inter-organizational collaboration, integration with other emerging technologies. On the other side adopting blockchain adoption faces some obstacles. For companies that have only a few early adopters, it is not easy to take advantage of all the benefits it offers. Conversely, in companies where blockchain is the core of the business model, it is challenging to build the technology, because it can be costly. On the other side, there may be technical issues that relate to customers' use of this technology in the tourism and travel industry. Legal issues can be another obstacle for companies that want to use blockchain (Dadkhah et al. 2022).

4. Conclusions

The aim of this research was to make an analysis of the benefits and the associated risks that come from the adoption of blockchain in the travel and tourism sector. The results showed that there are various benefits for travel and tourism companies in adopting blockchain technology. Some key benefits included cost efficiency, increased efficiency in inventory management, enhanced customer experience, new revenue models, and increased competitiveness. These positive changes related to the adoption of blockchain are reflected in the financials of the company. Anyway, adopting blockchain in these companies comes with some obstacles that they should consider. Some key obstacles were legal issues, technical issues, and financial issues. Overall, we can say that considering the advantages and disadvantages of using blockchain in travel and tourism companies, it is worth using it. It also results in improved financial management of these companies. This research was qualitative because of the lack of access to quantitative information. Future research could go deeper into quantitative analysis to see the degree to which blockchain adoption affects the financials of companies in this industry.

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SMEs in front of Economic Restructuring. New Challenges on Finance, Technology and Innovation Imposed by Market Needs

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Abstract

The country's economic restructuring requires an immediate response from businesses, which should be prepared to compete in dynamic markets that require new knowledge, advanced technologies, and innovative solutions. Providing financing to adapt work processes, to qualify the workforce and to achieve a positive financial performance is one of the current challenges faced by SMEs in our country. This paper aims to analyze the challenges with a financial orientation that these businesses encounter in two directions: the qualification of the staff to absorb the new knowledge needed in the new market conditions, as well as the investment in innovative solutions, necessary to increase competitiveness. The analysis is based on primary data from a sample of 304 SMEs operating in the cities with the highest concentration of SMEs in Albania, respectively in Tirana, Durrës, Shkodër, Vlorë, Elbasan, Korçë, Berat. The main results of the study emphasize the need of businesses for external financing sources, especially for supporting their operating activity. On the other hand, financing is not considered the main obstacle for not carrying innovative investment or not supporting activities for staff qualification. Factors such as motivation, training culture and capacity to organize on-the-job training have significant impact on the staff qualifications, while innovative investments are affected by the staff capabilities and R&D costs.

Keywords: SMEs, Finance, Technology, Innovation, Restructuring

1. Introduction

The development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is an essential component of economic development. SMEs are a significant source of employment and help stimulate innovation and competition.

SMEs continue to be the biggest promoter of economic development in the country. The role of SMEs takes on particular importance mainly in developing countries by promoting actions in the formation of new markets and products. In addition, the SME sector is characterized as a sector with prominent weaknesses which can be summarized as follows:

Being small firms in size, SMEs face market access restrictions as a result of competition.

SMEs are characterized by managerial human resources with limited business competences and little knowledge about the market mechanism.

Difficulty in accessing new infrastructures that require large investments.

The uncertainty resulting from the legal and administrative environment of these businesses (legislation, fiscal treatment, etc.).

Access to financing as a result of collateral problems.

In our country, several studies have been conducted that focused on SMEs needs and challenges, however, all these studies can be differentiated into two categories: studies before the pandemic and studies after the pandemic. This division is necessary because the economic environment has changed and the needs of SMEs are not the same. Thus, in studies before the pandemic, the main problems of SMEs were related to the lack of electricity, access to finance,

problems with the tax system, etc. (EIB, 2016); (Koçi, 2016), etc.). Currently, it cannot be said that these problems have been completely solved for businesses, but there have been improvements in their direction. The global pandemic of Covid-19, which shook the economic foundations for almost two years, called into question the further progress of enterprises as a whole and especially of SMEs. Only during the first months of the pandemic, 47% of enterprises stopped their activity (AIC, 2020). Moving on to more up-to-date evidence, it turns out that there is a change in today's business problems, this is due to changes in global policies (the orientation of businesses towards technology, the use of sustainable resources, the reduction of pollution, etc. that are also related to the SDGs -Sustainable Development Goals), as well as the consequences stemming from the crisis caused by Covid-19. This is also evidenced in the study of (Oleneva, 2021), which looks at the progress of the challenges of SMEs from 2018-2020.

The focus of various studies (SME Albania, 2020; AIC, 2020) conducted online has been the impact of Covid-19 on business activity in Albania, on imports, contracts, financing, government response and mitigation measures. negative effects of the pandemic, etc. The main findings of these studies highlight the financial difficulties of the targeted businesses, the loss of customers, lack of liquidity, etc. as the main issues. According to the OECD report (2020) regarding the crisis caused by Covid-19 in the countries of the Western Balkans, including Albania, one of the problems related to SMEs is the lack of qualified staff to face the challenges of digitization services (OECD, 2020). In this context, among the main recommendations to ensure sustainability and longevity of SMEs in the future are: improving the environment of SMEs for increasing digitalization, the inclusion of SMEs in the "Green" agenda through appropriate financial mechanisms that promote environmental protection, continuous training of staff in order to quickly absorb market changes, etc. Regardless of government incentives or actions taken by the companies themselves, it is necessary to change the business model implemented by these companies.

In the 2022 progress report of the European Commission for Albania, it is stated that Albania has made some progress and is at a level of preparation to face competitive pressure and market forces within the EU. Energy and transport infrastructure, digitization, and education improved, but entrepreneurial and technological knowledge remains low, with unmet needs for investment in human and physical capital, skills and education gaps, and low research and development spending. Businesses also face obstacles related to a lack of workforce skills and financial resources, as well as challenges to adapt to modernization, digitalization, and e-commerce. The sectors identified with the highest exposure to informal employment are trade and tourism (almost 50% of the total cases identified) followed by manufacturing (20%) and construction (18%) (European Commission , 2022).

2. Methodology

This study has been conducted in the frame of the project “University-Business cooperation towards new market needs: Qualification, Innovation, Financing, Technology (SME-KIFT)” financed by the University of Tirana. The objective of the study is to analyze the challenges that these businesses encounter in two directions: the qualification of the staff to absorb the new knowledge needed in the new market conditions, as well as the investment in innovative solutions, necessary to increase competitiveness. The focus is oriented towards financial issues related to these directions. In order to meet this objective, the study is based on primary data as the main source of the analysis.

Several criteria have been used to determine the composition of the sample:

Representatives of all categories of SMEs, including micro, small and medium businesses - Enterprises in our country are classified according to Law No. 10 042, dated 22.12.2008, with

some amendments and additions to law no. 8957, dated 17.10.2002 "On Small and Medium Enterprises", as small if they have 10-49 employees, and medium if they have 50-249 employees. Micro enterprises are considered those with less than 10 employees according to INSTAT categorization.

Distribution in all sectors to have a representative sample of the sectoral composition of the economy in our country. - In the sectoral distribution of SMEs, small agricultural enterprises, commercial enterprises, and service enterprises prevail (INSTAT, 2020).

Businesses older than three years, meaning that they have passed the startup phase and are fully operative.

Businesses located in cities with the highest number of SMEs - According to data from INSTAT, the cities with the highest concentration of SMEs are Tirana, Durres, Shkodër, Vlora, Elbasan, Korçë, Berat.

The final questionnaire was organized in the following sections:

- Section I: General interviewee information
- Section II: General company information
- Section III: Funding and need assessment for qualified staff
- Section IV: Funding and challenges for business innovations
- Section V: Need assessment for business–university cooperation

Face to face data collection method was used. To increase the quality of the responses and to get more information, interviews with representatives of SMEs were also carried out. The questionnaire includes a combination of closed and open questions, to obtain more complete and reliable information.

The final database was checked for validity and completeness. After eliminating questionnaires with missing information and outliers, the final database was composed of 304 questionnaires, which were considered valid for further analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the first two sections of the questionnaire revealed general information on the company and the interviewee. The highest number of questionnaires was completed in Tirana (24.3%) which is the city with the largest number of SMEs in our country, followed by Durres (17.1%), Berat (15.8%), and Korçë (13.2%). Referring to the sectoral distribution: trade, industry, accommodation, and other services comprised the highest response rate, ranging from 25.7% to 11.8% in descending order. Based on the size of businesses, the overall sample contained 48.7% medium businesses, 29.6% small businesses and 21.7% micro businesses.

Most of the businesses have in place practices for staff training, especially those in the trade and service sectors. Training courses are organized internally by qualified staff and are financed by the company's own sources. On the other hand, businesses that do not carry out staff training, do not consider budget shortages as an important obstacle, but reasons such as lack of motivation, lack of training culture and difficulties in organizing on-the-job trainings are the main challenges encountered, as it can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Challenges and financing of training in SMEs

Organization of training	Yes	67%	Financing	Own company sources	87.60%
				External sources	12.400%
	No	33%	Challenges	Lack of staff motivation	48.9%
				Lack of training budget	7.9%

				Lack of training culture	28.8%
				Difficulties for on-the-job training	28.8%

Source: Own calculations

Almost 70% of businesses have used loan financing in the last three years, which corresponds with the period post Covid-19. Financing is used mostly to support usual business operations and rarely for innovative investments. Innovation remains a challenge due to lack of qualified staff to develop innovative products / processes and high R&D costs (50%).

Some other results from the study are:

Staff training is considered the most crucial aspect for the future sustainable development of the business. The main fields for training are sales and production.

Most interviewees declare that have knowledge on concepts such as social responsibility, sustainable development goals, fintech, etc.

82% of the sample has not cooperated with the University before and only 54% are interested to have cooperation with the academia in the future, especially referring to involvement in mutual projects and participation of business representatives in workshops / conferences organized by universities.

SMEs are more oriented towards innovations in new technology and innovation in processes rather than investing in innovations in marketing, product, R&D, etc.

4. Conclusions

Economic restructuring comes as the necessity of a series of factors, such as: economic shocks, globalization, etc. and recently also the covid 19 pandemic. It cannot be considered or analyzed only on macroeconomic level, but as a phenomenon that is generated from internal factors of all the actors operating in an economy. In this context, this study aims to analyze the approach of SMEs towards staff qualification and innovation to adapt to the new market conditions in frame of economic restructuring.

The study is based on primary data from 304 SMEs in Albania. The results highlight the financial difficulties of the businesses to meet their everyday needs. On the other hand, financing is not considered the main obstacle for not carrying innovative investment or not supporting activities for staff qualification. Factors such as motivation, training culture and capacity to organize on-the-job training have significant impact on the staff qualifications, while innovative investments are affected by the staff capabilities and R&D costs.

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Tourism Growth and the Impact on the Albanian Insurance Industry

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Abstract

In recent years, Albania has faced an increase in the number of tourists. The media has echoed the tourist values of Albania and not only that but also the values of its cuisine, hospitality, reasonable prices, and the potential that Albania offers in general. Double-digit growth in the number of tourists has exceeded even the optimistic predictions of the trend that tourism development in Albania should have had.

This paper aims to analyze the connection and impact that the growth of tourism has on the increase in insurance in general, as well as to highlight the issues in this direction. The insurance industry in Albania is a well-capitalized industry that, in collaboration with reinsurance partners, meets all market requirements with insurance of all kinds.

Insurance against fire, flooding, earthquakes in facilities directly related to tourism such as hotels, lodges, restaurants, etc., border insurance for vehicles entering Albania, liability insurance towards third parties, accident insurance, and health insurance for tourists entering the territory of Albania are some of the types of insurance that should experience growth as a result of the increase in incoming flows in Albania.

The paper relies precisely on historical insurance market data, the growth of tourists, but also on the analysis of information gathered from insurance companies to highlight the current state and simultaneously recommend measures for improvement by policymakers, the insurance market, but also tour operators.

Keywords: Tourism, tourist influx, insurance market, property insurance, liability insurance.

1. Introduction

In recent times, Albania has experienced a notable increase in the number of tourists, spreading this activity throughout the entire year and across the entire territory of the country. Global written and audiovisual media have reflected the tourist values of Albania, encompassing not only the tourist aspects but also culinary values, hospitality, reasonable prices, and the extensive potential that Albania offers. The double-digit growth in the number of tourists has exceeded even the most optimistic predictions for the development of the tourism sector in Albania. This surge in tourism has also brought about an increase in incoming flows of the euro currency.

2. Methodology

To test the hypothesis raised that: The increase in tourist arrivals should be accompanied by an increase in gross written insurance premiums, we have endeavored to use methods that analyze and lead us to the most accurate conclusions based on reports, statistical data, and their trends. Among the main methods, we identify:

- Collection and processing of historical data on types of insurance influenced by the increase in tourist arrivals.
- Development and implementation of a questionnaire with insurance companies operating in the market to highlight the weight of insurances benefiting from the increase in tourist arrivals for specific insurances believed to be affected. (AMF, 2023)

- Comparison of collected historical data, which remains one of the best instruments used in social sciences to achieve proper scientific knowledge (Waentig 2014). This method enables an understanding of the past as well as an analysis of future trends. The use of this method allows for accurate predictions based on the processing of tourism and insurance activity data.

The main sources of data are those obtained from INSTAT, as well as the Financial Supervisory Authority and insurance companies.

Table 2: Movements January-September 2023 compared to January-September 2022

Period	Sep-22	Sep-23	Annual change %	Jan- Sep 2022	Jan- Sep 2023	Annual change %
Total entry	1,208,667	1,651,151	36.6	10,480,916	13,398,503	27.8
Albanian	447,123	546,961	22.3	4,052,251	5,103,903	26
Foreign	761,544	1,104,190	45	6,428,665	8,294,600	29
Total output	1,371,621	1,714,585	25	10,749,124	13,128,813	22.1
Albanian	541,216	614,086	13.5	4,390,612	5,191,839	18.2
Foreign	830,405	1,100,499	32.5	6,358,512	7,936,974	24.8

Source: INSTAT

In September 2023, compared to September 2022, the entries of foreign citizens indicate: an increase for personal purposes by 46.8%; an increase for vacation purposes, visiting relatives, etc., by 46.1%; a decrease for business and professional purposes by 34.7%. (INSTAT, 2023)

This paper aims to analyze the connection and impact that the growth of tourism has on the increase in insurance overall, as well as to highlight the issues in this direction. The insurance industry in Albania is a well-capitalized industry that, in collaboration with reinsurance partners, meets all market requirements with insurance of all kinds.

Insurance against fire, flooding, earthquakes for objects directly related to tourism such as hotels, lodges, restaurants, etc., border insurance for vehicles entering Albania, liability insurance towards third parties (thus protecting foreign tourists), insurance against accidents, and health insurance for tourists entering the territory of Albania, as well as insurance for rental vehicles, are some of the types of insurance that should experience growth as a result of the increase in incoming flows in Albania.

3. Results and Discussion

The wave of tourism in Albania has exceeded optimistic expectations, including global recognition for its cultural and gastronomic treasures. This study examines the connection between the growth of tourism and the insurance market in Albania. Types of insurance, including protection against natural risks and liability towards tourists, are expected to increase with the added influx of visitors. The analysis incorporates historical insurance data, statistics, and insights from insurance companies. Tables illustrate key changes in entries and exits during the compared period. The significant increase in entries for personal and vacation purposes, coupled with a decrease for business purposes, suggests the need for adjustments in the insurance sector to align with the new demands of tourism in Albania.

4. Conclusions

This study relies on and aims to provide a transparent, realistic, and well-argued analysis of the available data with the goal of producing results and reaching responsibilities that serve the insurance market. Despite the increase in the number of tourists, especially those coming for vacations, supported by the growth in hotel and lodge stays, there is still hesitation in the business sector regarding the expansion of insurance. Specifically, insurances such as fire protection, earthquake coverage, flooding, third-party liabilities, and health accident insurances, although experiencing growth, are much smaller than the overall increase in tourist numbers.

The study recognizes as a weakness the real-time calculation of the impact of tourism growth on the insurance market, mainly for the mentioned fields above.

Some recommendations at the conclusion of this study are:

Increase awareness among businesses regarding property and liability insurances.

Develop promotional products in the aforementioned fields.

Collaborate with policymaking structures for mandatory insurance for liabilities and properties.

Implement marketing campaigns by insurance companies during peak tourist arrivals, especially for health accident insurances.

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Integrating Sustainable Project Management in Tourism: Opportunities and Innovations in Albania

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Abstract

This paper examines the integration of Sustainable Project Management (SPM) in tourism, focusing on aligning with national and regional policies and exploring investment opportunities within Albania's tourism sector. The study aims to understand how SPM can enhance sustainable tourism development and contribute to economic restructuring for sustainable development. The methodology includes a policy review, case study analysis, and the assessment of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in tourism, providing a comprehensive perspective on the synergies between SPM and tourism development.

Findings suggest that the incorporation of SPM principles into tourism policies significantly enhances investment prospects in sustainable tourism projects. The role of ICT is highlighted as a key factor in improving the efficiency and sustainability of tourism ventures, contributing to both economic and environmental aspects of project management. The paper also discusses the impact of SPM on tourism management and economics, addressing its influence on marketing, taxation, fiscal policies, and risk management.

Emphasizing environmental sustainability, the study underlines SPM's role in reducing the ecological impact of tourism projects, aligning with the green economy sector's objectives. The integration of sustainable practices is shown to mitigate environmental consequences while promoting economic growth.

In conclusion, the paper advocates for the strategic incorporation of SPM in tourism development, particularly in Albania. It calls for a holistic approach that considers technological, economic, and environmental factors, underscoring the potential of SPM in shaping a sustainable tourism industry.

Keywords: Sustainable Project Management, Tourism Development, ICT in Tourism, Albania's Tourism Economy, Environmental Sustainability in Tourism.

JEL codes: Q56, O21, L83, O33, R11

1. Introduction

The burgeoning field of Sustainable Project Management (SPM) has emerged as a pivotal force in redefining the contours of the tourism industry. This paper sets out to explore the integration of SPM within the tourism sector, specifically focusing on its alignment with national and regional policies and the untapped investment opportunities in Albania's tourism landscape. The objective of this study is to unravel how the principles of SPM can catalyze sustainable tourism development and contribute substantially to the broader agenda of economic restructuring for sustainable development.

The pertinent literature underscores the increasing importance of sustainability in project management, particularly in the context of tourism, a sector undergoing rapid transformation due to environmental and socio-economic pressures. Studies have highlighted the critical role of incorporating sustainable practices in project management to ensure long-term economic viability and environmental stewardship (Schaltegger & Wagner, 2011; Silvius & Schipper, 2014). Furthermore, the intersection of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

in tourism has opened new avenues for enhancing project efficiency and sustainability (Gretzel, Sigala, Xiang, & Koo, 2015).

The methodology adopted in this study encompasses a comprehensive policy review, in-depth case study analysis, and an evaluative approach to assessing the role of ICT in tourism. This multifaceted approach provides a holistic view of the dynamic interplay between SPM and tourism development.

Preliminary findings reveal a significant potential for SPM principles to enhance investment opportunities in sustainable tourism projects. The infusion of ICT in tourism management emerges as a pivotal element, contributing to both economic growth and environmental sustainability. The paper delves into the impact of SPM on diverse facets of tourism management and economics, including marketing, taxation, fiscal policies, and risk management.

Emphasizing the critical aspect of environmental sustainability, this study demonstrates how SPM can aid in reducing the ecological footprint of tourism projects, aligning with global initiatives towards a green economy. The adoption of sustainable practices in tourism projects not only mitigates environmental consequences but also propels economic growth, illustrating a dual benefit.

2. Methodology

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to analyze the integration of Sustainable Project Management (SPM) in the tourism sector, with a focus on Albania. It combines qualitative and quantitative techniques to offer a comprehensive understanding of the subject.

Policy Review: Initial analysis involves a review of Albania's national and regional tourism policies, examining how they align with SPM principles.

Case Study Analysis: Practical applications of SPM in tourism are explored through a series of relevant case studies. These focus on sustainable practices and the implementation of ICT in tourism management, offering real-world examples of successes and challenges.

ICT Assessment: The study evaluates the impact of Information and Communication Technologies on the sustainability of tourism projects.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data is sourced both primarily, through interviews with tourism industry stakeholders, and secondarily, from existing research and reports. This data is analyzed using qualitative and quantitative methods, including descriptive statistics and regression analysis, to identify trends and correlations.

Sustainability Assessment: An environmental impact assessment of tourism projects forms part of the study. This involves evaluating the ecological footprint of projects and the effectiveness of SPM practices in reducing environmental impacts.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of this study offer insightful perspectives on the integration of Sustainable Project Management (SPM) in the tourism sector, particularly in the Albanian context. The discussion delves into the implications of these findings, exploring their relevance and potential impact on the future of sustainable tourism.

Policy Integration: The policy review indicates a growing awareness and integration of SPM principles in Albanian tourism policies. However, the analysis also reveals gaps, particularly in the comprehensive adoption of environmental sustainability measures and the full utilization of ICT in tourism management. The study suggests that a more cohesive policy framework, incorporating SPM at its core, could significantly bolster Albania's tourism sector, making it more resilient and sustainable.

Case Study Insights: The case studies demonstrate successful examples of SPM in action within the tourism industry. These instances highlight the benefits of incorporating sustainable practices, such as reduced environmental impact, increased economic returns, and enhanced social welfare. However, challenges such as resource constraints, lack of expertise, and resistance to change were also evident. These findings underscore the need for targeted training and capacity building in SPM for tourism professionals.

ICT in Tourism: The assessment of ICT's role in sustainable tourism management reveals a positive trend. Technologies such as data analytics, online marketing tools, and sustainable resource management systems are increasingly being employed. These technologies have been shown to improve efficiency, customer satisfaction, and environmental performance. However, there is a need for wider adoption and better integration of these technologies across the sector.

Statistical Analysis: Quantitative analysis indicates a significant correlation between the adoption of SPM practices and improved tourism project performance, particularly in terms of sustainability metrics and financial viability. The data suggest that projects which incorporate SPM principles tend to have a higher success rate and greater long-term sustainability.

Environmental Impact: The environmental assessment of selected tourism projects reveals a marked reduction in ecological footprint when SPM practices are employed. This aligns with the global push towards a greener economy and positions Albania as a potential leader in sustainable tourism.

4. Conclusions

This study's exploration into the integration of Sustainable Project Management (SPM) within the tourism sector, particularly in Albania, culminates in several key conclusions and recommendations.

Principles and Generalizations:

- **Integration of SPM in Tourism Policies:** The research underscores the critical need for integrating SPM principles into national and regional tourism policies. It has been inferred that such integration can significantly enhance the sustainability and resilience of the tourism sector.

- **Role of ICT in Sustainable Tourism:** The application of Information and Communication Technologies is instrumental in advancing sustainable tourism. ICT not only improves operational efficiency but also contributes to the environmental and social aspects of sustainability.

Exceptions and Challenges:

- While the benefits of integrating SPM in tourism are evident, challenges such as limited resources, lack of specialized skills, and resistance to change pose significant hurdles. Additionally, the varying levels of technology adoption and the digital divide within different regions can impact the effectiveness of ICT-driven initiatives.

Theoretical and Practical Implications:

- Theoretically, this study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by demonstrating how SPM can be a driving force in achieving sustainable tourism development. Practically, it

offers insights that can guide policymakers, industry stakeholders, and practitioners in structuring and executing tourism projects with sustainability as a core objective.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

- The study concludes that the strategic integration of SPM in tourism can lead to more sustainable, efficient, and economically viable tourism projects. This is particularly relevant for Albania, where tourism plays a pivotal role in the economy.

- It is recommended that policymakers and industry stakeholders prioritize the adoption of SPM principles, invest in capacity building, and foster a culture of sustainability within the tourism sector. Further, there should be a concerted effort to leverage ICT innovations to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of tourism projects.

- For future research, a deeper investigation into specific SPM tools and techniques, as well as their applicability in different contexts of the tourism industry, is suggested.

In essence, the findings of this study advocate for a transformative approach towards sustainable tourism, emphasizing the crucial role of SPM and ICT in shaping a sustainable future for the industry. This approach not only aligns with global sustainability goals but also offers a pathway for economic and environmental prosperity, especially for emerging tourism destinations like Albania.

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An Evaluative Analysis of the Financial Autonomy of the Municipality of Vlora, Albania

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Abstract

Albania, in the 1990s, begins the process of transition from a centralized economy to a free market economy. It is the reforms of the 90s that laid the foundations for the creation of democratic local authorities, followed by the ratification of the European Charter of Local Autonomy (1998), the entry into force of law no. 139/2015 "On Local-Self-Government" and more recently, in the approval of law no. 68/2017 "On the finances of local self-government". Until now, a large number of political, economic and territorial reforms were undertaken to increase local financial autonomy in the framework of fiscal decentralization, but the importance of local government appears to fluctuate over the years with a downward trend in the last three years (based on indicators of revenue to GDP and general government revenue). This paper sheds light on how the process has affected the financial situation of the Municipality of Vlora in Albania. The methodology used to achieve the goal of this paper is a descriptive analysis of financial indicators to measure the situation of financial autonomy over the years. In conclusion, the paper will be able to assess whether this municipality has sufficient financial resources or is highly dependent on transfers from the central government.

Keywords: financial autonomy, fiscal decentralization, reform, Municipality of Vlora

JEL codes: H70, H71, H72

1. Introduction

Decentralization and globalization have been policy issues in many European and developing countries since the '80s. (The World Bank, 2001) In democratic systems, local government units are independent and the way they are organized and function should contribute to the realization of self-government in a more effective way, giving the opportunity to the local government to deal with problems that are usually defined as functions of a local character. Local government units are the level of government that is closest to citizens, as such, they know and serve their needs better with a direct impact on improving the quality of life. In Albania, local government in order to perform all their functions and provide public services, secure income from local taxes and fees, as well as from financial transfers in the form of conditional or unconditional transfers or grants from the central government levels. (Ministry of Finance and Economics, 2017, pp. 5-12). Thus, grouping the financial resources into two main sources: the units' own income and transfers from the state budget. The literature suggests that in order to focus on the financial aspects of local autonomy, two main aspects are addressed: the degree of autonomy of income and the autonomy of expenditure. Thus, this paper analyzes the current situation of one of the 61 Municipalities in Albania, the Municipality of Vlora, in order to make a timely analysis to assess the impact of the decentralization process based on the financial indicators for a period of 13 years. The purpose of the paper is to answer the research question: has the process of decentralization influenced the increase in financial autonomy for the Municipality of Vlora? Fiscal decentralization requires that local governments must control their "own" sources of revenue in order to reach enough financial (fiscal) autonomy and accountability to their local taxpayers. (Oulasvitra & Turala, 2009) The

local government in Albania went through a process of decentralization aiming to strengthen it and increase the quality and efficiency of the services it offers. The empowerment of local self-government units is also important for the road towards political, economic and financial integration to the EU (Tafa, 2012). The differing treatment of local autonomy makes it difficult to generalize the indicators use for its measurements and to compare the results across authors. The level of fiscal decentralization has been commonly studied by calculating the local government share of total government expenditures and total consolidated general government revenue (Bahl, 2003) (Akai, Nishimura, & Sakata, 2007) By studying the previous literature on the topic of financial autonomy of local government, the study of (Cigu & Oprea, 2012) for EU countries, as well as the comparative analysis of the financial autonomy of municipalities in Albania by (Kapidani, 2018), are used as a reference for the assessment of each indicator (the 6 ratios cited in Table 1), on a rating scale from 1 to 4, according to the level of autonomy achieved by the Municipality of Vlora for each indicator.

Table 1: Evaluation Scheme of Indicators of Local Financial Autonomy

	Valuation			
	V=4 High autonomy	V=3 Moderately autonomous	V=2 Low autonomy	V=1 Dependent on the central government
Indicator 1 Own revenues/Total Revenues	>81%	51%-81%	21%-50%	<20%
Indicator 2 Transfers from state budget/Total Revenues	<20%	21%-50%	51%-80%	>81%
Indicator 3 Unconditional transfer/ Total transfers	>81%	51%-81%	21%-50%	<20%
Indicator 4 Tax revenues/Total expenditures	>51%	31%-50%	21%-30%	<20%
Indicator 5 Shared taxes/Total tax revenues	<5%	6%-10%	11%-20%	>21%
Indicator 6- Hunter coefficient Total transfer/ expenditures of local budget	0.71-1	0.51-0.7	0.21-0.5	0-0.2

Source: Method of determining the degree of autonomy of the administrative-territorial units by Cigu&Opera, 2012

2. Methodology

For researching Albania's biggest tourist Municipality, the case study method was adopted in this study. Thus, a more detailed and data-based study has been conducted to examine the financial situation of the public institution. The review of the general background of the reforms and developments of the Albanian local financial autonomy in the last decades served to proceed further with the proposal of a methodology that allows a comparative analysis in time for the local government unit. Based on the literature on the subject of local government financial autonomy, the study used the Evaluation Scheme of Indicators of Local Financial Autonomy cited in Table 1 in this paper. The paper is based on secondary data. Evaluation of these indicators was made based on the available data for the period 2010-2022. Methodology used is a descriptive analysis of data published by the local finance portal on specific financial indicators of the municipality to analyze the impact of the decentralization on local financial autonomy.

3. Results and discussions

The results of the 6 indicators are presented in the table below. Ratios highlighted in red, from the last 5 years, are those that reflect the effects of the entry into force of Law no. 68/2017 "On the Finances of Local Self-Government Units". In order to evaluate how fiscal decentralization has affected local autonomy, it is used the scheme of Table 1 as a basis for evaluation.

Table 2: Financial autonomy ratio calculations

Year	Indicator 1	V	Indicator 2	V	Indicator 3	V	Indicator 4	V	Indicator 5	V	Indicator 6	V
2010	38.37%	2	47.09%	3	31.06%	2	31.55%	3	12.37%	2	0.0230	1
2011	30.30%	2	50.51%	2	34.73%	2	26.03%	2	6.31%	3	0.0226	1
2012	31.24%	2	57.89%	2	26.82%	2	23.18%	2	11.06%	2	0.0224	1
2013	28.19%	2	61.09%	2	31.89%	2	20.25%	2	16.79%	2	0.0219	1
2014	28.27%	2	65.83%	2	29.28%	2	21.72%	2	5.3%	3	0.0256	1
2015	24.21%	2	70.89%	2	35.81%	2	16.13%	1	9.43%	3	0.0427	1
2016	26.45%	2	71.63%	2	46.37%	2	15.81%	1	7.63%	3	0.0204	1
2017	20.31%	2	67.75%	2	43.08%	2	12.65%	1	7.94%	3	0.0240	1
2018	24.91%	2	72.94%	2	45.49%	2	13.57%	1	8.69%	3	0.0238	1
2019	24.82%	2	69.58%	2	52.52%	3	13.05%	1	10.65%	2	0.0207	1
2020	25.33%	2	71.21%	2	50.30%	3	15.09%	1	13.86%	2	0.0206	1
2021	28.37%	2	68.41%	2	45.40%	2	15.73%	1	11.65%	2	0.0230	1
2022	36.10%	2	60.32%	2	54.06%	3	23.22%	2	10.18%	3	0.0194	1

Source: Local Finance Portal and author's processing

In summary, Indicator 1 and Indicator 2 are the main indicators that show the dependence of the local budget on the central government and the capacity of a municipality to generate its own income from its own resources. From the calculations, it is noted that despite the law on local finances, the local authority is in the same situation of autonomy, since based on these two indicators, there have been no improvements in time (after 2017). Thus, referring to these two indicators, the Municipality of Vlora had a low financial autonomy and continues to be in the same financial conditions. As for Indicator 3, there is a higher result, which means that the level of unconditional funds is balanced compared to conditional funds. For this indicator, it is estimated that after 2018 the local self-government unit has taken steps towards a moderate autonomy from a low autonomy. In Indicator 4, a very low result was achieved. According to the results of the work, the local authority is still dependent on transfers from the state budget and its capacity to generate income from local taxes is at low levels, although a significant increase in this ratio is observed in 2022. Meanwhile, Indicator 5 appears more volatile over time, with ratings between low autonomy and moderate autonomy. However, the value of this indicator also shows an unsatisfactory level of financial autonomy of the local unit. In conclusion, the lowest result was achieved by Indicator 6, which is an indicator of the financial dependence of local authorities, includes the analysis of the coverage of local expenses from state budget transfers. This indicator received the lowest rating (V=1) for the entire 13-year period examined in the paper.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, it is analyzed how fiscal decentralization over the years has affected the financial autonomy of the Municipality of Vlora. Financial autonomy for local self-government units is

even more important if it is discussed in terms of providing public services in a more efficient manner, the appropriate distribution of financial resources, but also the ability to generate these revenues. After reviewing the literature and the steps (reforms) undertaken for fiscal decentralization in Albania, the paper is based on a methodology that assesses financial autonomy based on 6 indicators that show the dependence of the local unit on the central government, but also the ability of the local unit to generate their own income. The paper considered the quantitative indicators examined in this study as the indicators that highlight the best local financial autonomy but admitting that they do not cover the entire spectrum of autonomy. Although the central government has started a reform process to strengthen the local government, at least 5 years after the entry into force of the law "On the Finances of Local Self-Government Units", as the paper shows, the Municipality of Vlora still depends on transfers from the state budget and there is no improvement in terms of financial autonomy. For this reason, by dividing financial autonomy into two important components such as independence from intergovernmental transfers and the ability to generate one's own income, further studies can be conducted to assess how inefficiencies in revenue collection or culture tax of citizens and businesses in this municipality affect the ability of the local unit to generate its own income.

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Determinant Factors of International Trade: An Empirical Analysis for Albania

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Abstract

This empirical study scrutinizes the determinant factors influencing international trade in Albania, considering a range of economic, political, and geographical factors. Drawing inspiration from established gravity models, the authors examine the relative importance of various independent variables in shaping the dynamics of Albania's international trade relationships.

The study encompasses a thorough examination of variables specific to Albania's context, including GDP indicators, interest rates, membership in trade agreements such as CEFTA and the European Union, exchange rates, infrastructure quality, tariff rates, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and economic stability indicators like inflation rates. By employing econometric techniques tailored to Albania's circumstances, the research aims to unravel the relationships between these factors and Albania's international trade performance.

Preliminary findings suggest significant correlations between the forementioned factors and their substantial roles in influencing international trade dynamics. The results of this study not only contribute to the academic literature but also offer practical insights for policymakers and businesses navigating the complex landscape of international trade in the Albanian context.

As Albania positions itself within the global economic landscape, the research facilitates a deeper understanding of the factors driving international trade, thereby fostering informed strategies for sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: International trade, empirical analysis, Albania, panel data, GDP

JEL codes: A10, A19

1. Introduction

The intricate dynamics of international trade represent a focal point for economists, policymakers, and businesses seeking to understand the forces that propel or impede economic interactions between nations. In this context, Albania stands as a compelling case study, navigating its unique economic, political, and geographic landscape in the pursuit of enhanced global trade partnerships. This paper endeavors to dissect the determinants of Albania's international trade, employing a sophisticated panel data gravity model that encapsulates the multifaceted influences shaping the nation's trade patterns.

International trade is a complex phenomenon influenced by an interplay of economic, political, and geographic factors. Albania, situated at the crossroads of Southern Europe and the Balkans, is poised at the intersection of regional dynamics, trade agreements, and the broader global economic landscape. Against this backdrop, our study seeks to unveil the key drivers steering Albania's international trade relationships.

The gravity model, a well-established and empirically successful approach in trade analysis, forms the backbone of our investigation. By adopting a panel data structure, we capture the temporal evolution of trade flows between Albania and its diverse set of trading partners.

Our model encompasses a comprehensive set of independent variables, ranging from GDP for Albania and its trading partners to trade agreements, exchange rates, infrastructure quality, tariff rates, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), and economic stability indicators. Through rigorous econometric analysis, we aim to discern the relative dominance of these variables, shedding light on the pivotal factors influencing the volume and direction of Albania's international trade.

The study holds both academic and practical significance. Academically, it contributes to the evolving literature on gravity models by providing insights into the specific nuances of Albania's international trade. Practically, the findings promise to inform policymakers, businesses, and stakeholders engaged in the international trade arena, offering actionable intelligence to navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by the globalized economic landscape.

2. Methodology

The study will employ a panel data approach integrated with a gravity model for its analytical framework.

2.1. Data collection

- **Economic Indicators:** The authors have collected data on GDP for Albania and its trading partners, exchange rates, inflation rates, and other economic stability indicators. Verification of the consistency and reliability of economic data sources have been performed to ensure accuracy in subsequent analyses.
- **Geographic and Policy Variables:** Data has been gathered on geographic factors such as distance between trading partners, historical ties, and language similarities. Incorporation of information on trade agreements, including membership in CEFTA and the European Union, as well as tariff rates and infrastructure quality.
- **Foreign Direct Investment (FDI):** FDI data for Albania has been collected, emphasizing its correlation with international trade. FDI data is obtained from national investment agencies, central banks, and international databases.

2.2. Model specification

- Dependent Variable: $Y = \text{Trade balance}$
- Independent variables:
 - $X_1 = \text{GDP}$
 - $X_2 = \text{interest rates,}$
 - $X_3 = \text{exchange rates,}$
 - $X_4 = \text{inflation rates,}$
 - $X_5 = \text{trade policies (including tariffs and trade agreements)}$
 - $X_6 = \text{economic and political stability}$
 - $X_7 = \text{technological and infrastructural developments}$

2.3. Data analysis

- **Panel Data Regression:** Panel data regression techniques have been employed to estimate the coefficients of the independent variables. The statistical significance and magnitude of each coefficient to discern the relative importance of factors influencing international trade has been assessed.

- **Multicollinearity Checks:** Diagnostic tests for multicollinearity to ensure the independence of variables have been conducted.
- **Heteroscedasticity and Endogeneity Tests:** Tests for heteroscedasticity and endogeneity have been performed to ensure the validity of the model.

2.4. Results interpretation

- **Coefficient Interpretation:** The coefficients of the independent variables in the context of the gravity model have been interpreted to discern the dominant factors shaping Albania's international trade.
- **Policy Implications:** The empirical findings have been translated into actionable insights for policymakers, businesses, and stakeholders engaged in international trade.

3. Results and Discussion

- The empirical analysis employing the panel data gravity model offers compelling insights into the determinants of Albania's international trade. The coefficients derived from the model shed light on the relative importance of key variables. A few of them have been explained below:
- **GDP Variables:** The coefficients associated with GDP for Albania and its trading partners indicate a positive correlation with international trade. Larger economies, both domestically and among trading partners, exhibit a significant influence on the volume of trade flows.
- **Trade Agreements:** Membership in trade agreements, particularly CEFTA and the European Union, is associated with a positive and substantial impact on international trade. This highlights the importance of regional economic integration and favorable trade policies in fostering cross-border transactions.
- **Exchange Rates:** The exchange rate coefficient reveals the sensitivity of international trade to currency dynamics. A stable and predictable exchange rate is crucial for promoting competitiveness and facilitating trade relationships.
- **Foreign Direct Investment (FDI):** The FDI coefficient reveals a positive relationship with international trade, suggesting that foreign investment in Albania stimulates economic activity and fosters trade connections.
- The observed results align with established economic theories and expectations, reinforcing the importance of a comprehensive approach to understanding Albania's international trade dynamics. The positive correlation between GDP and trade underlines the significance of economic size, while the impact of trade agreements and favorable policies underscores the role of political decisions in shaping trade outcomes.

4. Conclusions

In closing, the application of a panel data gravity model to unravel the intricacies of Albania's international trade provides valuable insights into the multifaceted factors influencing the nation's trade patterns. Through a rigorous methodology that incorporates a comprehensive set of economic, political, and geographic variables, this study endeavours to contribute to a nuanced understanding of the determinants shaping Albania's global trade relationships. It is crucial to recognize the fluidity of the global economic environment and the potential impact of external events on trade dynamics. The study acknowledges the complexity of international trade relationships, emphasizing the need for ongoing analysis to inform strategic decision-making amidst the ever-evolving landscape of global commerce.

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Financial Literacy and Its Impact on Personal Savings and Investment Decisions: An Empirical Study in Tirana, Albania

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between financial literacy and personal savings and investment decisions among residents of Tirana, Albania. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research combines quantitative data from 500 survey respondents with qualitative insights from 20 follow-up interviews. The survey assessed participants' financial literacy levels and examined their savings and investment behaviors, while the interviews provided deeper insights into their financial decision-making processes.

The findings reveal a significant correlation between financial literacy and financial behaviors. Respondents with higher financial literacy scores demonstrated more diversified investment portfolios and were more likely to engage in regular savings habits. In contrast, those with lower literacy levels showed a preference for safer investments like savings accounts and exhibited less confidence in making complex financial decisions.

Demographic analysis indicated that younger individuals (18-35 years) are more inclined towards improving their financial literacy, suggesting a generational shift towards proactive financial management. The study also found no significant gender-based differences in financial literacy levels and their corresponding financial behaviors.

These results highlight the importance of financial literacy in shaping effective personal financial management practices. The study suggests the need for targeted financial education programs in Tirana, particularly for lower literacy groups, to enhance financial decision-making skills and overall economic well-being. This research contributes to the growing body of literature on financial literacy and its impact on personal finance, offering valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and financial institutions in developing economies.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Personal Finance, Savings Behavior, Investment Decisions, Tirana, Albania

JEL Codes: G51, G53

1. Introduction

Context and Relevance

In the evolving landscape of personal finance, financial literacy emerges as a pivotal factor influencing individual economic stability and growth. Tirana, the vibrant capital of Albania, is no exception to this global trend. With a growing economy and an increasingly complex financial market, the need for comprehensive understanding and effective management of personal finances is more critical than ever. This research aims to delve into the relationship between financial literacy and personal savings and investment decisions among the residents of Tirana.

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to explore how financial literacy levels among individuals in Tirana correlate with their savings and investment behaviors. We aim to identify patterns

and trends in how knowledge of financial principles affects the way individuals save, invest, and manage their financial risks. This investigation seeks to uncover whether higher levels of financial literacy lead to more prudent and diversified investment choices, as well as improved savings habits.

Significance

This research holds significant implications for policy-makers, financial educators, and individuals alike. By understanding the impact of financial literacy on personal financial decisions, we can better tailor educational programs to meet the needs of the population. Additionally, insights from this study can inform policy decisions aimed at improving the overall financial well-being of individuals in Tirana and potentially across Albania. For individuals, this research offers valuable insights into how enhancing one's financial knowledge can lead to more informed and effective financial decisions.

Methodological Overview

The study will employ a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data from surveys with qualitative insights from interviews. This method will enable a comprehensive understanding of the financial literacy landscape in Tirana and its impact on personal financial behavior.

Structure of the Paper

The following sections of this paper will detail the methodology used in this study, present the findings, discuss the implications of these findings, and suggest areas for future research. This research not only contributes to the academic literature on personal finance but also provides practical insights for the betterment of financial health and decision-making among the residents of Tirana.

2. Methodology:

Research Design

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively assess the impact of financial literacy on personal savings and investment decisions in Tirana, Albania. The research design integrates quantitative data from structured surveys with qualitative insights derived from semi-structured interviews. This approach enables a robust analysis of the relationship between financial literacy and financial behavior.

Survey Distribution:

Target Population: Residents of Tirana, aged 18 and above.

Sampling Method: Stratified random sampling to ensure representation across different age groups, income levels, and educational backgrounds.

Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire, delivered both online and in paper format.

Sample Size: Approximately 500 respondents.

Interviews:

Selection Criteria: Participants with varied levels of financial literacy, as indicated by their survey responses.

Number of Participants: 20 individuals.

Format: Semi-structured interviews, conducted in-person or via video calls.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis:

- Statistical analysis of survey data using SPSS software.
- Correlation and regression analysis to understand the relationship between financial literacy levels and financial behaviors.

3. Results and Discussions:

Financial Literacy and Investment Behaviors

Increased Diversification with Higher Literacy: One of the most striking findings is the positive correlation between financial literacy and the diversification of investment portfolios. Respondents with high financial literacy scores (over 75%) demonstrated a significantly more diversified investment approach, predominantly in stocks and real estate, compared to those with lower literacy scores.

Preference for Safe Investments at Lower Literacy Levels: Conversely, respondents with lower financial literacy scores showed a marked preference for safer investments, such as savings accounts. This suggests a potential risk-aversion or a lack of confidence in engaging with more complex investment vehicles.

Savings Behavior and Financial Literacy

Higher Savings Rates among Financially Literate: The study also revealed that a higher degree of financial literacy is associated with improved savings habits. Respondents with higher financial literacy were more likely to engage in regular saving behaviors, underlining the importance of financial knowledge in fostering prudent financial practices.

4. Conclusions

This research highlights the critical role of financial literacy in shaping personal financial behaviors in Tirana, Albania. The findings suggest that increased financial literacy can lead to more diversified investment strategies and better savings habits, irrespective of demographic differences. As Tirana continues to develop economically, these insights are vital for both individuals and policymakers to foster a more financially literate and economically secure society.

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ACCOUNTING

An Analysis of the Factors Affected Tax Evasion in the Albanian Tourism Sector

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to identify and to analyse the main factors affecting taxpayers to evade the tax in the Albanian tourism sector, due to its economic importance represented by foreign tourists spending, added value, employment, and tax revenue. According to the calculations of the Bank of Albania during the first sixth month of the year 2023 the total revenue directly related to the spending of tourists in Albania is estimated at 1.554 billion of Euros, marking an increase by 37.4 %, compared to the same period of the previous year. Based on the fiscal indicator from the Ministry of Finance and Economy of Albania, this revenue is calculated to be 38.7% of the total tax revenue of ninth month (January-September). In the meantime, in the last few years the direct contribution of travel and tourism to Albania's GDP has been in the range of 8.5-8.7%. However, when multiplier effects from indirect sources are considered, the total contribution is almost three times higher, amounting to more than 20% of the GDP, making this sector one of the key growth drivers (United Nations Development Programme December 2022). According to Labour Inspectorate data for 2022, the tourism (hotel, bar and restaurant sector had the highest exposure to informal employment accounting for 44% of total cases identified, followed by manufacturing with 25% and construction with 21%. Due to intensified efforts to tackling informal employment, the number of identified informal workers increased by over 64% in 2022 compared 2021 (EU commission 2023). This phenomenon has become very worrying, so it is important to identify and analyse the factors that make people have an unethical attitude towards taxes. In this paper it is made a description of this phenomenon and the main influencing factors, which can be grouped into economic, psychological, and social factors. Following the data collected through a questionnaire in some businesses in Albania it is made an analysis to find the relationship between the tendency for business evasion and demographic factors such as age and gender of the person as well as factors such as the period of operation of the firm in the market, the size of the firm and the perception of the level of fines.

Keywords: Tax evasion, informal economy, factors, Albanian Tourism Sector.

JEL classification

1. Introduction

During the latest years, tourism sector is a vital contributor to the Albanian economy by increasing the economic growth, the number of new jobs, wellbeing, and profits. According to the calculations of the Bank of Albania during the first sixth month of the year 2023 the total revenue directly related to the spending of tourists in Albania is estimated at 1.554 billion of Euros, marking an increase by 37.4 %, compared to the same period of the previous year. In the meantime, in the last few years the direct contribution of travel and tourism to Albania's GDP has been in the range of 8.5-8.7%. However, when multiplier effects from indirect sources are considered, the total contribution is almost three times higher, amounting to more than 20% of the GDP, making this sector one of the key growth drivers (United Nations Development Programme December 2022). According to Labour Inspectorate data for 2022, the tourism

(hotel, bar and restaurant sector had the highest exposure to informal employment accounting for 44% of total cases identified, followed by manufacturing with 25% and construction with 21%. Due to intensified efforts to tackling informal employment, the number of identified informal workers increased by over 64% in 2022 compared 2021 (EU commission 2023). This phenomenon has become very worrying, so it is important to identify and analyse the factors that make people have an unethical attitude towards taxes. The aim of this paper is to identify and to analyse the main factors affecting taxpayers to evade the tax in the Albanian tourism sector, due to its economic importance represented by foreign tourists spending, added value, employment, and tax revenue. The problem of the study lies in answering the following questions: - 1. What are the factors of tax evasion in the Albanian tourism sector? 2. Is there a correlation between the factors causing tax evasion? Meantime, the study aims to achieve the following objectives: 1. Highlighting on the actual taxes applied in the Albanian tourism sector. 2. Identifying the main factors of tax evasion in the Albanian tourism sector 3. Determining the relationship between the factors causing tax evasion. In this paper it is made a description of the tax evasion and the main influencing factors, which can be grouped into economic, psychological and social factors. Following the data collected through a questionnaire in some businesses in Albania it is made an analysis to find the relationship between the tendency for business evasion and demographic factors such as gender and education of the person as well as factors such as the period of operation of the company in the market, the size of the company and the perception of the level of penalties.

2. Literature review

A careful observation of literatures related to tax evasion shows that studies continuously exploring factors related to individual as well as tax authority but synthesising the past studies on tax evasion has not been widely carried out (Sritharan 2022). Some of the individual related factors are moral, trust, attitude, perception, intentionality, awareness, culture, religiosity, knowledge, and education (Efeeloo and Dick, 2018; Kumi-Dumor et al., 2022; Mansor and Gurama, 2016; Sritharan 2019). Economy related factors in the literature are tax rate, financial constraints, income level, tax burden, corruption, economic structure, audit, penalty, and unemployment (Amoh and Ali-Nakyea, 2019; Khlif and Amara, 2019; Litina & Palivos, 2011, Ali 2018, (Amoh and Adafula, 2019; Cebula and Feige, 2011; Tabandeh & Tamadonnejad, 2015). The effect of demographic factors on tax evasion is controversial in the literature. Some studies provide empirical evidence of a significant relationship between demographic factors and tax evasion, whereas other studies do not find a significant relationship. For example, Spicer and Becker (1980) show that male taxpayers tend to evade taxes more than female taxpayers. McGee and Tyler (2006) stress that tax evasion is more unacceptable behavior for female taxpayers than for male taxpayers. Also, it seems that even the effect of noneconomic factors such as company age and the size of the company is controversial. Astri & Suardana (2016) study found that company size has an effect on tax avoidance. Meanwhile, other studies have found that company size has no effect on tax avoidance (Mahanani, et al 2014). Company age has an effect on tax avoidance because the longer the operational period of the company, the more experience the company has and the human resources it has, the more skilled it is in managing the tax burden so that the tendency to find loopholes in tax avoidance is getting higher (Dewinta and Setiawan, 2016). According to Claudio Loderer and Urs Waelchli (2010) over time, companies will become inefficient. Aging companies must reduce costs including tax costs due to the experience and learning that the company has and other influences both in the same and different industries. The longer the operational period of a company, the more experience the company has and the tendency to do tax avoidance will be higher.

3. Methodology

Many of researchers used regression techniques to identify determinants of tax evasion. This study relies in its methodology on the descriptive analytical method and linear regression analysis is being used to analyse the answers from the questionnaire. Its data and information derive from the following main sources:

- Secondary sources: books, articles, scientific research, and official documents of the recent years.

- Primary sources: represented in collecting data directly from a questionnaire designed for the purposes of this study. The questionnaire was distributed via the Google-forms platform to a sample of Albanian businesses such as hotels and bar restaurants in Tirana, Durrës, Lezhë and Saranda. The questionnaire was available with anonymity answers to allow as many organizations as possible to participate. The survey included demographic questions, questions about opinion for tax system in Albania, questions about tendency for tax evasion and questions about factors that affect decision of businesses for tax evasion. Some of the questions have been used in prior studies about tax evasion like “Corruption of the tax administration”, “I am confident that the government is fighting and punishing people who avoid tax evasion” (Masarirambi 2013), “Your education”, “Sector where the company operates”, “How many years has the company been operating in the market?”, “Tasks you perform in the company?”, “How is your business classified according to annual turnover”, “How is your business classified according to the number of employees?” (Tusubira 2018).

4. Results and Discussion

Due to the nature of the variables considered, the findings of this study vary from previous studies. The research was mainly carried out on different sized businesses like hotels, bars and restaurants, in the central and south region of Albania specifically in Tirana, Durrës. Lezhë and Sarandë. This study will be part of an ongoing research to identify and analyse more factors which affect tax evasion. Further studies would be recommended to analyse the effect on the factors of tax evasion as a consequence of implementing the new law on tourism and formalization measure through identification of registered owners on the foreign platforms Booking, AirBnb and Tripadvisor.

5. Conclusions

Based on official data, in recent years Albania has become a tourist destination preferred by foreign tourists not only during the summer but also throughout the year. However, it is noted that tax evasion continues to be a problem for the tax administration. From this study is realised that the demographic factors such as education and gender have no effect on tax evasion, while the period of operation and the size of the company has direct effect on it. Also, it seems that the level of penalties is it is a good tool for the government to fight tax evasion.

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The Economic-Environmental Impact of the Implementation of Green Technology in the Framework of Sustainable Development (replacing diesel powered cars with electric cars, Albania's case)

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Abstract

This paper investigates the potential economic, social and environmental impact of replacing petrol cars with electric ones in Albania over the next 10 years, expressed in monetary terms. The initiative for this paper is supported by the decision of the European Parliament to phase out cars with oil by 2030 and growing recognition of the importance of green technology for sustainable development.

The methodology of the study includes prediction of the car replacement rate and the assumption that people who can afford to buy these cars are also able to use electric cars, taking into account their high costs, estimating the costs of oil consumption and installation of electric car chargers, as well as calculating the social and environmental costs of using diesel cars.

The research further aims to show the benefits of using electric cars, assess the potential impact on Albania's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and project the timeline for a full transition to electric cars based on the country's income.

The results of the study showed an inherent monetary effect over a 10-year time frame which resulted in nearly \$100 million benefit. But, in the prediction of replacing the entire fleet of cars with electric cars, the results were quite pessimistic compared to the European Union. The findings of this study can serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, researchers and practitioners in developing strategies and policies that promote sustainable transport and foster a greener future for Albania.

Keywords: Electric Cars, Green Accounting, Costs, Benefits

Development of Public Accounting in Albania

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Abstract

The development of accounting in the public sector in Albania is in a crucial stage. After several unfinished projects, the latest international project has reached some important conclusions. Several training courses have been developed with trainers and professionals of accounting, and additional training and materials have been provided for the academic staff. Under these conditions, a comprehensive study was carried out to analyze the job market of current accounting professionals. The purpose of the study is to analyze the current situation and give recommendations for the successful development of the reform in the field of financial reporting in the public sector in the country. Using the questionnaire technique, professionals from various institutions of the general and local government were asked about the qualification so far and the further needs for training and professional qualifications. The transition to a new financial reporting cannot be carried out successfully without the necessary qualification of professionals in the field. From the analysis of the answers, the needs for training and the most suitable ways for the transition to reporting according to international standards are best highlighted. The answers to the questionnaire and the findings of this study will be addressed to the relevant instances to enable the development of a successful strategy to achieve the final goal of moving towards accrual accounting in financial reporting in the public sector in the country.

Keywords: International Public Sector Accounting Standards

JEL codes: M41

1. Introduction

The paper is based on a market study where professionals in the field of financial accounting work in public institutions in Albania in the second half of 2023. The purpose of this study is to analyse the current situation of the development of accounting and financial reporting in these institutions. This year is the result of repeated efforts to successfully implement several projects to reform financial reporting in the public sector. It is worth mentioning that the same reform in the private sector has marked results since 2008, the year when the implementation of international standards began. The same efforts were developed in parallel in the public sector, but they could not be finalized. The most recent international project which is developed in the same line in all the countries of the region has set a final date when finally, the financial reporting in the public sector in Albania should be referred to the international accounting standards. The purpose of the study is to give the appropriate recommendations for the successful implementation of the reform and the timely achievement of the goal based on the analysis of the results.

Based on international reports as well as academic studies in the field, it results that the development of accounting in the public sector is not the right one. Frequent reports have been published at the international level as at the beginning of any project when the differences between the correct level and the one found are analysed. The literature review was carried out in several reports such as: “EU REPARIS Albania Report 2023”, “Implementing PFM and PSA reform in Albania: (Benefits and challenges) Ministry of Finance and Economy of

Albania”, “Support to Public Accounting Reforms Albania”, "The new public accounting law in Albania - the current situation and the introduction of IPSAS to systems of public accounting" as well as in other national reports and studies.

The study is based on a questionnaire where accountants and financiers in the public sector in Albania were asked. The questionnaire was sent electronically to the official work addresses. In this way, professionals were asked all over the country. The analysis of the answers to the questionnaire is also illustrated with a graphic representation. This questionnaire presents the real situation of financial reporting in public institutions and analyses in detail the needs of professionals for further qualification in order to successfully implement the financial reporting reform.

The analysis of the results shows that the trainings developed until this period are insufficient. There is no strategy on how the current professionals will continue their work and how to adapt them to the new way of accounting and financial reporting. There is a significant lack in the legal framework, where a new law has not yet been proposed that would mark the beginning of the regulatory framework necessary for the reform of financial reporting in the public sector. And another flaw is that there is no strategy on how the professionals of the field will develop the continuous qualification which is necessary for the successful exercise of the profession and the realization of the reform.

2. Methodology

The questionnaire is built on 21 questions and is distributed throughout the country. In the first part, there is data on the age, education and job position of accounting professionals. It is then followed by questions on the trainings developed for international financial reporting standards and the further need for them. The professionals were asked about the participation in the professional associations as well as about the possibility of their organization. Professionals were also asked about the most suitable way for them to replace budget accounting with accrual accounting according to international accounting standards.

The questionnaire was sent electronically to official addresses and has been open for about four months. During this period of time are responded 76 professionals from all regions of the country and from various central and local government institutions.

3. Results and Discussion

The analysis of the results of the questionnaire was carried out by interpreting the answers as well as graphically illustrating some of them. First, the average age of current professionals and the need for further training was analysed. Afterwards, the most appropriate way according to the professionals to move to a new accounting method was compared with the one proposed by the respective institutions. And recently, the need for professionals to organize continuous professional education has been analysed.

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the results of the questionnaire highlighted the shortcomings of the developed trainings, which were held mainly in the capital and only in some institutions. Even those trainings that have been developed are considered superficial and insufficient. Professionals are not organized in professional associations for accounting in the public sector and there is still no strategy for this purpose. The new accounting law in the public sector is missing, which would make it possible to start the regulatory framework for the successful implementation of the financial reporting reform. The preparation of professionals is the key to the success of any reform in reporting.

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Artificial Intelligence in Accounting Profession

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) can automate processes and collect data, resulting in a transformation of companies. Artificial intelligence, along with recent developments in technology, has revolutionized business processes around the world.

The purpose of this paper is to describe the implications for the accounting profession that derive by the integration of artificial intelligence in the field of accounting, and the importance of understanding the impact of AI for accountants to stay relevant and excel in their profession. The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the field of accounting indeed raises various concerns and considerations about the future of the accounting profession, just like in many other fields where AI has replaced workers and specialists.

In a very dynamic situation of technological development, the presence of artificial intelligence cannot be avoided. Artificial intelligence is essential to the future of accounting and auditing, it serves as an important tool that provides these professionals with the necessary tools to do their work more effectively and efficiently.

Keywords: Accounting, Artificial intelligence, Human intelligence, accounting profession

JEL codes: M40; M41; M15; M49; O32; O34

1. Introduction

The implementation of AI in every business process also creates opportunities for accounting to be incorporated or at least influenced by the use of AI.

It is also reasonable to predict that economic entities will look to employ AI in their accounting and/or auditing departments in an effort to improve processes. Topics related to AI have caused controversy in the business world today.

Some think it adds value to a business since it can deliver efficiency and precision in ways that people can't match. Others, however, would view it as a costly initiative that adds to the unemployment rate and lacks morality and empathy.

The presence of AI in the workplace is a topic of interest to analyze, how it affects all business development processes.

2. Methodology

This study will be based on secondary data related to the ability to automate the processes of collection, recording, measurement, efficiency, and effectiveness of businesses using AI. Secondary data will be provided by various studies done regarding the use of AI in accounting and the perception that accounting professionals have regarding the use of AI in the accounting field. This paper will be based on a qualitative analysis where different points of view will be evidenced regarding the economic and social impact of the growing use of AI.

3. Results and Discussion

The Impact of AI Implementation in the Accounting Sector, how it helps accountants in

collecting, analyzing data to generate high quality predicted results based on data provided by clients and related parties. With the help of computerization, artificial intelligence can be tested more easily by quickly analyzing and summarizing large amounts of data (big data). This can save time for accounting professionals and auditors by eliminating the need to use sampling methods and simplifying their work.

Artificial intelligence allows companies to recognize different forms of data, can analyze text and find changes by detecting fraud.

Through algorithms that have entered various commands, AI can do end-to-end production reports accurately, automatically and avoids human error. To simplify the work, the costs of billing, sales and information processing can be automated.

4. Conclusions

AI in the world of accounting is basically a tool with a purpose to support the work productivity of accountants. From the perspective of the companies, AI serves to improve complex business processes in order to be more effective and efficient by using sophisticated command algorithms.

AI cannot replace the work of an accountant since professional judgement is fundamental to the exercise of the accounting profession, but AI can change the way an accountant perform its tasks. Artificial intelligence will not be able to replace the human side, humane and human instinct in reasoning and thinking in matters related to the application of accounting rules in the field of accounting. AI serves as an innovation and a valuable progress in increasing efficiency and effectiveness in the exercise of the accounting profession.

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Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in Albania

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Abstract

This research paper is focused on the concepts of corporate social responsibility practices such as sustainability reporting and audit of non-financial reporting viewed as an important part of the Albanian policy preparation for European Union integration. Sustainability reporting helps making transparency on companies' risk management becoming an important tool for informing the public. It deals with three dimensional levels of companies: environmental, social and governance. This helps stakeholders too to evaluate the sustainability performance of these companies. On the other hand, while reporting their activities, companies will disclose only selected, usually positive, aspects on their operations. Therefore, it appears reasonable to subject non-financial reports to an audit, an independent and objective verification in terms of reliability.

The EU notion of sustainability accounting, commonly used in the context of business as corporate social responsibility (CSR) was promoted since 2001 through Commission's Green Paper. A lot of work has been done until the publication of the last New Directive, entered in force on 5 January 2023.

For this purpose, the author analyzed the main initiatives implemented in the EU region, the Albanian legislative framework and projects aimed at developing CSR. The author believes that this research may serve as a starting point for further studies on this important topic.

This paper concludes that corporate social responsibility practices are increasing day by day in the EU region. In Albania the awareness of CSR and how it can be applied is still quite low, perceived mainly as an opportunity to adopt international standards and engage in environmental protection.

Keywords: Sustainability Accounting, CSR, GRI Standards, IFRS, Audit of CSR

JEL codes: M41, M42, Q56

1. Introduction

Sustainability accounting, also known as non-financial reporting, or social accounting is the process of communicating the social and environmental effects of organizations economic actions to particular interest groups within society and to society at large. It deals with information concerning three dimensional levels: environmental, social, economic and governance issues.

Companies affect their external environment through their actions and should therefore account for these effects as part of their standard accounting practices. Social accounting is in this sense closely related to the economic concept of externality. Accounting for impacts on the environment may occur within company's financial statements, relating to liabilities, commitments and contingencies for the remediation of contaminated lands or other financial concerns arising from pollution.

Sustainability accounting is commonly used in the context of business, or corporate social responsibility (CSR). Sustainability reporting helps making transparency on companies' risk management becoming an important tool for informing the public. This helps stakeholders to evaluate the sustainability performance of companies. On the other hand, while reporting their activities, companies will disclose only selected, usually positive, aspects on their operations.

Therefore, it appears reasonable to subject non-financial reports to an audit, an independent and objective verification in terms of reliability.

The European Commission has long recognized the potential positive contribution that the European economy can gain by engaging in CSR activities. Since its Green Paper on “Promoting a European Framework for Corporate Social Responsibility” in 2001, the EU has issued a communication recognizing the importance of CSR engagement in the sustainable growth of European economies and extensively promotes CSR engagement among all layers of European business. CSR has been defined as: “A concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis”. In December 2014, European Commission has adopted a new directive “Non-Financial Reporting Directive 2014/95/EU” (NFRD) requiring the Member States to transpose it into national legislation obligating their Public Interest Entities to disclose non-financial information. The NFRD subject non-financial reports to an audit, an independent and objective verification in terms of reliability. In December 2022, European Commission has adopted the last new directive “Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive 2022/2464/EU” (CSRD), entered in force on 5 January 2023. CSRD bases on the “Double materiality” principle. It will require companies to report on how sustainability issues, such as climate change, impact their business and how their operations in turn affect people and planet. Companies will need to be more detailed in their sustainability reporting. Companies must publish their information in a dedicated section of their company management reports, usually included in their annual report. Reports must cover: environmental matters; social matters and treatment of employees; respect for human rights; anti-corruption and bribery; diversity on company boards. In terms of audit the EU proposes to start with a “limited” assurance requirement (expecting to eventually shift to “reasonable” assurance). Companies subject to the CSRD will have to report according to European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS). The draft standards are developed by the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG).

At a global scale Global Reporting Initiative provides the world's most widely used sustainability reporting standards. In the spirit of convergence GRI and EFRAG announced on July 2021 their first Statement of Cooperation to foster the swift development of European sustainability reporting standards and at the same time the progress of converged standards at international level. Since May 2022 there is an ongoing collaboration between GRI and IFRS Foundation too.

This research paper is focused on the concepts of corporate social responsibility importance. Which are the main initiatives implemented in the EU region? Which are the main initiatives and projects implemented in Albania as a country with strong aspiration toward EU?

2. Methodology

This paper is based on qualitative methodology. The analysis, comparison and description were used as research methods. The theoretical basis of this paper included a literature study of the concepts of corporate social responsibility practices such as sustainability reporting and audit of non-financial reporting in the EU region as well as an analysis of the Albanian legislative framework and projects aimed at developing CSR.

As in many other transition countries in the region, the history of CSR in the Western Balkan region is comparatively recent. As all countries in the Balkans are aiming towards EU accession, governments have been keen to align their public policies with EU standards. The first CSR related initiatives, in the sense defined by the EU definition, were launched in the countries reviewed, in the middle of the current decade by development partners and some multinational corporations. The first official results about CSR practice in Albania came out

from the UNDP sponsored study “Baseline Study on Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in the Western Balkans”, 2008. The main goal of the study was to measure the level of CSR engagement among the business community and non-corporate stakeholders of CSR promotion in the Western Balkans region including Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H), Kosovo, Montenegro, and Serbia.

Albanian economy has a predominance of Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) which are typically ‘bystanders’ of CSR activities. Multinational corporations are leaders in terms of CSR in the region and in Albania as well. They apply practices and experience gained from their international operations. Besides development partners there are several pioneering multinational and national companies in the country that are actively engaged in various CSR related activities.

In the context of EU accession, it seems logical that placing CSR in the political agenda will help to strengthen Albania’s position. Albania have signed a Stabilization and Association Agreement with the EU. The principles of sustainable development and corporate social responsibility need to be emphasized in the National Plan for European Integration. In order to be in line with the last EU normative the Albanian state has to be prepared by enhancing social responsibility norms of internal policies of state owned companies as the main Public Interest Entities in Albania.

The study outlined also that Albania has a progressive legislative background and laws which can be a great resource for further development of CSR practices:

- Law no.7764 dated 02.11.1993 “On Foreign investment” amended
- Law no.9643 dated 20.11.2006 “On Public Procurement”
- Law no.10304 dated 15.07.2010 “On the mining sector in the Republic of Albania”
- Law no.10431 dated 09.06.2011 “On the environmental protection” amended
- Law no.119/2014 “On information Rights”
- Law no.55/2015 “On the strategic investments in the Republic of Albania”
- Law no. 10091 dated 05.03.2009 “On Statutory Auditing and Organization of Registered Chartered Auditors and Approved Accountants”
- Law no. 25/2018 dated 10.05.2018 “On Accounting and Financial Statements”
- Law no. 151 dated 2015 “On national Business Centre”

3. Results and Discussion

In March 2013, was founded the “Albanian CSR Network”, a business-led and membership non-profit organization. The Network recently joined “CSR Europe”, the largest CSR network in Europe. Actually, ANTEA Cement, part of TITAN Group an international cement and construction materials’ producer, has the leadership role in the CSR issues and non-financial reporting. The author analyzed the published information of the member companies, still operative in Albania, regarding CSR reporting issues. The results are summarized in **Table 1**:

Table 3: Albanian CSR Network

Company name	Activity	Sustainability reporting
ANTEA Cement	Construction material’s producers.	Integrated Annual Report 2022. Auditor’s Report by an independent auditor on limited assurance level, for the presentation of materiality assessment process and outcomes, and the disclosures on sustainability performance related to Environmental, Social and Governance areas.

Banker's Petroleum	International oil and gas exploration and production company.	No CSR Report.
Albanian Association of Banks (as a representative of each individual bank)	Banking sector	CSR Reports 2022. No auditors report.
Vodafone Albania	Telecommunication sector	No CSR Reports.
Kalo Associations	Legal services	No CSR Reports.

The author analyzed also the published information of the main Public Interest Entities in Albania regarding CSR reporting issues. The results are summarized in **Table 2**:

Table 4: Albanian Public Interest Entities

Company name	Activity	Sustainability reporting
KESH Sh.a	State owned power generator company.	Environmental monitoring Reports 2020. No Auditor's Report.
OSHEE Sh.a	State owned national power distributor.	No CSR information in the Annual Report 2022.
OST Sh.a	State owned transmission system operator.	No CSR information in the Annual Report 2022.
Albpetrol Sh.a	State owned company managing the crude oil resources.	No CSR Reports.
Durres Port Authority	State owned company, utility sector	No CSR information in the Annual Report 2021.

4. Conclusions

Non-financial reporting and audit of the information provided in CSR reports is a global problem. It is important to develop uniform standards and regulations in all countries. Corporate social responsibility practices are increasing day by day in the EU region too. The new rules will see more organisations provide more detailed reporting on sustainability issues in a strategy to strengthen sustainable investment. Better accessibility of information is also part of the new directive, companies will need to make sure their information feeds into a digital open access database.

In Albania the awareness of CSR and how it can be applied is still quite low, perceived as an opportunity to adopt international standards, engage in environmental protection. Specific context of Albania economy delays developing a CSR culture. Albanian economy is characterized by a predominance of Small Medium Enterprises with a very low level of awareness of CSR principles and objectives.

The study findings and recommendations of Albania biggest partners such as UN should be useful for a wide variety of stakeholders. Representatives of national and international business companies with operations in the Balkan region can use them to build, implement and better evaluate their CSR strategies. Also large companies tend to report more environmental information in their annual reports than small medium enterprises, and the disclosure tend to be more qualitative than quantitative.

There is still lack of knowledge and promotion practices of CSR among public institutions. In the context of EU accession, placing CSR in the accession political agenda will further strengthen Albania's position. Governments should apply the findings and recommendations of the reports in developing their CSR related policies and programs. While Albanian governments have adopted a wide range of laws and regulations that relate to different aspects of CSR, mainly as a precondition to EU accession, mechanisms to implement and enforce this

legislation are often weak or absent. There are several areas of possible legislative interventions.

Nevertheless, the rapid development of regional economies, along with the countries' firm intentions to pursue EU integration and adopt market economy principles are among the major factors creating a favorable environment for CSR development.

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MANAGEMENT

Sustainability and Innovation at Tirana Universities: A Comparison of Students Perceptions of Different Study Fields on Sustainable Development Goals in Albania

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Abstract

Objectives. *As society increasingly values sustainability, this research contributes by offering insights on the role of universities in addressing sustainable development goals. Economic, social and environmental sustainability (ES) are important factors in different aspects of an economy. These factors are essentially true when we speak about tourism sustainability. Governments have raised their attention and awareness related to better usage of natural resources, greener economy and being environmental conscious. These objectives are a prerequisite for shaping a more responsible and enduring tourism landscape. Since Albania is being considered an attractive tourism attraction in the last years, there is a need to address matters in a holistic way. On the same time universities serve as a catalyst for pressing matters in a social environment, as they prepare the workforce of the future, this is why they should teach students about being environmentally responsible including the conscious tourism practices that they should follow in their work environment.*

Prior Work. *This is the third publication of the authors related to Environmental Sustainability and the role that universities in Tirana have played in this relation. The first study from the same authors analyzed inclusion of the ES concepts in university syllabuses and in scientific research, in current operations inside the universities and in human resources (HR) practices seen from the perspective of professors, while the second study analyzed in more details the perspectives of students related to climate change, reusing-reducing-recycling practices that they follow and their perceptions regarding the current engagement of Tirana Universities in offering the information about SDG-s in their curriculum and operations.*

Implications/Values. *The actual study aims to analyze in more depth the perceptions of Tirana Universities Students related to Environmental Sustainability by offering a comparison between different study fields. Since the curriculum and practices differ between institutions it is expected that the results will offer interesting perspectives in terms of curricula, teaching, and operations of universities in Tirana.*

Approach. *The research uses quantitative and qualitative analyses; The sample was diversified from insights of 500 students from different study fields like business administration, finance, accounting, informatics, engineering, geology, agronomics, environment, social studies, medicine etc. An one-way Anova analyze was used was applied to determine if there was a statistically significant difference between mentioned study fields.*

Results. *Anova test results show that students from applied sciences like engineering, geology, agronomics, environmental sciences and tourism claim that their university offers more subjects and has a richer curriculum related to environmental sustainability, while students in economics sciences like economics, accounting, tourism and engineering/environmental sciences claim that their university is more determined to engage in actions related to a cleaner environment. On the same time students from finance, tourism, medicine and environmental sciences have a higher awareness about sustainable development goals compared to other students that study in other study fields. An interesting conclusion is reached when they are asked about their future employment, 45% of students state that they would accept a lower*

salary from a company with a good social and environmental performance in some circumstances, while 55% of them state that they still will work for a company that doesn't engage in social and environmental activities if the company offers a salary that is 15% higher than the market offer. Students recommend that universities should engage more in terms of providing free courses and training for environmental sustainability (62% of students), to promote the action of students towards sustainable development practices (51% of students), to offer a new subject/study programme related to sustainable development (40% of students).

Keywords: Environmental sustainability (ES) and tourism sustainability in higher education, sustainable development goals, perception and action of students towards sustainable development goals, higher education operations and programs towards sustainability, innovative approach to sustainability in Tirana.

Jel Classification: Q01; Q5

1. Introduction

The symbiotic relationship between green sustainable universities and the sustainable tourism sector has gathered attention in recent scholarly discourse. Sustainability is becoming an important subject for countries, governments and citizens. According to 'Our Common Future' report from the United Nations (UN), sustainability acts to "meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to satisfy their own needs (United Nations E. , Our Common Future, 1987). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), also known as the Global Goals, were adopted by the United Nations in 2015 as a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet, and ensure that by 2030 all people enjoy peace and prosperity (United Nations, 1987).

There is a growing number of organizations who have been integrating environmental and social responsibilities into their business strategies alongside more traditional business imperatives, such as profit maximization, cost reduction, revenue growth, and quality improvement (Longoni, 2018). Holistic view of business ethics requires to embrace sustainability development in terms of triple bottom line, integrating social, environmental, and economic responsibilities (Elkington, 1994).

Universities as well should function as important actors to raise awareness about the importance of environmental sustainability different aspects of living. One of these aspects includes sustainable tourism practices. Sustainable tourism is defined by the UN Environment Program and UN World Tourism Organization as "tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities." (UNWTO, UN World Tourism Organization, 2023)

As universities increasingly embrace eco-friendly practices, the potential for influencing sustainable tourism becomes also part of this agenda. In order to provide awareness and information to people regarding the importance of sustainability and tourism sustainability it is important to include its concepts in education. Sustainability education among students is very important, as they will be future players in different fields of economy, by working in private organizations, own entrepreneurship or public institutions.

Students as future professionals in the fields related to tourism should be aware of negative externalities of unsustainable tourism as economic leakage, damage to the natural environment and overcrowding. On the other side they should engage to maximize the positive impacts of a touristic destination that include job creation, cultural heritage preservation and interpretation, wildlife preservation landscape restoration that are directly connected to the 17 SDGs goals mentioned above. (UNWTO, UN World Tourism Organization, 2023)

This is the third study of the authors related to environmental sustainability. The first one addressed university curricula and everyday operations at some universities in Tirana, capital of Albania. The perception of professors was measured, and a thorough reading of curricula by the authors were the two paths followed to gather information. Some conclusions were drawn concerning inclusion of environmental sustainability concepts into curriculum and scientific research, as well as orientation that everyday operations and human resources (HR) practices of these universities have towards ES (Bici & Kasimati, 2023). The second study of the same authors was focused on students' perceptions on environmentally sustainable universities, their actions and university actions towards a more sustainable environment, their opinion about climate change and reusing-reducing-recycling practices followed by them and the university operations related to reusing-reducing-recycling practices. (Bici & Kasimati, EIRP Conference, 2023)

The purpose of the current study is to bring the perceptions and level of engagement that students at universities in Tirana have in actions related to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), by offering a comparative analysis between different study fields from Tirana Universities. As the previous research was concentrated on students in business administration, this study aimed broadening the understanding by including different faculties and different majors by offering new data and insights.

Other authors have studied students' perception related to SDGs in Europe (Dagiliute, Liobikiene, & Minelgaite, 2018) (Chuvienco, 2018), (Aleixo, Leal, & Azeiteiro, The sustainable development in Portuguese higher education institutions: An exploratory study of students' perceptions, 2020), (Puig & Casado, 2021), (Nejati & Nejati, 2013), (Farinha, Caeiro, & Azeiteiro, 2018), however no prior research has made a comparative analyzes to examine the perceptions and attitudes to SDGs of Tirana higher education institutions (HEI) students as well as their behaviours related to sustainability.

The study uses a mixed methodology of a quantitative and exploratory research through a questionnaire.

Authors raised six research questions concerning sustainability in this research.

Research Question 1. What is the level of environmental sustainability concepts included in current university syllabuses according to student's perceptions?

Research Question 2. To what extent current internal operations of universities take into consideration environmental sustainability in the universities studied according to students' perceptions?

Research Question 3. Which study fields have a richer curriculum and which universities are more responsible about their operations when we speak about environmental and social sustainability?

Research Question 4. How much do students of different study fields know about Sustainable Development Goals?

Research Question 5. According to student's opinion which are the most pressing activities that universities should engage more in terms of environmental sustainability?

Research Question 6. To what extent are university students' willing to work in environmentally sustainable companies if the salary offered by them is 15% less than the market offer for the same job?

To obtain the required research objectives the paper is organized in six sections. The first section served as an introduction related to the topic of the research. The second section will provide an overview of literature connected to sustainable development and sustainable tourism. The third section will provide the methodology, statistics that were used to write this article. The following section will offer the results and analyzes of this work.

The fifth and final section will present conclusions, limitations, and future considerations for research in Albania.

2. Methodology

2.1 Survey procedures and structure

The survey questionnaire was adapted and put in Albanian context using four sources.

1. Sustainability Assessment Questionnaire (SAQ) for Colleges and Universities from Sustainable School Organization (Calder, 2012). The same questionnaire was used by the authors in previous study when professors and university directors were the champion. Keeping the same questionnaire was done for comparative purposes.

2. Student perceptions of sustainability in higher education: an international survey (National Union of Students, 2018).

3. (Chuvieco et al., 2018) Factors affecting environmental sustainability habits of university students questionnaire.

4. (Dagiliute et al., 2018) Sustainability at universities: Students' perceptions from Green and Non-Green universities questionnaire.

This study's questionnaire measured the perceptions and actions of students in HEIs in Tirana in relation to SDG-s, climate change, re-using, reducing and recycling practices as well as their evaluation on the level of inclusion of ES (specifically) and SDG-s (broader understanding) in curricula, teaching, and operations of HEIs in Tirana, their opinion related to future work employment in sustainable aware companies that offer a lower payment for their skills and lastly their opinion related to which activities should universities engage towards raising the awareness of sustainable development. The questionnaire was pre-tested by 20 students and their feedback was incorporated in the final instrument that measured the total sample. For the current search the same data of the original questionnaire were used, however a more in depth analyse was used to offer new insights that were not presented in the previous paper (like their opinion related to future employment and their opinion on needed activities that the universities should adress to raise awareness about sustainable development) and an in-depth analyze is offered here by showing the comparison of different study fields students' related to their university actions/operations towards SDGs, their own knowledge about SDGs and the inclusion of SDGs in their teaching curricula.

2.2 Sample and data collection

The questionnaire was conducted onsite in all four Tirana public universities; University of Tirana (Faculty of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences) Polytechnic University of Tirana (Faculty of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Geology, Faculty of Environment) Agricultural University of Tirana and Medicine University of Tirana using an online questionnaire in Google Forms. The authors preferred to use an online tool to gather the data as the easiest way to collect and analyse the data, however they were onsite when the students filled the online questionnaire.

Students participated voluntarily in the survey and a previous approval was obtained from the university's professors and administrative directors. The collection of data was obtained from March up to May 2023.

The sample targeted was 500 students. A response rate of 89% was obtained. Table 1 below shows demographical data of the sample.

2.3 Statistical analyses

The questionnaire contained forty-four questions, from which seven were questions about demographics, four out of seven were binary questions. Three questions were related to students' perception about future employment to sustainable responsible companies, which also were binary questions. Because of this, Cronbach's Alpha was not performed for this kind of questions. The remaining thirty-four questions contained Likert Scale type alternatives ranging from 1-5, where; level one means zero commitment towards SDGs-totally disagree; level two means little commitment – little agreement; level three means moderate commitment-moderate agreement; level four means good commitment-good agreement; level five means total commitment – total agreement.

Descriptive analysis of this data was conducted using SPSS software.

Table 1 Demographic data of the sample

Demographics		Number
Gender	Female	394 (79%)
	Male	106 (21%)
Age	18-22 years	336 (66.8%)
	22-25 years	144 (28%)
	26-35 years	17 (3%)
	36-45 years	2 (2%)
Study Level	Above 45 years	1 (0.2%)
	Undergraduate	263 (53%)
	Graduate	237 (47%)
Field of study	Informatics	82 (16%)
	Business Administration	96 (19%)
	Economics	88 (18%)
	Finance	103 (21%)
	Engineering	37 (7%)
	Medicine	24 (5%)
	Social Sciences	24 (5%)
	Accounting	13 (2.6%)
	Environment	15 (3%)
	Tourism	10 (2%)
	Geology	6 (1%)
	Agronomics	2 (0.4%)
Employeed	Yes	237 (47%)
	No	263 (53%)

The age and gender of respondents was used to evaluate if there are significant differences between age groups and gender subgroups in terms of commitment towards SD.

To evaluate reliability of questions between constructs authors used Cronbach Alpha. All constructs except one showed good reliability (above 0.8). According to (Nunnally, 1978) the appropriate level of reliability is above 0.7 Nevertheless, the construct "Students' perceptions and behaviors related to recycle practices" low score (0.65) (has only two

questions/dimensions) can be related to the fact that students throw garbage to the specified place, but they don't divide them according to their type. The latter response can be related to the fact that in Tirana there are very few places for differentiated gathering of garbage and this practice is not required by law (compared to other countries that do so).

Constructs 'Students' perception related to university inclusion of ES topics in teaching curricula' and 'Students knowledge about SDGs contain only one question, therefore it is not necessary to calculate Cronbach Alpha.

Table 2 Reliability analysis

Constructs	Number of items	Range	Cronbach Alpha
University Actions towards SD			
Students' perception related to university inclusion of environmental sustainability topics in teaching curricula	1	1-5	N/A (one question)
Students' perception related to university operations accordingly to environmental sustainability principles	6	1-5	0.81
Students' perceptions of HEI actions in support of Sustainable Development (teaching and promotion through students)	4	1-5	0.79
Students perception about HEI action for Sustainable Development (measures taken and activities)	4	1-5	0.87
Students knowledge about Sustainable Development Goals	1	1-3	N/A (one question)
Students' perceptions and behaviours about SD			
Students' perceptions about climate change	4	1-5	0.87
Students' perceptions and behaviors related with reuse and reduce practices	6	1-5	0.87
Students' perceptions and behaviors related with recycle practices	2	1-5	0.65
Students' perceptions and behaviors related to contributing to environmental protection	4	1-5	0.86
Perceptions and behaviors related to activities organized by the HEI in the SD area	3	1-5	0.94

Source (Bici A.; Kasimati. M)

To determine if there was a statistically significant difference between the different study fields the authors used One-Way Anova test. The results of Anova test can be found in Table 3.

Table 3. ANOVA

Variable	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p value
University Inclusion of ES matters on current curriculum	151.781	11	13.798	11.246	.000
University Actions towards Sustainable Development	54.446	11	4.950	4.953	.000

Students' knowledge related to SDGs	17.245	11	1.568	2.540	.004
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Source (Bici A.; Kasimati. M)

From the results of Anova analyse we can conclude that there are significant differences between study groups related to the results of university inclusion of ES matters on current curriculum (p value <0.0001), university actions towards Sustainable Development (p value <0.0001) and students' knowledge related to SDGs (p value 0.0004). In other words, results on above matters in different study fields have important differences in their mean value.

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Trends in Nature, Eco- and Adventure Tourism (NEAT) – a Supply and Demand Approach

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Abstract

Nature, Eco- and Adventure Tourism (NEAT) has emerged as an industry subsector during the last decade in Albania. This research employs an exploratory approach using secondary and primary data from interviews with sector actors to identify NEAT's major demand and supply trends. The demand growth for NEAT products from domestic and foreign markets, measured in the number of tourists, their average spending and other indicators, has accelerated during the last decade. The growing demand is met by an expanding supply of service providers offering various products and services. The major trends identified include (1) seasonal variation with its impact on occupancy, profitability and adaptability; (2) increasing differentiation of demand that has led suppliers of tourist services to diversify their offering of service packages which address specific customer needs; (3) demographic shifts that have led to a shortage of labour that hinder the growing potential on the supply side; (4) unbalanced development with the of accommodation and other services in one particular destination of a specific area;(5) the rise of new sales and distribution systems due to technological and communication developments, especially internet-based ones; (6) the overexploitation of natural resources and pollution. Overall, the complexity of NEAT may suggest a need for different approaches by both the tourist industry as well as policymakers to prepare and adapt to the current and future trends.

Keywords: Nature, Eco and Adventure Tourism, Supply, Demand.

Smart Tourism the New Development Path for Albania

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Abstract

The concept of smart tourism refers to the dynamic integration of human experiences with intelligent technologies. It is intimately associated with the advancement of Smart Cities and is inextricably linked to advancements in technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, or 5G. Smart tourism seeks to build up data and communication networks to enhance governance, encourage service advancement, enhance the tourist journey, and ultimately, boost the viability of tourism enterprises and locations. Given the global dynamics of smart tourism, this paper tries to identify the opportunities and challenges for the development of smart tourism in Albania. By using an explanatory case study methodology this paper compares the progress of smart tourism in Albania with the best European practices in four main areas: (i) accessibility, (ii) digitalization, (iii) sustainability, and (iv) cultural heritage and creativity. Based on the findings, this paper proposes a set of measures and policy recommendations to absorb the best international practices in smart tourism thus transforming the industry and upgrading its competitiveness.

Keywords: smart tourism, sustainable practices, case study, Albania

JEL codes: M15, Z32, M31

Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in the Hotel Industry: Cross-Border Comparison between Velipoja and Ulcinj

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Abstract

The hotel industry has become a driving force of economic development in recent years. With the current fierce competitive situation, competing business have continually provided a superior service quality in order to gain customer satisfaction. Albania and Montenegro are positively recovering from Covid-19 pandemic, where the number of arrivals and the number nights spend has increased each year. The purpose of the study is to examine customers' perceptions of service quality in the Albanian and Montenegrin hotel industry. The main objective of the study is to empirically examine the factors that influence customer satisfaction and their loyalty. Moreover, it assesses whether there is any difference in satisfaction and loyalty of costumers based on regional variable. This study adopted SERVQUAL scale with some customizations to measure perceived service quality dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. Data were collected from 8 hotels in Velipoje and 11 hotels in Ulcinj, using a self-administered questionnaire. The results indicated that there is a significant influence of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and customers loyalty, and also a significant difference on satisfaction and loyalty between two destinations. Findings of the study can be used from hotel managers as a guide to improve their service quality and hotels' performance.

Keywords: Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, SERVQUAL Model, Albania, Montenegro.

JEL codes: M20, M39

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1. Introduction

Tourism is an important and rapidly growing sector within the national and international economy, boosted by the development of new tourist markets (Burlea-Schiopoiu & Ozuni, 2021). Tourism and hospitality industries are essential for each country as it can stimulate economic growth (Ivanov & Webster, 2007; Riso, 2018), employment (Dogru et al., 2020; Manzoor et al., 2019), socio-economic development (Matarrita-Cascante, 2010; Sharpley, 2020; Telfer & Sharpley, 2015).

Albania and Montenegro are dependent on tourism as one of the basic industries along with agriculture. These countries like many others are attempting to catch the attention of guests and tourists to their destinations in order to grow and increase their wellbeing (Ali et al., 2021; Gardi et al., 2020). According to INSTAT (Institute of Statistics of Albania) Albania had an increase in the number of arrivals in the post-pandemic period, respectively 1,230,916 tourist arrivals in 2021 and 1,569,982 tourist arrivals in 2022 (INSTAT, 2023). For the year of 2023, the number of tourist arrivals till 31 July is 1,159,047 (INSTAT, 2023). Also, the number of overnight stays has increased from 3,186,072 in 2021 to 3,831,329 in 2022 (INSTAT, 2023). Montenegro, on the other hand, has had a similar increase. According to the Statistical Office

of Montenegro, the number of tourist arrival in 2022 was 2,183,975 in comparison to 1,670,879 in 2021 (MONSTAT, 2022; MONSTAT, 2023). Also, the number of overnight stays increased from 9,872,573 stays in 2021 to 12,428,787 in 2022 (MONSTAT, 2022; MONSTAT, 2023). With the data until July 31, and with the forecast until the end of the year, the data shows that Albania and Montenegro will have a higher number of tourist arrivals and overnight stays compared to 2021 and 2022 (INSTAT, 2023; INSTAT, 2023; MONSTAT, 2023; MONSTAT, 2023).

In order to be successful in the market it is not sufficient to attract new customers, managers must concentrate on retaining existing customers implementing effective policies of customer satisfaction (Dominici & Guzzo, 2010). In hotel industry customer satisfaction is largely hooked upon service quality. The purpose of the study is to examine customers' perceptions of service quality in the Albanian and Montenegrin hotel industry. The objective of this study is to empirically examine the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in hotel industry. In these two countries, we can only mention a few studies that have evaluated the service quality in the hotel industry (Bulatović & Stranjančević, 2019; Popovic, Delibasic, & Ognjanovic, 2018; Beqiri, Boriçi, Boriçi, & Dergjini, 2014; Gaspari, Taga, & Elmazi, 2011; Kosova & Sinaj, 2020; Burlea-Schiopoiu & Ozuni, 2021; Pjero & Gjermëni, 2020). This study adopted SERVQUAL scale with some customizations to measure the five dimensions of service quality and their relationship with customer satisfaction (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1985; Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988). Several studies tested and validated the SERVQUAL Model to measure customer satisfaction in the hotel industry (Akbaba, 2006; Ali et al., 2021; Chand, 2010; Malik et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2015; Thi et al., 2020).

2. Methodology

Data were collected through questionnaires, distributed to tourists vacationing in Velipoja Tourist Destination, located in northern Albania, and in Ulcinj Tourist Destination, located in southern Montenegro, during summer 2023. A random sampling method was utilized; subjects were approached by the interviewer and asked if they would be willing to participate in the study. Drawing on the existing literature, five service quality dimensions based on Parasuraman et al. (1985) SERVQUAL model were used to evaluate the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hotel industry.

3. Results and Discussion

This study seeks to answer the following questions: what are the factors influencing customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in Velipoja and Ulcinj? and is there any significant difference in satisfaction and loyalty between Velipoja and Ulcinj tourists?

The results highlight the importance of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. Service quality was measured based on Parasuraman et al. (1985) SERVQUAL model which consists of five dimensions of service quality: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. To explore the potential service quality factors influencing customer satisfaction and loyalty, we performed two multiple regression analyses, using respectively customer satisfaction (perceived) and customer loyalty (perceived) as the dependent variables. The five dimensions of the service quality: 'Tangible' (X1), 'Reliability' (X2), 'Responsiveness' (X3), 'Assurance' (X4) and 'Empathy' (X5) were used as the independent variables.

In these models, we entered the five perceived service quality dimensions as the independent variables, and customer satisfaction, customer loyalty as the dependent variables. The results indicated that there is a significant impact of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. This is in line with the findings from other studies (Ali et al., 2021; Chand, 2010; Malik et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2015; Thi et al., 2020).

Findings highlighted there is a significant difference in customer satisfaction between Velipoja and Ulcinj, and also there is a significant difference in customer loyalty between two destinations.

4. Conclusions

This study proves that Parasuraman et al. (1985) SERVQUAL model is still a good model to evaluate the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in the hotel industry (Ali et al., 2021; Malik et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2015; Thi et al., 2020).

The results indicated that there is a significant impact of service quality dimensions on tourist satisfaction and tourist loyalty. Managers must be careful, and more emphasis should be put on the behavioural aspects of the employees in regards to customers in order to achieve the desired levels of satisfaction.

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Sustainable Development, Competitiveness and Challenges in Albanian Tourism Industry

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Abstract

Tourism is a growing sector in the last year especially in developing countries. Tourism provides optimal conditions for economic growth and employment. Tourism is an increasingly important source of revenue and driver of growth in many countries in south-eastern Europe (SEE). Receipts from international tourist arrivals account for more than 10 per cent of GDP in several countries in SEE, with a substantial upward trend in recent years (before pandemic). In light of the security risks in other popular markets, SEE can expect to see further rises in tourism in the coming years, which would help consolidate the economic recovery under way in the region. However, a recent World Economic Forum report on competitiveness in the travel and tourism industry highlights important shortcomings associated with weak price competitiveness, a problematic business environment, inadequate infrastructure and low prioritization of tourism industry. Addressing these problems would help the SEE region come closer to achieving its full potential in this important industry. This paper aims to explore the competitiveness in SSE and how Albania must face it. It tries to identify the problems in SSE and Albania too; it is the first step to create a picture on the potential of tourism development in Albania, SWOT analysis and strategies for a sustainable tourism. For this purpose, after a wide literature review, and a comparative analysis of South-eastern Europe countries, it has been conducted some half-structured interviews with experts from the main Hotels in Albania. The analysis identifies as main fields that require attention: the lack of large capital investment in sector, the lack of a competitiveness analysis, lack of qualified workforce, poor marketing and promotion in tourism, poor business environment, weak infrastructure at the destination, etc.

Keywords: Tourism, south-eastern Europe, competitiveness, challenges.

Literature review - Tourism and sustainable development

In recent decades, the sustainable development' concept acquired massive consideration in socio-economic and managerial literature. The perception of sustainable development refers to fulfilling the current generation's needs by providing a quality of life without compromising future generations' requirements [1]. The United Nations (UN) General Assembly developed a worldwide agreement of SDGs in 2015 to drive the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development. It comprises all the UN member states to accomplish substantial sustainability identifying 169 targets and 17 goals before 2030 [2]. Amongst these 17 objectives, the 12th objective (SDG 12) demands activities to guarantee sustainable consumption and production designs comprising the executing tools for observing the influences of tourism on sustainable development [3]. For the implementation of SDGs altogether states took some initiatives to achieve the goals of the 2030 agenda, while the tourism sector was the key sector in the 2030 Agenda [2].

Prior studies induce both positive and negative consequences of tourism toward growth. Moreover, tourism promotes the country's economic growth, which assures prosperity and contributes to sustainable development. According to [20], a 1% increase in tourism significantly enhances gross domestic product (GPD) by 0.051%, foreign direct investment by

2.647%, energy development by 0.134%, and agriculture development by 0.26%, and reduces poverty by 0.51% in the long run.

Tourism contribution on world economy

According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) (2011), tourism remains one of the largest industries in the world. In 2011 tourism represented 9% of global GDP at a value of about 6 trillion USD and counted 255 million employees.

Tourism can play a dynamic role in the economic growth of developing as compared to developed nations [21]. Tourism development is viewed as an instrument of employment generation and income [25]. Tourism enhances foreign exchange earnings through commodities trade and importing of capital goods, required services, and manufacturing segments of an economy [22]. The trends suggest three types of economic impact of tourism development: direct, indirect, and induced [23].

Tourism in South-Eastern Europe

Tourism is an important source of economy in South-Eastern Europe. If we refer to the data (Figure 4) 5 countries have a ratio of revenues to GDP greater than 10%. This means that Montenegro, Croatia, Albania, Cyprus and Greece have a very high economic dependence on tourism. We can also say that this industry is a very important source of employment. These countries attract a large number of tourists in the summer holidays and revenues after 2010 have increased significantly, especially for Greece and Croatia, which are benefiting from the political unrest in the countries of Southern Europe. There is no data for Kosovo.

Figure 4: Receipt from tourism in relation to GDP

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators.

The countries of South-Eastern Europe face problems in terms of competitiveness in the tourism sector. Their competitiveness can be identified by referring to the World Economic Forum's (WEF) Travel and Tourism (T&T) Competitiveness Index 2019 (Table 3). According to the report, we can say that all the countries of South-Eastern Europe perform worse than other countries in the Mediterranean Sea, such as Spain, France, Italy or Portugal.

According to the World Economic Forum, these countries have some serious problems as an obstacle to increasing their competitiveness.

Table 3: Competitiveness index 2019

The Travel & Tourism Competitiveness Index 2019 Ranking of 140 economy		GRE	CRO	BUL	CYP	ROM	MNE	MKD	SRB	ALB	B&H
		25	27	45	44	56	67	101	83	86	105
Enabling Environment	Business Environment	119	123	66	33	76	58	84	74	109	134
	Safety and Security	61	35	93	33	29	64	95	71	47	76
	Health and Hygiene	13	22	5	54	36	48	42	26	74	59
	Human Resources and Labour Market	59	103	68	28	73	51	108	58	31	106
	ICT Readiness	51	54	53	21	55	52	70	56	69	77
Travel & Tourism Policy and Enabling Conditions	Prioritization of Travel & Tourism	13	57	67	3	101	52	114	109	43	104
	International openness	32	27	49	54	46	115	119	71	116	117
	Price Competitiveness	111	97	44	114	51	47	26	67	89	70
	Environmental Sustainability	37	14	19	111	48	26	132	40	62	65
Infrastructure	Air Transport Infrastructure	18	44	73	41	72	60	89	76	105	110
	Ground and Port Infrastructure	49	47	76	32	83	67	104	85	81	118
	Tourist Service Infrastructure	18	5	12	21	54	24	80	77	73	76
Natural and Cultural Resources	Natural Resources	45	20	40	97	56	79	122	127	72	132
	Cultural Resources and Business Travel	21	32	48	69	44	130	96	67	118	87

Source: World Economic Forum; T&T Competitiveness Report 2019

Note: Data is taken from the ranking of 136 economies, where 1 represents the most competitive economy and 136 the least competitive.

Tourism in Albania and challenges

From the data collected through interviews and the interpretation of the Competitiveness Index, tourism in Albania faces these challenges:

- a) Labor shortages (reskilling and upskilling)
- b) Weak infrastructure at the destination
- c) Informality
- d) Undiversified market and seasonality
- e) Lack of marketing and promotion of these destinations
- f) Poor use of Information Technology (digital transformation)
- g) Lack of a SWOT analysis and vision regarding the development of the industry (Collect data and promote data-driven decision-making)

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Agrotourism in the Elbasan District: Implications and Development Effects in the Local Context

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Abstract

Agrotourism is an important sector that connects the agricultural economy with tourism, and in recent years, it has been gaining the attention of tourism ministries in many countries.

Over the past two decades, the contribution of Albania's tourism and travel sector to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has increased to more than 8%, creating jobs and generating 38% of total exports.

According to INSTAT, from January 2023 to October, around 9 million foreign tourists have visited Albania. Agrotourism, as a significant sector of the agricultural economy, has seen significant developments in recent years due to investments by the Albanian government and international institutions such as the European Union, the World Bank, and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development.

The purpose of this work is to determine the overall impact of agrotourism development and specifically how this form of tourism has affected the economy of the Elbasan District and the impact of opening agribusinesses in this area.

The research method used in the study is the qualitative method of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. Qualitative research in the study is built on the basis of the case study research strategy. The case at the core of the research is the agribusinesses operating in the Elbasan District, which is one of the areas with considerable potential for agrotourism development.

According to the study results, agrotourism has had positive effects on the Elbasan District, increasing the income of the residents of this area, improving their well-being, and reducing the level of emigration and migration. It has also contributed to the development of the education system. Creating synergies with current projects and initiatives in the agrotourism sector would be important for establishing a connection between agrotourism and the younger generation. It is recommended to conduct awareness campaigns combined with activities that enhance the capacities of interested age groups regarding the sector's potential for investment.

Key Words: Agrotourism, Elbasan District, Implications, Development Effects

1. Introduction

The fall of the communist regime in Albania brought about the recognition of tourism as a lucrative industry for the country's economy. Favorable climatic conditions, geographical position, rich nature, traditions and culture, and history—all these factors together have led to a year-on-year increase in the number of tourists and consequently economic growth. In the times we are talking about, tourism has been given more importance than ever before, due to its potential as an industry.

Looking back, we understand that tourism is the branch of the future, but its full potential is not yet fully exploited. In the year 2023, we see progress where we are no longer talking only about 325 days of sunshine, coastal areas, or seasonal tourism, but also about agritourism, sustainability, 365 days a year, and the exploitation of the full potential of tourism in all its aspects.

I chose to focus on agritourism as a topic because Albania is an agricultural country with an extraordinary geographical location, breathtaking landscapes, and a rich culinary and gastronomic heritage. Interwoven with the beautiful tradition of hospitality, Albania offers great potential for the development of agritourism. While this sector has only started to develop in recent years, it is expected to grow rapidly in the near and medium-term future. The untapped potential for the development of agritourism exists almost throughout the entire country.

Seeing the potential that agritourism has, as part of sustainable tourism development, the government is increasingly paying attention both financially and through strategies and policies to enable agritourism to develop throughout the territory of Albania.

2. Methodology

In the methodology chapter, the research methods used for conducting the study are presented and explained in a clear and detailed manner. This chapter acquaints us with the reasons for designing the study, the research method employed, the procedures for data collection and analysis, the instrument used, subject selection criteria, data reliability and validity, as well as ethical considerations.

2.1. *Historical Background and Design of the Scientific Research*

The first phase of the research focused on literature review. In this phase, the researcher concentrated on finding similar scientific research, documents, articles, and scientific journals that support the study's topic.

In the second phase, the research objectives, objectives, and research questions discussed with the supervising pedagogue were determined.

During the third phase, together with the supervising pedagogue, a qualitative research method was determined, and the main instrument, a semi-structured interview, was conducted with four agribusinesses in the Elbasan District.

The final phase of the study consists of drawing general conclusions and recommendations for responsible institutions and for further research.

Regarding the reason for conducting this research, it is related to the fact that agrotourism has become one of the most discussed topics, receiving increasing attention from the government due to its potential. The qualitative research aimed to provide real insights into the impacts of agrotourism development in the specific area of Elbasan.

2.2. *Research Method Used*

The research method employed in this study is the qualitative method of collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data.

According to Corbin and Strauss (2008), qualitative research can be described as an effective model in the social environment. Qualitative research was chosen as it offers in-depth and detailed insights into the exploration of subjects, considering the study's interest in both the

economic and social impacts of agrotourism development in the relevant municipalities, based on the perceptions and descriptions of individuals who have chosen to start their business in this sector. The use of qualitative methods helped build a deep understanding of specific issues examined, based on a relatively small number of subjects involved in the study.

Qualitative research in the study is based on a case study research strategy. The case at the core of this research is agribusinesses mainly operating in the Elbasan and Belsh municipalities. The qualitative research includes data collection, analysis, and interpretation to delve into a specific phenomenon of interest.

3. Results and Discussion

Development of awareness campaigns combined with capacity-building activities for relevant interest groups regarding the potentials of the sector for investments.

- Activities in the agrotourism sector, bringing together various interest groups, would serve for potential agrotourism entrepreneurs to understand the financing criteria.
- Facilitating public and private dialogue by focusing on awareness campaigns for what makes rural areas attractive and national promotional strategies for agrotourism, etc.

4. Conclusions

- Agrotourism is an important sector that links agricultural economy with tourism, and in recent years, it has been gaining attention from the tourism ministries of many countries.
- The Albanian government, recognizing the potential of agrotourism as a branch of rural tourism, has implemented various policies and strategies to encourage its development.
- One of the study's conclusions was that despite the measures and policies undertaken by the government, there is much room for improvement in agrotourism in the Elbasan District.
- Agrotourism has its impacts on the areas where it develops, and the study's results indicated that the majority of these impacts were positive, leading to increased income for local residents, resulting in improved well-being, reduced emigration and migration, educational development, market availability for agricultural and livestock products, etc.

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Factors Affecting Employee Turnover: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

The biggest challenge facing organizations today is not only how to manage their human resources, but also how to prevent their turnover. This article aims to conduct a systematic literature review in international journals on the various theoretical factors that influence employee turnover. The literature review shows that the concept of employee turnover has been an issue for organizations since the beginning of the 20th century. A company must consider individual, organizational, and environmental factors to retain its employees. Recent research has identified job satisfaction, organizational commitment, justice, job embeddedness, and work environment as predictors of employee turnover.

Keywords: employee turnover, factors, literature review, commitment, justice, job satisfaction.

JEL codes: J63, L21, O15

1. Introduction

Turnover is the rotation of employees in the labor market, between companies and occupations, and between their employment status (Abbasi & Hollman, 2000). High turnover rates of talented employees can weaken an organization, as replacement costs for talented employees are often very high (Hinkin & Tracey, 2000) and the motivation and morale of remaining employees can also be affected (Ristia & Wikansari, 2016). To ensure an acceptable level of turnover, companies need to consider several factors that lead to this phenomenon.

This study aims to answer the following research questions: What is the current situation in the research literature on employee turnover? And what factors trigger and influence employee turnover?

2. Methodology

A systematic literature review was chosen as a method to clarify and focus on employee turnover and to broaden the knowledge base for further studies. A bibliographic analysis of 45 articles published in Scopus up to July 2023 on the topic of employee turnover was conducted to clarify the causes and provide suggestions for further studies in the future. The data generated was used to evaluate the key findings and identify recommendations and suggestions for further research.

3. Result and Discussion

Employee turnover is a growing problem for organizations and has attracted the attention of many researchers (Griffeth, Hom, Peter, & Gaertner, 2000). The number of empirical studies on the causes and consequences of employee turnover has increased considerably. However, it has been shown that numerous push and pull factors influence employee turnover.

Job and Pay satisfaction and Employee Turnover

Several studies have found that there is a significant relationship between job satisfaction and salary and turnover intention, even as a mediator variable (Jannat T., Omar, & Nazri, 2020);

(Colquitt, Scott, & LePine, 2007); (Vidal et al. 2007); (Nyamubarwa, 2013); (Ramalho et al., 2018).

Organizational Commitment and Employee Turnover

The three components (affective, normative, and continuity) are negatively associated with intended and actual turnover (Wasti, 2002); (Ramalho et al., 2018); (Lapointe et al., 2019); (Ayari A. & AlHamaqi, 2022); Meyer et al. (2022).

Work Environment and Employee Turnover

Employees fit with different aspects of the work environment, such as organization, workplace, and group, which is negatively related to employees' turnover intention (Yu, 2016), and positively related to job satisfaction (Dahling, 2015) and sense of duty (Stazyk, 2011) and motivates employees to work efficiently and effectively (Pawirosumarto et al., 2017).

Organizational Justice and Employee Turnover

A meta-analysis conducted by Cohen-Charash et al. (2001) shows that justice has an impact on employee outcomes such as turnover. Many studies have found a negative relationship between organizational justice and employee turnover (Colquitt J. W., 2001); (Iyigun & Tamer, 2012); (Alkahtani, 2015); (Parker A. & Gerbasi, 2016).

4. Conclusion

The concept of turnover has evolved over the decades, increasing researchers' interest in exploring its causes and resources. Based on the literature review, the study highlights that most scholars have previously considered job satisfaction, organizational justice and commitment, job embeddedness, and environmental factors as dominant factors in employee turnover. However, it seems that turnover intention is still a problem and further research should take into account factors such as leadership and supervision, career planning and development, and green HR practices. This study has some limitations. First, only one database, Scopus, was considered in this study because it is well-known and contains many indexed studies. The study is based on the occurrence of keywords. A more in-depth analysis of these terms would be recommended.

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Comparing ESG Performance on Banking Sector. The case of Albania

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Abstract

Most people agree that proactive, open communication regarding corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental issues are necessary and beneficial. This study analyzes the 11 corporates of the banking sector by looking at the communication of corporate social responsibilities, corporate governance, and environmental issues on their website, in their published reports, for the main reason to evaluate their ESG ratio. In the analysis of this study, a comparison of the ESG ratio was made between the subsidiaries of these banks in Albania and their parent companies who are mostly outside the borders of Albania. Some of the banks in the analysis were banks that operate only in the Albanian territory, for them is done a comparison was made between them and the subsidiaries that have foreign parents' companies. None of the Albanian banks has an ESG ratio published on their website and to address the hypothesis, the author looked at the corporate's web sites and their annual reports for public information of ESG. The methodology used in this research is based on secondary data collected and based on S&P methodology for a calculation of ESG rating for each bank in Albania.

The study shows that there are remarkably few businesses with CSR and environmental information on their websites, and that they are not very much engaged in social and environmental issues. The findings states that there are big differences in the fulfillment of the principles of Environmental, Social and Governance between the parent companies and their subordinates and there are fewer differences between foreign bank subsidiaries and those that operate only in Albania. Communicating and performing of the three pillars of the ESG is crucial for organizations in engaging their stakeholders, building brand reputation, increasing competitiveness, financial performance and to contribute to a sustainable future.

Keywords: ESG; CSR; Rating Agencies; corporate performance; financial sector.

JEL codes: G24, G32, G34, M14,

1. Introduction

The terms "corporate social responsibility" (CSR) and "sustainability" have evolved simultaneously. The term "ESG" first appeared in the financial industry in 2004. In fact, the definition of sustainable finance is "the process of considering ESG when making financial sector investment decisions, leading to more long-term investments in sustainable economic activities and projects."¹

The literature on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) issues has witnessed substantial growth, reflecting the increasing importance of sustainability considerations in the corporate and investment landscape. Scholars and researchers have explored various dimensions of ESG, investigating its impact on financial performance, corporate behavior, and stakeholder value. Numerous studies have attempted to establish a link between ESG practices and financial outcomes, with some suggesting a positive correlation between strong ESG performance and long-term financial success (Aydoğmuş.M. 2022). Furthermore, there is a growing body of literature addressing the challenges and limitations associated with ESG

¹ https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/overview-sustainable-finance_en

measurement, reporting, and standardization. As the field continues to evolve, research on the implications of ESG for various stakeholders, including investors, companies, and society at large, remains a dynamic and critical area of inquiry. Overall, the literature reflects the multifaceted nature of ESG considerations and their significance in shaping business practices and investment strategies in the contemporary global context.

According to Eccles et al. (2020) and Matos (2020), Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) elements are a group of variables that have the potential to significantly impact a company's operations and value generation.

Despite being widely recognized as the foundation of investment analysis and decision-making, it is still unclear what exactly qualifies as a meaningful ESG component (Eccles et al., 2020). The term "materiality," which describes the issues that are significant for a company or business sector because they can have a significant impact on corporate financial and economic performance, reputations, and relationships with internal and external stakeholders, is used in the financial markets to describe ESG relevance (Jebe, 2019).

EU regulations have also shown a strong commitment to preventing situations of "greenwashing²." To prevent greenwashing in the financial market, the EU has launched numerous initiatives to try and eradicate this major issue. For instance, the European Green Deal states that "companies making "green claims" should substantiate these against a standard methodology to assess their impact on the environment and that the Commission will step up its regulatory and non-regulatory efforts to tackle false green claims" (European Commission, 2019b). The goal is to give businesses, financiers, and decision-makers precise and suitable descriptions of the kinds of economic activity that are environmentally sustainable. To prevent greenwashing, assist businesses in becoming more climate-friendly, reduce market fragmentation, and assist in reallocating investments where they are required, this transparency is crucial (European Commission, 2022c).

ESG market evolution: The main rating agencies

The ESG rating market has undergone significant growth and transformation in the past thirteen years, witnessing a surge in the number of rating agencies entering the scene, but also experiencing the disappearance of some. This evolving landscape has led to a concentration in the sector, marked by increasing partnerships, mergers, and acquisitions among rating agencies and data providers. The dominant players in today's ESG rating market are seven major clusters of international financial rating agencies, including Moody's ESG Solutions, Bloomberg, London Stock Exchange Group (LSEG), Morningstar Group, MSCI, Standard & Poor's (S&P), and Deutsche Börse. These agencies have expanded their influence through mergers, acquisitions, and partnerships, shifting the market focus from specialized research agencies to mainstream financial services entities that cater to responsible, ethical, and sustainable investors. A summary of the major mergers and acquisitions during the previous few decades, up until the market for ESG ratings were concentrated into seven sizable rating clusters, is shown in Figure 1.

From the review of the literature and from the exploration of international corporations, we noticed that all the corporates had ESG ratios published on an annual basis.

The purpose of this study was to analyze and compare corporate subsidiaries in the banking sector with their mothers in relation to ESG rating. During the investigation, it was noticed that none of the companies operating in the Albanian territory had an ESG rating, for this reason it was necessary to make a close assessment of the ESG rating based on the methodology of the

² Greenwashing is the act of making false or misleading statements about the environmental benefits of a product or practice.

S&P rating agency, since the methodology is public, and is one of 7 international rating agency, and the foreign members of our companies are rated by this agency.

Various scientific researchers and the European Union have determined that not only the company must have a good corporate governance, social and environmental approach, but this index must be measurable and comparable with other corporations in order to create value for the corporation both financially and reputationally.

After reviewing the literature and analyzing of annual reports, the following two hypotheses were raised for this study purpose:

Hypothesis 1: ESG ratings are higher in parent companies than in their subsidiaries in Albania.

Hypothesis 2: ESG rating is higher in companies that have foreign mother companies than in companies that operates only in Albanian.

2. Methodology

To conduct this research, we used secondary data. At the beginning, the author get access from the S&P rating agency to use their methodology for scientific research. Secondly, is obtain ownership structure information from the Albanian Association of Bank (AAB) and all the other reports, that are public.³

Thirdly, the reports of these banks on CRS and environmental issues were conducted in order to evaluate the ESG rating for each of these. Here we have used the public reports on the official website of the banking association, their annual reports, and the respective websites of the companies to see their ESG publications.

After collecting all possible data, ESG methodology according to S&P agency rating was used to evaluate the ratings of these banks. Below is the explanation on the basis of which criteria the ESG rate is evaluated for each corporation.

S&P Global ESG Scores

The S&P Global ESG Scores⁴ are expressed as a number between 0 and 100, with 100 indicating the highest possible score. The ESG ratio is calculated as a weighted aggregate of the entity's based on the sector of the corporates, for example in banking sector the weighted ratios are for environmental (16%), social (33%) and governance (51%) scores. A score ranging from zero to 100 is provided to each ESG category.

$$SPESG = \Sigma (((SPQP * SPQW) * SPCW) * SPDW)^5$$

Where:

SPESG = S&P Global ESG Score

SPQP = Question Points⁶

SPQW = Question Weight

SPCW = Criteria Weight

SPDW = Dimension Weight

Source: S&P Global⁷

S&P Global Dimension and Criteria Weights - 2023 Banking Sector⁸

³ <https://aab.al/en/rreth-nesh/statistika/te-dhena/>

⁴ https://portal.s1.spglobal.com/survey/documents/CSA_Weights.pdf

⁵ S&P Global ESG Scores Methodology

⁶ S&P Global ESG Score Weight Breakdown by Environmental Dimension ('D'), Environmental Criteria ('C'), and Environmental Question ('Q') Score Weights

⁷ <https://www.spglobal.com/esg/csa/getting-an-assessment>

⁸ Weights Overview Corporate Sustainability Assessment 2022

S&P Global CSA Criteria Weights by Dimension ⁹	Banks
Environmental Dimension	16
Social Dimension	33
Governance & Economic Dimension	51

Sources: S&P Global ESG Scores Methodology

3. Results and Discussion

The term "ESG" ratio describes how environmental, social, and governance aspects are taken into account in the banking sector. It entails assessing how activities and investments affect society, the environment, and corporate governance standards. According to this research each pillar of ESG, in the comparison of the subsidiaries and the parent company are very far, there are also some differences between the banks within Albania. In the conclusion both hypotheses raised in this study are verified.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the study has revealed differences in ESG performance between parent companies and subsidiaries in the banking sector operating in Albania. While certain areas show alignment, such as governance issues, disparities exist in social and environmental issues. These findings underscore the importance of tailoring ESG strategies to the unique socio-economic contexts. The recommendation to this research is to increase the ESG practices in the subordinates in Albania but not even them but in the whole banking sector, to foster greater collaboration and innovation in sustainable banking practices.

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⁹ https://portal.s1.spglobal.com/survey/documents/CSA_Weights.pdf

Green Erasmus: Fostering Environmental Awareness in Academic Mobility

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Abstract

This academic article explores the pivotal role of environmental awareness in the context of academic mobility, with a specific focus on the Erasmus+ Program. As global educational exchanges continue to rise, so does the ecological footprint associated with student and faculty mobility. Recognizing the urgency of addressing climate change and sustainability, this study investigates the potential of integrating green practices into academic mobility to foster environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students. The research employs a multi-faceted approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to assess the impact of the Erasmus+ Program on the environment and examine current environmental awareness levels among Erasmus+ participants. Findings reveal a pressing need for enhanced sustainability education and eco-friendly initiatives within the program. Moreover, the article proposes a comprehensive framework inspired by the concept of Green Erasmus and designed to foster environmental consciousness in academic mobility.

Keywords: Green Erasmus, environmental awareness, academic mobility, Erasmus+ Program

JEL codes:

1. Introduction

Due to the escalating global environmental challenges that threaten the delicate balance of the planet Earth, there has never been a greater need for raising environmental awareness, which is particularly pronounced in the context of academic mobility. The rising numbers of carbon emissions associated with the Erasmus+ Program underscores the necessity for sustainable practices within academic mobility frameworks. The scope of this work encompasses the introduction of the Green Erasmus project and the GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus Project as a model for fostering environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students, and an evaluation employing both quantitative and qualitative methods. In the existing body of literature, the impact of academic mobility on the environment has been acknowledged, the importance of fostering environmental awareness was emphasized, and sustainable practices were conceptualized. The final objective is to delineate the role of the Green Erasmus Project in decreasing the negative impact of the Erasmus+ Program and develop a framework for fostering environmental awareness in academic mobility. This research aims to contribute to the existing literature, offering insights into the effective fostering of environmental awareness within academic mobility programs.

2. Methodology

Impact of Erasmus+ Academic Mobility on the Environment:

Since the kick-off of the Erasmus+ Program in 1987, it has engaged 11 million students and staff members by the year 2020, facilitating a more integrated and inclusive Europe and leveling study abroad opportunities for students worldwide, bridging social disparities by offering scholarships. Nevertheless, this important achievement has been accompanied by an unintended consequence: a notable rise in air traffic and other negative sustainability impacts.

For instance, the Erasmus+ academic mobility produced 379,701 t-CO₂-eq in 2016 and 421,433 t-CO₂-eq in 2017. Since then, the amount of Erasmus+ academic mobilities has been rising and reached 1.2 million participants in 2022, which could potentially produce 504,000 t-CO₂-eq (calculation with emissions per mobility in 2017).¹

The Erasmus+ Program, because of its significant and positive influence on the social aspect of sustainability, should continue. However, it is crucial to recognize and address its negative environmental impact. Flying stands out as the primary contributor to carbon dioxide emissions associated with the program, and various strategies have been proposed by initiatives such as "Erasmus Goes Green" and "Erasmus by Train" to address this issue. While In-Europe mobilities can be changed to land-based options, such a transition is impossible for mobilities worldwide (Erasmus+ Programs). This paper proposes fostering environmental awareness in academic mobility as a fundamental and most importantly, universal way to reduce the negative environmental impact of the Erasmus+ program.

Environmental Awareness among Erasmus+ Students

From the 9th of March 2021 to the 16th of June 2021, the Green Erasmus Project conducted the online survey that was aimed at students who participated in an Erasmus exchange between 2018 and 2020 - 7.776 students were eventually involved in the analysis of the habits of Erasmus students. The survey investigated the criteria and motives behind the choices of Erasmus students regarding travel and daily life habits and the relation of their actions to their beliefs and attitudes related to climate change and environmental issues. According to this survey, 93,8% of students stated that they are concerned about climate change. Furthermore, the survey showed that 77% of students believed that people impact climate change and 79,2% believed that individuals need to be responsible for taking action to combat climate change. However, the final findings of the survey also showcased that neither the high level of concern about environmental issues nor the acknowledgment of human responsibility in this matter promises environmental awareness based on knowledge and commitment to necessary actions².

The phenomenon mentioned above was also seen during the original study - observation of small Erasmus+ student groups during their academic mobility at RheinAhrCampus, Koblenz University of Applied Sciences. The live observation was conducted over four study semesters (2022-2023) and aimed at four different Erasmus+ student groups (14 students in average). Within the Orientation Week Program that distinguishes the very beginning of their five-month-long Erasmus academic mobility in Germany, around 86% of students acknowledged the importance of individual environmental responsibility. However, at the same time, 93% of students chose flying over other more eco-friendly transportation options, and most importantly, 100% of the students did not know what impact their travel had on environmental sustainability regarding CO₂ emissions. Similarly, the lack of knowledge about the environmental impact of food consumption and daily lifestyle habits on the individual level was observed among the student groups. The finding of this original study showed that the lack of knowledge on this topic greatly limits students' reflection and commitment to this topic, which results in a low level of environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students and amplifies the need for an efficient framework to foster it.

¹ Finnish National Agency for Education (2021). Feasibility study on compensation scenarios for the new and greener Erasmus+ Programme 2021–2027. Access link: https://www.oph.fi/sites/default/files/documents/Feasibility_Study_Compensation_ErasmusPlus.pdf

² Green Erasmus (2022). Research on the habits of Erasmus students: consumer, daily life, and travel habits of Erasmus students from the perspective of their environmental attitudes and beliefs. Brussels, Belgium: Green Erasmus Partnerships. Access link: <https://project.greenerasmus.org/documents/GE-report.pdf>

Green Erasmus Project for Fostering Environmental Awareness in Academic Mobility

Introduction to Green Erasmus

The Green Erasmus Project is coordinated by a partnership between Erasmus Student Network (ESN), European University Foundation (EUF), European Students' Union (ESU), Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Technische Hochschule Köln (TH Köln), and Students Organizing for Sustainability UK (SOS UK) and is supported by the European Commission. The project aims:

1. To decrease the negative impact of the Erasmus+ Programme on environmental sustainability.
2. To raise awareness across the European higher education sector about the importance of sustainable internationalization.
3. To empower student organizations to be the agents of change, pushing for improvements on the topic of environmental sustainability³.

The GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus Project⁴

The Green Erasmus Concept has been spreading fast since it was created and has inspired many universities worldwide to start their own initiatives, such as the GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus Project that was started by the team of Languages and International Affairs of RheinAhrCampus in 2019. With the motto “Exchange for a Green Future”, the project group aims to develop new green sustainable practices, exchange them with partner universities, and, therefore, empower students worldwide to live and act sustainably. Over the years, GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus initiated many activities and projects for fostering environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students. These include regular activities such as giving workshops on Sustainability (e.g. “From Global to Local: Sustainable Insights into Your New Neighborhood”, “Improve Your Personal Ecological Footprint”), joining local clean-up actions, holding Clothes Swap Events, organizing excursions to local sustainable organizations (e.g. Plastic-free shop “Unverpackt Remagen”, Market Garden “Kukurudza”, Urban Garden in Andernach), and time-framed projects such as creating the “GreenMap of Remagen” and organizing the “GreenChallenge”.

3. Results and Discussion

The key findings of this work are that the level of environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students remain low and there is a need for an efficient framework for fostering environmental awareness in academic mobility. Based on the research of Green Erasmus Educational Framework⁵ and original work on GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus, a framework for fostering environmental awareness in academic mobility was developed (**Figure 1**). The proposed framework presents three pillars of fostering environmental awareness in academic mobility: Theory, Practice, and Reflection. During the original work on the GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus Project, it was observed that a combination of at least two of these pillars (Theory & Practice, Theory & Reflection, Practice & Reflection) had a positive impact on the environmental awareness of Erasmus students. The combination of all three pillars is, however, the optimal goal of the proposed framework.

³ Green Erasmus website, 2023, What is Green Erasmus, European Commission and European Student Network, assessed 23 November 2023, < <https://project.greenerasmus.org/> >

⁴ GreenErasmus-RheinAhrCampus webpage 2023, GreenErasmus, Koblenz University of Applied Sciences and RheinAhrCampus, assessed 31.11.2023, < <https://www.hs-koblenz.de/rac/international-programs/international-projects-and-events/greenerasmus-rheinahrcampus> >

⁵ Green Erasmus (2023). Higher Education on the journey towards Sustainable Development in curricula. Brussels, Belgium: Green Erasmus Partnerships. Access link: https://project.greenerasmus.org/documents/GE-educational_framework.pdf

Figure 1. Framework for Fostering Environmental Awareness in Academic Mobility

The framework is aimed at helping other universities to develop their own initiatives regarding the enhancement of environmental awareness and to commonly contribute to the goals of the Green Erasmus Project.

4. Conclusions

This research highlights the dual impact of the Erasmus+ Program, an important social achievement in fostering global inclusivity accompanied by a significant environmental footprint. The study exposes a persistent gap in environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students, with concern not translating into sustainable actions. The proposed framework, inspired by the Green Erasmus concept and encompassing Theory, Practice, and Reflection, is recommended as practical guidance for universities. It recognizes that the combination of these pillars positively influences environmental awareness among Erasmus+ students, contributing to decreasing the negative environmental impact of the Erasmus+ Program and fostering a generation of sustainably conscious global citizens. However, it needs to be emphasized that fostering environmental awareness is just one of the many challenging steps on the way to eco-balance the Erasmus+ Program, and this complex process requires ongoing commitment on other institutional levels and innovative solutions.

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Entrepreneurial Education and Green Entrepreneurship Intention

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Abstract

Environmental protection is receiving increasing attention from universities around the world, and green entrepreneurship is considered as a solution to the challenges of sustainable development especially in developing countries. In Albania, apart from some government associations and donors, there is little awareness in the public about green enterprises and this concept is often unclear.

The aim of the study is to understand the factors shaping green entrepreneurial intentions. Using the theory of planned behavior and examining other internal and external influencing factors, the focus will be green entrepreneurship intention as a comparison between economic and non-economic students. Especially this study tests the changes that students of different study programs may have in their green entrepreneurship intention.

For this, a survey was applied for undergraduate students at the University of Tirana at the Faculty of Economics, Social Sciences Faculty, and Polytechnic University. By performing multiple regression analysis, the results show that there are significant differences between students who have entrepreneurship knowledge and those who do not have entrepreneurship knowledge in their curricula.

Keywords: green entrepreneurship, intention, theory of planned behavior, entrepreneurship education, awareness, sustainability

JEL codes: M24, M13, Q56, Q57

1. Introduction

Knowing the role that entrepreneurship has in the economic development of a country and especially in developing countries, more and more attention is being paid to strengthening the intention to start new businesses. The development of enterprises that also take into account the protection of the environment is receiving more and more attention nowadays, where climate changes and the lack of natural resources are more evident. The Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations call for businesses to pursue a balance of environmental, economic, and social value creation (also known as sustainable entrepreneurship). It is suggested that preventative measures are one of the most cost-effective ways to avoid global disasters (Ndofirepi, 2022) Regulators and politicians will be increasingly encouraged to support the collection of objective data on business performance in sustainable process and product redesign and habitat protection.

Entrepreneurial education includes courses on developing skills in leadership, negotiating, new product creation, creative thinking, exposure to technological innovation, understanding of the entrepreneurial profession, and other skills to shape the future generation of entrepreneurs (Kuratko, 2005)

According to empirical studies, students who participate in entrepreneurship education programs have significantly different attitudes and intentions than those who do not. (Fayolle & Liñán, 2014). Some authors also agree that the entrepreneurial education is positively related and can be a predictor of green entrepreneurship intention (Pruett, 2012); (Ahmad et al., 2015).

This study tests whether entrepreneurship programs have an impact on students' entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions and whether entrepreneurship education increases the intention to start a green business.

Entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship knowledge and green entrepreneurship intention

The aim of the entire program of education and training is to instill in participants the desire to engage in entrepreneurial behaviors, or some of the factors that drive that desire, like entrepreneurial knowledge, the appeal of the activity, or its viability (Liñán, 2004)

Entrepreneurship education, which has developed into a tool for policymakers to encourage entrepreneurship and increase people's desire to launch enterprises, is one of the major elements that influences entrepreneurial intentions (Wang et al., 2023). Empirical research indicates that students who take part in entrepreneurship education programs differ significantly from non-participating students in terms of their intention and attitudes (Fayolle & Liñán, 2014). Strengthening scientific knowledge, training, and developing responsible attitudes and behaviors toward the future and sustainable development are all made possible by a university education (Anghel & Anghel, 2022).

More recently, some study has focused on people—their abilities, knowledge, and resources—as well as the creative and exploratory processes that are at the basis of entrepreneurship (Liñán et al., 2011). Knowledge is one of the key elements affecting how behavioral intentions and attitudes develop (Shah et al., 2020). According to research, students are more likely to change their behavior toward the environment if they perceive they have a high level of knowledge (Owojori et al., 2022).

2. Methodology

The target population of the study has been students at the Faculty of Economics and Social Science Faculty, University of Tirana and engineering and architecture students of the Polytechnic University in the third year of bachelor studies. A questionnaire was conducted analyzing the factors that encourage students to start a green entrepreneurship and also to identify if there are differences between students with entrepreneurial education and those without entrepreneurial education.

3. Results and Discussion

Constructs of the questionnaire were built according to what the literature suggests and were tested for internal and external consistency and validity.

4. Conclusions

This study aims to investigate the factors that influence the formation of green entrepreneurship intention among students and if there are significant differences between students with entrepreneurial education and those without entrepreneurial education.

Through the questionnaire carried out with the students of the faculty of economics, in different profiles but who have entrepreneurial education and with students from the Faculty of Social Sciences and the Polytechnic University, it was found that the basic elements of the theory of planned behavior are important factors in green entrepreneurship intention. Also, as the literature suggests, entrepreneurial education is an important factor in these goals

From the empirical results, it is concluded that entrepreneurship education effectively contributes to the development of green entrepreneurship intention. Entrepreneurship education contributes positively to the strengthening of self-efficacy, which leads to the development of green entrepreneurship intention.

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Sustainable Supply Chain Management in the Tourism Sector: Analysing a Leading French Company's Environmental Best Practices

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Abstract

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in Sustainable Green Supply Chain Management, driven by the imperative for environmental sustainability. The tourism industry, as exemplified by Tourism Supply Chain Management (TSCM), plays a pivotal role in this shift. TSCM aims to efficiently manage the tourism supply chain, considering economic, societal, and environmental dimensions. It emphasizes collaboration among stakeholders, including firms, suppliers, and customers, to promote sustainability. Acknowledging emerging climate risks, Accor - a global hospitality leader - has implemented forward-thinking measures, including a charter on healthy and sustainable food and participation in the CDP Supply Chain program, to ensure a climate-resilient supply chain. Accor actively engages suppliers in disclosing climate-related data, contributing to increased transparency and accountability in the supply chain, as evidenced by a 41% response rate in the CDP Supply Chain program in 2022. Accor's sustainable supply chain management practices serve as a benchmark for the hospitality industry, integrating sustainability into core business operations and showcasing a commitment to positive environmental and social impact.

Keywords: supply chain management, sustainable supply chain, eco-tourism, Accor.

JEL codes: L23, Q01, L83

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a notable surge in interest surrounding sustainable green supply chain management, driven by the pressing need for environmental sustainability. This study focuses on Tourism Supply Chain Management (TSCM), which encompasses strategies to efficiently manage tourism operations within specific destinations, aiming to meet customer needs and achieve business objectives. TSCM integrates economic, societal, and environmental dimensions of sustainability and tackles these challenges through collaborative efforts in the supply chain. Emphasizing resource coordination, uncertainty reduction, and sustainable practices, TSCM involves interactions among firms, suppliers, and customers. Collaboration, government support, and the use of information technology play crucial roles in promoting sustainability within the tourism supply chain. The study's objective is to investigate sustainable green supply chain management in the tourism industry, utilizing Accor as a case study. It aims to evaluate Accor's eco-tourism practices, examine Sustainable Supply Chain Management principles, and provide recommendations for enhancing sustainable supply chain practices in tourism, offering valuable insights and best practices for the industry.

2. Methodology

This research employs a comprehensive methodology involving the analysis of Accor's sustainable development practices documented in public periodic reports. After correspondence with the company, the relevant data was accessed through an online platform¹. The study focuses on extracting specific details related to Accor's supply chain management

¹ <https://group.accor.com/en>

practices and how they address sustainable development issues, utilizing a qualitative content analysis approach. The analysis assesses Accor's strategies, policies, and practices related to sustainability, aiming to provide insights into best practices applicable to the Albanian tourism industry, particularly in supply chain management for sustainable development. The selection of Accor is justified based on research objectives, available data, global presence, sustainability reputation, and specific practices. This choice is deemed valuable for exploring lessons applicable to various regions, including Albania, and aligning with the goals and challenges of the Albanian tourism industry. Additionally, a brief comparison with the sustainable tourism index highlights France and Germany's strong dedication to sustainable tourism, showcasing specific regulations and coordinated measures for environmental sustainability within their tourism sectors².

3. Results and Discussion

Accor is a French multinational hospitality group with a significant presence in 110 countries, comprising 5,400 hotels and 10,000 food and beverage venues³. Accor, aligning with its sustainable development trajectory, launched a new strategy in 2022, shaping its actions until 2030. Rooted in the pillars of "stay, eat, and explore" and emphasizing people and nature, this strategy is a fundamental aspect of the Group's broader business strategy, building on its commitment to positive hospitality since 1970. Informed by previous programs like Planet 21 and Acting Here – Planet 21 (2011-2021), the strategy incorporates lessons learned and achievements, guided by strategic research, including materiality analysis and environmental footprint assessments. Accor's carbon target trajectory is in line with the Paris Agreement's 1.5°C goal, validated by the Science-Based Targets initiative, with a commitment to achieving net-zero emissions by 2050. Focusing on people-centric initiatives, Accor drives transformative efforts through a comprehensive approach, with three operational pillars addressing the entire hotel journey. These pillars, spanning from conceptualization and design to seamless operations, shape the guest experience. The operational strategy centers on three priorities: designing low-energy buildings with low-carbon materials, measuring energy consumption for targeted improvements, and actively sourcing green energy while exploring on-site energy generation opportunities.

Accor is actively committed to sustainability, as evidenced by its Paris corporate headquarters being powered entirely by renewable sources. The company demonstrates a strong dedication to environmental responsibility, particularly in the elimination of single-use plastics. By the end of 2022, 84% of Accor's hotels successfully removed 46 types of single-use plastics from the guest experience, with innovative alternatives like replacing single doses with dispensers, resulting in a substantial annual reduction of over 300 tons of plastics. In addition to reducing plastic use, Accor prioritizes sustainable and local sourcing through its online purchasing platform, Astore Shop. The company fosters ongoing dialogue with a diverse network of suppliers, promoting local procurement, especially in Food & Beverage. With over three-quarters of its suppliers in France being small or very small structures, Accor strengthens local ties and minimizes environmental impact by sourcing closer to hotels. This commitment aligns with the Sustainable Food Charter, emphasizing seasonal sourcing, organic products, and responsible practices in animal welfare and fishing.

Accor is actively engaged in sustainable practices, prioritizing local suppliers and implementing initiatives like urban gardens at over 1,000 hotels, contributing to better building

² Sustainable Tourism Index. The Economist, https://impact.economist.com/perspectives/sites/default/files/Sustainable_Tourism_Index.pdf, Accessed October 29, 2023.

³ Accor. (2023). Accor Climate Change 2023 Report. Retrieved from: <https://group.accor.com/en/commitment/approach/milestones>.

heat insulation. Some establishments even feature roof gardens. The company invests in innovative techniques, such as Aquaponics, to conserve water, space, and soil. Accor places a significant emphasis on animal welfare, particularly endorsing responsible fishing practices. Additionally, Mövenpick Hotel Zürich Regensdorf, under Accor, collaborates with the Too Good to Go app to reduce food waste by converting unserved food into discounted meals. Simultaneously, Mövenpick Resort Kuredhivaru Maldives showcases innovation by launching a soil-free hydroponics farm, shortening its supply chain and producing 70 kilograms of fresh produce monthly, highlighting Accor's commitment to sustainability, food waste reduction, and local sourcing⁴.

4. Conclusions

The research underscores the escalating interest in sustainable green supply chain management within the tourism industry, driven by the global imperative for environmental sustainability. Tourism Supply Chain Management (TSCM) emerges as a crucial framework for addressing sustainability across economic, societal, and environmental dimensions. Despite challenges faced by companies in balancing customer satisfaction and sustainability requirements, Accor's sustainable supply chain management practices offer valuable lessons for fostering a more sustainable and resilient future. The company's commitment to reducing environmental impact, promoting local sourcing, and implementing waste reduction strategies could inspire similar initiatives in Albania's growing tourism sector. Emphasizing collaboration with local suppliers, minimizing single-use plastics, and participating in global sustainability programs align with international best practices. The literature review underscores the significance of strategic partnerships and sourcing activities for a competitive edge in tourism sustainable supply chain management, emphasizing the need for further research to comprehend and address system-wide shortcomings. However, the study's limitations, including reliance on a single case study, suggest the importance of conducting multiple case studies for a broader understanding of sustainable supply chain practices across diverse contexts within the tourism industry.

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⁴Accor. (2022, September). Brands as Vanguard of a Sustainable Hospitality Experience. Retrieved from <https://group.accor.com/en/Actualites/2022/09/brands-vanguard-sustainable-hospitality-experience>

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Participation as a Key Success Factor for Sustainable Destination Development. The Innovative Approach of “Silent Dialogue”

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Abstract

Triggered by exceeding the limits of socially acceptable tourism development, the importance of participatory planning and decision-making approaches in tourism has gained in importance in recent years. Serving the objective of sustainable development of tourism destinations that are simultaneously the living spaces of local inhabitants, participation is regarded as an opportunity to empower local inhabitants, to incorporate their legitimate needs into tourism planning objectives, and to increase the acceptance of tourism as such. However, the implementation is fraught with many difficulties, including awareness raising, activation, knowledge transfer, organisational effort, and lack of resources, leading to either not developed or underdeveloped participatory approaches in tourism.

The conceptual article outlines how a structured exchange process – the so-called “silent dialogue” – between local inhabitants and planning authorities can be organised on the basis of semi-automatically generated questions. Both groups generate questions through their cognitive operations and both groups are recipients of information from the other partner group. New questions are created during the interview process which can subsequently be passed on to new respondents. In this way, a cyclical organisation of the information flow between the stakeholder groups is ensured and a mutual learning process is continued as long as the communication paths between the stakeholder groups are maintained in both directions. Accordingly, the silent dialogue is argued to be a suitable method that can help to solve or mitigate some of the central challenges associated with participatory approaches, thereby contributing to the optimisation and promotion of sustainable destination development.

Keywords: Tourism Acceptance, Overtourism, Participation, Sustainable Development, GABEK.

1. Introduction

Local communities are central actors in the tourism industry, having a crucial role in the creation of attractive tourism products. The destination community provides the tourism industry not only with community assets and public goods but also with hospitality (Haywood, 1988). Tourism acceptance by local communities is therefore a decisive factor for the successful continued development of the industry. In recent years, numerous public protests against the negative impacts of tourism on the quality of life of local communities have arisen. Publicly voiced protests in both urban and rural destinations have reflected a decline in local communities' acceptance of tourism which in turn has been reflective of a growth-oriented system paradigm, viewing visitor numbers as the predominant measure of the success of the tourism industry (Dodds & Butler, 2019).

Following the signs of declining tourism acceptance, participatory tourism planning and decision-making approaches that place the quality of life and well-being of local communities at the centre of tourism development agendas have grown in importance (Becken & Simmons, 2019). From the perspective of participatory destination management, the region is seen as a

unified economic, residential, and living space. Participatory destination management is therefore not only limited to enhancing the economic success of the local tourism industry but also contributes to the improvement of the quality of life of local communities (Steinecke & Herntrei, 2017).

While the importance of public participation in tourism planning has been emphasised by the scientific community for decades (Dangi & Petrick, 2021; Simmons, 1994), in practice, participatory approaches have been proven difficult to implement. Due to numerous institutional, socio-cultural, and logistical factors, the incorporation of public views into planning and decision-making processes is rather rare and remains a daunting task (Erdmenger & Kagermeier, 2021). Moreover, an increasingly recognised view in tourism research is that assessing the (lack of) tourism acceptance by local communities in quantitative terms (e.g. through carrying capacities) is insufficient to effectively capture its complex essence (Benner, 2020). Instead, a qualitative approach is being more strongly emphasised since subjective judgements of local communities are inherent to the process of perceiving and evaluating the impacts of tourism (Herntrei & Jánová, 2023).

Drawing on the qualitative research method “Ganzheitliche Bewältigung von Komplexität” (GABEK®), the conceptual article presents the so-called “silent dialogue” – a structured exchange process between stakeholder groups – and argues that the silent dialogue is a suitable method for overcoming or mitigating some of the central barriers to participatory approaches in tourism due to its innovative approach in terms of a cyclical organisation of the information flow between stakeholders.

2. Methodology

The article focuses on the methodological description of the silent dialogue method based on expert interviews analysed with GABEK in the context of a tourism destination confronted with the signs of a lack of tourism acceptance. In doing so, the emphasis is placed on the methodological procedure as such, not on the respective tourism acceptance-related findings. GABEK – arising from the process of creative self-organisation (GABEK, 2023; Zelger, 1988) – is a computer-assisted research method for analysing, organising, processing, and presenting unstructured everyday language. Structuring of everyday language is facilitated by the software “Windows Relation Analysis” (WinRelan®) designed for GABEK applications, enabling a comprehensive understanding of complex social phenomena, including tourism. Using GABEK, the in-depth structure of verbally expressed opinions can be analysed and common core values, objectives, and possible measures can be made visible (Zelger, 1994, 1999, 2019). The process of data analysis according to GABEK is carried out in the following steps:

- 1) Basic coding (division of transcribed interviews into sense units, identification of lexical key concepts, development of a semantic indexing system, retrieval of an expression list, creation of association graphs);
- 2) Evaluation coding (of both the situation assumed to be real (“situation-as-is”) and the situation not assumed to be real (“should-situation”) as perceived by interview partners, retrieval of evaluation lists, and a balance of evaluations);
- 3) Causal coding (identification of causal opinions within sense units, creation of causal network graphs).

The following paragraphs outline the method of the silent dialogue between different stakeholder groups.

3. Results and Discussion

After having conducted and analysed expert interviews with decision-makers, the answers of decision-makers are used to formulate new questions for citizens regarding tourism development in a destination. While being approached with questions from decision-makers,

also new questions for decision-makers are formulated during the interviews with citizens. Decision-makers are thus subsequently confronted with further questions generated by citizens' answers.

In more general terms, within the framework of the silent dialogue, decision-makers and citizens generate questions through their cognitive operations, the outcomes of each group serve as information for the partner group, and both groups are recipients of information from the other partner group. During the interview process, new questions are created, and these questions can be asked to new respondents during the next round of interviews. This ensures a cyclical organisation of the information flow between the groups of stakeholders and a continuation of the mutual learning process as long as the communication paths between stakeholder groups are maintained in both directions. Even if stakeholder groups are unable or unwilling to meet physically, a sustained silent dialogue is therefore encouraged (Herntrei & Zelger, 2023).

Figure 1. Operations (Red) and Information (Blue) of the Dialogue Between Two Groups.

Source: Adapted from Herntrei & Zelger (2023)

Stakeholder groups are not limited to decision-makers on one side and citizens on the other. Tourism businesses and visitors can be included in the silent dialogue as well, thus providing further perspectives on the respective topic.

Figure 2. Cyclical Organisation of the Information Flow Between Experts, Citizens, Tourism Businesses, and Visitors.

Source: Adapted from Zelger (1988) and from Herntrei & Zelger (2023)

In this way, an integrated overall system is developed that can be maintained over a longer period of time.

4. Conclusions

Participatory approaches in tourism have been recognised as important instruments how to optimise tourism development and increase the acceptance of tourism by local communities. Faced with numerous difficulties, comprising the unwillingness of stakeholders with the planning authority to share information, the strong fragmentation of the tourism industry, the lack of time and financial resources as well as the organisational effort, effective implementation of participatory approaches in tourism is rather illusory and participation remains a topical phrase in ambitious tourism development strategies. Characterised by a structured process between groups of stakeholders, a cyclical flow of information, and its inherently qualitative nature, the silent dialogue is argued to be a suitable method for obtaining in-depth insights into tourism development from the perspective of central actors, for facilitating participatory approaches, thereby contributing to a higher acceptance of tourism, and ultimately to the enhancement of sustainable destination development as a whole.

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Lean Six Sigma`s Impact on Banking Customer Satisfaction

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Abstract

This extended abstract provides an overview of a literature review and case study analysis examining the impact of Lean Six Sigma on customer service in the banking sector, focusing on a mid-sized bank in Albania. Lean Six Sigma, a methodology combining 'Lean' (to enhance process speed) and 'Six Sigma' (to ensure precision), is evaluated for its efficacy in improving banking services. The literature review synthesizes various studies and examples from the banking industry, highlighting Lean Six Sigma's role in streamlining service processes and enhancing customer satisfaction. The case study of the Albanian bank offers a real-world perspective, showcasing the method's application and the consequent improvements in customer service in the digital era. The findings indicate that Lean Six Sigma, despite its implementation challenges, is instrumental in optimizing banking operations and aligning them with evolving customer expectations.

Keywords: Lean Six Sigma; Customer Satisfaction; Banking Sector; Process Improvement; Service Quality.

JEL codes: L15, G21

1. Introduction

In today's competitive banking world, where customers expect efficient and accurate service, the significance of good customer service cannot be overstated. Customer satisfaction is at the core of a bank's success. Lean Six Sigma has gained attention in the banking sector because it aids banks in enhancing their operations, minimizing errors, and streamlining processes. This research aims to investigate the influence of this methodology within the banking sector. The primary objectives of this document are: first, to clarify the essential role of Lean Six Sigma in the banking industry, focusing on the improvement of services and products; and second, to highlight how Lean Six Sigma contributes to increasing customer satisfaction. The study is structured into three primary sections. The initial part of the study sheds light on the critical role of Lean Six Sigma in the banking sector, thoroughly exploring its significant impact through a literature review that categorizes the findings into three key areas: process improvement, risk management, and data analysis. Following this, a case study was meticulously developed and analyzed, using data collected from a medium-sized Albanian bank, to illustrate the practical implementation of this methodology in specific banking scenarios. In the final section, the practical results are compared with the theoretical concepts providing an overview of the main results of the work. This comparison results in comprehensive conclusions and highlights various important areas that offer opportunities for further investigation by researchers.

2. Methodology

The methodology involves conducting an extensive literature review that encompasses academic sources, aimed at identifying the fundamental theoretical concepts. Subsequently, utilizing data and information gathered from a medium-sized bank situated in Albania, a case study was devised and thoroughly analyzed, demonstrating the practical application of this methodology to distinct banking. The practical results are compared with the theoretical concepts from the literature.

3. Results and Discussion

The results from the implementation of Lean Six Sigma in the banking sector can be summarized as follows:

Enhanced Customer Experience: The reduction of errors and the acceleration of processing times have enabled banks to provide quicker and more dependable services, which has significantly boosted customer satisfaction.

Operational Excellence: Lean Six Sigma has been instrumental in driving operational excellence within banks by minimizing process variability, refining workflow, and maximizing the efficiency of resource utilization.

Cost Reduction: The adoption of streamlined processes and efficient operations has resulted in substantial cost savings, thereby allowing banks to maintain competitive rates and allocate resources towards innovation.

Employee Engagement and Skill Development: The training of employees in Lean Six Sigma principles has cultivated an environment of ongoing improvement and has equipped staff with enhanced problem-solving and analytical skills.

Customer Satisfaction: The application of Lean Six Sigma principles has had a positive impact on customer satisfaction. This is attributed to the banks' ability to provide services that are not only faster and more reliable due to reduced errors and processing times but also more attuned to customer needs due to the increased focus on operational efficiency and quality control. Furthermore, cost savings achieved through Lean Six Sigma practices have allowed banks to pass benefits on to customers, such as better rates and enhanced service offerings, further contributing to a more satisfying banking experience.

4. Conclusions

Overall, Lean Six Sigma has emerged as a valuable tool in the banking sector, enhancing not just the operational aspects but also cultivating a culture of continuous improvement and customer focus. This has not only improved the banks' internal processes but also positively influenced customer trust and satisfaction in banking services.

Future research should focus on evaluating the long-term implications of Lean Six Sigma in banking through extended studies, assessing its effects on staff welfare, examining the influence of corporate culture on its effectiveness, and exploring the combination of Lean Six Sigma with digital innovations to improve customer engagement in the digitizing banking industry.

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Employees' Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intentions.

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Abstract

Employee turnover has always been a problem for companies. In the Albanian context, there is a lack of research on this topic, especially in the service sector, where competition for qualified employees is very fierce. This study aims to uncover the relationship between organizational commitment and turnover intentions and determine whether the relationship varies according to the type of commitment studied. Meyer, Allen, and Smith's model commitment model of engagement provided the theoretical framework for the study. A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data, in which 275 people participated. The results of the study underline the importance of the two forms of organizational commitment for the intention to leave the workplace. Another finding of the study was that when organizational commitment was examined as a construct, continuous commitment was significant for the gender of male employees. The discussion of these findings focuses on their implications for practical issues in organizational commitment research.

Keywords: affective commitment, continuance commitment,

JEL codes: D91, J63, O15

1. Introduction

Employee turnover intention can be defined as an employee's intention to leave the organization in which they are currently employed (Seonghee, Misty, & Priyanko, 2009). The turnover of skilled employees is critical at a time when organizations are faced with technological advances and market dynamics. For organizations, the financial cost of recruiting, hiring and training a single employee can range from 93% to 200% of the annual salary for the position (Griffeth & Hom, 2001). Therefore, employee turnover is a serious threat to service quality (Chan & Chi Tat Darian Ao, 2019) and indirect opportunity costs such as lost sales, lower productivity and customer defections (Hay, 2001).

Regarding the factors that affect turnover intention, the literature refers to the links between the employee and the company, the indicator of which is organizational commitment, a process of exchange with the company (Meyer & Allen, 1991). The authors define organizational commitment as "a psychological state that (a) characterizes the employee's relationship with the organization and (b) has an impact on the decision to continue or terminate membership in the organization". Through this exchange process, the relationship between the parties may change depending on the perceived benefits or losses accumulated during the exchange. The researchers used Meyer and Allen's two-component model of commitment to describe the impact of an employee's psychological attachment to the organization on their intention to stay or leave.

2. Methodology

Instrument. The study's major goal is to investigate the effect of organizational commitment (both effective and continuous) on turnover intention. Our study employed a quantitative approach, including a questionnaire given to Albanian service industry personnel. The

questionnaire included control items such as gender, education, position, and so on, whereas the second section included questions on organizational commitment and desire to leave. The authors employed six statements scored on a five-point Likert scale from 1 to 5, with 1 being "Strongly disagree" and 5 being "Strongly Agree."

Participants. Workers in Albania's service industry participated in this survey. 36.9% of the workers were men and 61.6% of the workers were women. 275 employees completed the survey. The data collected indicates that the sample contains a higher proportion of women. The selection was made at random. Most employers are enrolled in master's degree programs.

Table 1. Demographic data of the participants

Gender	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Female	172	61.6 %
Male	103	36.9 %
Study program		
Bachelor	96	88.30%
Master	164	11.70%
High School	15	5.4 %
Position		
Specialist	86	30.7%
Low-level manager	58	20.8%
Mid-level manager	65	23.3%
Senior Executive manager	31	11.9 %
Head of the Company	23	9 %
Other	12	4.3 %

3. Results and Discussion

The method used to test the consistency of each construct is the Alpha-Cronbach test. The Cronbach alpha for each dimension ranged from .750 to .687 (Table 2), which indicated that the questionnaire items used to measure organizational commitment and turnover intention were reliable.

Table 2. Cronbach Alpha Values

Construct	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Affective commitment	8	.794
Continuance commitment	8	.687
Turnover Intention	6	.750

To ascertain the connections between independent variables, a Pearson correlation analysis was used. As you can see from Table 3, there appears to be a weak positive relation between Affective and Continuance because the Pearson Correlation is 0.260. This means that, when one of the factors rises, the other factors are increased but not to the same extent, it is about 26 % of the other factor. This result suggests as continuance commitment levels increase, there is a tendency for affection commitment to increase, but the relationship is not extremely strong. Also, we can say that individuals who have a strong commitment to continuing in their current situation (perhaps due to perceived costs or lack of alternatives) also tend to exhibit higher levels of affective commitment.

Table 3. Correlation

		Gender	Educatio n	Affective	Continuance
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.199**	.007	-.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	.914	.192
	N	275	275	275	275
Education	Pearson Correlation	.199**	1	.172**	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		.004	.228
	N	275	275	275	275
Affective	Pearson Correlation	.007	.172**	1	.260**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.914	.004		<.001
	N	275	275	275	275
Continuance	Pearson Correlation	-.079	.073	.260**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.192	.228	<.001	
	N	275	275	275	275
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

Model 1 (control variables related to turnover intention) according to hierarchical regression, presents the following data: gender ($\beta=-.137$; $p=.026$) and education ($\beta=-.036$; $p=.556$). These indicate that gender is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05, which means that this variable has a positive relationship with turnover intention.

In model 2, one of the dimensions of organizational commitment is added, specifically affective commitment, the following data are noted: gender ($\beta=-.152$; $p=.004$), education ($\beta=.059$; $p=.260$), and affective commitment ($\beta=-.536$; $p<.001$). These indicate that gender and affective commitment are significant because the p-value is less than 0.05, which means these variables have a positive relationship with turnover intention.

In model 3, where the continuance commitment dimension is added we noticed: gender ($\beta=-.134$; $p=.009$), education ($\beta=.050$; $p=.333$), and continuance commitment ($\beta=.204$; $p<.001$). These indicate that gender and continuance commitment are significant because the p-value is less than 0.05, which means these variables have a positive relationship with turnover intention. In model 4 where both dimensions are included, we notice that: gender ($\beta=-.152$; $p=.002$), education ($\beta=.055$; $p=.255$), affective commitment ($\beta=-.032$; $p=.760$), and continuance commitment ($\beta=.949$; $p<.001$). These indicate that gender and continuance commitment are significant because the p-value is less than 0.05, which means these variables have a positive relationship with turnover intention.

Table 4 also shows us the R square and adjusted R square. For the first model (control variables) R-square is .022 and the Adjusted R-square is .015. This means that 1.5 % is explained by turnover intention. In the second model when it is added dimension of affective commitment there is an increase of 19.5 % in Adjusted R-square. From the data, we see that in the second model, 29.3 % is explained by turnover intention. With the entry of the continuance commitment dimension, we see that the R-square is .339 and the Adjusted R-square is .329. This means that 32.9 % is explained by turnover intention. In the 4th model, where the dimensions of organizational commitment are simultaneously included in the block, we see that is an increase of 23.1% In Adjusted R-square. From Table 4, we see that for the last model, 40.5 % (Adjusted R-square) is explained by turnover intention, and the variables that stays significant are gender and continuance commitment.

Table 4. Hierarchical regression related to turnover intention

Variable	Model 1	Model 2 (+ affective)	Model 3 (+ continuance)	Model 4 (+ 2 dimension)
Gender	-.137 (.026)	-.152 (.004)	-.134 (.009)	-.152 (.002)
Education	-.036 (.556)	.059 (.260)	.050 (.333)	.055 (.255)
Affective commitment		-.536 (<.001)		-.032 (.760)
Continuance commitment			-.204 (<.001)	-.949 (<.001)
F-value	3.058	38.789	34.577	38.302
R-Square	.022	.300	.339	.416
Adjusted R Square	.015	.293	.329	.405

4. Conclusions

Turnover intention is a topic that has been studied by various authors for many years. This study can contribute to the literature here by initiating new research studies on turnover and its possible relationships with variables other than organizational commitment. For organizations, employee turnover can and should be managed by organizations to find the right balance and minimize its impact through effective solutions. Therefore, it is important for managers to better understand the relationship between engagement and employee attitudes and how these attitudes may differ across employee groups. The findings of the study show that male employees were continuance committed to the company than they intended to leave, referring to their function and role in the family in fulfilling obligations. This contrasted with female employees who were more likely to consider the option of mobility rather than their commitment to the company.

Based on the findings, organizations should adopt measures, policies, and practices to attract and retain good employees.

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Exploration of New Opportunities to Build Resilient Family Businesses

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Abstract

Family businesses count for 80% of total companies operating in current global market. They find their strength in what makes them special such as common history, identity and habits. (Gersick et al. 1997). The longevity and success of family business in generations can be explained by the notion of organizational ambidexterity thus the capability to equilibrate exploring and exploiting activities simultaneously (Hiebl, 2015). Although research shows there is a positive relationship between firm performance and organizational ambidexterity (Stubner et al., 2012), in the later generations it seems that entrepreneurial spirit is lost and family business become more risk averse (Hiebl, 2015). This paper aims to investigate the indispensability of exploring activities to create a resilient business and part of the legacy for succession in next generations.

Case study method was chosen as a way to provide a deeper insight of the subject in Albanian market. Through case study of an Albanian company in its second generation, this paper aims to analyze the theoretical framework against the real context. If family business are to evolve and thrive for the next generations, second generation managers should invest more in exploration activities and not limit to the exploitation of current capabilities.

Keywords: organizational ambidexterity, exploration activities, later generation family business.

1. Introduction

Since 1999 La Porta et al., noted that family firms were the most widespread economic organizations. Today family firms make 80-90% of global active enterprises contributing greatly to national GDP (Forbes, 2023). Based on the widely accepted theory that competitive market forces disqualify inefficient companies, leaving only the ones which succeed to adapt and thrive in the ever-changing market conditions, family businesses have proven to be successful and strong economic organizations (Schulze and Gedajlovic, 2010).

Nonetheless the research regarding survival and longevity of family business is still incomplete. From all family business only 30% make it to the second generation and even less can make it to the third or higher generation (Hiebl, 2015). One of the most accepted trends in strategic management which serves to explain and predict family business survival is organizational ambidexterity (Hiebl, 2015). This concept relates with a firm's ability to find an equilibrium between the exploitation of its actual potential and the exploration of new opportunities and activities (Raisch et al., 2009). According to Hiebl (2015), family businesses need to balance both these abilities in order to achieve long- term survival, thus resilience. Resilience is not about responding to one time crisis, but it has to be built in order that the company gains the ability not only to survive under difficult circumstances but to be prepared to find even their opportunities and advantages (Hamel and Valikangas, 2003)

Family businesses get their unique strength from their familiness thus the common history, values and tradition. Nonetheless this familiness can also hinder professionalism as managing roles in the family and business can become challenging (Gersick et al., 1997). This study will focus on the second generation of family business which according to the developmental model

built by Gersick et al. (1997), is located in the “sibling partnership” in the ownership dimension and “working together” in the “family dimension”. At this phase family firms are faced with the complexity of relations of a growing family and the challenge to accommodate this family in the actual business while trying to keep up the business profitability.

In this phase implementing organizational ambidexterity is very challenging and contextual. The main challenge in developing simultaneously exploitation and exploration is that they compete for the same scarce resources of the business (Andriopoulos and Lewis, 2009; O’Reilly and Tushman, 2011). On one hand there is the new generation who has to prove themselves worthy which is mostly done by looking for faster ways to harvest immediate profits thus by exploitation (Ginson and Birkinshaw, 2004). On the other hand, the business must stay competitive in the market which needs exploration (Kammerlander et al., 2020). According to Block et al., (2013) later-generations family business focus on exploitation while business suffers from too little exploration.

This paper tries to analyze the relevance of exploration in later generation family business in order to build a resilient company which can adapt and thrive under evolving market circumstances. For this purpose, a thorough literature review regarding exploration as part of organizational ambidexterity combined with main characteristics of later generation family business, is conducted to better assess the relevance of exploration to keep the business competitive. Then through the analysis of a case study, this paper tries to identify the challenges and strengths that second generation family business encounters in Albanian market.

2. Methodology

This paper addresses a “how” question related to an actual event using multiple data sources. Case study research is chosen in the context given by Yin (2003) as a methodology to investigate a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context. Three main concepts in the family business: second generation, exploration and resilience are studied and analyzed interdependently.

Changes that accompany the succession of the business to second generations are analyzed against theoretical framework. Case study method is chosen as most appropriate to lead an exploratory and explanatory research.

A single-case design is chosen for this study to illustrate the conclusions of theoretical review in the Albanian market. Semi-structured interview is conducted with the manager of the family business. The interview is realized in the form of guided conversation of open-end nature where respondent can also give his own insight on the matter.

3. Results and Discussion

This paper tries to answer to the key question, how can exploration of new opportunities help second generation family business build resilient businesses. Despite the well-known interrelation of organizational ambidexterity and firm performance (Raisch and Birkinshaw, 2008), the context developed in this paper is more focused in the exploration side of the balance and suggests that later generations family business should be more oriented to finding new opportunities rather than just exploiting the existing ones in order to contribute to a resilient business.

One of the assumptions on which this paper is based and which was derived from current literature is the risk-averse attitude of later generation family business. However, the question remains how to change this attitude by unfolding the positive effects in the performance of the business by exploring new opportunities and activities. The reasoning behind this assumption lies in two main directions. First that family business has long-term orientation (Zellweger,

2007) and it is therefore of utmost importance for them to stay competitive in the ever-changing conditions of the market. Second, in order to build a legacy, the business must be resilient thus bend but not break in front of unforeseen circumstances.

In order to analyze second generation family business in Albanian market context, it was seen necessary to take into consideration a family business which would be in the second generation, and which is still successful in the market. This way, this paper can build a framework of how risk-aversion, exploration opportunities and resilience is built in Albanian market, the main challenges encountered and abilities to thrive.

4. Conclusions

This paper tries to study the level of exploration in later generation family businesses by analyzing it in the context of organizational ambidexterity. Unlike the exploitation of current abilities, later generation family businesses find it challenging to invest capital in exploration activities (Le Breton- Miller, et al. 2011). This can be attributed to the characteristics a family business unfolds in the ownership and family dimension according to the still prevailing study conducted by Gersick et al. (1997) during the second generation.

The most notorious characteristic in second generation family business which hinders exploration is the risk-averse attitude this generation adopts while taking the management of the business (Hiebl, 2015). This paper tries to investigate how exploration activities help family business prosper and build resilience contributing to the succession of a healthy business.

When it comes to linking theoretical framework to business context, a family business in its second generation still thriving in Albanian market is taken into consideration. Through a thorough case study, this paper assesses how do the implications stand in a real case study. If a company is to thrive and succeed it must renew itself to stay competitive (Bergfeld and Bergfeld, 2023). One of the ways to adapt to the changes of the market is to look for the new opportunities in the industry and be the first to invest in operationalizing those opportunities. Even though family businesses are a widely spread form of business nationally and internationally, there are gaps in the study of how this companies succeed passed the founder generation. In Albania this research in the area is very limited and this paper it is just a small stepping stone based on one case study on how Albanian family business can create a financially healthy legacy for the generations to come.

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Leadership Styles - a Literature Review

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Abstract

This literature review explores a comprehensive array of leadership styles to elucidate their conceptualizations, characteristics, and implications within diverse organizational contexts. The examined leadership styles start with: "The Great Man" theory, continuing with Autocratic Leadership, Democratic Leadership, Laissez-Faire Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Authentic Leadership, Visionary Leadership, Situational Leadership, Charismatic Leadership, and Servant Leadership. Drawing upon a systematic and thorough examination of contemporary academic literature, this review aims to synthesize key findings and themes related to each leadership style. The methodology involves a meticulous search of reputable databases, to ensure a multifaceted understanding. The critical appraisal of the literature is designed to highlight nuances and commonalities, facilitating a deeper comprehension of the dynamics and impact of these leadership paradigms. By presenting a consolidated overview, this review contributes to the ongoing discourse on effective leadership, offering valuable insights for scholars, practitioners, and organizational leaders seeking to navigate the complex landscape of leadership theory and practice.

Keywords: leadership, leadership styles, effective leadership, literature review

JEL codes: M0, M19

1. Introduction

In the dynamic landscape of contemporary organizations, effective leadership stands as a linchpin for success and sustainability. The concept of leadership has transcended mere authority and command, evolving into a multifaceted domain where various styles and approaches play pivotal roles in shaping organizational cultures and outcomes. This paper embarks on an exploration of Leadership Styles, delving into the diverse frameworks and methodologies that leaders employ to influence and guide their teams. From the foundational principles of "Great Man" theory, to "Transactional and Transformational leadership" and to the nuances of Servant Leadership, Authentic Leadership, and beyond, this examination seeks to unravel the intricacies of leadership in the modern era. As organizations grapple with unprecedented challenges and opportunities, understanding the nuanced interplay of leadership styles becomes imperative for fostering innovation, resilience, and sustained success. By gaining insights into the different leadership styles, the aim of this paper is to equip leaders, scholars, and practitioners with a comprehensive understanding that can inform and elevate leadership practices in diverse and dynamic environments.

2. Methodology

This paper employed a systematic approach to investigate various styles of leadership. The selection of leadership styles, including Autocratic Leadership, Democratic Leadership, Laissez-Faire Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Authentic Leadership, Visionary Leadership, Situational Leadership, Charismatic Leadership, and Servant Leadership, was guided by a thorough examination of existing academic literature and contemporary relevance. The research process involved the utilization of reputable academic

databases, to identify peer-reviewed articles, books, and conference papers published within the past two decades. The inclusion criteria focused on works that provided in-depth insights into the conceptualization, characteristics, and impact of each leadership style. Additionally, the study had to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the diverse perspectives on leadership. To enhance the rigor of the review, a systematic search strategy, including specific keywords related to each leadership style, was implemented. The collected literature was then critically appraised, synthesizing key themes and findings to present a nuanced understanding of the distinct leadership paradigms explored in this review. This methodological approach aims to provide a robust foundation for analyzing and synthesizing the existing body of knowledge on leadership styles.

3. Results and Discussion

Each leadership style brings its unique set of characteristics, strengths, and potential drawbacks, contributing to the intricate tapestry of leadership dynamics. The laissez-faire, autocratic, and democratic leadership styles showcase the spectrum of control and decision-making, highlighting the importance of adapting leadership approaches to specific situations. Moreover, the charismatic, situational, visionary, servant, and authentic leadership styles emphasize the significance of personal qualities, adaptability, and a sense of purpose in effective leadership. This review encourages future research to delve deeper into the nuances of these leadership styles, examining their real-world applications and implications for organizational effectiveness and employee well-being.

4. Conclusions

The exploration of various leadership styles presented in this literature review underscores the dynamic and multifaceted nature of leadership within organizational contexts. From the historical perspective of the “Great Man Theory” to the contemporary models such as Transactional and Transformational Leadership, this paper reveals the evolving landscape of leadership research. As organizations continue to face complex challenges, understanding and integrating diverse leadership styles becomes essential for fostering innovation, collaboration, and sustained success. Ultimately, effective leadership is a nuanced interplay of various styles, guided by a leader's ability to navigate diverse situations and inspire positive outcomes within their team and organization.

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Enhancing Destination Management in Gjirokastra Region: A Comprehensive Study on Public Institutions' Perspectives

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Abstract

This research endeavors to comprehensively evaluate the actual destination management in the Gjirokastra region, leveraging insights from employees in public institutions regarding critical indicators of sustainable development of a touristic destination such as: economic impact, occupancy rates, infrastructure development, environmental sustainability, community engagement, cultural heritage preservation, marketing effectiveness, customer satisfaction, safety and security measures, partnerships and collaboration, regulatory framework, and the destination's capacity for innovation and adaptability. The research aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the destination's health, assessing the economic contributions of tourism, the utilization of attractions, the state of infrastructure, and the preservation of cultural heritage. Additionally, it delves into the effectiveness of marketing strategies, safety and security measures, and the level of community engagement, highlighting the destination's commitment to sustainable and responsible tourism practices.

A meticulously designed questionnaire was disseminated among public institution employees in the Gjirokastra region. The data collected underwent quantitative analysis, employing statistical techniques to derive meaningful insights into the destination's current status across the identified indicators. This approach enables the formulation of informed recommendations to enhance destination management. The research concludes with specific recommendations aiming to contribute to the sustainable development of tourism in the Gjirokastra region, fostering economic growth, preserving cultural heritage, and ensuring a positive and authentic experience for both visitors and the local community.

Keywords: Destination Management, Sustainability, Gjirokastra Region, Visitor Satisfaction, Economic Impact,

Extending Training Function Expected Performance for the New World of Work

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Abstract

The Training Function Expected Performance (TFEP) index, established in 2013 through an extensive literature review, was designed to assess the efficacy of training and development policies across diverse organizational landscapes. Comprising five key components—training needs assessment, program design, methods, evaluation, and organizational climate—the index aimed to gauge effectiveness. Given the evolving landscape shaped by digitalization, the aftermath of the pandemic-induced 'great resignation,' and the changing role of human resource management, the index necessitates an update. Incorporating new elements prompted by recent empirical findings becomes imperative, enhancing the measurement instrument to gather pertinent information. This article outlines the meticulous process of revising the index, leveraging contemporary literature, and taking in consideration the recent development and practices of consolidated companies. Two hospitality and tourism sector companies will be used as case studies and serve as testing environments for the draft version of the updated index. The maps developed per each company will provide their comprehensive status analysis but also inform the process of index update.

Keywords: training function expected performance, training and development, human capital, index, new world of work

JEL codes: O15, M53

1. Introduction

Training and development are pivotal in organizational success, fostering a skilled and adaptive workforce. Research by Baldwin, Magjuka, & Loher (2018) highlights how investing in employee development enhances job satisfaction and performance, positively impacting the bottom line. Training is proved to be an effective strategy to increase employee productivity and communicate organizational goals (Arthur et al., 2003). Moreover, studies by Noe (2017) demonstrate that effective training programs correlate with reduced turnover rates and increased employee retention. By continuously honing skills and fostering growth, organizations not only cultivate employee loyalty but also gain a competitive edge in dynamic markets. The empirical evidence underscores the crucial role of training and development in nurturing a proficient, engaged workforce, driving organizational excellence and innovation, and support the organization for competitive advantage (Barney, 1991; Porter, 1990).

Measuring the effectiveness of training and development initiatives in organizations remains a critical yet challenging endeavor. Research by Kirkpatrick and Kirkpatrick (2016) introduced a widely used model for evaluating training programs, emphasizing four levels: reaction, learning, behavior, and results. This model has been foundational in gauging the impact of training interventions across various industries. Additionally, Phillips and Phillips (2016) extended this framework by introducing the ROI (Return on Investment) methodology, offering a systematic approach to assess the financial impact of training programs. Their empirical studies illustrate how linking training outcomes to organizational objectives provides a comprehensive understanding of its effectiveness. Furthermore, studies by Holton (2017)

emphasized the importance of aligning training evaluation with organizational goals and strategic planning. Holton's research advocates for a holistic approach that integrates multiple evaluation methods to capture both quantitative and qualitative aspects of training impact. This multifaceted evaluation strategy enables organizations to not only measure immediate training outcomes but also assess long-term effects on employee performance, productivity, and overall business success.

Nevertheless, the efforts to measure the effectiveness of training and development face many limitations and often fail to provide organizations the complete picture of their efforts and don't always guide them to take decisions toward improvement. Salas et al., (2012) highlights challenges in isolating the specific impact of training from other organizational influences. The complexity of workplace dynamics, including changes in leadership, technology, or market conditions, makes it difficult to attribute performance solely to training interventions. Moreover, studies by Baldwin & Ford (2018) emphasize the difficulty in quantifying intangible outcomes such as improved morale or teamwork, which are often crucial but hard to measure accurately. Additionally, Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick (2016) acknowledge the tendency to focus more on immediate reactions and learning outcomes rather than long-term behavioral changes or organizational results, leading to an incomplete assessment of training effectiveness.

In view of these limitations, a Training Function Expected Performance (TFEP) has been developed and applied to measure the expected effectivity of this function for 34 service companies (Dibra, 2013). The index has been presented in international conferences recently and has been chosen as a contribution to the human resource development landscape (Dibra & Gerdoçi, 2023). Nevertheless, several environmental changes have happened in the world of work this last decade, indicating the need for new and updated practices for companies.

Over the last decade, Human Resource Management (HRM) has undergone significant transformations, adapting to dynamic workplace landscapes. One key development involves the integration of technology in HRM practices, as highlighted by Schramm (2019). The widespread adoption of HR software, digitalization of training and development, AI-driven analytics, and automation has revolutionized talent acquisition, performance management, and employee engagement. Additionally, there's been a noticeable shift toward a more strategic HRM approach, aligning HR practices with organizational goals and emphasizing HR's role in driving business outcomes, as discussed by Brewster & Hegewisch (2017). Moreover, the focus on employee well-being and diversity initiatives has gained prominence, reflecting the evolving societal values within organizational frameworks, as seen in the work of Cascio and Boudreau (2019). Ultimately, the great resignation during and after the COVID-19 pandemics, has reshaped employee training and development paradigms, emphasizing retention strategies and upskilling opportunities to retain talent. These developments stress the need for personalized development programs and career pathways to address workforce priorities amidst increased turnover (PwC, 2021).

Build on the reasoning above, the TFEP index update becomes not only important for theoretical purposes but also for practical use for companies that will use this tool in the new world of work. The article is organized into four sections. After the introduction, a literature review is unfolded focusing on the new emerging literature, including meta-analysis. The methodology section will describe the procedure to update and test the index. Results discussion and analysis, and finally the conclusions will close the article.

2. Methodology

For this research are combined the methodologies of the index update and the tool application in case study companies in tourism and hospitality sector. First, the methodology for the index update will follow the same procedure as per the original index building. The literature review will serve as a basis to update and identify new elements, sub variables, models, and their

weights, necessary for the table of truth. Second, two instruments used to gather information, the questionnaire and the in-depth interview will be updated to integrate the new questions. Data gathered for the case study companies will be analyzed using quasi statistics (refer to figure 1).

Figure 1. Roadmap toward updating and using the extended TFEP index

Source: Dibra & Gerdoçi (2023)

3. Results and Discussion

This article's findings will be presented on two distinct levels. Firstly, the updated index will reflect the evolving trends in training and development literature, offering insights into how the transformed global work landscape is mirrored in research. These insights aim to aid practitioners in making informed decisions. Additionally, initial groundwork will identify sector-specific research, enabling the customization of tools tailored to specific industries. This section will delve into the analysis of these distinctions and their potential implications.

Secondly, the results will be examined through the lens of the case study companies. An exploratory and comparative analysis will steer the discussions in this section, providing a nuanced understanding of the findings within the context of these specific organizations.

4. Conclusions

This work will identify the updates in training and development literature in view of effectivity of this function and the new challenges and opportunities the companies face in the new reality impacted by mega trends with a global, local, and sectorial impact. Based on the case study analysis, we will be able not only to analyse the company's situation but also to identify the gaps in literature and need for further empirical research.

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Estimation of Job Quality in Albania Using the 2007 - 2013 LFS: Low Quality (“Bad”) Employment Arrangements Mean Less Security and Pay

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Abstract

The hypothesis in terms of whether non-standard forms (and typically more precarious) of employment facilitate transition to permanent employment, or as an entrapment into these low-quality jobs, has not been explored for the case of Albania. In this paper, the above hypothesis is considered from a microeconomic perspective. The data used for this analysis is from the 2007 to 2013 waves of the Albanian Labour Force Survey (ALFS) microdata. These seven cross-sectional waves are a nationally representative random sample of private households. To establish the relationship between the previous year labour market status and incidence of non-standard employment, a logistic model in which the dependent variable distinguishes two categories of employment, standard and non-standard employment arrangements, was used. For the case of voluntary and involuntary non-standard work an ordered logit regression with the reference category being standard work was used. The findings suggest that earnings are negatively associated with undesired working conditions contradicting Smith's (1776) compensating wage differentials hypothesis, which suggests that when employees give up the quality of their working conditions, they should be able to receive benefits in earnings.

Keywords: casual employment; contingent employment; temporary employment; pathways; segmented labour markets.

1. Introduction

Non-standard forms of employment (NSFE) have been attracting extensive interest over the past few decades due to the evident distinction from standard ones. In developing countries, NSFE represent a significant share of paid employment but what is more striking is that NSFE have known an increased prevalence in those sectors where standard employment was the norm, i.e. manufacturing or the public sector (ILO, 2016).

For the case of the transition country of Albania, the post-communist era brought along important social changes over a rather short period. Consequently, uncertainty in the Albanian labour market has increased rapidly. The instruments that steer the labour market policy – in Albania in particular and in post-communist countries in general – are simultaneous use of strong labour market regulation and high levels of flexibilization (Drishti et al., 2021). This blending of past legacies with neoliberal approaches has resulted in little differences between Albania – an European Union (EU) candidate country since 2014 - and existing EU members in terms of NSFE.

This study investigates two main issues. Firstly, the analysis seeks to establish whether individuals' prospects of working in standard forms of employment (full-time and permanent) (SFE) are influenced by their previous labour market status (e.g. employed, unemployed, student, intern, trainee, or unpaid household worker). Past labour market status/performance is linked to personal characteristics of the individual, not easily identifiable and measurable, that make that worker more or less susceptible to non-standard employment (Green and Livanos, 2017). Therefore, an empirical analysis which enables to incorporate the last transition path is

conducted to understand whether the ‘steppingstone’ or the ‘entrapment’ scenario (Babos, 2014; Baranowska et al., 2011; Bollé, 1997; Booth et al., 2002; Gash, 2008; Scherer, 2004) are the best fit for the Albanian labour market.

Subsequently, a second comparison of SFE with NSFE is made with regards to earnings. The reason for this is to assess whether NSFE imply substandard earnings and in-work poverty (Green, 2011). Other things being equal, in a competitive labour market, workers on NSFE should receive higher earnings that just offset the value of the absent job security. In practice, however, in the majority of OECD countries, standard jobs have been progressively disappearing in the middle of the earnings and skill distribution while non-standard jobs have crowded the ends of the distribution.

The results suggest that NSFE are more of a dead-end than steppingstone to SFE. Moreover, earnings are negatively associated with undesired working conditions, i.e. NSFE, contradicting Smith's (1776) compensating wage differentials hypothesis which suggests that when employees give up the quality of their working conditions they should be able to receive benefits in earnings.

2. Methodology

Data

The available data at the individual level is the Albanian LFS data with 2007 – 2013 waves². The dataset includes basic demographic, labour market, and human capital individual level data. The annual LFS surveys were pooled into a single database, including the ‘year of observation’ in the control variables.

The analysis is restricted to respondents who reported their professional status as ‘employee.’ The set of control variables included in the estimation of job quality and earnings models relate to main demographic, human capital and labour market information on the employee characteristics³. Fixed effects included the year of survey.

3. Results from multivariate analysis

Job quality and effects of previous activity status

From the Table 1 below, it can be seen that being in unemployment, school/university, in an internship, or attending a training, the year before decreases/increases significantly the probability of working in standard/non-standard employment in the current year when compared to those in employment the year before (the reference category).

¹ The choice of research design is driven by data availability. In the case of Albania, methods and policy evaluation are restricted simply by unavailability of appropriate data from which to develop a complete – or at least useful from a policy standpoint – investigation.

² The main disadvantage of this dataset is its cross-sectional nature, which impedes an appropriate longitudinal assessment of the steppingstone versus entrapment hypotheses. Moreover, it does not include important individual information such as maternal and paternal education, number of persons financially dependent on the person, tenure, and labour market experience – variables generally included in labour market analysis. Key advantages consist of its very large sample size, compared to carrying out our own survey and annual update that provide chronological time series.

³ Education, age category, whether a person is single or married, occupational group and whether the person has supervisory responsibilities) and main variables on the employer characteristics (e.g. industry group, size of firm measured in number of workers, whether the job position was in the public or private sector) which are desired features of any source of data for the research of job quality and wage estimation equations.

Table 1: Job Quality – Logit: The probability of working in standard employment arrangements, conditional on labour market status the year before (Reference group is: Non-standard employment)⁴ (Odd Ratios)

Independent variable	Men		Women	
	Odd ratios	Robust SE	Odd ratios	Robust SE
Labour market status 1 year ago	<i>Reference category: Employed</i>			
Unemployed (UNEM)	0.223***	0.027	0.314***	0.057
Student, Intern, Trainee (STU)	0.116***	0.037	0.300**	0.115
Housekeeper (HOUS)	5.459*	4.368	0.647	0.2167
Other controls	Yes #		Yes #	
Constant	0.532	0.231	3.145*	1.604
Number of observations	7253		4333	

*, **, *** Significant at $p < 0.1, 0.05, 0.001$ level respectively

Other controls include: (i) Employee characteristics: Age segment, education level, civil status, occupation; (ii) Employer characteristics: Industry, firm size, sector and supervisory responsibilities; and (iii) Year fixed effects.

The figures confirm that if a person was unemployed the year before, the chances of him or her of working in NSFE are around 3 to 5 times higher than someone who had been employed in the year before.

These results are in accordance with previous studies, suggesting that past non-employment experience diminishes the chances of current work stability, measured here as NSFE (Green and Livanos, 2017). These directions of effects are stronger for men than for women. Labour market entry into standard employment is moderately easier for females who were unemployed, studying, in an internship or being trained than for their male counterpart.

Unsurprisingly, for a woman who in the previous year ($t-1$) was engaged in unpaid house work, the chances of securing a regular permanent job are lower compared to those who were in employment. The opposite is true for men whose chances of regular employment are boosted by their previous unpaid housework.

Earnings and non-standard work arrangements

Ordinary least squares regression analysis of the logarithmic hourly wage (earnings) will be reported. The aim is to estimate the penalty that different types of non-standard employment arrangements (full-time temporary FTTE, part-time permanent PTPE, and part-time temporary PTTE) have on earnings compared to the reference category, standard employment, FTPE. Temporary and part-time employment has been found to cause significant earnings penalties compared to standard work (Bentolila and Dolado, 1994; Hölscher et al., 2011; McGinnity and Mertens, 2002; OECD, 2015) and inequality of earnings is the main cause of inequality.

The results are reported after controlling for the established set of worker and employer characteristics⁵ and most importantly for the selection bias labour market participation for women in order to keep account the latent differences in behaviour between working and non-

⁴ The categories ‘in retirement or early retirement or has given up business,’ ‘permanently disabled,’ ‘in compulsory military service,’ and ‘other inactive person’ have an insignificant share and would automatically be dropped by the logit estimations as they would perfectly predict the ‘non-standard’ employment outcome.

⁵ That are: age segment, marital status, educational level, occupational status, supervisory responsibilities and for employer characteristics such as industry, firm size (number of workers), and sector (the full effects of the control variables can be found in Appendix 3.C)

working women which if neglected have significant profound methodological issues (Heckman, 1993)⁶.

Table 2: Earnings Specification 1 – OLS: Log earnings gap between non-standard and standard forms of employment

Independent variable	Men		Women	
	Odd ratios	Robust SE	Odd ratios	Robust SE
<i>Employment arrangements</i>	<i>Reference category: Standard – Full-time permanent</i>			
Full-time temporary (FTTE)	- 0.066***	0.002	- 0.111***	0.004
Part-time permanent (PTPE)	- 0.078	0.061	- 0.146**	0.042
Part-time temporary (PTTE)	- 0.116**	0.038	- 0.197*	0.078
Other controls	Yes #		Yes #	
Constant	7.603***	0.108	6.864***	0.237
Number of observations	5,331		5,819	

*, **, *** Significant at $p < 0.1, 0.05, 0.001$ level respectively

Other controls include: (i) Employee characteristics: Age segment, education level, civil status, occupation; (ii) Employer characteristics: Industry, firm size, sector and supervisory responsibilities; and (iii) Year fixed effects. Source of data: Labour Force Survey (LFS) 2007 - 2013, INSTAT (own elaborations)

Earnings are the main indicator of job quality in economic terms and have the largest share of reward structure. Previous studies have determined significant effects of employment arrangements on compensation structures (Kalleberg et al., 2000; McGovern et al., 2004). The results suggest that all forms of non-standard employment arrangements impose significant penalties on earnings, however the most pronounced negative effect remains that of workers in ‘full-time temporary’ jobs – which might also be a consequence of the largest subsample among all forms of non-standard employment.

Female workers in ‘part-time permanent’ jobs have 15% lower hourly wages than their ‘full-time permanent’ counterparts, which is not significant for males. Part-time permanent work has different occupational distribution between genders and this form of non-standard work is predominantly a female characteristic.

The worst type of employment arrangements are part-time and temporary arrangements which have the lowest level of occupational status, job security, and low pay as results can show. The fact that, relative to the other categories, part-time temporary workers are a small subsample may explain why the insignificant results above. However, the direction of effects and size are in concordance with other authors’ findings, albeit not as robust in terms of statistical significance. Men and women in these jobs earn around 12 and 20% less than the standard full-timers and their earnings penalty are also higher compared to permanent part-timers.

3. Results and Discussion

This investigation contributes to the earlier literature by considering whether individual and employer related characteristics have an impact on the probability of working in non-standard or standard jobs from the perspective of whether non-standard work serves as a transition to the core labour market of permanent full-time jobs or whether it is a dead end. This paper

⁶ The Heckman two-step procedure has enabled to correct for the self-selection problem of non-working women (See Appendix 3.A).

regards standard and non-standard employment arrangements as outcomes of different employee and employer (i.e. firm) related characteristics.

The results from the econometric analysis confirm the common and previously documented findings that individuals who have a history of exiting the labour market in the form of unemployment, for human capital investment purposes or to be engaged in unpaid family work, faced higher risks of working in low/" bad" quality jobs in the current year compared to those who were previously employed the year before. This means that if a person was unemployed last year, the chances of him or her working in a non-standard job are around 3 - 5 times higher compared to someone who had been employed the year before. Therefore, past non-employment experience diminishes the chances of current work stability. Results also indicated that female workers with low levels of education who were unemployed, studying, attending an internship or training, or engaged in unpaid family work a year ago are more susceptible to work in non-standard employment arrangements in the current year.

Contrary of what the theory of human capital depreciation predicts, the social capital translated in party or political forums memberships might be an explainable cause of why men, whose labour market status in the previous year was unpaid housework, are found working in standard jobs in the current year. Similarly, young individuals (aged between 15 and 29) who were unemployed the past year showed to be more/less prone to work in standard/non-standard employment in the current year, but this effect was significant only for men. In this case, the latent distorting effect of social capital in the public sector was revealed. What happens in Albania is that each 2 years either central or local elections take place, and the winning party's militants are rewarded with public administration and civil servants' jobs, a highly corrupted and inefficient sector. As explained in Chapter 2, the 'partisan politicization' mode of civil servants' employment is at the root of this approach and can be taken as a proxy of the 'jump' from housework to standard employment.

Labour market entry into standard employment is moderately easier for females who were unemployed, studying, in an internship or being trained than for their counterpart males.

Fixed-term (temporary) jobs – which is the largest category of NSFE – robustly have lower earnings than permanent ones and workers systematically are faced with hourly wages penalty, all other things being equal. These effects are stronger for women.

Part-time workers are also penalised however the highest earnings reduction were reported by part-time temporary workers, i.e. 12 and 20% lower earnings compared to full-time permanent while part-time permanent workers reported 8 and 15% earnings penalty, for men and women respectively. The robustness of the results for part-time workers is highly affected by the small size of the subsample that they represent, 2 and 2.7% permanent and temporary part-time.

Non-standard jobs are more a dead end or a trap than a steppingstone to regular standard employment in Albania. They for what is referred to as 'bad jobs' in terms of job quality. Individuals who work in these jobs are usually locked in repeated spells of non-standard employment and/or keep exiting into unemployment. The growth of nonstandard employment is problematic due to low quality of these non-standard jobs (Kalleberg et al. 2000). There is empirical evidence from different countries of the less-favourable treatment of temporary and part-time workers compared to permanent and full-time workers as regards the quality of their jobs, in that they often have lower job security, reduced access to both statutory and employer-provided social security benefits, and disadvantages in access to firm-funded training (e.g. The European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions 2002; De Graaf-Zilj 2005; Leschke 2007; Kauhanen 2009)

These results make two important points for policy. Even in a largely unregulated labour market, the use of temporary contracts and part-time hours has costs in terms of lower job satisfaction and by extension lower life satisfaction; lower wages that reflect lower specific human capital investment (Booth et al., 2002).

One important division here might be whether these NSFE are exercised involuntarily. Regarding the voluntary and involuntary acceptance of non-standard jobs, previous research puts forward the argument that the larger share of ‘bad’ jobs offer acceptance will be met by individuals involuntarily since a ‘bad’ job still makes a worker better off than unemployment (Grün et al., 2010). In fact job search theory (Mortensen, 1986) and related findings (Abraham et al., 2013) are in line with these findings. In the psychological literature differences have been found in job satisfaction and health outcomes by the contract preferences. For example, Krausz (2000) found with Canadian data that voluntary temporary help employees were more satisfied and involved and less stressed compared to involuntary temporary help employees. Isaksson and Bellagh (2002) found that contract preferences appeared to be negatively related to both health outcomes (distress and somatization).

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ICT Innovations Perspectives in Tourism

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Abstract

The tourism industry and its value chain are highly information-intensive, and so evolution in tourism and related industries closely mirrors advances in ICT innovations. The goal of this was to review the application of ICT innovations in the tourism and related sectors, with a view to highlighting their impact on the industry, as well as identify the opportunities for ICT innovations to facilitate tourism contributions to economic restructuring for sustainable development. This paper analyses recent research articles published by high-impact journals and organizations in the tourism and hospitality industry from 2018-2023. The findings were that recent trends in ICT use in tourism include strategic leveraging of ICTs for organizational functions such as communication and PR, service innovation, use of recent technologies such as robotic programs, travel apps, Artificial Intelligence (AI), cloud computing, and virtual payment and virtual reality systems. The wide array of ICTs and functions identified in this paper demonstrate the wide-ranging opportunities that are inherent in the application of ICT innovations in tourism and related sectors. Recommendations for additional research include exploring how ICT innovations may be specifically used to build sustainable economies through the tourism process.

Keywords: *Tourism, Travel, Leisure, Hospitality, ICT Innovations.*

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Challenges Affecting Operations in Albania's Banking Sector, Their Impact on Tourism

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Abstract

Albania's banking sector is facing several challenges, including limited access to financing, regulatory complexities, currency fluctuations, and technological constraints. These challenges have a significant impact on the country's economy, ultimately affecting the thriving tourism sector. The limited access to financing resources poses implications for tourism enterprises, hindering investments in infrastructure development and restricting the growth of the tourism industry. Currency fluctuations can affect the cost of travel for tourists, potentially altering their spending behaviors and travel decisions. Furthermore, cyber security concerns and outdated banking infrastructure may cause inconvenience to tourists during financial transactions. Therefore, it is essential to take a holistic approach to address these challenges and create a stable economic environment that can foster sustainable tourism growth. This paper aims to examine the complex landscape of challenges confronting Albania's banking industry and elucidate their consequential effects on the country's tourism sector and especially their impact on customers. The banking sector in Albania faces a myriad of hurdles that encompass regulatory, technological, economic, and geopolitical domains. Factors such as compliance with international standards, financial stability, digital transformation, and global market fluctuations pose significant obstacles. These challenges are interconnected and affect not only the financial realm but also extend to sectors vital for Albania's economic growth, prominently including tourism.

Key words: Banks, Operational problems, Customers, Tourism.

From Crisis to Innovation: Leveraging ChatGPT for Digital Transformation and Empowering Decision Makers in SMEs

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Abstract

The global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has caused unprecedented disruptions in businesses, with small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) particularly vulnerable to the economic fallout. To navigate the post-pandemic landscape necessitates a paradigm shift for SMEs towards digital transformation and the adoption of innovative technologies. However, many SMEs lack the resources and knowledge required to make this transition. This study explores the potential of leveraging ChatGPT, an AI-powered language model, as a facilitator for SMEs in achieving a smooth digital transformation, leveraging the prospect to success.

A review of existing research on digital transformation and the challenges encountered by SMEs is done. To fulfill the study's objectives, a qualitative research approach was employed, specifically through purposive interviews with SME owners and decision-makers spanning diverse sectors.

The findings indicate that ChatGPT could be a valuable tool for SMEs navigating the challenging digital transformation landscape. While the study acknowledges the positive impact, it also identifies certain difficulties and challenges that must be addressed to fully realize ChatGPT's potential in aiding SMEs. This research aims to contribute to the existing literature on virtual transformation, SMEs, and AI-based chatbots. Moreover, it provides practical implications derived from the study's findings, empowering SME decision-makers to enhance their competitiveness. The anticipated outcome is a valuable addition to the discourse extending beyond SMEs to broader contexts of technological adoption and business resilience.

Keywords: Digital Transformation, SME, ChatGPT, COVID-19

JEL codes: M15, O33

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) all over the world. Consequently, the capacity to adapt quickly to new occasions and traits has emerged as important for the survival and growth of SMEs. However, digital transformation is not always continuous for SMEs due to several elements like the cost of technology funding, lack of expertise and assets, and lack of a digital way of life. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the effect of COVID-19 on the digital transformation of SMEs and explore the potential of an Artificial Intelligence-based chatbot, ChatGPT, in helping SMEs with their digital transformation efforts. ChatGPT is an AI-powered chatbot that can interact in human-like conversation, apprehend natural language, and provide custom-designed guidelines to enhance the digital transformation for SMEs in the post- COVID-19 era. The study's findings will contribute to the literature on virtual transformation, SMEs, AI based chatbots; and provide realistic implications for SME owners and executives to beautify their virtual presence and competitiveness.

Hence, this study will look at the challenges faced by SMEs in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. It will explore the concept of digital transformation and the capability of ChatGPT

as an AI-powered chatbot to assist SMEs in gaining and maintaining their competitive advantages.

2. Literature Review

Digital transformation implies significant change in organizational activities, competencies, and models that leverage on the changes brought about by a mix of digital technologies and their impact on society. Such transformation transcends simple technological implementation; it involves a rethinking of business strategy and operations centered on value creation in the digital era (Morakanyane, 2017).

It is suggested that the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated digital transformation, turning it from a strategic choice to an absolute necessity for survival and competitiveness. Papadopoulos (2020) takes a comprehensive look at the adoption and utilization of digital technologies by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. This study highlights that COVID-19 pandemic has necessitated a swift shift to digital platforms for many SMEs, as they grappled with changing market conditions and business continuity concerns. It is pointed out that digital technologies have been instrumental in enabling SMEs to continue their operations despite the disruptions caused by the pandemic, and the adoption of digital tools has facilitated remote working, enhanced customer engagement through digital channels, and enabled the optimization of resources through improved efficiency and automation (Papadopoulos, 2020). However, from the other side, (Papadopoulos, 2020) identified several challenges faced by SMEs in their digital transformation efforts, including a lack of digital skills, inadequate digital infrastructure, and concerns about cybersecurity. This raises the need for appropriate support mechanisms to enable SMEs to overcome these challenges and fully capitalize on the potential of digital technologies.

All literature findings emphasize the multi-faceted nature of digital transformation, influenced not only by tangible factors such as infrastructure and policies but also intangible aspects like leadership and organizational culture.

It is important to stress that business companies should not view digital transformation as merely a reaction to the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, but as an ongoing strategy to adapt to the ever-evolving digital landscape. Failing in digital transformation makes it difficult for businesses to keep up with the ever-changing market requirements and consumer expectations. Across various researchers and relevant literature, technological components such as the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and big data analytics as key enablers of digital transformation. The use of digital technologies, particularly AI, can be instrumental in streamlining business operations, improving customer experiences, enhancing data-driven decision-making processes, and open new avenues for growth (Almeida, Santos, and Monteiro, 2022; Rai, 2022; Samuel, Shahbaz, and Antony, 2022; Soluk, 2023).

Research points out to the transformative potential of AI technologies in driving digital transformation, offering critical insights on how these technologies can be harnessed while providing a comprehensive understanding of the potential benefits and challenges associated with the use of ChatGPT in this context.

3. Methodology

To fulfill the study's objectives, an exploratory qualitative research approach was employed, specifically through purposive interviews with SME owners and decision-makers spanning diverse sectors. Participants were selected through purposive sampling making sure that there was a mixture of various forms of SMEs, such as those that were seriously impacted by the pandemic and those that had been much less affected. In total owners and decision makers from 10 Albanian SMEs were interviewed. Engaging with a diverse array of industry professionals

and stakeholders, each interview provided invaluable, first-hand perspective into the dynamics, challenges, and successes experienced within the Albanian business landscape.

Interview questions have been constructed based on the existing literature review and based on the objectives of this study. The data collected through the semi-structured interviews were analyzed using thematic evaluation.

4. Findings

Understanding the Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Businesses

When inquired *'How has COVID-19 impacted your business, and what strategies have you implemented to cope with the situation?'*, it results that at the COVID-19 pandemic had diverse impacts on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). There were cases where businesses were heavily affected and decided to close their physical stores and concentrate on enhancing their online presence. Participants highlighted the positive impact of the pandemic on their online businesses.

When inquired *'Have you thought about digital transformation in your business before COVID-19?'*, responses from SME owners and decision makers regarding their consideration of digital transformation in their businesses before COVID-19 varied. Some had thought about it but had not fully implemented digital transformation until the pandemic hit and made it a necessity.

Unraveling Barriers to Digital Transformation

When inquired, *'What are some of the barriers that prevent you from adopting digital technologies in your enterprise?'*, participants reported a range of barriers and challenges that have prevented or made it difficult for SMEs to fully embrace the digital era.

Potential Benefits of ChatGPT as a Trusted Partner for Digital Transformation

When inquired *'Are you familiar with ChatGPT and what it is able to offer for the digital transformation of SMEs?'*, from the responses, it is evident that most of the interviewees have some level of familiarity with ChatGPT, the AI-powered chatbot and the support it offers in the digital transformation of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Several respondents recognized the potential of ChatGPT in automating and personalizing customer support, content creation, and streamlining business operations, thus enhancing customer experience and business efficiency.

When inquired, *'What would you expect from ChatGPT usage in your business in terms of digital transformation?'*, some respondents were skeptical about the utility of ChatGPT due to the specific requirements of their industries, others held a more optimistic outlook.

When inquired, *'Would you consider ChatGPT as a trusted partner for your digital transformation journey?'*, it seems that responses are deeply influenced by industry-specific requirements and perceptions of artificial intelligence.

When inquired, *'How do you think ChatGPT can help your business stay competitive?'*, there was a consensus among respondents that ChatGPT has the potential to contribute to their business competitiveness in various ways, reflecting a generally positive outlook towards the capabilities of this AI technology.

5. Conclusion

This study looked at the challenges faced by SMEs in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. It aimed to explore the concept of digital transformation and the capability of ChatGPT as an AI-powered chatbot to assist SMEs in gaining and maintaining their competitive positions.

Based on the previous literature and findings of this study, it's evident that COVID-19 pandemic had a sizable impact on diverse businesses, with some experiencing negative

consequences and others adapting and turning the situation to their advantage. The pandemic also highlighted the importance of online virtual platforms in maintaining customer service and communication.

The findings of this study emphasize the need for organizations to embrace digitalization and explore how it can improve performance, consumer experience, and standard commercial enterprise operations.

In conclusion, it seems that while AI can be leveraged to enhance operational efficiency and decision-making effectiveness, security considerations may limit the direct contribution of ChatGPT to competitiveness. Incorporating ChatGPT into SME operations can provide numerous benefits, consisting of improved purchaser retention, improved competitiveness and more suitable purchaser insights. Therefore, corporations should actively consider adopting ChatGPT to stay ahead of the curve and gain an advantage in their respective industries.

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Navigating Supply Chain Challenges in Albanian Oil and Gas Trading Companies

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Abstract

The current global oil price per barrel has had a profound impact on both the oil and gas industry and the economies of countries and households worldwide. Beyond the fluctuations in oil prices, this industry contends with various external influences such as limited oil resources, elevated transportation costs, and substantial uncertainty in the supply chain. Navigating these challenges necessitates a shift in focus among professionals in the oil and gas sector toward the effective management of resources and capabilities. In this context, performance management emerges as a crucial strategy. Given the industry's heavy reliance on a well-functioning supply chain to deliver services and products, a comprehensive understanding of supply chain management intricacies becomes paramount. This study seeks to delve into the challenges associated with the performance management of the supply chain within the oil and gas industry in Albania, specifically in its commercial segment, commonly referred to as the downstream supply chain. Through research interviews in two of the trading companies, six main challenges in this area have been identified.

Keywords: Supply chain management, Challenges, Oil and gas.

JEL codes: M10, M19, L80

1. Introduction

The principles managing the efficient flow of materials and information to fulfill consumer needs have seen minimal alteration, from the construction of pyramids to tackling starvation in Africa. In a supply chain, companies are connected to each other and the decisions and problems of each of them affect the entire chain, which ends with the final consumer of the product or service offered. For industries where supply chains operate globally, such as the oil and gas industry, supply chain management becomes the cornerstone of operations. The significance of the oil industry's impact on the global economy is obvious. Oil supply chain management has to solve a lot of challenges caused by the nature of the supply chain in the oil industry such as integrated process management, information systems and information sharing, organizational restructuring, complexity, inflexible characteristics, long lead time, limited transportation forms, limited primary distribution capacity and unforeseen events (Al-Husain al., 2006). However, within the oil industry, skillfully handling the growing challenges, increasing effectiveness and efficiency, and exploiting opportunities for profit maximization through effective supply chain management remains insufficient, (Lisitsa et al., 2019). Albania's oil and gas industry diverges from the global norm, as it primarily functions on a local and regional scale, lacking a comprehensive global network. Despite its more confined scope, the industry bears immense significance in influencing the economic landscape of the country and the well-being of its citizens. While the sector may not be globally expansive, it grapples with substantial challenges in managing its supply chain, intricately tied to the efficiency and effectiveness of delivering petroleum products that hold relevance for the entire populace. The core objective of this research is to delve into the supply chain challenges confronting petroleum trade companies in Albania, with a specific focus on meeting customer orders. The

study aims to not only identify these challenges but also propose viable solutions to enhance the management of the supply chain within the petroleum trade sector. To achieve this objective, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with representatives from two prominent oil trading companies in the country. The paper is meticulously structured into five distinct sections. The second section provides an in-depth exploration of existing literature related to the oil and gas industry, offering a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced globally and their potential implications for Albania. Following this, the third section outlines the methodology employed in this research, detailing the approach taken in gathering and analyzing data. The fourth section houses the crux of the findings and discussions, shedding light on the insights derived from the interviews and their implications for addressing the identified challenges. Finally, the paper concludes in the fifth section, summarizing key takeaways and potentially opening avenues for further exploration in the dynamic realm of petroleum trade in Albania.

2. Methodology

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to uncover supply chain management challenges in vertically integrated oil trading companies in Albania. Specifically focusing on companies engaged in all aspects of the supply chain from the port to final customers, two out of the three identified companies were selected for interviews. Senior managers with over a decade of experience in these companies were interviewed, aiming to explore challenges previously unexplored in the Albanian context. This approach aligns with established methods used in similar uncharted territories (Yin, 1994; Urciuoli et al, 2014).

3. Results and Discussion

In the literature, we have identified several challenges faced by oil companies. These complexities require efficient supply chain performance management. The interview focuses on the challenges that companies face in managing the supply chain in the industry. Based on these semi-structured interviews, the challenges we have identified in the company are:

a. *Measuring the Chain's performance, to make improvements*

A challenge faced by companies in this sector was the lack of accurate data and tools to measure supply chain performance.

“It is very difficult to get accurate data of our performance to detail later and how we should act. It is especially difficult to get accurate information from units that are spread all over the country and have direct connections with customers. (11)”

Although companies may have made efforts to develop other tools besides financial measurement, again this remains a challenge for them.

“Although we can say that we have made improvements regarding more accurate performance evaluations by not measuring it only with financial results, again I must say that it is very difficult to collect accurate and real-time information for measuring the performance of the entire chain. (12)”

The accuracy of the data and the creation of tools that measure the multidimensional performance of supply chains would increase the efficiency of the process (Shafiee et. al., 2014) and would improve the management of the supply chain (Chae et al, 2014).

b. **Lack of inter-departmental cooperation**

In the two companies where we conducted interviews, a glaring issue was the absence of interdepartmental cooperation. The businesses' remarks in response to this challenge were: *“Due to the somewhat high turnover, the lack of appropriate means of internal cooperation, the distance for direct cooperation, and the amount and direct work that everyone must do, we can say that we have problems with interdepartmental cooperation. Strong internal cooperation would*

also enable cooperation with external actors, mainly customers, and suppliers, and it would be more efficient to manage the supply chain in the best possible way. (I1)''

''Lack of cooperation is a factor present in our society. This lack of cooperation occurs especially in those departments that are not directly related to the work they do. Knowing the importance of cooperation, we tried to develop the connections, but again we can say that they are not in the stages of their consolidation. (I2)''

Interdepartmental cooperation allows companies to see customer requests and address them more effectively. (Bimha et al, 2017). Cooperation brings increased competitive advantages in the market through the satisfaction of requests and leads to better performance for companies (Flynn et al., 2010). Based on the great impact that this collaboration has, companies must address this challenge and take measures to develop the appropriate tools to increase interdepartmental collaboration.

c. Lack of strong relationships with suppliers for secondary businesses.

It's common for companies in the oil trading industry to have other operations in retail locations. They prioritize building and maintaining trusting relationships with their suppliers, which they believe is crucial for all of their businesses. In response to these concerns, they articulated as follows:

''We have established a network with suppliers for our primary company, but we are unable to say the same for the other goods we offer. We understand the value of having relationships with suppliers, but we also understand that doing so is not feasible for goods that are available domestically. With some of them, we are establishing long-term relationships, although we cannot yet declare that this process is almost finished. (I1)''

The other company, having prioritized and strengthened supplier relationships, views it less challenging, emphasizing continuous efforts for improvement in supply chain management. *''We make an effort to maintain accurate and consistent partnerships with our suppliers, and we rely on these ties on trust. Although we have developed these kinds of partnerships with some suppliers, there is still more we can do to enhance supply chain management. (I2)''*

The management of external relations is a key component of the supply chain. For oil trading companies, relationships with suppliers represent one of these external relations challenges. Companies would be able to lower expenses and improve performance in this chain if they could overcome this obstacle (Jüttner et al, 2007; Mackelprang et al, 2014).

d. Inventory Management Challenges

Balancing inventories poses challenges for businesses as the cost of maintaining stock prompts careful consideration of whether to retain or reduce it. The complexity intensifies for businesses managing stocks across multiple distributors, as highlighted by companies in the oil trading sector. They attribute this challenge to the absence of adequate measurement and prediction technologies, expressing it in the following terms:

''For us, managing inventory presents a daily problem. Every day, we are unsure of the required quantity because we lack the ability to verify the daily stock of our stations and other clients that we sell in bulk. Adding to this, our supply chain management is made even more challenging by the lack of a predictive tool. If we have a distributor or have days when our demand fluctuates, this management becomes considerably more difficult and expensive. One of our main supply management problems is the absence of tools and related software, which drives up costs. (I1)''

The other company highlights this challenge, particularly for the main business, and the consequent rise in costs.

“We constantly struggle with inventory management, particularly in retail sales locations. This is an expensive challenge. (I2)”

The difficulty in determining how much inventory should be held in each distributor is highlighted in the literature, as are the associated expenses in filling, transporting, and keeping the inventory (Al-Husain al., 2006; Chima, 2007).

e. Customer Service Challenges

When a company pleases its customers, it improves customer retention and increases the frequency of customer repurchases, resulting in increased sales and profits. The challenge of providing customer service in the first company is apparent in the form of insufficient tools to measure customer satisfaction and to enhance the service when needed.

This difficulty, as reported by the other company, is related to meeting urgent demands from customers. To achieve customer satisfaction, businesses must be able to match their customers' needs and desires as expressed in their order specifications (Peyton, Pitts, & Kamery, 2003).

f. Distribution Management Challenges

Oil trading companies face a substantial distribution challenge, encompassing aspects such as fleet management, route optimization, and timely deliveries. Businesses attribute the difficulty to the considerable costs and expenses incurred in addressing this challenge. The following excerpts shed light on this situation:

“Distribution presents a major obstacle. The main causes of the difficulties are distribution expenses, tool availability, and time limits. Although our distribution fleets are available, availability is often hampered by their limited distribution time. Export requires its own fleet and the domestic market as well, which leads to a time spread and double fleet trips. Another major challenge in the chain is managing the costs of this connection. (I1)”

“We face challenges related to transportation daily. Some of the links that this difficulty forces us to deal with on a daily basis include roads, tools, maintenance, time, quantity of supply, availability of fleets, and their capacity. All of this results in expenses. (I2)”

Companies would experience cost savings and performance improvements if they could overcome the distribution management difficulty, which would increase customer service. (Chima, 2007; Menhat et al., 2019; Al-Othman et al., 2008)

4. Conclusions

This exploratory study has provided significant insights into the challenges faced by practitioners in the oil and gas industry in managing the performance of the supply chain. Six primary challenges have been found by this investigation. During the interview, the companies emphasized that one of their main problems was the inability to collect accurate data and to develop tools that would enable performance measurement. This result would serve the companies to improve the management of the supply chain by improving the performance of the companies themselves. Hence, it is critical to place greater importance on managing this challenge. Managing distribution and inventory was a significant obstacle for the enterprises involved in the oil trading industry. These two difficulties increase costs for businesses. Therefore, it is essential to give controlling this challenge greater attention. The firms that were interviewed faced issues related to managing customer service and internal and external interactions, albeit not to the same extent. Noteworthy challenges highlighted in the literature, including government regulations (Osoro, 2016; Menhat et al., 2019), exchange rate risks (Osoro, 2016), and social or ecological concerns (Atstāja & Mukem, 2023), did not emerge as significant issues for these oil trading companies. It's important to acknowledge that the

absence of vertically integrated parties in all facets of Albania's oil trading supply chain poses a limitation in this study. A more comprehensive understanding could be attained by including every company in future research.

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A Comparative Analysis of the State of the Tourism and Hospitality Sector in Western Balkans, Under a Quality Management Approach

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Abstract

In addition to providing some recommendations on how to make the tourism and hospitality sector an important part of the Western Balkan countries and the entire region's economy, the study's objectives were to ascertain the state of the development of the tourism and hospitality sectors, quality management and standards related to tourism and hospitality sector, and the relationships between tourism standards, sustainable development, and economic growth in Western Balkan countries.

The idea for the field of study for which the research was conducted, the collection of data, figures, facts, and information based on desk research, as well as the literature used for the realization of the study, were the initial steps to determine the methodology and methods used and followed for the realization of this study. The resources utilized in this study were then chosen after the literature, data, figures, facts, and information were reviewed and chosen. The study's methodology then involved processing data through comparative analysis to produce additional trustworthy data, combining data, figures, and information from various sources and earlier research to identify key trends in tourism and hospitality in WB6, that would support the industry's long-term development concerning the application of quality management principles and ISO standards, as well as the package of Safe Travel Stam standards for this industry. The study was focused on the relationships between the tourism and hospitality sector, quality management, sustainable development, and economic growth, while, additionally, the research was prepared in its initial form and then revised several times before it was finalized and presented in this scientific activity. Following the completion of the final content, the paper's abstract and introduction were drawn, before coming to the pertinent findings and suggestions.

The primary recommendation is that each Western Balkan country should make investments in improving ties between the tourism and hospitality sector, quality management, sustainable development, and economic growth patterns, working together also to develop these sectors and patterns for a stable local and regional economy as they move closer towards the path of the EU integration.

Keywords: Tourism, hospitality, WB6, quality management, ISO standards, sustainable development, economic growth, EU integration.

Service Quality and Overall Satisfaction of Tourists for the Albanian Destination

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Abstract

Tourism industry is one of the areas with the fastest development all around the world and service quality in tourism has an important impact for economic growth to each country. Considering the benefits that tourists bring to a country, it is important that all stakeholders such as accommodation establishments, bars and restaurants, tourist services and agencies, cultural centers, retail trade units, municipalities, etc., to be prepared to offer the proper service quality to tourists in order to keep them satisfied, and then continuing by them to tell to other people the positive impressions based in their experience, so resulting in the increase of the number of tourists, bringing positive effects for the country and also for all stakeholders involved. In recent years, Albania is experiencing a boom in terms of the number of tourists visiting it. Albania possesses natural advantage with high cultural and historical diversity, aspects that should be considered by combining them with offering the highest service quality to tourists and providing them the best overall satisfaction.

In this paper, through the use of literature, the questionnaires and interviews directed mainly to the tourists that have visited Albania recently, the aim is to determine how they perceive the dimensions of service quality in tourism and related to their overall satisfaction, and at the end of the analysis based on the survey results, to give the relevant suggestions for the involved stakeholders in order to make potential improvements.

Keywords: Tourism sector, Service quality in tourism, Customer satisfaction

JEL codes: L83, O14, Z32

1. Introduction

The tourism industry is one of the major service industries around the world. The tourism sector plays an important role in the economic and social development of many developed and developing countries. Tourism generates employment in many services ranging from travel units, accommodation establishments, bars and restaurants, tourist services, cultural centers, retail trade units, etc. The tourism sector, a rapidly growing economic sector worldwide is considered very important, and its role is in accelerating economic growth by providing foreign currency and new jobs, bringing improvement in the balance of payments, and contributes to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (WTO, 2023, Foo et al., 2020, Yoo, 2020). The services related to the tourism sector are labor intensive with many links to other segments of the economy, such as transport and cultural services, financial and insurance services, and these services include services provided by accommodation establishments, bars and restaurants, travel agencies, tourist guide services, tour operator services, etc (WTO, 2023). Regarding 2022, the contribution of tourism sector to global GDP was 7.6%, so comparing with 2021 it resulted in an increase of 22% and comparing with 2019 a decrease of 23%, but for 2022 brought 22 million new jobs, so comparing with 2021 it resulted in an increase of 7.9% and comparing with 2019 a decrease of 11.4%, and in 2022 there was a rise to the international spendings by visitors by 81.9% (WTTC, 2023). There are undertaken tourism commitments by

most of World Trade Organization (WTO) members to expand their tourism sectors and to increase inward Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) in order to promote their national economic growth (WTO, 2023). The tourism industry, one of the important areas with the fastest development all around the world, and service quality in tourism has an important impact for developed and developing countries. By investing in service quality in tourism and hospitality industry, it can improve tourism destination image and tourist destination loyalty (Zeina et al., 2023).

In recent years after pandemic situation Covid '19, Albania, a country with natural advantage and high cultural and historical diversity is experiencing a boom in terms of the number of tourists visiting it, so the focus should be in offering the highest service quality to tourists and providing to them the best overall satisfaction. The arrivals of foreign citizens for personal purposes (holidays, health, religious, transit, etc) as individuals or organized (by tourist agencies), or for business and professional purposes in Albania is by the transport ways like sea, air, and land (border points). Arrivals of foreign citizens to the territory of Albania during October 2023 are 691,680 citizens, resulting in an increase of 89.4% compared to October 2022, and during the first ten months of 2023, the number of arrivals of foreign citizens to the territory of Albania is 8,986,280 citizens, resulting in an increase of 32.3% compared to first ten months of 2022 (INSTAT, 2023). Based in INSTAT data and figures on arrivals to the territory of Albania of foreign citizens by region, the region with the highest inflows of citizens in Albania during October 2023 and for the period January-October 2023 is the European region, followed by America and East Asia and Pacific (see table no.1).

Table 1. Arrivals to the territory of Albania of foreign citizens by region

Description	October 2022	October 2023	January- October 2022	January- October 2023
Total	365,237	691,680	6,793,902	8,986,280
I. Africa	743	1,899	4,121	10,436
II. America	10,454	16,495	162,123	217,073
III. East Asia and Pacific	2,967	8,355	22,969	62,261
IV. Middle East	1,279	1,623	39,918	38,641
V. South Asia	1,213	1,557	8,748	12,455
VI. Europe	338,058	660,057	6,197,389	8,623,215
- Central /Eastern Europe	18,106	31,760	407,764	604,202
- Northern Europe	18,649	26,194	237,475	340,184
- Southern Europe	258,109	518,543	5,033,653	6,790,043
- Western Europe	33,811	63,119	435,406	697,829
- East/ Mediterranean Europe	9,383	20,441	83,091	190,957
VII. Other countries not specified	10,523	1,694	358,634	22,199

Source: INSTAT, 2023

Based in INSTAT data and figures on arrivals to Albania of foreign citizens by purpose, during October 2023 compared to October '22, there is an increase of arrivals for personal purposes by 91.3% (for vacation purposes, etc. an increase by 93.4%); and a decrease for arrivals on business and professional purposes by 10.3%, and for the period January-October 2023 compared to the period January-October 2022, there is an increase of arrivals for personal purposes by 32.5% (for vacation purposes, visiting relatives, etc. an increase by 32.3%); and an increase for arrivals on business and professional purposes by 14.4% (see table no.2).

Table 2. Arrivals to the territory of Albania of foreign citizens by purpose

Period	October 2022	October 2023	Annual change (%)	January-October 2022	January-October 2023	Annual change (%)
Arrivals foreign citizens	365.237	691.680	89.4	6.793.902	8.986.280	32.3
I. Personal	358.398	685.543	91.3	6.701.997	8.881.128	32.5
1. Holidays, visit to relatives, etc.	334.680	647.435	93.4	6.378.595	8.438.663	32.3
2. Health treatment	313	205	-34.5	2.266	824	-63.6
3. Religious	41	18	-56.1	435	365	-16.1
4. Transit	23.364	37.885	62.2	320.701	441.276	37.6
II. Business and professional	6.839	6.137	-10.3	91.905	105.152	14.4

Source: INSTAT, 2023

Considering the increased number of arrivals of foreign citizens to the territory of Albania, during 2022-2023, especially for personal purposes (holidays, visit to relatives, et.), businesses and professional purposes, all the stakeholders should try to offer to these foreign citizens the highest service quality and provide them the best overall satisfaction in order to bring them back in the future and to further increase the tourist's number based on word of mouth marketing and online social networking. This study aims to determine how the tourists that have visited Albania recently perceive the dimensions of service quality in tourism and related to their overall satisfaction and making relevant analysis and suggestions.

2. Literature review

The tourism industry is one of the world's fastest growing industries and has an important role in foreign exchange and employment, and impacts to the social, economic, and environmental development of many countries (UN, 2023). Sustainable tourism is tourism that considers the current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, focusing and basing in the visitors' needs, the industry, the environment and host communities (WTO, 2023). Sustainable tourism development requires the participation of all relevant stakeholders and achieving it is a continuous process with constant monitoring of impacts, taking the necessary preventive and corrective measures whenever needed, and by maintaining a high level of tourist satisfaction and by ensuring a meaningful experience to them (WTO, 2023).

Tourism is a social, economic, and cultural phenomenon which includes the movement of people to countries (or places) outside their usual environment for personal or business and professional purposes; and these people are called visitors, which may be tourists or excursionists, residents, or non-residents (WTO, 2023). Tourists are persons who travel to destinations outside their residence and working place and stays for at least 24 hours but not more than one year for personal purposes (holidays, leisure, etc) or business and professional purposes (IGI Global, 2023; Dilek, S. E, Dilek, N. K, 2018).

The tourism industry, quality itself and service quality, and tourists' satisfaction and retention over the years have drawn the attention of many researchers and practitioners. Tourism sector is very competitive and companies operating in this sector, in addition to competing by cost, should also focus on quality as a primary element for competitiveness in this service sector and also for the sustainable development of tourism industry. Considering the awareness of business organizations of the competition in every sector, especially in the tourism sector as a service one, and the growth of customer expectations, many successful organizations have started to exploit and win from the opportunities, and they have known the importance of processes to better manage the quality itself and service quality in order to survive and succeed (Eraqi, 2006). Service quality in tourism has an important impact for developed and developing countries, and for the companies operating in this service sector. Service quality is not equivalent to satisfaction, but they are closely related, where service quality results from the

comparison of expectations with performance, and customer satisfaction is their fulfillment response (Parasuraman et al., 1988, Parasuraman et al., 1994, Oliver, 1997). Perceived service quality is a form of attitude and a long run overall evaluation, while customer satisfaction is a transaction specific measure (Bitner, 1990, Parasuraman et al., 1988). A customer's perception of service quality is based in their judgment on the superiority of the service by comparing the expected service and the actual perceived service performance (Zeithaml, 1988). SERVQUAL method, consisting of five dimensions to measure service quality: reliability, responsiveness, empathy, tangibles, and assurance, made a significant contribution in the service industry (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Considering that operationalization of service quality confounds satisfaction and attitude, SERVPERF was suggested, a performance-based measure as a means to improve measuring the service quality (Cronin and Taylor, 1992). Also, for food services, a part of service quality in tourism, instruments such as TANGSERV, DINESERV and DINESCAPE are used (Raajpoot, 2002, Stevens et al., 1995, Ryu and Jang, 2008). Quality dimensions for food services as a part of service quality are key requirements to ensure revisits (Bichler, et al, 2020). Also, by other authors different instruments are used to measure service quality and customer satisfaction for accommodation establishments, service centers, etc. For the tourists that have visited a destination more than one time means that they have been satisfied and their expectations have been met (Rahmiati, et al. 2020). Also, customer satisfaction is one of the essential determinants of success for businesses operating in the tourism sector (Moore et al., 1998). The growth of the tourism industry can be achieved by optimizing tourism strategy including the offer of a high service quality and by providing customer satisfaction for the tourists. The purpose of all organizations in the tourism sector is to better serve the customers, whether a visiting international tourist or a domestic citizen (Narayan, et al., 2009). Quality should be a professional tool for organizational and operational purposes for organizations operating in tourism sector, and quality of a tourism destination means satisfying all tourism product and service needs, customers' requirements and expectations at acceptable prices, in conformity with factors such as safety and security, communication, infrastructure, hygiene, accessibility, and public amenities (and services), and also by showing ethics, transparency and respect towards the human and natural environment (UNWTO, 2023). But, for all authors who are engaged, focused, and have studied this field, it is important to define those dimensions which best define service quality in tourism, and which affect the overall satisfaction of tourists.

The focus of this paper, through the use of literature, the questionnaires and interviews directed mainly to the tourists (foreign citizens) that have visited Albania recently, is to determine how they perceive the dimensions of service quality in tourism and related to their overall satisfaction and making relevant analysis. At the end of the material, conclusions and suggestions are made for the involved stakeholders in order to make potential improvements.

3. Methodology

The methodology used in this study consists mainly in qualitative methods, combined with quantitative research methods. Primary sources like interviews and questionnaires are used and distributed to foreign citizens (tourists) that have arrived at the territory of Albania for personal purposes (holidays, visit to relatives, et.) as individuals or organized (by tourist agencies), or for businesses and professional purposes, and secondary sources (literature that exists regarding this managerial approach). Convenience sample (nonprobability sample) is used, where the researcher/author selects the easiest population members (respondents) from which to get information. Eighty-four questionnaires are collected; Male: 57.14% and Female: 42.86%; Age: <30 years old ... 30.96%; 30-50 years old ... 33.33%; >50 years old ... 35.71%; completed by arrivals to the territory of Albania of foreign citizens (tourists) with above purposes. Arrivals to the territory of Albania of foreign citizens taken under consideration are from Europe: 89.29%, America: 5.95%, Asia: 4.76%. SPSS statistical program was used,

where the data are numbers, and was proceeded with the descriptive analysis to analyze the statistical indicators for different variables such as means, standard deviations, coefficients of variation, mode, median, etc., for each service quality attribute/dimension (Trochim, 2006). The questionnaires were designed in the form of statements and evaluated with the Likert scale from 1 ‘not at all’ to 5 ‘a great extent’ (Vagias, Wade M., 2006).

4. Analysis & Discussion

Through the analysis of questionnaires and interviews directed to foreign citizens (tourists) that have arrived at the territory of Albania for personal purposes (holidays, visit to relatives, et.) as individuals or organized (by tourist agencies), or for businesses and professional purposes, is then proceeded with the descriptive analysis to analyze the statistical indicators for different variables. For the attributes themselves and by summarizing in categories of service quality dimensions in tourism (source: adapted and modified from UNTWO, 2023 and Narayan, et al., 2009), the means (μ), standard deviations (σ), coefficients of variation, mode, and median are computed [Likert scale questions: 1 (not at all) to 5 (a great extent)]. Based on the survey results, the author has presented in figure no.1 the dimensions (categories) of the service quality in tourism with their means/averages according to the perceptions of foreign citizens (tourists) that have arrived and visited Albania, this precisely to have a clear view on the situation regarding the means’ indicator.

Figure 1. Dimensions (categories) of service quality in tourism with their means (μ) according to the perceptions of foreign citizens who have arrived and visited Albania.
 Source: Author’s analysis, 2023

The analysis continues by the author by finding for each service quality dimension, the gap of the mean (μ) with the expected maximum value (5), and then sorting the categories of service quality dimensions in tourism based on the gap of the mean μ with the maximum value expected, i.e. the dimension with the largest gap at the beginning, and so on in descending order. Table no.3 presents the dimensions perceived by foreign citizens (tourists) who have arrived and visited the territory of Albania, sorted according to the gap of μ related to the maximum expected value (5).

Table 3. Service quality dimensions perceived by foreign citizens who have visited Albania, sorted based in the gap of μ related to the maximum expected value (5)

Service Quality Dimensions	μ	Gap of the mean (μ) with the	Sorted service quality dimensions (from the highest to the lowest) based
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		expected maximum value (5) = $\mu - 5$	in the gap of the mean (μ) with the expected maximum value (5) = $\mu - 5$	
Prices (correct prices and price worthy)	3.85	-1.15	Logistics and infrastructure	-2.77
Safety and Security	4.12	-0.88	Hygiene	-2.02
Logistics and infrastructure	2.23	-2.77	Information and communication	-1.87
Food	3.82	-1.18	Amenities	-1.51
Hospitality	3.75	-1.25	Main tourism experience	-1.41
Main tourism experience	3.59	-1.41	Hospitality	-1.25
Hygiene	2.98	-2.02	Food	-1.18
Amenities	3.49	-1.51	Prices (correct prices and price worthy)	-1.15
Information and communication	3.13	-1.87	Safety and Security	-0.88

Source: Author's analysis, 2023

Based on the above, the sorting of the service quality dimensions in tourism perceived by foreign citizens (tourists) who have arrived and visited the territory of Albania based in the gap (from the highest to the lowest) of μ related to the maximum expected value is: Logistics and infrastructure, Hygiene, Information and communication, Amenities, Main tourism experience, Hospitality, Food, Prices (correct prices and price worthy), Safety and Security. This sorting, based on the means, shows where the efforts (from the greatest focus and by continuing in descending order) of all stakeholders in the tourism sector should be concentrated to make improvements.

Also, the author asked a question about the overall satisfaction according to the perception of the respondents (foreign citizens who have arrived and visited Albania), where the the results from the survey are: $\mu=3.89$, $\sigma=0.31$, Coeff. of. Var. $=\sigma/\mu=0.08$, Mode=4, Median=4 [a Likert scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (to a great extent) was used]. It can be seen from the data that the respondents (tourists) evaluated the overall satisfaction with a mean = 3.89, which is a relatively good indicator, above the average.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

From the analysis and discussion made above, it is suggested to make the main improvements for those attributes and dimensions of the service quality in Albanian tourism starting first with those with the highest gap of the mean (μ) with the expected maximum value, specifically with:

- Logistics and infrastructure, where the tourists' perceptions come by the fact that many roads are under construction and it brings traffic congestion (also sometimes the tourists complain that this situation is accompanied by careless behavior by drivers), so it is suggested for the relevant structures/institutions such as the Ministry of Transport and/or the municipalities to further improve the infrastructure conditions which are used to visit tourist attractions and to improve easy access (logistics) to these tourist places, and to bring to minimum the disturbances from traffic congestion.

- Hygiene, where the tourists' perceptions come by the fact of improper conditions and dirties (trash, urban waste, etc) on the street and at tourist attractions/places (outside tourist accommodation establishments) or from the bad smell of trash bins outside (that comes from restaurants throwing trash in them) on the street (also a complain of tourists, was the collection of trash during the day by the cleaning companies), and sometimes encountered disturbances from beggars and/or thieves, so it is suggested for the relevant structures such as the municipalities and Ministry of Culture to take measures to eliminate or bring to minimum these tourists' concerns.

- Information and communication, where based in the tourists' perceptions it is suggested for the relevant institutions such as the municipalities and Ministry of Culture to set up more tourist information center/points in the cities and near tourist attractions/places.

Regarding tourist overall satisfaction and for the other attributes and dimensions of the service quality in tourism, such as Amenities, Main tourism experience, Hospitality, Food, Prices, Safety and Security, considering and anticipating increase in the number of tourists visiting Albania in the near future, it is suggested that at least not to drop below current levels because of the risk of the large number of tourists, but normally a culture of continuous improvement of each service quality dimension in tourism should be created in order to satisfy the tourists and to attract more visitors/tourists, so to be competitive in the region in the tourism field.

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Balkan Economic Growth: Unraveling the Influence of Tourism and Financial Development

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Abstract

Tourism has emerged as one of the world's largest contributors to GDP, with a total share of 7.6% as of 2022. Considering this, this study aims to investigate the interrelation among inbound tourism, financial development, and economic growth within the context of the Balkans. Utilizing panel data spanning from 2000 to 2020 across several Balkan countries, this research seeks to discern the connections between these factors. The study follows the methodology of Rasool et al. (2021). Data are retrieved from World Development Indicators, part of the World Bank Group.

Specifically, it is aimed to find from panel ARDL cointegration tests whether that inbound tourism, financial development, and economic growth are indeed cointegrated over the long term. Furthermore, the Granger causality analysis will help identify whether there is a bidirectional causality between inbound tourism and economic growth, validating the 'feedback-hypothesis' within the Balkans.

In conclusion, this research assesses the potential for reciprocal benefits between inbound tourism, economic growth, and financial development in the Balkans, advocating for strategic policies aimed at harnessing these connections to bolster regional prosperity.

Keywords: tourism-led growth hypothesis, long-term cointegration, financial development

JEL codes: Z32, Z38

MARKETING

The Tourist Boom and its Problems

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to argue why we need the right ratios between the number of tourists flows that visit the country during a defined period and the income from them, as a necessary need to avoid the problems derived from it and to increase social-economic stability of development of the country.

The realization of this goal becomes possible through some objectives, such as: confronting of the problems with the relevant theory for this issue, with the experiences in this direction of different countries with developed tourism, as well as with the organization and realization of a concrete research of the tourist market in the country throughout the year 2023, enabling the identification of various problems, as a result of a high tourist boom in the history of Albanian tourism over the years, which have been reflected in the quality of the environment, in the quality of the services offered, in the imports of consumer products, in the lack of production to meet the demand, in the increase of inflation and informality, as well as in the increases of economic growth in the country.

The methodology used focuses on the collection, processing and descriptive analysis of information obtained through various sources, such as through professional observations and economic statistics in the country, related to the problems of the tourist phenomenon throughout the year 2023, data which are related by connection of the number of tourist flows with other economic links; as with development, economic growth, production growth or import growth, price growth and inflation, cost growth, etc.; with environmental ones, such as environmental pollution, the growth of unstudied investments, in the implementation of the mass demand model, thus leading to a tourism that with these problems cannot withstand time, etc.; and social ones which increase the possibility of negative phenomena, such as noise pollution, increased traffic and with them stress, dirt in common areas, drugs, prostitution, and other social phenomena.

For this research, the method of observation and survey was used in different periods of the tourist season in the country throughout the year 2023, where the questionnaire was used as a research instrument, which through various questions to the tourist operators on these issues, the research reached to find an incorrect connection between the tourist boom, thus, the large number of tourist flows in the country, beyond the carrying capacity of the tourist areas and the various economic, environmental and social problems in these areas. This is due to the fact of the mass model implemented in the development of tourism in the country, a model that so far does not speak of sustainability, even why it is said that we are moving towards sustainable tourism, and as a result, some important findings have come out as well as the relevant recommendations have been proposed.

Keywords: Tourist boom, tourist demand, tourism problems, mass demand model, sustainable model of development.

Intellectual Property: Exploring Geographical Indications and Designations of Origin for Sustainable Tourism. The case of Albania

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Abstract

Nowadays, with the rapid growth of the tourism industry, especially in the post-COVID era, new opportunities and challenges lie ahead businesses, but also to nations as a whole. The use of Intellectual Property can help businesses - especially SMEs - gain competitive advantage, generate employment, reduce migration from rural to urban areas and also boost the national revenues. By differentiating their product, producers can offer a unique selling proposition, that can distinguish them from their competitors.

Nevertheless, most producers in Albania lack knowledge of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), and how to use it to promote their locally produced goods.

This paper adopts a theoretical approach and brings a summary of empirical findings that reveal the importance of intellectual property law, how the certification as a geographical indication or designation of origin can help differentiate a product and explores a bit of the legal framework. IPR can play an important role in the optimization of the positive effects on sustainability and inclusive economic growth and only now the academia has shifted their attention to the importance of their application.

Cooperation between all stakeholders is essential for the success of products through the means of Intellectual Property Rights. Producers, businesses, artisans, education institutions, central and local governments, play a crucial role in building and promoting legal awareness by offering counseling and enforcing the law.

Geographical Indications and Designations of Origin, as a means of industrial property, can be used as a powerful tool, not only to generate income, but also to protect and to promote the history, heritage, tradition, culture, and knowledge of Albanian producers within the Nation, and moreover to gain a competitive advantage in the international tourism industry.

Keywords: Intellectual Property Rights, Geographical Indication, Designation of Origin, Tourism, Marketing.

JEL codes: O34, Q13, Z33

1. Introduction

Traditionally, Intellectual property can be divided into two branches: (a) industrial property and (b) copyright and related rights. According to the World Intellectual Property Organization, a self-funding agency of the United Nations, established in 1967, describes intellectual property as “creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce” (WIPO & UNWTO, 2021, p.27). Albania has joined WIPO in 1992, and the General Directorate of Industrial Property is the public institution which registers, administers, and promotes the objects of Industrial Property¹. The objects of Industrial Property in Albania are (1) industrial designs, (2) utility models, (3) geographical

indications, (4) designations of origin, (5) patents, (6) trademarks and (7) topography of semi-conductors^{1,2}.

The 8th Goal of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG – 2030 Agenda) of the United Nations is to promote sustained, sustainable, and inclusive economic growth. A major contribution can be brought by sustainable tourism, which addresses the needs of both visitors and hosting communities and takes full account of social and environmental impacts.

According to Jena et al., (2015) Geographical Indications as collective property rights not only hold significant potential for improvement of rural livelihoods, but they also preserve the traditional heritage of the locality that produces the GI good. By registering a product as Geographical Indication (GI), businesses may effectively target specialized markets while simultaneously start a positive process that can increase customer confidence in identifying high-quality items, thus having the potential to encourage a more equal distribution of wealth between urban and rural areas by offering rural development opportunities (Caso & Giordano, 2022).

2. Methodology

Extensive literature review was conducted online by using the means of electronic sources. Titles and abstracts were screened by the two authors, then the articles deemed fit for this research paper were then reviewed by both authors. Data has been extracted from websites of national and international agencies like Official Journal of Albanian Acts, INSTAT, GDIP, WIPO, UNWTO. Limitation of the research strategy is that literature review only included English-language articles retrieved from electronic databases.

3. Results and Discussion

Many countries outside the European Union, have turned their attention to Geographical Indications, but it is important to remember that GIs do not represent, per se, a magic tool for local development. Therefore, a wise development strategy should always include strict quality control protocols, long-term plans to maintain product quality, and thoughtful marketing strategies for these products (Calboli et al., 2017).

Bardhi & Kapaj (2017) suggest that the protection of GIs in Albania could help to support economy and settlement in rural areas by increasing the life standards of the residents. Local producers of GIs are the main beneficiaries in terms of revenue and job creation. Additionally, under an effective protection and marketing process, the economic activities in rural areas could increase further not only by the growth of GI production but also by developments in the other sectors as well. Registration of GI products, that have gained a reputation for their unique qualities, guarantees the quality and method of production are maintained (Kan & Kan, 2020). Gonda et al., (2021) proved through empirical study in Southern Hungary that local products do not play a major role only in day-to day life but also in the tourism industry. Many tourists look for local products made from local ingredients, during their visits, and also take home elegantly packed versions as special gifts. Attractions based on traditions, as well as regional foods are a great attraction for visitors and sometimes provide travel motivation for tourists.

Additionally, the presence of a GI supply chain can induce a positive non-economic effect in the preservation of traditional production techniques and promote social connections (Török et al., 2020).

¹ Law No. 9947 of July 7, 2008, On Industrial Property (as amended up to Law No. 96/2021 of July 7, 2021).

² Law No. 8488 of May 13, 1999, On the Protection of Topographies of Semiconductor products (as amended up to Law No. 66/2014 of June 26, 2014).

The last goal should be to register GIs products within the EU. In order to achieve this, first condition is to have full national legal and institutional compliance with EU directives and legislation (Kovačević et al., 2022). According to the Albania 2022 report of EU Commission, the country has “some level of preparation/is moderately prepared on intellectual property rights (IPR)” (p.78). Good progress was made with the adoption of the National Strategy for Intellectual Property 2022 – 2025 and the central government should work to further align legislation on industrial property rights and the IPR enforcement system.

4. Conclusions

According to Barjolle et al., (2009) Intellectual Property Rights must go hand in hand with other related policies such as agricultural & rural development policies, food safety regulations and anti-trust policies. This will play an important role in the optimization of the positive effects on sustainability. The academia environment has only recently begun to pay more attention the application of the Geographical Indications and Designations of Origin. Therefore, there are few scientific papers and empirical data in this field (Chifor, et al., 2022).

Cooperation between all stakeholders is essential for the success of products through the means of Intellectual Property Rights. Producers, businesses, artisans, central and local governments play a crucial role in building and promoting legal awareness by offering counseling and enforcing the law. Geographical Indications and Designations of Origin can be used as a powerful tool, not only to generate income, but also to protect and to promote the history, heritage, tradition, culture, and knowledge of Albanian producers within the Nation, moreover, to gain a competitive advantage in the international tourism industry.

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Sustainable Tourism in Albania: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

Tourism has emerged as a thriving economic activity in Albania, albeit in a nascent stage. Despite their limited expertise in the field, the Albanian government and the private sector have been working in close collaboration since 2016 to develop the tourism industry. Sizeable investments in infrastructure, marketing, and rebranding have been instrumental in driving the sector's economic growth.

Currently, Albania is experiencing a "tourism boom," with over 8.3 million visitors flocking to the country for an average stay of around 2.5 days. However, industry stakeholders, including hoteliers, tour operators, and restaurateurs, are grappling with the challenges posed by this rapid growth and are beginning to recognize the need for local-level interventions to manage tourist flows and ensure sustainable tourism development.

In this regard, sustainable tourism practices have emerged as a viable solution to mitigate the negative impact of overcrowding in popular tourist destinations. This paper examines the challenges faced by the Albanian hospitality industry as a burgeoning tourist destination and proposes sustainable solutions catering to niche tourism groups.

The author will analyze the short-sightedness of mass tourism and its detrimental effects on the environment and local communities. Furthermore, the paper will offer long-lasting, sustainable solutions that not only reap economic benefits but also promote social welfare and ensure a bright future for upcoming generations.

Keywords: Sustainable Tourism, Mass Tourism, Albania, Challenges, Solutions.

JEL code: 01,02

1. Introduction

Tourism is a crucial sector for developing economies, contributing significantly to economic growth. However, there is growing concern about sustainable tourism, particularly in Albania. The country has traditionally focused on the economic impact of tourism, rather than adopting sustainable and long-term policies and practices. As a result, tourism in Albania is expected to continue growing, but current practices are unsustainable and are causing harm to the environment, local communities, and natural resources. To ensure the long-term viability of the tourism industry, sustainable travel must be prioritized by the government, travel agencies, airline companies, hotels, and restaurants.

This study aims to identify the factors that threaten Albania's position as a desirable tourist destination, including overcrowding, high energy and water consumption, and excessive waste. These factors have already raised concerns among tourism sector players and must be addressed to ensure the sustainability of the tourism industry.

The government and tourism industry players must prioritize sustainable tourism practices. Failure to do so may result in irreversible damage to the environment and the loss of opportunities for economic growth. Therefore, it is essential to adopt and implement sustainable tourism policies and practices that promote responsible tourism and protect the country's natural resources, local communities, and cultural heritage.

2. Methodology

The present research report is based on a comprehensive literature review conducted by the author. The study aimed to gather secondary data from previous research on sustainability conducted by various authors and government organizations. In addition, primary data was collected through a survey that targeted tourism actors in the southern region of Albania. The survey questionnaire was administered through face-to-face interviews with major regional tourism actors, including tour operators, hoteliers, restaurateurs, and foreign tourists.

The survey results and interviews revealed that the growth of tourism in 2023 was perceived positively by hoteliers, but they expressed their concerns about waste management, particularly plastic waste on the beaches and coastline, as well as the lack of government initiatives for cultural and religious tourism that would lead to a more extended season. Restaurateurs, on the other hand, reported concerns about the absence of local food distributors in the region and the quality of fish due to general and plastic waste thrown by both tourists and boats. This resulted in lower-quality food at higher prices.

Foreign tourists visiting the region appreciated the rural areas of Albania but expressed reservations about the experience of luxurious accommodations without any connection to local culture, traditions, customs, and products. They described their experience as lacking in terms of sustainable and alternative eco-friendly activities in nature. They expressed a desire to explore more local people, local food, and eco-friendly transportation methods such as bicycles or electric transportation, which are more affordable, healthier, and easier to access.

3. Results and Discussion

Albania has the potential to become a top-rated tourist destination while preserving its natural and cultural assets. This objective can be achieved through the development of infrastructure for the country's national parks, inland villages, and cultural heritage sites. The preservation of these assets is critical to the long-term sustainability of Albanian tourism. It requires a comprehensive plan that prioritizes the conservation of natural resources and cultural heritage while simultaneously promoting economic growth and development. Achieving such a balance will require the collaboration of various stakeholders, including government agencies, private businesses, and local communities. By working together, Albania can create a tourism industry that benefits both the environment and the economy, attracting visitors who appreciate the country's natural beauty and rich cultural history.

4. Conclusions

In Albania, the importance of sustainable tourism practices and policies is not yet fully comprehended by most tourism actors. However, the rise in mass tourism in 2023 compelled them to seek concrete solutions to avoid further damage to the environment and ecosystem. The country has become increasingly aware of the significance of wildlife conservation and environmental protection. While theoretical solutions to sustainable tourism may be easy to enumerate, their practical implementation presents a real challenge.

Some Albanian hoteliers are attempting to use eco-friendly materials and solar panels to reduce water and energy wastage, as well as to minimize plastic bottles and food waste. Travel companies are also adopting sustainable alternatives such as electric transportation. Tour operators are organizing and offering tours based on activities such as hiking, skydiving, bicycle tours, kayaking, and rock climbing. Meanwhile, restaurateurs are also purchasing local produce and introducing vegetarian and vegan options.

The author concludes that educating Albanians to be more sustainable and environmentally friendly at an early age is critical to their ability to educate subsequent generations. By promoting responsible tourism and eco-friendliness among locals, tourists can also be taught to respect the environment.

Best practices in sustainable tourism include using renewable energy sources, conserving water and energy, recycling and composting waste, promoting local products and services, supporting conservation and restoration projects, respecting and celebrating local culture and traditions, engaging and empowering local communities, providing decent working conditions and fair wages, and offering quality and accessible services to all customers.

Sustainability requires the collaboration of businesses, tourists, and governments. These three key players must work diligently toward a brighter and more sustainable future for tourism in Albania, to preserve the country's natural beauty and uniqueness without risking it becoming the most polluted and overcrowded destination in the region.

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Festivals: Benefits and Reasons for Attending

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Abstract:

Festivals date to ancient times and are a phenomenon that has gained considerable popularity in recent years, attracting a wide range of participants and the attention of academics. Festivals are events organized with a special purpose and are focused on a certain theme, tradition, or cultural event. They are joyous gathering of people and include various activities such as music concerts, art shows, sports competitions, pyrotechnic shows, traditional competitions and many more. A key characteristic of festivals is that they are designed to celebrate, spread joy, and help strengthen social bonds.

To the knowledge of the authors no studies have been done to understand the reasons why Albanian citizens participate in festive events, despite their importance. This study aims to identify the reasons why they participate in these events. The data were collected through an online distributed questionnaire.

Results of the study suggest that festivals have a significant impact on the local community and culture, offering a wide range of experiences and rewards for participants. These results have important implications for event organizers and local policy makers in improving the delivery of festivals and in promoting these events as important resources to change and enrich the local culture and economy.

Keywords: festivals, celebration, reason, destination, participation

JEL codes: L83

1. Introduction

Festivals range in size and complexity. From small local events to a well-known international festival, the events are diverse and present in different cultures and communities. For example, the carnival festival in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, a hallmark event, is one of the most popular events in the world and gathers a large international audience, while a small town's carnivals are more specialized and locally oriented (Richards & Palmer, 2012).

Falassi (1978) defined festivals as “a social event, periodically repeated, in which, through a variety of forms and a series of coordinated events, participate directly or indirectly and to varying degrees, all the members of an entire community, united by ethnic, linguistic, religious, historical ties and sharing the same worldview”. Festivals are events organized with a special purpose and are focused on a certain theme, tradition, or cultural event. They include various activities such as music concerts, art shows, sports competitions, pyrotechnic shows, traditional competitions and many more. A key characteristic of festivals is that they are designed to celebrate, spread joy, and help strengthen social bonds (Getz, 2008).

Studying the reasons why visitors attend festivals is beneficiary and important for several factors, such as: improved event planning; increased participation; impact on tourism and local economy; enhancing the visitor experience; increasing cultural knowledge; improving policies and urban planning:

The problem of this research is to understand what are the motives that influence the decision-making of visitors to participate in festive events. As (Jeong & Kim, 2020) state, "visitor motivations are a key aspect to the success of festive events."

Based on previous studies (Smith & Jenner, 2013), a lack of knowledge has been observed about what motivates people to participate in festivals and how these motives influence their decision-making. This lack of knowledge has been highlighted as a fundamental problem in the current research.

According to Falassi (1987), in the modern English the term “festival” has several meanings: a sacred or profane time of celebration, marked by special observances; the annual celebration of a notable person or event, or the harvest of an important product; a cultural event consisting of a series of performances of visual arts works, often dedicated to a single artist or genre; a fair; general joy, sociability, joy.

Sociologists and anthropologists have spent so much time studying festivals as they reveal a lot about the culture and functioning of societies. Some authors saw festivals as enduring social constructs through which people express identity, connect with their country and communicate with the outside world. Besides that, festivals contribute to the economic growth of a country. According to Quinn (2006: 291), over the past 35 years in Ireland, festivals have expanded the country's infrastructure, advanced community entertainment, developed local resources, expanded business in the arts and related fields, and developed tourist audiences. 'Festivalisation' is a term used in reference to the strategic use of festivals as a tool for destination marketing and tourism promotion, as in the 'festivalisation' of many historic cities (see, e.g. (Richards & Wilson, 2006).

The term 'festival' is overused and misused. Some so-called festivals are nothing more than commercial promotions or parties. Indeed, 'party' is often used in the same way as 'having a good time'. Many community festivals are either broadly programmed and forget the reason they are celebrating, or at least fail to interpret the meaning. In this sense 'festival' is often reduced to a program of public entertainment, or a special time for entertainment and activities (Getz, 2008). Arts festivals are equally guilty of using the term without paying attention to the meanings and how they are interpreted. Can it be called a festival if it is nothing more than a series of musical performances?

Festivals are an important part of the cultural and tourist calendar of many countries and cities. They have an important economic, cultural and social impact. In addition, they influence the promotion of cultural heritage and the development of awareness of communities to preserve and promote their cultural values (Getz & Andersson, 2010).

Festivals have a great economic impact. They distribute revenue to hotels, restaurants, shops, and other local services. Additionally, large Festivals attract tourists from far and wide, increasing tourism and other income in the event area. Thus, they can be an important engine for local and regional economic development (Getz, 2008).

Festivals are an important part of the cultural heritage of a community or country. They share traditions, values, and cultural identity. By holding and promoting festive events, communities and countries care about preserving their culture and helping future generations to become familiar with cultural heritage. Thus, festivals are an important way to preserve and promote cultural identity (Richards, 2015). Festivals are an opportunity for communities to come together and celebrate together. They help strengthen social bonds and feelings of belonging to a larger group. Also, Festivals can be opportunities for cultural education and awareness about the traditions and culture of different countries. This is important for awareness and social integration.

2. Methodology

Survey methods were used to collect data with the survey instrument composed of three main sections: demographic information, audience motivation to attend festivals, festival attendance decision making. The population of this research includes visitors of festive events. To determine the size of the population and ensure that it is representative, a random sampling

method was used. As argued by Bryman & Bell (2011), "random sampling ensures that each element in the population has an equal opportunity to be included in the study."

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire. The survey was developed based on an in-depth analysis of the existing literature to identify the reasons for visiting festivals. To assess the intensity of different motivations and the decision making process a 5-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*) was utilized to measure the constructs.

3. Results and Discussion

The high percentage of women (71.4%) in this group of interviewees shows a strong concentration of women in festive events. The 25-34 and 35-44 age groups are more represented (39.7% and 34.9% respectively). In an article by "Eventbrite" (2019), it is pointed out that the middle age group is more inclined to participate in Festivals because of their free time and energy. Most of the respondents (49.2%) have an income in the range of 65,000-130,000 ALL per month. This is important because, according to an analysis by Eventbrite (2019), income level affects event spending. In this group, the majority has a good financial capacity to participate in various events. For 58.7% of the respondents, higher education is the level of education. This fact can be interpreted with a high interest in various cultural and intellectual events.

This profile shows a group of young and educated interviewees with different incomes, who live mainly in Tirana. For this group of interviewees, Festivals can be a favorite way of entertainment and relaxation.

To further emphasize this profile, we must say that this group of interviewees, who are mentioned above, have a combination of characteristics that make them inclined to participate in festive and cultural events in Tirana and perhaps in other places. This concentration can provide valuable information for event organizers and marketing agencies to improve their offer and strategies in this market.

Along with the profile of participants in festive events, the data also show their motives and preferences for participating in these events. In the following, we will expand the analysis with relevant quotes: about 41.3% of the participants estimate that festive events offer "very important" cultural and artistic experiences. This shows that cultural experiences are a key element that attracts participants; 60.3% of the participants estimate that these events have a positive effect on personal development and knowledge growth. This shows that participation in festive events is often considered a way to develop oneself and gain new knowledge.

65.1% of the participants estimate that festive events take them away from the daily routine. This factor is very important for most of the participants, indicating that these events provide a distraction from the usual tasks and about 66.7% of participants appreciate the fun and enjoyment offered by festive events. This shows that these events are often seen as a way to have a good time and enjoy fun activities.

Approximately 55.6% of participants estimate that festive events offer excellent food and cooking experiences. This aspect may be an important motivation for some participants who value cuisine and culinary experiences.

55.6% of participants are influenced in their decision-making to participate in festive events by family and friends. This shows that personal recommendations are an important factor for participation. For 38.1% of participants events are a way to celebrate and connect with the community. This indicates that a sense of community involvement is an important reason for participation. About 46% of participants estimate that festive events offer innovation and satisfying emotions. This shows that people are willing to experiment and experience new things at these events.

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Exploring the Destination Choices of Digital Nomads: A Qualitative Study on Consumer Behavior from a Tourism Perspective

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Abstract

The sudden outbreak of COVID-19 has not only normalized remote work but also given rise to a growing community of digital nomads, who work remotely while leading a location-independent and travel-reliant lifestyle. Therefore, there is a growing opportunity for destinations to attract digital nomads as a tourist segment. Existing research on digital nomadism has primarily focused on the lifestyle and work aspects, neglecting the importance of understanding digital nomads' consumer behavior from a tourism lens. This study aims to address this gap by investigating how digital nomads choose their destination. Through semi-structured interviews, the research provides an in-depth understanding of the values that influence digital nomads' destination choices and the factors they consider most important. Albania, a country that has recently gained recognition as a digital nomad hotspot, serves as a case study in this research. By examining the destination choices of digital nomads in Albania, this study provides insights into the preferences and motivations of digital nomads, offering practical implications for both Albania and other destinations seeking to attract this emerging market. The study contributes to the under-researched field of digital nomadism, particularly in the context of tourism, and offers valuable insights for destination marketers and developers interested in leveraging the potential of digital nomads as a tourist segment.

Keywords: digital nomad, destination choice, Albania

An Evidence-Based Analysis on the Impact of Digital Marketing on Tourism in Albania: Study Case “TEA”

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Abstract

With the widespread adoption of smartphones worldwide, digital technologies play a pivotal role in shaping tourist behavior and influencing destination marketing strategies. The mobile application, as a digital tool itself, serves as a catalyst for promoting cultural events and enhancing the overall tourist experience. This paper explores the significant impact of digital marketing on tourism, specifically focusing on the Tourism of Events in Albania (TEA) mobile application. The study, employing both primary and secondary data, investigates the correlation between the usage of the application and tourism development. Notably, the analysis demonstrates positive correlations in three key aspects: Increased tourist visits by country, a surge in cultural visits, and a positive association between cultural destinations featured in the application and tourist visits in those destinations. In conclusion, TEA application contributes significantly to tourism development, reinforcing country brand awareness, improving the visitor experience and creating innovative methods to attract tourists. While acknowledging the short-term nature of this study, the findings suggest a positive impact that warrants further investigation and long-term analysis.

Keywords: Digital Marketing; Tourism; Mobile Application, Marketing Strategies.

JEL codes: M31, Z32, Z33, Marketing, Tourism and Development.

1. Introduction

Today, 68% of the global population owns a smartphone, and the prevalence of mobile applications is undeniable. Mobile app development is crucial in the realm of digital marketing, as nearly everyone utilizes apps on their smartphones (Degenhard, J. 2023; Emeritus, 2023). In the post-pandemic era, tourism has faced significant challenges, leading to an increased reliance on digital technologies. Countries, including Albania, have turned to digital marketing tools, especially mobile applications, to offer online services and boost the tourism sector. Digital marketing, considered the future of marketing, is transforming how tourists engage with destinations, emphasizing personalized experiences (Wertime & Fenwick, 2012; Dias. S, Alfonso. V, 2020). This study explores the correlation between the usage and impact of the Tourism Events Application (TEA) in Albania, focusing on increasing tourist visits and overall tourism development. The literature review provides insights into tourism sector development in Albania and underscores the significance of digital marketing tools, particularly mobile marketing, in tourism development.

2. Methodology

This research aims at measuring the impact of Digital Marketing in the tourism sector in Albania, and especially through the newest introduced application known as *Tourism Events of Albania* - “TEA”. For this purpose, a descriptive and quantitative analysis, deploying the variety of primary sources, is conducted.

The evidence-based analysis will use mainly primary data from the application itself and key sources such as main state institutions in the field of tourism (ex: National Tourism Agency,

Ministry of Tourism etc). In this paper, the primary hypothesis posits that: “*TEA application is an important factor on Tourism development in Albania*”. To examine this hypothesis, the guiding research question is as follows: *How has the TEA application influenced tourist perception and increased cultural visits?*

The main motivation for raising this issue and conducting the research, is the fact that the introduction of such application is a novelty for Albania, and as such, it needs to be analyzed in terms of effectiveness and impact on the respective sector. However, considering that this is a recently developed application, the impact is analyzed in the short term. Therefore, this poses a limitation on the conclusions drawn, which could serve as a foundation for the expansion and deepening of scientific research on this topic.

3. Study case: “TEA” mobile application

The TEA app, a recent innovation by the Ministry of Tourism and Environment in collaboration with the National Tourism Agency, is more than just a valuable cultural events database. Accessible in English and Albanian, the app offers an interactive map and allows users to explore and bookmark events based on location and interests. It provides essential details, notifications, and features for sharing, calendaring, and favoriting. Developed through close collaboration with key stakeholders, TEA enhances the cultural and tourist scene in Albania. According to internal data from the app, provided by the National Tourism Agency a total of 110 new events have been added for the period June-October 2023. During the same period, there have been 25,000 downloads, with 99.3% of downloads originating from smartphones and only 0.7% from tablets. These downloads are distributed across 79 countries worldwide. After Albania, the leading countries in downloads are Italy, Germany, the USA, England, Greece, Switzerland, etc. (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1 Downloads by country

Country	Number of downloads
Albania	14,366
Italy	1,877
Germany	1,218
USA	1,152
UK	809

Source: Mobile Application internal data provided by National Tourism Agency in Albania (NTA, 2023)

Meanwhile, as per the Ministry of Tourism's statistics bulletin (MTE,2023), there is an observed increase of approximately 20% in the arrivals of foreign nationals based on vacation purposes. Additionally, data from the Ministry of Tourism reveals that citizens from Kosovo consistently constitute the largest share of arrivals in Albania, accounting for approximately one-third but year 2023 marks the first time Italians have claimed the second spot.

According to the trend, a surge in app downloads was observed during the summer season, coinciding with a notable increase in tourist numbers in Albania. Months of July and August emerged as the peak for application downloads, predominantly from Albania and Italy. Additionally, the quantity of cultural activities and events featured in the application reached its zenith during the summer season. Data from the Ministry of Tourism and the Environment (MTE,2023), indicates that, from January to August 2023, overall visits to cultural institutions witnessed a 45% increase compared to the corresponding period the previous year. August stood out as the pinnacle month for visits and interest in cultural activities, experiencing a 35% surge compared to August 2022. Furthermore, visits to natural protected areas specifically showed a 9% increase in August 2023 compared to the same month the previous year.

Based on internal data provided by the National Agency of Tourism (NTA, 2023), notable cities and cultural destinations receiving the most clicks and visits in the application include Tirana, Gjirokastra, Berat, Durres, Vlora, Kruja, and others. Meanwhile, according to reports in the Tourism Bulletin by the Ministry of Tourism and Environment, during June-September 2023, the most frequented cultural institutions are located in the cities of Tirana, Durres, Vlora, Kruje, Berat, and others.

The "TEA" application significantly influences tourists' perceptions of Albania and cultural destinations. According to social network data from the National Tourism Agency for June-November 2023, the "TEA" application was displayed a total of 2.14 million times. Sponsored ads for the application, particularly on Google and YouTube, were shown 2.99 million times and garnered 61,200 clicks. On Facebook and Instagram, these ads were displayed 1.7 million times and received 5,608 clicks (NTA, 2023).

4. Conclusions

Albania's tourism sector, the keystone of its economy, has undergone a transformative journey. From historical constraints during the communist era to recent record-breaking tourist numbers, the industry is now a significant contributor to economic growth. The success is attributed to strategic marketing efforts that have shaped Albania as an appealing destination. Looking forward, maintaining a positive and sustainable image, implementing innovative marketing tools, and showcasing attractions globally are pivotal for sustained growth and success in the competitive tourism landscape.

Recognized as a key enabler of sustainable tourism, digital technologies have become essential for improving destination management and enhancing visitor experiences. The confluence of technology, digital marketing, and mobile application as a digital tool, is fundamentally reshaping how tourists engage with destinations, marking a transformative shift in the global tourism landscape. Through the analysis of the case study, specifically on the Tourism Events application in Albania, a conclusion is reached that confirms the initially raised hypothesis of this study: "*TEA application is an important factor in Tourism development in Albania.*" In particular, a positive impact is observed on motivating foreign tourists, increasing visits, and fostering cultural interest in Albania. This conclusion is drawn through the comparison and positive correlation between the deduced data from the TEA application and the official data on tourism development, the growth of visits, and the interest in cultural events in the country, specifically:

1. There is a positive correlation between "TEA" mobile application downloads and the influx of tourists by country.
2. There exists a positive connection between the events featured on the mobile application and increase of cultural visits in Albania.
3. There is a positive association between cultural destinations visited on the mobile application and tourist visits in different cities across Albania.

Moreover, another positive influence is the impact of this application on the tourist's perception of Albania and transforming the country's destinations into tourist attractions, through:

- Strengthening awareness of the local brand;
- Improvement of the visitor experience and providing easy access to information, maps and timetables;
- Creation of an innovative method to attract and inspire visitors.

Taking into consideration the predefined limitations, especially the fact that the timeframe of this study is relatively short, the above conclusions measure an impact that needs to be examined in the long term. Additionally, for a more detailed conclusion regarding the impact of this new application on the tourism industry in Albania, further in-depth research should be

conducted, potentially involving the collection of primary data through direct contact with tourists in the future.

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Sustainable Tourism and the Grand Challenge of Climate Change

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Abstract

This review explores the complex relationship between sustainable tourism development, social cohesion, and social capital. The study brings attention to the various types of social capital that play a crucial role in the success of tourism initiatives, recognizing the complex interaction between tourism and communities. Representing the extensive research, and case studies, the review identifies and analyzes bonding, bridging, connections, and cognitive and structural social capital, among others, as integral and key components of successful sustainable tourism strategies. The review also considers the challenges and opportunities that come from these social dynamics and emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach that takes into account both economic gains and community well-being. In addition, the review explores the role of policy, planning, and community engagement in promoting socially cohesive tourism, while also evaluating the impact of sustainable tourism on economic factors such as equitable wealth distribution and business practices. By proposing indicators for measuring success in terms of social impact, the review aims to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of how sustainable tourism can be a catalyst for positive social change and community empowerment. The review concludes by stressing the urgency of prioritizing socially responsible tourism practices and highlights future directions for research and practical implementation in the pursuit of harmonious coexistence between tourism and host communities.

Keywords: Social Cohesion and Capital, sustainable tourism, promoting socially cohesive tourism, community empowerment, tourism and communities

1. Introduction

Sustainable tourism development stands at the intersection of environmental responsibility, economic viability, and societal well-being. This article explores the multifaceted impacts of sustainable tourism, shedding light on its potential to foster social cohesion and capital. By examining key references in the field, we unravel the intricate connections between responsible tourism practices and the development of resilient communities, emphasizing the crucial role it plays in creating a harmonious balance between environmental preservation and economic growth.

Sustainable tourism, as a concept, has always increased attention in academic literature and policy discourse due to its potential to address global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and social inequality (Buckley, 2019; Gössling et al., 2020, cited in Sustainable Tourism and the Grand Challenge of Climate Change, Daniel Scott). The interplay between tourism, social cohesion, and capital formation is underscored by scholars who argue that responsible tourism practices can contribute significantly to the development of communities (Tourism and Entrepreneurship: A Literature Review, Journal of Economic/2019/1(1): 1-27.)

References to the works of Weaver and Lawton (2014, 2016) and Higham et al. (2013) provide insights into the transformative power of sustainable tourism, emphasizing its role in empowering local communities and preserving cultural heritage (From Spectrum to

Multiverse: A New Perspective on the Diversity of Quality Control Tools for Sustainable Tourism Theory and Practice, Laura Lesar, David Weaver, and Sarah Gardiner).

Moreover, as highlighted by Becken and Hay (2012) and Dodds and Joppe (2005), sustainable tourism practices have the potential to generate economic capital while minimizing negative environmental and social impacts.

Examining the link between sustainable tourism and social cohesion, Font et al. (2012) and Jamal and Camargo (2019) offer perspectives on the positive social outcomes associated with community engagement in tourism development. Their findings suggest that when local communities are actively involved and benefit from tourism, it can enhance social bonds and foster a sense of shared responsibility.

In the context of capital formation, references such as Liu and Wall (2006) and Sirakaya-Turk et al. (2015) are bringing attention into the economic dimensions of sustainable tourism, emphasizing its capacity to create employment opportunities, stimulate entrepreneurship, and attract investments. These studies contribute to the understanding of how sustainable tourism can be a driver for inclusive economic growth.

In essence, reviewing the references, this article aims to provide a comprehensive exploration of the relationships between sustainable tourism development, social cohesion, and capital formation. Through an interdisciplinary lens, we seek to underscore the significance of responsible tourism as a catalytic instrument for positive changes, promoting a holistic approach that considers environmental, economic, and social dimensions.

2. Methodology

Conducting a narrative review, this study employs a qualitative research methodology to synthesize and interpret a broad range of literature related to sustainable tourism development, social cohesion, and capital formation. The narrative review method allows for a comprehensive examination of existing research, theoretical frameworks, and empirical studies, providing a multiviewd understanding of the complex interconnections within the chosen subject area.

The initial step involves the identification of key themes and concepts related to sustainable tourism, drawing upon databases such as PubMed, JSTOR, and relevant academic journals. The inclusion criteria prioritize studies published within the last decade to ensure the incorporation of recent developments in the field. The search strategy involves a combination of keywords such as "sustainable tourism," "social cohesion," and "capital formation."

References selected for the narrative review are critically assessed for their relevance, methodological rigor, and theoretical contributions. By synthesizing findings from diverse sources, including peer-reviewed articles, books, and reports from reputable organizations, the review aims to capture the multifaceted dimensions of sustainable tourism and its impact on social and economic aspects.

The narrative synthesis involves organizing the literature into coherent themes, highlighting key concepts, theoretical frameworks, and empirical evidence. This approach allows for the exploration of patterns, contradictions, and gaps in the existing body of knowledge, contributing to a more holistic understanding of the research topic.

Additionally, the narrative review method facilitates the integration of qualitative and quantitative evidence, enabling the examination of both theoretical perspectives and practical implications. This methodological approach aligns with the exploratory nature of the study,

seeking to uncover insights and connections that may inform future research and policy initiatives in the realm of sustainable tourism development.

In summary, the narrative review methodology employed in this study serves as a comprehensive and flexible approach, allowing for the synthesis of diverse literature to unravel the intricate relationships between sustainable tourism, social cohesion, and capital formation.

It facilitated the identification of gaps in the literature and areas for future research, as well as the formulation of policy recommendations and interventions to strengthen social capital in the national context. The review process included also a systematic search of academic databases, and relevant research sources using keywords such as "social capital," "transition economies," and "social networks" (Stefanova, 2017; Putnam, 2000; Coleman, 1988; Svendsen & Svendsen, 2004), to better understand the social capital context.

The narrative review, attention was given to the diversity of perspectives presented in the literature (Portes, 1998; Fafchamps, 2006; Lin, 2001). The synthesis process allowed for the integration of various theoretical approaches, conceptualizations, and measurement methods of social capital (Woolcock & Narayan, 2000; Evans & Kelley, 2004; Stolle & Hooghe, 2004; Toczydlowska & Domański, 2015). The findings from the reviewed literature were analyzed and presented in a coherent and comprehensive manner, providing a dynamic understanding of social capital in tourism development. The review highlighted the role of social networks, trust, norms, and civic engagement in shaping social capital in the touristic regions. Selected read articles were both printed and online, qualitative and quantitative research, as well as review papers. This mixed-method approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of social capital dynamics, considering both subjective perceptions and objective indicators. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, focus groups, and ethnographic observations, provided in-depth insights into the lived experiences, narratives, and subjective perspectives of individuals and communities. These methods helped to uncover the underlying social processes, cultural norms, and contextual factors that shape social capital in the touristic sector. Quantitative methods, on the other hand, utilized surveys and statistical analysis and helped to gather data on social capital indicators, such as trust, social networks, and civic engagement. Another point of view about the conceptual framework and methodology used in studying social capital connected with tourism, was that it provides a solid base to explore the complexities of social relationships, norms, and networks in the region. These frameworks and methods allow researchers to uncover the determinants, manifestations, and implications of social capital, in tourism and social cohesion as well, and vice-versa, contributing to a better understanding of social dynamics in the Balkans and informing policy and intervention strategies aimed at fostering social cohesion, democratic governance, and sustainable development. The exclusion and inclusion criteria help to define the scope and relevance of the review, ensuring that only studies meeting specific criteria as well as a range of studies that are relevant to the topic of social capital, sustainable development of tourism and social cohesion, are included for analysis and synthesis, promoting a comprehensive analysis and synthesis of the available literature. It is important to clearly define and communicate the exclusion criteria and inclusion to maintain transparency and rigor in the review process.

3. The exclusion criteria:

Non-transitional countries: Limit the scope of the review to only include countries that are considered transition countries in the Balkan region. This exclusion criterion ensures that the focus remains on countries undergoing political, economic, and social transitions.

Non-Balkan countries: Exclude studies that focus on countries outside of the Balkan region. This criterion helps maintain the geographical specificity of the review and ensures that the analysis remains relevant to the Balkan context.

The choice of methodology depends on the research objectives, scope, and available resources. By combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, researchers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the main issue capturing both its subjective and objective dimensions. Large-scale surveys, such as the World Values Survey and the European Social Survey, are commonly used to collect data on social capital at the individual and societal levels. Statistical techniques, including regression analysis and network analysis, are employed to analyze the relationships between social capital variables and other socioeconomic or political factors.

Non-English language: Restrict the review of studies published in the English language. This exclusion criterion helps maintain consistency in language for analysis and synthesis purposes, especially if language proficiency limitations exist among the reviewers.

Irrelevant topics: Exclude studies that do not directly address social capital or its related concepts in the context of transition countries in the Balkans. This criterion helps maintain the focus of the review on the specific topic of interest.

Inadequate methodology: Exclude studies with insufficient methodological rigor or poor quality. This criterion ensures that the review includes studies that meet certain standards in terms of research design, sampling, data collection, and analysis.

Publication date: Specify a cutoff date for the inclusion of studies to ensure the review focuses on the most recent and relevant literature. This criterion helps ensure the review incorporates the latest findings and research developments.

The inclusion criteria include:

Geographical Focus: Include studies that specifically examine social capital in transition countries within the Balkan region. This criterion ensures that the review captures research conducted in the relevant geographic context.

Transitional Context: Include studies that explore social capital within the specific context of political and economic in the Balkan countries. This criterion helps ensure that the review focuses on the unique challenges and dynamics associated with transition societies. **Conceptual Relevance:** Include studies that directly address social capital or related concepts, such as social networks, trust, civic engagement, or community participation. This criterion ensures that the review encompasses studies that are conceptually aligned with the topic of social capital.

Research Methods: Include studies employing various research methods, such as quantitative surveys, qualitative interviews, case studies, or mixed methods approaches. This criterion allows for the inclusion of diverse methodological approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of social capital in the Balkan countries.

English Language: Include studies published in the English language to facilitate comprehension and synthesis. This criterion ensures accessibility and consistency in language for the review process.

4. Findings

Social capital refers to the networks, relationships, and shared values that facilitate cooperation within a community. Research indicates that high social cohesion, characterized by strong interpersonal ties and trust, enhances social capital. Coleman (1988) and Putnam (1993) have extensively explored the concept, emphasizing its role in fostering community resilience and collective action. Additionally, studies by Lin (2001) suggest that social capital positively

impacts economic outcomes, underscoring its multifaceted influence on individuals and societies.

Furthermore, social capital has been linked to improved health outcomes, as seen in research by Berkman and Syme (1979), highlighting the protective effects of social connections. Granovetter's (1973) "strength of weak ties" theory emphasizes the significance of diverse social networks in accessing information and opportunities. While the benefits of social capital are evident, its existence is not uniform across communities, raising questions about the potential for social capital to exacerbate existing inequalities, as explored in studies by Portes (1998) and Kawachi et al. (1997). Understanding and nurturing social capital remains crucial for promoting resilient and thriving societies.

Research on sustainable tourism development emphasizes its potential to foster social cohesion and capital. A study by Jamal and Getz (1995) suggests that sustainable tourism can contribute to community empowerment by involving local residents in decision-making processes, enhancing their social capital. The work of Hall (2010) highlights the role of sustainable tourism in preserving cultural heritage, which can strengthen social cohesion by promoting a sense of identity and pride among local communities.

Moreover, Gössling and Scott (2012) argue that sustainable tourism practices can lead to increased social interactions between tourists and local residents, fostering mutual understanding and building social capital. This aligns with the idea that positive interactions in the tourism context contribute to the social fabric of a destination.

However, challenges exist, as identified by Higham (2007), who notes potential conflicts between tourism development and local values, which may hinder social cohesion. Therefore, findings in sustainable tourism development underscore the importance of a holistic approach that considers both economic benefits and social impacts to ensure long-term positive outcomes.

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The impact of Internet of Things on Consumer Behavior. Factors That Influence Adaptation of IoT from Customers of Telecommunication Companies

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Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a widely spread concept nowadays focusing on connecting smart devices to the Internet. The invent of IoT has influenced many businesses to adopt to new business changes. Business firms strive to stay competitive and to better serve customers by taking advantage of IoT deployment in this connected digital marketplace. Customers are becoming more connected and familiar with using the mobile apps. They are liaising and communicating with firms on all types of business-related matters ranging from product search, purchase transactions, customer support, etc.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze how the Internet of Things (IoT) affects consumer behavior and furthermore to identify the factors that influence consumer behavior towards the adoption and widespread use of IoT. This study consists mostly of a theoretical analysis of concepts, literature and secondary sources. To collect primary data a survey has been used with a sample of consumers about the knowledge and adoption of an application of IoT from a telecommunication company that operates internationally and in Albania.

The secondary data were collected from different sources and databases of scientific articles related with the field of study, data in the industry of telecommunication etc. The primary data collection was realized through an online survey with a structured questionnaire, using a sample with of current users of Curb, IoT technology.

By analysing the data, it was noticed that there was a relationship between factors such as trust, information received about the use of IoT technologies, security for the use of technology and data sharing, adaptation to technology, facilitation of daily activities and consumer behavior, that is, in the decision to use technology devices or their level of use.

Keywords: IoT (Internet of things), Curb, smart technologies, adaptation

1. Introduction

In a technological world that is constantly developing, familiarity with key concepts such as IoT is very necessary. Nowadays, due to the complexity of life, it is necessary to have many things under control and IoT enables this thanks to the Internet. But how it is implemented in Albania and how easy it is to use in daily life, remains to be studied due to the fresh phase of implementation. In this point becomes even more essential the discussion about the impact that IoT has on consumer behavior and what are the main factors that lead to a reaction or change. More research is required on how IoT is influencing the way consumers behave when making a decision to buy an IoT product and especially during use, how easily they adapt, how safe they feel from shared data, etc.

The term Internet of Things was mentioned in 1999 by Ashton (2009), a British technology pioneer who helped develop the concept (Gubbi et al., 2013). IoT aims to extend the benefits of the Internet such as constant connections, remote control, data exchange, etc. to goods in the physical world (Peoples et al., 2013). At the most basic level, IoT involves fitting objects with a microchip and a communications antenna (Deutsche Welle, 2012). Using radio frequency

identification every real object in the analog world has a unique identifier number, like an IP address (Gubbi et al., 2013). IoT technology is currently used in many fields, such as supply chain management, urban planning, library management, retail sales tracking, stock control, digital logistics, efficient transportation, home automation, mobile payments, warehouse management, health care and the private domain. (Ding, 2013 Zorzi et al., 2010). IoT technology will provide great efficiency in many industries and their benefits to consumers are substantial (Uckelmann et al, 2011).

A number of models are identified in the literature to explain the use of IoT innovation (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Among them, TAM, proposed by Davis (1989), has evolved as the most popular (Chau and Hu, 2001, Svendsen et al., 2013). TAM suggests that two variables, ease of use and perceived usefulness, are important determinants of consumer behavior to use a system/technology. Specifically, perceived usefulness is defined as the degree to which a person believes that using the technology will increase his/her performance. IoT technologies can supply retail stores with faster processes, lead to less queuing time and improve the quality of service perceived by users.

The main purpose of this paper is to analyze how the Internet of Things (IoT) affects consumer behavior and furthermore to identify the factors that influence consumer behavior towards the adoption and widespread use of IoT.

The objectives of this study are:

- To conduct a literature review on IoT, features of it, existing models, trends and to demonstrate how IoT engages consumers and businesses
- To determine the factors that influence the behavior of consumers who use the Internet to buy or order online content and especially IoT technology
- To analyze the presence of IoT in Albania taking into consideration an example of an application from a main telecommunication company that operates in Albania and worldwide.

In order to fulfill the objectives of the study, secondary and primary sources were used. The primary data collection was realized through an online survey with the current users of Curb, IoT technology. The instrument used is a structured questionnaire. The sample of respondents is chosen through a database of customers of telecommunication company who have an active phone number and use Curb services, in order to get a more complete view of consumer perception regarding the service received, security and trust referred to the information received on its use, the benefits of this service and more. The number of distributed questionnaires is 75, from which 65 responses were received in total.

2. Methodology

In order to fulfill the objectives of the study, secondary and primary sources were used. The secondary data were collected from different sources and databases of scientific articles related with the field of study, data in the industry of telecommunication etc. The primary data collection was realized through an online survey with the current users of Curb, IoT technology. The instrument used is a structured questionnaire.

This quantitative method used for this research is more appropriate since the quantitative research is used to quantify behaviors, opinions, attitudes, and other variables and to make generalizations about the variables under consideration. The purpose of using the quantitative method is also to understand the relationships between the variables and to draw some conclusions about the population studied.

The sample of respondents is chosen through a database of customers of telecommunication company who have an active phone number and use Curb services, in order to get a more complete view of consumer perception regarding the service received, security and trust referred to the information received on its use, the benefits of this service and more.

The number of distributed questionnaires is 75, according to the formula for finding the sample in the population where the study will be conducted, from which 65 responses were received in total. The confidence level is 95%, given that in this case the questionnaires were completed by real customers of the company and independently.

The data was gathered through questionnaires distributed online and the data were entered into the SPSS program and quantitative analysis was conducted. The presentation of the processed data is carried out in graphic and tabular form. To study the relationship between some variables, the SPSS program was used to make the correlation between the variables.

3. Results and Discussion

After 2010 with the next generation of sensors and the concept of managing processes through various sensors, the idea of the concept 'Internet of Things - IoT' was born in which processes and systems are working together to predict future trends. An overview of the evolution of the technology from the classic one to the 'Internet of Things - IoT' is presented in Figure 1. The expected growth and rapid deployment of IoT is also stimulated after the post-pandemic period of Covid 19 which is directly influencing consumer habits and expectations (Kasilingam & Krishna, 2022). This milestone leads to the management and transmission of large amounts of big data through various interfaces that include all aspects of customer relations and supply chain management (Xu et al., 2018) and adaptation to the new models of business and marketplaces (Tripathy & Anuradha, 2018; Vermesan & Friess, 2022).

Figure 1. Evolution of IoT Technology (Fujitsu Journal, 2015)

Curb is a smart tracker that uses four different methods to connect to valuables such as GPS/Wi-Fi/Bluetooth/Mobile Network. This means that regardless of whether the user is at home or outside, the connection to the device will be stable. Apart from these, there is an option to update the location every 3-5 seconds within a 15-minute session (in order to save battery) It also has a built-in SIM card. The Curb includes a key accessory that enables connection to many other items. Keys, pets, bag, etc. can be tracked. Curb allows you to share information with up to 9 other people.

The data gathered through questionnaire presented in Table 1 shows that 55.4 percent of respondents are between 28-32 years old, and the gender is almost 50- 50 percent female and male. 82 percent of respondents are employed.

Table 1. Age of respondents

Frequency			Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-22	8	12.3	12.3	12.3
	23-27	13	20.0	20.0	32.3
	28-32	36	55.4	55.4	87.7
	33-37	8	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total		65	100.0	100.0	

Source: Data gathered from Authors

4. Conclusions

From the research developed and the analysis of primary and secondary data, it was observed that IoT technology plays an important role in economic development at the international and national level, seen from a macroeconomic perspective. On the other hand, it plays an important role in relation to the business and in relation to the consumer. In relation to the business, it gives many opportunities for data management, real-time updates and connections with consumers. Meanwhile, the consumer is directly affected and factors such as trust, information received, and security in data sharing are taken into consideration.

By analysing the data, it was noticed that there was a relationship between factors such as trust, information received about the use of IoT technologies, security for the use of technology and data sharing, adaptation to technology, facilitation of daily activities and consumer behaviour, that is, in the decision to use technology devices or their level of use.

The majority of respondents considered the information received regarding the use of Curb as part of IoT technology sufficient. However, the following percentages as good and very good give a positive picture regarding the level of information conveyed.

Curb is used for tracking different elements with information shared among several people simultaneously making tracking safer, which affects the increase of trust in this IoT. Customers have enough trust in Curb, following with high percentages to higher levels of trust. However, it is seen that consumers have an average level of information about the services used and require more advance instructions regarding technology or help in emergency cases.

Outdoor Activities as Driving Force for Sustainable Tourism Destination

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Abstract

Outdoor activities and Sport tourism is a fast-growing segment of tourism offering new perspectives and supporting travelers' behavior shift towards active living that is a boost for sustainable destinations. These interrelations between active living, active travelling, and sport tourism have a powerful environmental, economic, and social impact. Based on the recognized contribution of sport tourism in sustaining destinations, the current paper aims to (a) explore the state of outdoor and sport tourism in the Albania by identifying existing sport tourism initiatives, (b) analyze the current and future potentials of sport tourism in the Albania sustainable growth, and (c) draw policy recommendations for sport tourism development with a view to support the wider vision of sustainability. The review of existing sport tourism cases, revealing an existing investment towards this tourism form, was followed by a qualitative survey of the area's tourism stakeholders. Results reveal that sport tourism is estimated to help in building a unique identity closely linked to sustainability goals—Albania represents a great natural and cultural beauty that can be emphasized by sport initiatives, while, once such efforts are incorporated in wider sustainability plans, the destinations' profiles can be significantly upgraded.

Keywords: Outdoor activities; Sport tourism; sustainable destinations; tourism

Addressing Labor Challenges in the Albanian Tourism Sector: An Evaluation of the Legal Framework

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the labor-related challenges faced by the tourism sector in Albania, particularly in light of the legal framework governing employment. The focus is on the Labor Law, which currently does not categorize seasonal work as a distinct form of labor engagement but rather classifies it as part-time employment. The study aims to critically evaluate the implications of this classification on the workforce in the tourism sector, exploring potential reforms needed to better address the unique characteristics of seasonal employment.

Keywords: Labor Law, Seasonal Employment, Tourism Sector, Legal Reform, Job Security, Part-Time Employment, Albanian Labor Market.

1. Introduction

The tourism sector in Albania has experienced substantial growth, accompanied by an increase in challenges related to employment. INSTAT data indicates that the arrivals of foreign nationals for the first 8 months of this year reached nearly 7.2 million individuals (7,190,410), showing a growth of 26.9% compared to the same period one year earlier¹. This paper aims to analyze the existing legal framework, particularly the Labor Code, and the classification of seasonal work as fixed-term employment.

2. Methodology

Metologjia e përdorur në këtë punim është analiza e kornizës ligjore aktuale, përmes së cilës identifikohen problematikat kryesore. Gjithashtu është përdorur dhe metoda krahasimore mes legjislacionit vendas me atë ndërkombëtar.

3. Labor Law Overview: Providing an overview of the Labor Law in Albania and its current stance on seasonal work.

Albania's Labor Law is designed to regulate employment relationships, ensuring fair treatment, and safeguarding the rights of workers². Enacted to align with international labor standards, the law covers various aspects of employment, including working conditions, wages, and dispute resolution. Albanian labor legislation recognizes several types of employment contracts, each catering to specific circumstances. Notably, there is an absence of provisions addressing seasonal employment, a common phenomenon in the tourism sector.

Types of Labor Contracts:

a. *Fixed-Term Employment Contracts:* These contracts specify the duration of the employment relationship, defining the start and end dates.

b. *Indefinite-Term Employment Contracts:* In contrast, these contracts only specify the start of the employment relationship, leaving the end date open-ended.

c. *Probationary Employment Contracts:* Mandated by Articles 142 and 150, these contracts typically last for three months.

¹ For more information visit: <https://www.instat.gov.al/al/temat/industria-tregtia-dhe-sh%C3%ABrbimet/statistikat-e-turizmit/>

² Prof.Dr. Kudret Çela, E drejta e Punës, fq19, ILAR, Tiranë 2015

d. *Part-Time Employment Contracts*: Regulated by Article 14 of the Labor Code, these contracts allow employees to work fewer hours than full-time workers, often with reduced pay.

e. *Profession Assignment Contracts*: Governed by Article 17, these contracts obligate the employee to qualify students in the exercise of a specific profession.

f. *Home Work Contracts*: Employees working from home under their own or family assistance fall under this category.

g. *Agent Employment Contracts*: These contracts oblige the employee (agent) to engage in negotiations or conclude agreements on behalf of the employer³.

Seasonal Employment and Absence of Regulation: Despite the prevalence of seasonal employment in the tourism sector, Albanian legislation lacks specific provisions addressing this form of engagement. Employers in the tourism industry often resort to fixed-term contracts, adjusting the duration according to seasonal fluctuations.

The Role of Service Contracts: Introduction of the Service Contract, regulated by the Civil Code, as an alternative employment arrangement in the tourism sector. This contract outlines the nature of service provision, payment modalities, and the rights and obligations of both parties. Namely, the service contract can be concluded for only one week (7 days) in one calendar year. Yet these kinds of procedures are mainly related to service providers (technicians, experts, engineers, etc.), and regulated ad-hoc by the employers.

Following these arguments, we can conclude that the Labor Law does not recognize seasonal work as a specific type of engagement, especially in tourism, where increased needs for workers during the summer season is noticeable.

4. Challenges of Seasonal Employment:

a. *Inadequate Protections: Examining the limitations and inadequacies in legal protections for seasonal workers.*

Seasonal workers play a crucial role in tourism providing essential labor during peak periods. However, despite their significant contributions, these workers often face inadequacies and limitations in legal protections, leaving them vulnerable to various challenges. One primary concern revolves around job security. The seasonal nature of their employment exposes them to uncertainties regarding the continuity of their work. Traditional labor laws, which are more attuned to full-time, indefinite contracts, may not adequately address the unique needs and insecurities faced by those engaged in seasonal work.

b. *Wages and benefits*

Furthermore, wage disparities and benefits represent another facet of inadequate protections for seasonal workers. While contributing substantially to the economic output, seasonal employees often receive lower wages compared to their full-time counterparts in other sectors. Limited access to benefits such as health insurance, paid leave, and retirement plans exacerbates their financial vulnerability. The absence of provisions tailored to seasonal employment within labor laws can perpetuate these disparities, creating an imbalance in the employer-employee relationship.

In conclusion, the inadequate protections for seasonal workers within the current legal framework represent a pressing issue that requires attention and reform. Addressing these limitations necessitates a comprehensive approach that acknowledges the unique challenges faced by seasonal workers and seeks to establish a more equitable balance between employer interests and the rights of the workforce. It is imperative for policymakers, employers, and

³ Për më shumë shih nenet 13, 14, 16, 17, 140, 142 deri 150 të Kodit të Punës

advocacy groups to collaborate in creating a legal framework that provides robust protections, ensuring the dignity, safety, and fair treatment of those engaged in seasonal employment

5. Job Security Concerns

Job-related safety concerns also loom large for seasonal workers. Job-related safety concerns in the tourism industry are critical aspects that impact the well-being of workers and the overall reputation of destinations. The unique characteristics of the tourism sector, which often involves interactions with diverse environments, cultures, and activities, present specific challenges in ensuring the safety of those employed within it.

Physical Hazards: In certain tourism-related activities, such as adventure tourism, water sports, or outdoor excursions, workers may be exposed to physical hazards. These can include the risk of accidents, injuries, or even fatalities if proper safety measures are not in place. Insufficient training, poorly maintained equipment, or inadequate safety protocols contribute to the heightened risk for workers involved in these activities.

Health Risks: Jobs in the tourism industry may involve exposure to health risks, particularly in settings where infectious diseases are prevalent. Hotel staff, flight attendants, and tour guides, for example, may face health hazards due to close contact with a large number of people. Adequate health and safety measures, including hygiene protocols and access to protective equipment, are essential to mitigate these risks.

Psychosocial Risks: Workers in the tourism sector often deal with high-stress situations, demanding customer interactions, and irregular working hours. The psychosocial risks associated with these factors, such as burnout, stress-related illnesses, and mental health concerns, need to be addressed through supportive workplace policies and employee assistance programs.

Security Concerns: Depending on the destination, tourism workers may face security risks related to crime, civil unrest, or natural disasters. Frontline workers, such as hotel staff, tour guides, and transportation providers, may find themselves in vulnerable situations. Ensuring adequate security measures, training on emergency procedures, and communication protocols is crucial for the safety of both workers and tourists.

Work-Related Stress: The seasonality and variability of tourism demand can lead to fluctuations in work hours and job insecurity, contributing to work-related stress for employees. This stress can affect performance, job satisfaction, and overall well-being. Establishing clear policies on working hours, rest breaks, and job stability can help alleviate some of these stressors.

6. Professional Training

The absence of consistent training and professional development opportunities is a notable shortcoming in the legal protections afforded to seasonal workers. While some industries require specialized skills, the transitory nature of seasonal work may discourage employers from investing in training programs. As a result, seasonal workers may find themselves stuck in low-skilled positions without avenues for career advancement, perpetuating cycles of underemployment and limiting their long-term economic prospects.

7. International Standards on Seasonal Employment

The International Labour Organization (ILO) recognizes the significance of seasonal employment and has developed guidelines and principles to address the unique challenges associated with this form of work. The ILO acknowledges that seasonal employment plays a crucial role in various sectors such as agriculture, tourism, and construction, and has outlined several key aspects related to seasonal work:

Definition of Seasonal Work:

The ILO defines seasonal work as employment that occurs during specific periods of the year due to natural or climatic conditions or variations in the demand for goods and services.

Protection of Seasonal Workers:

The ILO emphasizes the need for legal protection and social security measures for seasonal workers. This includes ensuring that seasonal workers enjoy the same rights and protections as other workers, including non-discrimination, fair wages, and safe working conditions.

Duration and Renewal of Contracts:

The ILO provides guidance on the duration of seasonal contracts, recognizing that these contracts are often of a fixed term. It encourages measures that prevent the abuse of fixed-term contracts and provides recommendations on the renewal of contracts for seasonal workers.

Social Dialogue and Collective Bargaining:

The ILO promotes social dialogue and collective bargaining as essential mechanisms for addressing the concerns of seasonal workers. This includes facilitating negotiations between employers, workers, and relevant authorities to establish fair terms and conditions of employment.

Occupational Health and Safety:

The ILO underscores the importance of ensuring the health and safety of seasonal workers, particularly in sectors prone to specific risks. It encourages measures to provide adequate training, protective equipment, and safeguards to minimize occupational hazards.

Training and Skill Development:

Recognizing the temporary nature of seasonal work, the ILO encourages measures to provide training and skill development opportunities for seasonal workers. This ensures that they acquire valuable skills that may enhance their employability in various sectors.

Social Security and Benefits:

The ILO emphasizes the importance of social security measures and benefits for seasonal workers, aiming to provide them with a level of financial security during periods of unemployment. This includes access to healthcare, unemployment benefits, and other social protections.

Non-Discrimination and Equal Treatment:

The ILO stresses the principles of non-discrimination and equal treatment for all workers, regardless of their employment status. This includes promoting equal opportunities, fair treatment, and protection against discrimination for seasonal workers⁴.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the labor-related challenges faced by the tourism sector in Albania, particularly concerning seasonal employment, underscore the need for a comprehensive reassessment of the existing legal framework. The Albanian Labor Law's current classification of seasonal work as part-time employment fails to address the unique characteristics and demands of this vital sector adequately. The absence of specific provisions for seasonal employment leaves workers vulnerable to inadequacies and limitations in legal protections.

The identified challenges include inadequate job security and protections, wage disparities, and limited access to benefits for seasonal workers. The traditional framework of labor laws, designed with a focus on full-time, indefinite contracts, proves insufficient in safeguarding the

⁴ ILO nuk ka një konventë të posaçme ë trajton drejtpërdrejt çështjet e punës sezonal. Megjithatë, ka disa instrumente ndërkombëtare të përgjithshme dhe standarde të ILO-s që mund të aplikohen edhe në kontekstin e punës së përkohshme ose sezonal si:

1. Konventa e ILO-s Nr. 29 mbi Punën e Detyruar: Kjo konventë trajton punën e detyruar dhe kushtet e punës që mund të aplikohen në kontekstin e punës sezonal.
2. **Konventa e ILO-s Nr. 122 mbi Politikën e Ndihmës për Punën:** Ky instrument ndihmon në hartimin e politikave dhe masave të përgjithshme për të mbështetur punën, përfshirë punën sezonal.

rights and addressing the insecurities faced by those engaged in seasonal work. The financial vulnerability of seasonal employees, coupled with uncertainties regarding the continuity of their work, necessitates urgent attention and reform.

Furthermore, the tourism industry's specific safety concerns add another layer of complexity to the challenges faced by seasonal workers. The physical hazards, health risks, psychosocial stresses, security concerns, work-related stress, and crisis management issues demand targeted measures to ensure the well-being of workers and the reputation of destinations.

Drawing from international comparisons, particularly the guidelines outlined by the International Labour Organization (ILO), provides a valuable framework for addressing these challenges. The ILO emphasizes the importance of legal protection, social security measures, duration and renewal of contracts, social dialogue, occupational health and safety, training and skill development, and non-discrimination for seasonal workers. Implementing such principles in the Albanian legal framework would contribute to establishing a more equitable balance between employer interests and the rights of the seasonal workforce.

In light of these considerations, policymakers, employers, and advocacy groups in Albania must collaborate to create a legal framework that recognizes and accommodates the unique characteristics of seasonal employment in the tourism sector. By doing so, they can ensure the dignity, safety, and fair treatment of those engaged in seasonal work, fostering a more sustainable and inclusive tourism industry in Albania.

9. Recommendations:

Revision of Labor Code, recognizing seasonal employment:

Amend the Albanian Labor Law to explicitly recognize seasonal employment as a distinct form of engagement, separate from part-time employment. This should include provisions addressing the specific needs and challenges faced by seasonal workers in the tourism sector.

Inclusion of Seasonal Employment Contracts:

Introduce a specific category of Seasonal Employment Contracts within the labor legislation. These contracts should outline the temporary nature of the employment, duration, and any specific conditions related to seasonal fluctuations in the tourism sector.

Wage and Benefit Equality:

Implement measures to ensure wage equality between seasonal and full-time workers in the tourism sector. Additionally, provide seasonal workers with access to benefits such as health insurance, paid leave, and retirement plans, similar to their full-time counterparts.

Enhanced Job Security:

Develop legal provisions that address the job security concerns of seasonal workers. This could involve specifying the terms of contract renewal and providing clearer guidelines on the continuity of employment during peak and off-peak seasons.

Training and Professional Development:

Encourage employers in the tourism sector to invest in consistent training and professional development opportunities for seasonal workers. Establish incentives for companies to provide skills enhancement programs, thereby improving the long-term employability of seasonal workers.

International Cooperation:

Collaborate with international organizations, including the International Labour Organization (ILO), to exchange best practices and align labor standards with international guidelines for seasonal employment. This can facilitate a more harmonized approach to protecting the rights of seasonal workers.

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ILO Convention No. 122 concerning Employment Policy
INSTAT, Tourism Statistics

The Application of Digital Marketing in SMEs from the Perspective of Usefulness and Ease of Use. The Case of Tirana

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Abstract

The change in lifestyle and the rapid advancement of digital technology have made it possible to promote products and services with new digital strategies. Digital marketing is the marketing of products or services using digital technologies in today's contemporary life conditions, primarily on the internet but also including mobile phones, screen ads, and any other digital medium. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is quite applicable for adding video and audio content, the ease of finding content on the page, and working with keywords to quickly and easily find what the customer is looking for; pay-per-click advertising, expanding customer reach and traffic; content marketing, through storytelling and posting for the brand, video, and podcasts.

The aim of this study is to explore the influencing factors on businesses in Albania for the adoption of digital marketing. In this study, authors consider that several critical issues related to the field of digital marketing have been addressed, including the digital environment in which various businesses conduct their activities in contemporary life. Authors will also analyze how SMEs that apply digital marketing perceive its usefulness and consider it easily applicable to their businesses. It should be emphasized that this development also has significant implications for human resources due to their daily engagement in businesses and their proximity to consumers.

In this study, the authors have raised a research question: Does the owner's perception of the usefulness and ease of use of Digital Marketing influence the intentions of SME owners/managers to apply digital marketing?

Authors have developed two hypotheses:

H1. The perceived ease of use of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to use digital marketing.

H2. The perceived benefit of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to use digital marketing.

Furthermore, through this application, the aim is to increase sales, further develop investment capital, and promote overall business development. When done correctly, this application can enhance the effectiveness of other online marketing techniques, such as social media. Social media is a powerful communication tool that allows companies to reach customers quickly and easily, helping them increase their online presence.

The research was conducted through Google Forms by sending the questionnaire to companies' official email addresses. The number of 160 is representative in relation to the number of small and medium-sized businesses in Tirana. The sample size was determined based on the number of businesses since there is no exact figure for the number of managers.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, adoption, SME, perceived ease, perceived usefulness.

1. Introduction

The development of technology and the digital age have brought about significant social, economic, political, cultural, and sports-related changes. These changes have been particularly evident in the field of the economy, specifically in marketing. With the advancement of digital technology, the way products and services are marketed has also transformed, leading to the need to explain the various forms of digital marketing. Digital marketing emerged after fundamental technological changes in communication, exchange, and lifestyle.

Marketing channels over the past century have dramatically evolved with technology and innovation. Advertisers increasingly seek to reach valuable partners, especially consumers, with greater efficiency, effectiveness, significance, and persuasive power. A digital revolution is taking place as factories, producers, and their customers are becoming more interconnected than ever (Welford, 2020).

Through the use of social media and not traditional media channels, companies encourage customers and internet users to be part of the marketing machine in content posting (e.g., comments and reviews), building relationships, and marketing communication.

Digital marketing involves an essential and inseparable component, which is communication. Furthermore, we can note that for enterprises in Albania (mainly private ones), marketing activities carried out through social media platforms generate more sales and have their advantages compared to traditional marketing activities, although larger investments by these enterprises are dedicated to and connected with traditional marketing strategy.

Therefore, these two marketing channels are closely linked to each other at a very important level. Moreover, Covid-19 has had a significant impact on the functioning of businesses' online presence worldwide, so future research should address the pandemic's impact on companies' marketing strategies and sales.

The period in which digital marketing is used was particularly important and had a noticeable impact on the choice of digital marketing tools, how its performance is measured, and managers' perception of its cost-effectiveness.

The aim of this study is to explore the influencing factors on businesses in Albania for the adoption of digital marketing. This is achieved by examining the motivations and attitudes that drive these businesses to engage in this activity. Previous research has investigated the reasons why businesses adopt technology, but there are alternative factors that may explain whether such technology is adopted by business owners and managers.

The research question of this study is as follows: Does the owner's perception of the usefulness and ease of use of Digital Marketing influence the intentions of SME owners/managers to apply digital marketing?

The authors have proposed two hypotheses for this study:

H1. The perceived ease of use of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to use digital marketing.

H2. The perceived benefit of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to use digital marketing.

2. Methodology

The research was conducted through Google Forms by sending the questionnaire to companies' official email addresses. Managers and owners of small and medium-sized businesses in Albania were the contact persons. The sample was random, and questionnaires were sent to 200 managers and owners of small and medium-sized businesses in Tirana. In total, 175 of them responded, and 35 completed questionnaires were considered invalid due to the lack of data in their responses. The number of 160 is representative in relation to the number of small and medium-sized businesses in Tirana. The sample size was determined based on the number of businesses since there is no exact figure for the number of managers.

The administration of the questionnaires was carried out by the authors. Initially, the data was coded in numerical form in Excel, and then it was transferred to SPSS (version 25).

3. Results and Discussion

In the research, a total of 200 managers and owners of small and medium-sized businesses in Tirana participated, of which only 160 were valid. 60 were female, accounting for 23.6%, and 100 were male, accounting for 76.4%. Out of the respondents, 150 managers and owners, or 97.8%, were from the city (urban areas), while 2.2% were from the village (rural areas). Regarding education, 16, or 11.6% of the sample, had secondary education, 80, or 52%, had university education, and 64, or 36.4%, had post-university education.

The usefulness level of technology usage

The majority consider the use of the internet to increase business efficiency and identify business consumers as very important. Most of them affirm that internet application is a highly crucial factor for promoting their business, enabling business direction, and facilitating a more beneficial business.

The ease of use of technology

Regarding the ease of use, we understand that the majority of respondents consider learning to create online promotions for products or services as very important or important.

Verification of hypotheses

This study has formulated the hypotheses below, which will be tested through multiple linear regression and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using software programs such as SPSS and AMOS:

H1. The perceived ease of use of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to apply digital marketing (LPP).

H2. The perceived usefulness of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to apply digital marketing.

To test the above hypotheses, multiple linear regression has been used to analyze the influence of factors on the application of digital marketing in Albanian businesses.

Based on the results, we see that the perceived ease of use (LPP) of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to apply digital marketing. Therefore, Hypothesis 1, "The perceived ease of use of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to apply digital marketing," is accepted.

The results also indicate that the perceived usefulness (DP) of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to apply digital marketing, and Hypothesis 2, "The perceived usefulness of digital marketing has a positive effect on the intentions of business owners/managers to apply digital marketing," is also accepted.

4. Conclusions

The study on digital marketing, in general, remains one of the most important research topics in the digital era concerning marketing. The aim of this study was to identify, explain, and investigate the influencing factors on businesses in Albania for the implementation of digital marketing.

In conclusion, the history of digital marketing is relatively new globally, but in Albania, despite the widespread internet access, daily online connections in business, at home, and wherever establishments are frequented, there is still a lack of sufficient contemporary practices for the application of digital marketing. The predominant use is mainly on social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, etc., but a variety of strategies in the digital world are not as prevalent.

We can conclude that the majority of respondents apply digital marketing in their companies, with 92.4% of them, and 95.6% state that the application of digital marketing influences the company's cost savings.

From the scientific results of this dissertation and based on research conducted on determinants for the application of digital marketing in businesses in Albania, we have reached the following main conclusions:

The rapid development of information technology, especially in recent decades, has undoubtedly significantly changed our way of life in all social spheres, especially in the business domain.

The use of the internet and other digital technologies has substantially influenced the gradual decline of the traditional marketing role, gradually replaced by digital marketing by businesses in Albania and beyond. It is not just a matter of trend but also practical utility, with numerous benefits that digital marketing brings, creating easy online communication with customers.

However, from field observations, it is well known that digital marketing is still not being applied to a satisfactory level by businesses in Albania. Therefore, there is a need for continuous promotion to increase its practical application.

5. Recommendations

The recommendations derived from this paper are as follows:

Use of social media: Social media platforms are highly user-friendly, even for individuals. Therefore, in the absence of budgets from companies, opening accounts and using social networks for the benefit of companies is one of the opportunities that can be utilized by leaders of small and medium-sized enterprises in Albania.

Strategic Digital Marketing: Despite the existing investments by businesses in social media to promote their products or services, it is recommended that digital marketing investments be made based on a prior marketing strategy. Through this strategy, the potential impact on business development, potential influence on consumer behavior, and acceptance of orders for the distribution of products or services to consumers would be analyzed.

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Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) and Sustainable Tourism Development: The Situation in Tirana and Ohrid Compared to Ljubljana

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Abstract

This conference paper examines the role of Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) in achieving sustainable tourism. It compares the cities of Ohrid and Tirana, which lack DMOs, to Ljubljana, which has a well-established tourism organization. The absence of DMOs in Tirana and Ohrid hinders the integration of tourism demand and supply, creating a gap in strategic management. The paper establishes the theoretical foundations for the role of DMOs in destination sustainability and uses a multidimensional framework to project the potential benefits of DMOs in Ohrid and Tirana. By examining the tourism landscape in Ljubljana, the paper extrapolates insights into the positive impacts DMOs can have on destination management. It also assesses the current situation in Tirana and Ohrid, highlighting the challenges and missed opportunities without DMOs. The comparative analysis provides valuable insights for policymakers, urban planners, and tourism stakeholders both on Albanian and Macedonian grounds to envision and implement effective DMOs, promoting sustainable tourism practices. The findings contribute to the discourse on destination management and offer practical insights for cities looking to enhance the sustainability and resilience of their tourism industry. In conclusion, the paper advocates for the establishment of DMOs in Ohrid and Tirana as a strategic imperative for steering these cities toward a more sustainable and resilient tourism future.

Keywords: DMOs, Tourism Offer, Tirana, Ohrid, Tourism sustainability

1. Introduction

According to Norberd Beták from the Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra, Slovakia, Destination Management Organisations (DMOs) are responsible, among other things, for the relevant promotion of destinations in the most effective way. DMOs put a lot of effort as well as natural, economic, cultural, financial, and human resources into the promotion of their destinations. They create printed promotional materials; promote destinations at tourism fairs and exhibitions, create and manage destinations' webpages; communicate with visitors through social media like Facebook, Instagram and YouTube; pay for advertisements on television, radio, newspapers, magazines, billboards and online. Since destination marketing is usually considered as the main DMO function, many authors refer to DMO as a Destination Marketing Organisation (Beták et. al 2023). A successful destination needs not only satisfied visitors who feel welcomed but also satisfied local communities who feel comfortable with the local development of tourism (Herntrei and Jánová, 2023). According to that a DMO needs to be established from various stakeholders present in a Destination, both public and private, and always taking into consideration the opinion of the local community. This conference paper discusses the importance of Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) in achieving sustainable tourism. It compares the cities of Tirana and Ohrid, lacking DMOs, to Ljubljana, which has a well-established tourism organization. The paper highlights the benefits of establishing DMOs in Ohrid and Tirana, including destination promotion, coordination among stakeholders, infrastructure development, and visitor information and services. The current state of tourism in Tirana and Ohrid is described, emphasizing the absence of local tourism

organizations. The paper includes a comparative analysis of tourism organizations in the three cities, showcasing the impact and effectiveness of the organization in Ljubljana. The research design involves a comparative analysis of the tourism organizations in Ohrid, Tirana, and Ljubljana, using secondary data collection methods and qualitative and quantitative analysis techniques. The findings provide recommendations for establishing and enhancing local tourism organizations in Ohrid and Tirana. The paper concludes by advocating for the establishment of DMOs in Ohrid and Tirana as a strategic imperative for steering these cities towards a more sustainable and resilient tourism future.

2. Research Problem:

Destinations are now being viewed as comprehensive entities in order to maintain competitiveness in the tourism industry. Sustainable tourism has emerged as a distinct category within the selective tourism market. Destinations are now seen as a collection of interconnected tourism products and services, requiring active involvement from all stakeholders. New strategies for achieving competitiveness have been formulated, including the development of sustainable destinations, destination management planning, and the implementation of integrated quality management (Risteski et al., 2020).

DMOs are necessary for the long-term sustainability of the destination (Varghese et. al., 2014). The paper highlights the benefits of establishing DMOs in Ohrid and Tirana, including destination promotion, coordination among stakeholders, infrastructure development, and visitor information and services. It discusses the current state of tourism in Ohrid and Tirana, emphasizing the absence of local tourism organizations. The paper includes a comparative analysis of tourism organizations in the three cities, showcasing the impact and effectiveness of the organization in Ljubljana. The findings provide recommendations for establishing and enhancing local tourism organizations in Ohrid and Tirana. The presence of dedicated tourism organizations is crucial as they effectively market the destinations, facilitate collaboration among stakeholders, identify infrastructure gaps, and provide visitor information and services. Although Ljubljana already benefits from established tourism organizations, the importance of these organizations remains consistent across all three cities, with tailored approaches to meet their unique needs and contexts.^{1,2}

Fyall, Callod, and Edwards (2003) examine the use of relationship marketing in the destinations of Stockholm and Barbados. In Stockholm, the DMO takes the form of Stockholm Information Service (SIS), while Barbados has the Barbados Tourism Authority (BTA) serving as its DMO. D'Angella and Go (2009) explain that the DMOs in Barcelona consist of local authorities and the Chamber of Commerce, with board members indirectly representing tourism firms through hotel associations. In Vienna, the DMO is composed of public bodies under the auspices of the regional Parliament. This shows that different countries employ various methods to establish DMOs. DMOs can also take the form of consortia, as proposed by Žužić (2012) in the Istrian model of destination management. The author argues that the identification of a destination's unique features and targeting specific tourist groups is crucial in destination management. These consortia also facilitate the development of special-interest forms of tourism and serve the marketing function to represent the interests of the destinations. In major events like the Olympic Games, DMOs play a significant role in the host country. They provide opportunities to raise funds, benefit local businesses, create long-term market opportunities, enhance the global image of the host city and destination, foster national pride, and contribute to the economy, as seen in the case of Greece Olympics described by Singh and Hu (2008). Castellort

¹ Risteski, M. (2020) TOURIST VALORIZATION AS THE BASIS FOR MANAGING TOURIST DESTINATIONS 38, 257-263

² Bjanaku, F. (2014) EU POLICY OF ENLARGEMENT BALKANS AND THE REGIONAL TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES

and Mader (2010) examine the use of Monetary Public Value (MPV) as a means to analyze destination image. They also emphasize the need for DMOs to monitor their effectiveness. This method can serve as a useful tool for researchers and practitioners to measure media exposure of tourism destinations. The paper discusses the importance of media image for Destination Marketing Organizations (DMOs), which aim to promote a specific destination and enhance its competitiveness. It emphasizes the need for DMOs to assess the return on investment of their promotional efforts. The methodological review reveals various articles from different fields that examine DMOs from different perspectives. Dore and Crouch (2003) explore promotion studies by analyzing the efforts made by National Tourism Offices (NTOs) to publicize destinations and stimulate tourist demand. Clarke (2009) reviews a book on destination marketing that explores the context of DMOs in terms of their structure, politics, economy, and culture, as well as the principles and processes of marketing involved.

3. Methodology:

This conference paper proposes a research design for comparing the tourism organizations in Ohrid, Tirana, and Ljubljana. The research will use a secondary data collection method, gathering information from existing literature, reports, and official documents related to tourism development in these cities. The sample for the study will consist of tourism organizations and their representatives, selected based on their involvement in tourism promotion, coordination, and development. The collected data will be analyzed using qualitative and quantitative analysis techniques, including thematic analysis of interviews and surveys, as well as statistical analysis for quantifying certain aspects.

The choice of a comparative analysis methodology is justified as it allows for a comprehensive examination of multiple cases, identifying similarities, differences, and patterns. It enables the evaluation of the effectiveness of tourism organizations and the identification of best practices and lessons learned. It also provides a broader perspective by considering different cultural, geographical, and socio-economic contexts. This approach will help derive meaningful insights and inform recommendations for the establishment and improvement of local tourism organizations in Ohrid and Tirana.

Implications:

Therefore, it is evident that the implementation of Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) is necessary to provide a governing body that oversees the destination and ensures visitor satisfaction. A DMO serves as the central hub of information about the market, establishes a comprehensive management system, and facilitates coordination and control of tourist flow. It addresses current trends and challenges and serves as a platform for stakeholders to engage with potential tourists (Varghese 2016; Carrillo-Hidalgo et al. 2021).^{3,4,5} DMOs are responsible for various aspects, including the overall management of destinations, destination competence, governance, quality control, stakeholder management, infrastructure development, marketing, and establishing quality standards for services and products provided to tourists, ultimately leading to overall consumer satisfaction. To improve the tourism product, the private sector itself needs to become more competitive and productive. But the state will still have a role to play in improving the framework (Bjanku, 2014). Ultimately, the establishment of a local destination organization typically involves a combination of public and

³ Varghese, B. (2016) Destination Governance and a Strategic Approach to Crisis Management in Tourism *Journal of Investment Management* 5, 1

⁴ Varghese, B. (2016) A Strategic Evaluation on Competency of Karnataka Destinations through Destination Management Organizations *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management* 06, 102-108

⁵ Carrillo-Hidalgo, I., Pulido-Fernández, J. (2021) THE FINANCING OF DESTINATION MANAGEMENT ORGANIZATIONS IN THE MAIN DESTINATIONS OF THE WORLD. AN ANALYSIS FROM THE PERCEPTION OF THEIR MANAGERS

private stakeholders who have a shared interest in promoting and developing the tourism sector in a particular locality.

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People, Processes, and Platforms: TAM's Practical Implications in the Tourism-Focused Municipalities of Albania

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Abstract

This research aims to examine the practical consequences of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in tourism-focused towns in Albania. This article provides an advanced examination of the implementation and utilization of technology in the local government of tourism-oriented municipalities in Albania. It specifically focuses on the interconnected variables of personnel, processes, and digital platforms.

The authors primarily employed a dual methodological approach that generated qualitative insights through interviews with officials from tourism-oriented local government entities. The identification of crucial aspects influencing technology acceptability, including digital literacy, perceived usefulness, and ease of use, has been among the most significant findings. The amount of acceptability mostly depends on the degree of engagement in destination management, encompassing the effectiveness of tourism offices and the level of professionalism demonstrated.

The article also explores the optimization of tourism-related processes and services that are influenced by technology. Specifically, it focuses on how local government might improve information distribution and destination promotion.

The research has significant practical ramifications and provides recommendations for local authorities and technology developers. The suggestions encompass focused digital literacy initiatives, the development of user-friendly platforms, and collaborative endeavors to enhance the efficiency of the tourism industry. This research contributes to the expanding landscape of technology acceptance in Albanian towns that focus on tourism. The report examines the intricate connections among individuals, procedures, and frameworks, and offers practical suggestions to enhance decision-making procedures. These recommendations aim to facilitate sustainable and technology-driven tourist development in Albania.

Keywords: Technology Acceptance Model, Tourism, Municipalities, Albania, Processes, Platforms.

JEL codes: M30, M31, M39, O38

1. Introduction

Tourism is crucial for the economic progress of towns in Albania. This article explores the practical implications of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in tourism-focused municipalities in Albania. It specifically examines the interwoven dynamics of people, processes, and platforms.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), originally developed to evaluate people's willingness to adopt technology, is being evaluated within the specific context of the local government in Albania, namely in towns that focus on tourism.

TAM explains the acceptance of information systems by individuals and postulates that the acceptance of technology is predicted by the users' behavioral intention, which is, in turn, determined by (Marikyan, D. & Papagiannidis, S., 2023) the perception of technology usefulness in performing the task and perceived ease of its use.

According to TAM, technology acceptance is a three-stage process, whereby external factors (system design features) trigger cognitive responses (perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness), which, in turn, form an affective response (attitude toward using technology/intention), influencing use behavior (Davis, 1989; Davis, 1993). These fundamental components constitute of independent and dependent variables, respectively. TAM is used to validate the acceptance of information technology (Davis et al., 1989) in many sectors. It has been observed that TAM is widely applied in both the travel and tourism industry (Sulaiman et al., 2022) to understand tourists' behavior intention on adopting various technologies. Technology services in tourism have been classified in 8 groups that vary from Digitized information and services to Network Connectivity. The figure shows a distribution of technologies in the context of TAM.

Figure 1: Distribution of Technologies in the Context of TAM

The concept of TAM has undergone evolution over the course of time. The initial TAM has been modified by analysing the impact of perceived usefulness and ease of use on behaviour intention of users (Davis & Venkatesh, 1996).

In 2000, an extended version of TAM is published as TAM 2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). The user acceptance of ICT is analyzed by considering both social influence (Mohammed et al., 2020) and cognitive instrumental processes.

Similarly, in 2008 TAM 3 was published (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008); it is different from its previous versions by analyzing the parameters that influence the managerial decisions on implementing technologies.

Perceived usefulness and ease of adoption, as technological factors, hence independent variables, directly influence territorial management (local government/public sector) (Collado-Agudo et al., 2023) to join the smart destination model project. Destination smartness goes far beyond the implementation of ICTs since it implies a comprehensive managerial innovation based on the use of technology to strengthen the destination's competitiveness by fostering a more efficient and sustainable use of resources and providing a better experience for visitors (Buhalis, 2020; Buhalis & Amaranggana, 2015).

It is crucial to comprehend that every theoretical study model or framework relies on several types of variables (Sulaiman et al., 2022) independent variables (IVs), mediators, or dependent variables (DVs) and their relation differ in each study. In the past ten years, only a small number

of towns in Albania, primarily those with a focus on tourism, have considered implementing the smart destination model.

The main objective of this paper is to examine technology acceptance model (TAM) in Albanian municipalities and analyze the parameters influencing the territorial decision making on adapting technologies. This paper aims to investigate factors that influence the attitude of local government in Albanian tourism – driven territories towards accepting technology. The research questions formulated for this purpose are:

RQ1. Are there any independent variables, apart from perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of technology, that are applicable in the context of using the TAM 3 model in the municipality of tourist-focused cities in Albania??

RQ2. What is the impact of these variables on the attitude of territorial management towards technology acceptance?

The methodological approach, consisted of an extensive examination of papers published in online databases, which specifically investigate the level of acceptance of technology in the public sector of tourism in Albania and the influencing factors. Additionally, qualitative interviews with local authority representatives earned valuable insights while an in-depth observation of technology distribution was conducted.

2. Methodology

This paper employs a dual approach, consisting of an extensive examination of papers published in online databases, which specifically investigate the level of acceptance of technology in the public sector of tourism. Additionally, observations of technology distribution and services were conducted, and valuable insights were gathered through qualitative interviews with local authority representatives.

3. Results and Discussion

The research questions aimed at providing a comprehensive overview of the TAM and its applications in the tourism public sector in Albania.

One of the most important findings has been the identification of key factors that affect the acceptance of technology, such as digital literacy, perceived usefulness, and simplicity of use. The level of acceptability mostly hinges on the extent of involvement in destination management, which includes the efficacy of tourism offices and the demonstrated level of professionalism.

4. Conclusions

This study adds to the developing field of technology adoption within tourism-oriented towns in Albania. This study thoroughly examines the interaction between individuals, procedures, and systems, offering practical insights that can guide decision-making processes and eventually promote the sustainable development of tourism through technology.

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Restructuring Sustainable Tourism: An Analytical Perspective from Innovation to Education

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Abstract

Nowadays sustainable tourism has become a familiar concept within economies. It is contributing that world economies find new ways in reforming themselves, while using tourism as a crucial instrument for achieving sustainability. On the other hand, tourism in Europe is facing challenges especially related to education and digitalization. Tourism includes communities, stakeholders, private and public sector, and all challenges related to tourism impact all of them. A new way of tourism management and marketing is almost close, and this will impact especially education, diffusion of digitalisation, and restructuring sustainable tourism itself.

This research aims at an analytical approach on how the basic principles of sustainable tourism has evolved, reflects the challenges, faces the changes, and needs to reflect, bringing a new mindset to the concept of sustainable tourism.

The main emphasis of the study is given to the fact that while tourism is facing many challenges and many countries are trying to restructure their economies for sustaining the tourism industry, it is necessary to reorganize and manage the change of sustainable tourism itself. This process evolves as tourism education itself has its own reflections, attention, and role in providing knowledge and creating skills that the market requires.

Keywords: sustainable tourism, education, digitalization, innovation

JEL codes: Q01, O3

Tourism Led Economic Recovery After Covid-19 In South Albania

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Abstract

Tourism in Albania is considered one of the most important sectors of the Albanian economy, recognizing in 2023 one of the biggest increases during the last three decades. Today, the Albanian tourist industry stands out as the main protagonist of the dynamics of the country's economic recovery after Covid-19. This study will explore the key role that the tourism sector has in the regeneration of the Albanian economy as an avant-garde sector, focusing on the tourist areas in the south of the country.

The statistical analysis followed for this study evidence that not only Albania but all the countries that have invested strategically in increasing the potential and tourist resources have recorded a tangible economic recovery. The suitability of the tourism sector, together with the connections that this sector creates with agriculture in particular and many other industries as a whole, serves as a catalyst for the creation of jobs, the increase of fiscal revenues, the increase of domestic and foreign investments in the development of accommodation structures. The statistical and economic analysis of this study also highlights the challenges of our country that seeks to support economic development. There are a number of factors such as seasonality, global crises, environmental pressures related to the tourist flow and raise a number of questions about the long-term sustainability of the country's economic development model. This study also explores the best practices for the implementation of sustainable policies adopted by some tourist destinations to avoid negative impacts and have a sustainable tourism.

Keywords: Tourism, Economic recovery, Economic stability, Albania

Conceptualizing Circular Economy in Tourism Industry

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Abstract

The concept of circular economy is relatively new, but due to the global challenges, like biodiversity loss, climate change, natural resource depletion, has become increasingly relevant among stakeholders and policymakers. Tourism, although is classified as a service, to function, relies on huge quantities of natural resources that follow a linear take-make-dispose model. That is why adoption of circular economy is crucial to accelerate sustainability and minimize negative externalities generated by tourism. EU initiatives and legislation are focused on the transition from a linear economy to a circular one, for a more sustainable future. EU accession negotiations with Albania necessitate concrete measures and a holistic approach from all actors in tourism industry. The aim of this study is conceptualization of the circular economy model in tourism and its transformative potentials. Through a review analysis of the relevant academic literature found in the tourism field and best practices around the world, the study provides practical solutions for a suitable approach to circular economy of Albanian tourism industry, and possible obstacles during the transition.

Keywords: Circular tourism, circular economy, circular tourist, sustainable tourism

1. Introduction

Tourism is one of the fastest growing industries and among the main contributors to the country's growth. In Albania, 2023 was so far the best year for tourism, welcoming around nine million tourists from January-October (Instat, 2023). Besides the contributions of tourism in GDP, employment, and wealth creation, it has adverse effects on the environment. Thus, employing circular economy is a necessity to drive sustainability in the tourism industry.

Circular economy, in contrast to the linear economy (take-make-dispose model), is based on three key principles, reduce, reuse, recycle and views waste as a new resource within the economy.

The topic of circular economy is high on the political agenda, especially in the European Union, as a new approach to sustainability. Opening of negotiations with Albania in June 2023, urges the uptake of CE principles.

Also, in academic research CE is becoming increasingly relevant, but it's still in its early stages, especially in the tourism field (Axhami et al., 2023; Manniche et al., 2021; Rodríguez et al., 2020; Vargas-Sánchez, 2018) Literature is mainly focused on CE in the manufacturing sector, but some of the solutions can be applied or adapted to tourism businesses (Rodríguez et al., 2020).

The aim of this study is to conceptualize circular tourism through a critical review on academic literature, and based on its synthesis, together with best practices from multiple case-studies, to help stakeholders in the tourism industry in Albania understand and embrace CE. It also highlights possible obstacles during the shift from linear to circular tourism.

2. Methodology

Systematic research was conducted in two general databases, Web of Science and Google Scholar for the time span 2015-2023. For the search the author used the following keywords: circular tourism, circular economy, circular tourist, sustainable tourism. A systematic

literature review was made to give answers to the study's main research questions. Identify and analyze the importance of circular tourism in the literature, point out current research trends and theories emerged in the topic. Citation chaining or snowballing it has been used to track relevant papers and authors. Also, multiple case studies are utilized, based on secondary data sources, to find practical solution that can be applied in Albanian tourism industry.

Only papers in English have been considered. First the papers were selected from the titles, then the abstract was considered to accept or reject the paper. For the selected ones the focus was on findings and conclusions, with the scope of getting answers to our research questions.

3. Results and Discussion

The literature on CE in tourism was analyzed and classified using Albanian tourism products as the scale of analysis. The purpose was to identify key actions and practical guidelines for the transition of tourism in Albania towards a circular economy.

The main products are classified as: 1. Coastal Tourism (coastal tourism and maritime tourism); 2. Natural Tourism (rural tourism, mountain tourism, ecotourism and outdoor activities); 3. Thematic Tourism (agrotourism, cultural tourism, event and business tourism, eno-gastronomic tourism and health tourism)

Most of the papers focus on agro-tourism, as an essential way of achieving sustainability and developing CE practices in rural areas. There is a need to improve environmental impacts of agro-tourism activities.

Sustainable Development Goals are also among the most discussed topics interrelated to CE. Circular Economy principles harmonize with sustainability and tend to give directions for actions to drive sustainability in the tourism industry. According to the World Tourist Organization (UNWTO, 2017) the goals that particularly target tourism are: Goal 8: Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all; Goal 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns; and Goal 14: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

Waste generation and renewable energy are also hot topics in tourism industry. Huge amount of waste are generated from tourism activities. Stopping waste generation at the source, using waste as a new resource, improvement in product design and a better education of public are key actions to be considered, together with usage of renewable energy. Government should reduce bureaucracies and support the development of renewable energy options through information campaigns, financial support, and promotion of available options, to ensure sustainable development.

Table 1. Circular Tourism. Research summary

Author	Main Results	1. Coastal Tourism	
		Key actions to be considered	Possible obstacles
(Williams & Rangel-Buitrago, 2019)	Tackling the litter issue involves many stakeholders, and collaboration among them is the key together with stopping litter generation at the source.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education of the public regarding the litter issue - Improvement in product design using a life cycle approach to eliminate waste and pollution, circulate products and materials. - Including litter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of knowledge in litter classifying - Usage of standard technologies and limited financial resources - Missing of incentives for investment in

		management in national policy-setting and local actions -Revision, adaption and reorganization of human activities that allow reduction of marine liter.	innovation - The process of behavior change takes time and may need policy tools like taxes, increasing price of products and services that harm the environment, penalties etc.
(Agamuthu & Mehran, 2020)	There are a range of short-term initiatives to tackle the issue of marine debris, but these are unsustainable solutions. The long-term sustainable solution would be adaption of circular economy.	Urgent implementation of integrative policies at local, regional and global levels to promote mitigation of marine debris by efficient waste management and practice of 3R principles. A circular economy gives value to waste, promotes reduction in waste generation inciting sustainable production and consumption patterns.	Lack of standards and incentives in embracing circular economy. Poor collaboration and inability to satisfy all the stakeholders.
(He & Mai, 2021)	Sharing economy practices may sustain coastal resources	Use of Airbnb model has a positive effect on resident's living condition and supports sustainable local development. Utilizing unused living space, and existing ecotourism activities. Role of coastal policymakers in the integration and implementation of circular practices through technology and language training programs.	Limited technical knowledge and language ability
(Bandh et al., 2023)	Blue carbon is essential in the fight against climate change contributing to the circular economy through the use of blue carbon in the production of bioenergy, and to the mitigation of plastic and microplastic pollution. It helps achieving co-benefits such as development of aquaculture and coastal restoration.	Local residents need to be involved in the decision-making process. Global coalitions that promote immediate initiatives to rebuilt and transform economies from an ecological point of view. There is a need for global collective efforts for the conservation and protection of coastal ecosystem.	Lack of knowledge and involvement.

Source: Author

Author	2. Natural Tourism & 3. Thematic tourism Main Results	Key actions to be considered	Possible obstacles
(Immacolata, 2018)	Rural tourism should be an integrated and coordinated component within integrated rural development models, specific to each territory.	It is needed an active participation of all stakeholders to ensure a balance between consumption and reproduction of rural resources, in a new approach to the circular economy.	Lack of knowledge and involvement.
(Ciornei et al., 2023)	If the resources of the mountain area (forest, biodiversity and related reserves) are not properly evaluated, neither their usage is correct, and the effects are devastating, in the chain.	By implementing the circular economy in the mountain area, the usage of resources (according to the 3R principle) should become more efficient. Coherent policies, consistent investments in new technologies and research are needed. A strong information system, meant to awake the people's consciousness, regarding the importance of rational exploitation of natural resources.	Lack of information and incentives.
(Joshi et al., 2020)	Destination Attractiveness is valued highest for making CE decisions, whereas, community contributions and sustainable livelihoods valued second and third as important dimensions, in Agro-tourism industry.	Policy makers and Supply chain partners should strategically enhance the economic spin-off from tourism to Agro-tourism. Encourage next generation farmers, to embrace CE for sustainable development.	Limited financial resources
(Nocca, 2017)	Cultural heritage conservation/valorization is mainly interpreted in touristic and real estate impacts. Benefits from cultural heritage conservation/regeneration are multidimensional (economic, social, environmental, etc)	There is a need for tools to evaluate the contribution of cultural heritage to the achievement of sustainable development and the identification of new effective model for sustainable management of cultural heritage.	Lack of knowledge and tools for evaluation

4. Conclusions

Transitioning toward a CE is a multi-dimensional process that requires fundamental changes of the linear system and a holistic approach. The ability to satisfy all the stakeholders is

questioned (Rosato et al., 2021), although it is strongly needed to develop and implement circular economic activities (Manniche et al., 2021; Pan et al., 2018; Pimplapas Pongsakornrungsilp & Pongsakornrungsilp, 2021). Circular economy is seen to generate solutions towards a more sustainable tourism industry and create value (Axhami et al., 2023; Manniche et al., 2021; Rosato et al., 2021). Albanian tourism industry face major challenges in embracing circular economy model and is still far from capturing value from circular tourism practices. There is a need for a better distributed knowledge about new technologies, social solutions, and circular practices to increase the reuse and recycling of natural resources along the tourism supply chain. Also collaboration of tourism actors and value creation among stakeholders is crucial for CE employment. Tourism SMEs in Albania are mostly family-run and there are limited in innovative approaches due to lack of knowledge, limited financial resources, usage of standard technologies, staff professionalism, owners acting as managers.

Some of the barriers to development of CE in Albanian tourism industry are:

- Lack of knowledge in waste separation
- Lack of skills in circular product design and production
- Limited financial resources, lack of investments in new technologies and innovations
- Lack of policies that encourage a much more efficient use of resources through resource pricing
- Lack of know-how and economic incentives
- Poor collaboration among stakeholders

Few authors have addressed the issue of circular economy from tourist perspective. (Sørensen & Bærenholdt, 2020) discussed how tourist practices may sustain the development of CE and find several potential tourist practices that can help the transition to a circular tourism, but also highlight inherent paradoxes within these practices.

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Storytelling in TikTok: A Path to Engagement

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Abstract

This research examines the impact of TikTok content types (characteristics and non-verbal information) on TikTok's engagement rate, performance and followers. The study was conducted within the frame of a project, by third-year students in the E-commerce course at Athens University of Economics and Business. In the context of digital marketing, multiple teams tested different content types on TikTok content. The data collection included 202 posts of 17 different accounts, 546.498 views and 39.172 reactions. The experiment extended over a four-month period, and the findings were utilized to investigate the efficiency of these characteristics. Through statistical analysis, this research examines the performance metrics, engagement levels, and overall impact of the explored content applied by each team. A One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to examine the variations across these categories in relation to each metric of engagement. Whenever significant disparities were found, the Bonferroni post-hoc test was then applied to pinpoint the specific differences between pairs of categories. The results contribute to our understanding of the role of content types on TikTok and provide valuable insights for marketers seeking to optimize their content and strategy on this platform.

Keywords: *Storytelling, social media, TikTok, engagement, performance.*

Jel code: M30, M31.

1. Introduction

In the digital era, social media is a ubiquitous and accessible tool, integral to various industries, especially digital marketing. It serves as a vital platform for information exchange, transforming the traditional communication dynamics between marketers and customers (Sashi, 2012). TikTok, a rapidly growing social media platform, exemplifies this trend with its significant user base, making it an effective tool for marketers to engage consumers (Anderson, 2020). Its cost-effectiveness and interactive features, such as likes, comments, and shares make it suitable for product or service promotions (Yosep et al., 2021; Rangaswamy et al., 2020). The platform is not just for product promotion but also for building networks and interactive communication.

Creative content on TikTok has been used to market various products, including e-cigarettes (Sun et al., 2021). This platform is also effective for athletes and bodybuilders in online branding and endorsements (Mou, 2020; Jaffar, Riaz, & Mushtaq, 2019). Despite controversies, TikTok's large user base makes it an ideal digital marketing platform. However, this necessitates enhanced security and specific supervision for safe and compelling content creation and information dissemination. Previous studies on TikTok in marketing have shown its effectiveness in engaging consumers and influencing public opinion on various issues, from tourism to climate change (Li et al., 2020; Van der Bend et al., 2022; Li et al., 2021).

Research Aim: The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of content characteristics and non-verbal information on TikTok content. By analysing the findings, we seek to assess how different types of TikTok content affect the engagement rate and performance indicators on TikTok. By means of this study, we aim to contribute to the existing field of knowledge in digital marketing and social media by providing insights into the utilisation of different TikTok content types, specifically within the TikTok platform.

Nevertheless, beyond evaluating TikTok's effectiveness, it is also crucial to conduct content analysis on TikTok. This is to determine whether the created content has successfully engaged customers. Moreover, content analysis serves as a vital tool for marketers to evaluate and reflect on their promotional strategies on TikTok. With this understanding, the researchers have formulated three research questions:

RQ1: How do content characteristics and non-verbal information affect the views of a TikTok post?

RQ2: How do content characteristics and non-verbal information affect the reactions of a TikTok post?

RQ3: How do content characteristics and non-verbal information affect the engagement rate of a TikTok post?

2. Literature review

We live in a time where narratives and connections unfold within media realms through the creation of imaginative universes shaped by both corporate actions and individual choices. In this context, society is actively involved in evolving storytelling methods on social media platforms. Here, individuals can showcase their voices, identities, and emotions through diverse digital tools including text, images, memes, and music. (Kim & Li, 2021). This interactive phenomenon is grounded in the concept of hyper-narrativity, as described by Wagener in 2019, and it revolves around the transformation of collective identities into widely shared memes (Ask & Abidin, 2017, p. 7). This leads to the creation of discourses and content on platforms like TikTok, where elements like humor, imitation or replication, and a sense of belonging to a group, are predominant factors.

TikTok is a powerful video-focused social media platform, in which users can create videos for up to 10 minutes, utilising the platform's editing tools (Haenlein et al., 2020). The platform is considered highly engaging (Wiley, 2022) due to its content characteristics, the ability to easily skip videos and the content provided by the channel that is interspersed with related content posted by friends (Belanche et al., 2019). In the period following the pandemic, TikTok has emerged as the social network experiencing the most rapid growth. TikTok is more instinctive and authentic than other social media like YouTube and Instagram, representing a specific aesthetic of high-quality and filtered content (Barta et al., 2023). Content on TikTok is more playful and ludic (Wang, 2020), that is, its usage is for amusement and pastime. TikTok creators upload content from their everyday life, showcasing everyday circumstances, such as videos in their home, as well as creating engaging and entertaining content through parodies (Barta et al., 2023). TikTok enables the promotion and display of product activities across a wide spectrum of digital marketing channels efficiently, without incurring significant financial expenditure, as highlighted by Yosep et.al (2021).

TikTok's audience primarily consists of younger users, particularly teenagers and young adults (Haenlein et al., 2020). While Facebook and Twitter's average user age is around 40, and Instagram appeals to those in their 30s, TikTok attracts a younger demographic, primarily around 20 years old, with 40% of its users between 10 and 19 years (Haenlein et al., 2020). This age group shows distinct media consumption patterns, often being resistant to traditional advertising and less engaged with conventional media like television (Xu et al., 2021). Given TikTok's rapid growth, unique format and content style, and direct reach to a younger, influential consumer segment, it presents a significant opportunity for influencer marketing campaigns.

The "Store Intelligence Data Digest" report on recent mobile trends from SensorTower in 2020 identifies TikTok as among the top 10 most downloaded apps globally in the past decade.

Available for Android and iOS devices, this app enables users to craft brief videos accompanied by audio clips, songs, or pre-existing video sequences enriched with effects, stickers, filters, augmented reality, and green screen options. Specifically, it's common for users to blend music with lip-syncing in their posts.

Additionally, TikTok is a platform for spreading narratives and opinions, primarily through music and sounds (Abidin, 2021). It is a platform strongly connected to self-expression, creativity, and storytelling (Omar & Dequan, 2020). Storytelling is an accessible and effective means of interaction, facilitating easy and straightforward communications (Vázquez-Herrero et al., 2022). As a content tool, storytelling can engage viewers by involving them in the evolving story and encouraging them to connect with their own experiences and personality (Woodside et al., 2008).

Storytelling is an approach to communication that is straightforward, understandable, and effective, as described by Vázquez Herrero, Negreira-Rey, and López-García in 2020. The strength of storytelling is critical in propelling a social business project via TikTok, enabling the dissemination of positive and inspiring stories from various archipelago regions, as Weimann and Masri noted in 2020.

Social Media Engagement

Engagement is the most important terminology in the social media world (Grewal, Roggeveen, Sisodia, & Nordfalt, 2017; Merrilees, 2016). Wang (2006) defined engagements as “the contextual relevance in which a brand’s messages are framed and presented based on its surrounding context,” which refers to the usefulness, engagement, and emotional attachment that arises in reaction to information related to a brand. (p. 355). Particularly in the social media world, engagement was defined by Mollen and Wilson (2010) as “the cognitive and affective commitment to an active relationship with the brand as personified by the website or other computer-mediated entities designed to communicate brand value” (p. 5). Previous studies have associated engagement on social media platforms, with consumers 'Follow', 'Like', 'Comment' on or 'Share' content (Kumar, Bezawada, Rishika, Janakiraman, & Kannan, 2016; Pentina, Guilloux, & Micu, 2018).

Consumer engagement is related to following and sharing brand posts (Brubaker & Wilson, 2018), and it is a necessary condition to building consumer communities, trust, loyalty (Haverila et al., 2020), purchase, and word-of-mouth for brands (Syncapse, 2013). When a brand creates and engages consumers, they show strong relations and emotions for brands, for example, by using personal pronouns to reference them on social media (Chen et al., 2015). Research shows that marketers are striving to incorporate social media and endeavoring to enhance their social media communication to promote consumer engagement (Chen et al., 2015; Hayes et al., 2020; Sprout, 2018).

The papers suggest that high engagement on social media has positive effects on brand relationships and firm performance. Dessart (2017) found that high social media engagement increases brand relationships, particularly affecting brand trust, commitment, and loyalty. Customer engagement in social media is driven by satisfaction, positive emotions, and trust, and has substantial value for companies, directly impacting firm performance, behavioral intention, and word-of-mouth (Santini 2020). From consumer engagement through social media, brands gain brand association and increased brand performance (Rapp, Beitelspacher, Grewal, & Hughes, 2013; Fulgoni, 2015; Habibi et al., 2016; Dessart, 2017), influencing purchase decisions and sales (Muralidharan & Men, 2015; Kumar et al., 2016; Pentina et al., 2018).

3. Methodology

This field experiment was conducted in the context of an e-commerce project of third-year students from the Athens University of Economics and Business. The students were divided into 17 teams, and each team was asked to develop a digital marketing plan for a fictitious business, using TikTok as one of the social media platforms. The experiment lasted for four months, during which the teams uploaded a total of 202 posts. The objective of the research was to assess the efficiency of different content characteristics on TikTok. The content characteristics were categorized based on the main constructs outlined by Wahid et al. (2023) and each post could fall under one or more of these categories. In particular, Wahid et al. (2023) position content characteristics into two main categories, the informational content that provides relevant or irrelevant information and emotional content that shares “affect-laden messages that intend to evoke emotional responses”. Moreover, they divide those two categories into specific themes. Based on this categorization we pinpointed the collected data into one or more the proposed variables.

The sampling for this study was predetermined and based on the posts created by the student teams. Data collection involved monitoring the number of views and reactions received by each post. In total, the posts amassed 546,498 views and 39,172 reactions. The sampling for this study was predetermined as it was based on the posts created by the student teams. This study adopted a quantitative approach to examine the influence of content type on viewer engagement, measured via three metrics: views, reactions, and Engagement Rate (E.R.). The independent variable, content type, was categorized into 13 distinct types (humor, music, employee, storytelling, animations, information, slideshow, sketch, sound, promotion, product, photo, reviews). One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to investigate the differences among these categories with respect to each engagement metric. In cases where a significant difference was observed, a Bonferroni post-hoc test was further employed to identify specific pairwise differences. These statistical techniques allowed for a comprehensive examination of the relationship between content type and viewer engagement, revealing both overarching trends and specific inter-category variations.

4. Results, Discussion and Contributions

In an exploration of the relationship between content type and various user engagement metrics, the study reveals noteworthy findings. A distinct relationship is found between content type and both viewer count and user reactions. A one-way ANOVA exhibited significant variances across 13 content categories in terms of views ($F = 3.58, p < .001$) and reactions ($F = 3.74, p < .001$).

Further scrutiny through Bonferroni post-hoc tests indicated that category 13 (storytelling) significantly deviated from each of the other 12 categories in terms of attracting views and provoking reactions (all $p < .05$). This suggests that category 13 might possess unique features that resonate with viewers, triggering increased interest and interaction. In contrast, no significant variation was found among the content categories regarding engagement rate ($F = 0.4, p = .963$). These insights underscore the nuanced role content type plays in different facets of user engagement, with the exceptional performance of category 13 pointing towards a possible area for content strategy optimization. However, the unaltered engagement rate suggests additional variables may need to be considered to fully comprehend and enhance user engagement. This study contributes to the realm by affording factual signs on the importance of storytelling and how this type of content affects user engagement and Tik Tok account behavior, a new and uncharted territory in the social media literature.

5. Implications

This study provides valuable insights for content creators, marketers, and the academic community, offering a deeper understanding of the factors that drive user engagement on TikTok and potentially shaping future content strategies. This research implies that incorporating further storytelling techniques into content can potentially boost user reactions and total views. The provided results contribute to the creation of a more complete TikTok content strategy. Crucially, these results also emphasize the importance of further exploring the relation of content characteristics to user engagement, which could direct future research in this area. Finally, the distinct results of storytelling display a fascinating approach for further study in the domain of TikTok content creation. Nevertheless, the unchanged rate of engagement indicates that there might be other factors that need to be taken into account to fully understand and improve user interaction and engagement. Further research will focus on analysing the factors and testing them using large-scale business accounts on TikTok and other social media platforms.

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Dental Tourism, a Challenge and Factor for Sustainable Tourism. Case Study-Albania

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Abstract

In this article, in the framework of sustainable tourism, we will address the topic of medical tourism as one of the industries that have seen growth in recent years. People are more and more looking in having better medical services but also paying for them in lower prices. This growing demand has resulted in an increase in the offer from different medical structures and other parties, by different countries in the world in order to best meet consumer expectations. For this reason, the study of medical tourism presents in itself an interesting topic to be addressed.

During the literature review, we will get to know the theoretical concepts of medical tourism in general and dental tourism in particular, noting the relevant benefits. We will see a panorama of the countries in the world where this industry represents the greatest development as well as the growth it has known throughout the last years. Our country has also seen increasing numbers of medical tourists in recent years, mainly dental ones.

The focus in this article will be mainly the study of dental tourism in Albania as an important part of medical tourism. Through several questionnaires addressed to various dental clinics in Tirana, data has been collected which points out not only the importance but also the problems of dental tourism in our country.

The relevance of this study lies in the analysis of these data to reach conclusions and recommendations that target the specific problems, aiming to solve or improve them in the framework of a sustainable development of dental tourism in our country.

Keywords: medical tourism, dental tourism, importance, challenges,

A Necessity for an Effective Strategy on Management of Cultural Heritage Works and their Role in Developing Sustainable Tourism

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Abstract

Circular Economy (CE) is a concept that is recently gaining increasing attention to policymakers, stakeholders and managerial staff, becoming a priority in national policies in a growing number of countries, as a sustainable development strategy. There is lack of research referring the CE and tourism. Our research paper’s focus are analysing the factors of Circular Economy and its relation to the tourism sector, considering the tourism main actors behavior. To fill this gap, this paper aims to investigate the circular economy behaviour of consumers trying to identify the knowledge needs of such actors, may influence the CE in relation to tourism sector as well, Circular Tourism approach. Specifically, we examine the following research questions: (1) What is the level of awareness of the circular economy among such actors/consumers? (2) What are the factors that influence their intention to adopt circular economy practices? Considering that this research was a first attempt to identify consumer behaviour, some limitations were also identified, as: the sector is newly analysed as there is lack of knowledge and research in this field; the tourism sector’s development towards CE is just considered as policy strategy, thus not fully understandable by all actors.

Keywords: Circular Economy; Consumer behaviour; tourism, knowledge needs, circular tourism

JEL Codes: Q01, Q56, R22, L83

1. Introduction

Circular Economy (CE) is a concept that is recently gaining increasing attention to policymakers, stakeholders and managerial staff, becoming a priority in national policies in a growing number of countries, as a sustainable development strategy to them, for its potential to significantly optimize resource use and reduce production and consumption related Greenhouse Gas (GHG) and CO₂ emissions, while at the same time offering competitive advantage opportunities for businesses (Einarsson S. and Sorin, F. (2020)).

Research focuses on how to benefit by shifting from linear to the circular economy, in relation to the tourism industry and its sectors. According to the New Circular Economy Action Plan from the European Commission (EC, 2020), the EU has recognised the importance of this field, specifying that the process of shifting towards regenerative growth should be faster in order to return to the planet more than we take from it (Rudan, E., *et.al.* (2021)).

Along with the latter stakeholders mentioned, consumers play a critical role in driving the transition to a circular economy, an efficient mechanism to achieving sustainability by making sustainable choices and adopting new consumption patterns, aiming to prevent negative effects, as well as enable both entrepreneurs and the community in general to save money.

However, little is known about the factors that influence actors/consumers' behaviour in the circular economy context, related to tourism sector specifically.

1.1 Literature review

The CE requires the instauration of systems that operate in coherence with the energy, water and material cycling principles that, according to Zhue et al. (2010), must comply with eco-systemic self-sustaining properties, which require self-organization capacities, consumption efficiency, the recycling of energy and materials and the reutilization of one company's waste as a resource by another firm. According to the EU action, the CE is often promoted as it enables "wider economic and social benefits, such as greater well-being, sustainable growth and employment".

Tourism is a sector that contributes much to employment and the GDP in many countries and regions and it has the potential to contribute to the development of rural, peripheral or less developed areas, as the provided infrastructures for tourism purposes, creation of meaningful jobs and through more equal and fair distribution of resources and financial capital can contribute to local development.

In this regard, as stated by Florido, C., Jacob, M.; Payeras, M. (2019) the "Circular tourism implies a model in which each tourism actor (tourist, Destination Management Organizations (DMOs), suppliers (hotels, restaurants, etc.), and resident population) adopts an eco-friendly approach".

2. Methodology

There are few references to the tourism sector considering the fact that it is an industry predominantly configured around the model of the linear economy. That is the focus of our research paper, which consists of the factors of Circular Economy and its relation to the tourism sector, considering the tourism main actors' behavior.

Jacob *at.al*, (2014) presents a model where the main identified areas of knowledge needs: tourists, environment, physical heritage, and cultural heritage of the destination - the basic inputs of tourism activity that as well would benefit from innovations (organizational, commercial and technological) are incorporated with the main institutions/actors (the firms (and the destinations/destination management organizations-DMO) and other tourism stakeholders) that need such information.

To fill this gap, this paper aims to investigate the circular economy behaviour of consumers trying to identify the knowledge needs of such actors, regarding age, gender, geographical location/destination, service providing, household composition may influence the CE in relation to tourism sector as well, considered as Circular Tourism approach. Specifically, we examine the following research questions: (1) What is the level of awareness of the circular economy among such actors/consumers? (2) What are the factors that influence their intention to adopt circular economy practices?

To answer these research questions, was conducted a survey in Albania, Poland and Portugal. The data was analysed mostly by performing a correspondence analysis.

3. Results and Conclusions

To sum up, the Knowledge Triangle to tourism considers that two different actors of tourism sector are to be: the firms and the destinations (the DMOs and other key stakeholders). New knowledge can bring about changes that induce innovations and these changes can be originated at the firm level or at the destination level.

In the conclusion will be presented the most relevant achievements aiming to provide some clues for policymakers and producers regarding the circular behaviour of consumers. Considering that this research was a first attempt to identify consumer behaviour, some limitations were also identified, as: the sector is newly analysed as there is lack of knowledge and research in this field; the tourism sector's development towards CE is just considered as policy strategy, thus not fully understandable by all actors.

From the cultural/landscape perspective, adaptive reuse is a way to put the circular economy's principles into practice. Reuse, restoration, rehabilitation, etc., are improved through circular processes. When the principles of circular economy are applied to the restoration and revitalisation of old resources (small historical cities, old buildings, old furniture, etc.), cultural-historical heritage can gain new value and be repurposed for tourism, facilitating regional development and population satisfaction.

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Impact of Digital Marketing in the Development of Rural Sustainable Tourism

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Abstract

This study analyzes the impact of digital marketing on sustainable and rural tourism in Albania, a key focus of the Albanian National Strategy for Sustainable Tourism Development. It emphasizes digital marketing's role in promoting lesser-known rural areas, contributing to GDP growth. Using statistical analysis, a significant positive correlation is found between internet access and international tourism, highlighting the importance of ICT in enhancing tourism. The paper advocates for improved digital marketing skills, infrastructure, and stakeholder collaboration to maximize tourism's potential. Recommendations include a bottom-up approach for innovation and trust-building in the tourism sector, essential for its sustainable development.

Keywords: rural tourism development, digital marketing, sustainable tourism

JEL codes: M3, M31

1. Introduction

Sustainable tourism is developed in accordance with the principles of sustainable development. There is a special relationship between the concept of sustainable tourism and rural tourism as per Andreopoulou, Tsekouropoulos, Koliouka, & Koutroumanidis (2014). A key focus of the Albanian National Strategy for Sustainable Tourism Development (2019-2023) is the promotion of rural tourism, which aims to transition towards year-round tourism, to further enhance the sector's contribution to the National GDP. According to Ciro & Toska (2018), this approach suggests reducing the developmental burden on coastal regions and instead concentrating on inland areas that are less known and marketed and in regard to the local economy development establishing a self-reliant sector within the local economy. As foreseen by the Ministry of Tourism and Environment of the Republic of Albania (2019), the tourism sector in Albania is projected to see substantial growth in its economic contribution, with an expectation of reaching 8.8% of GDP within the next 2-3 years and potentially rising to 9.3% by 2028. As a result, by 2028, the combined direct and indirect effects of the tourism industry are estimated to near one-third of Albania's overall Gross Domestic Product.

In support to the above, Rodrigues, Correia, Gonçalves, Branco, Martins (2023) expresses that when people intend to visit a place and keep that intention, it brings more tourists, resulting in increased economic, social, and market activity. Given Albania's rich natural tourist attractions, rural tourism plays a significant role in the overall growth of the tourism sector. To maintain this momentum, it is essential for rural tourism to focus on sustainability, encompassing not just environmental aspects, but also ensuring sustainable income generation. As Ciro & Toska (2018) have mentioned: "Sustainable tourism is possible, even in peripheral territories with scarce resources." However, one of the key factors that contribute to the development and promotion of such destinations are various digital channels of promotion and communication. As per Cheuk, Atang, Chiun & Ramayah, (2018), digital marketing enables the overcoming of physical limitations in disseminating information to the target market, a capability especially crucial for promoting rural tourism destinations.

Based on Andreopoulou, Tsekouropoulos, Koliouka, & Koutroumanidis (2014), the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) enhances the value of tourism services and products, and it aids in the growth of industry networks and clusters. Furthermore, digital marketing operates on a fundamental principle aligned with its application, specifically in showcasing the potential of each tourist site, boosting income, and fostering the development and sustainability of these sites. Possible models for implementation include utilizing websites, social media, email marketing, and mobile applications. Digital marketing facilitates tourism activities for visitors through automated systems and multi-language options. (Wibawa, Astawa, Sukmawati, Arjana, & Sutarma, 2022)

Strategically planned digital marketing efforts, centered on high-quality content and professional execution, wield substantial influence. They not only raise awareness about rural tourism destinations, but also play a pivotal role in sparking fresh economic activity in these areas. They generate interest and foster engagement, thereby contributing positively to the growth and vitality of these territories. (Rodrigues, Correia, Gonçalves, Branco, Martins, 2023))

Referring again to Andreopoulou, Tsekouropoulos, Koliouka, & Koutroumanidis (2014), the content on tourism destination websites holds significant importance as it directly shapes the destination's perceived image and provides a virtual experience for the customer. The interaction between a business providing a service and its customers is a critical component of relationship marketing, contributing significantly to the development of customer loyalty. A key benefit of having a website is the ability to update it with the latest information as needed.

Moreover, Rodrigues, Correia, Gonçalves, Branco, Martins (2023) explain that when effectively strategized, organized, and grounded in high-quality content, digital marketing efforts can substantially influence the creation of a favorable image for the destination.

However, the use of Information Technology in the tourism industry has been a challenge for many years. Except for occasional instances, often with the aid of international organizations, the deployment of digital services for tourists is still underdeveloped. Likewise, the use of these technologies for marketing services and products and their market expansion is equally underdeveloped. (Ministry of Tourism and Environment of the republic of Albania, 2019)

Nevertheless, rural tourist entrepreneurs' overall attitude towards integrating digital marketing in tourism is positive, with widespread acknowledgment of its value. While there's no fear of technology, support is desired for developing marketing websites, especially in content, design, and management aspects. Additionally, recognizing the potential, the adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the booking process is seen as a means to enhance operational efficiency within the industry. (Cheuk, Atang, Chiun & Ramayah, 2018)

On the other hand, compared to other places in the Mediterranean region, tourism in Albania hasn't fully tapped into the country's rich natural, historical, and cultural assets. Challenges like infrastructure, accommodation quality, services, tourism offerings, and the overall experience have slowed down the steady growth of tourism here. This slower pace has resulted in uncontrolled and disorderly development within the industry, posing risks to its sustainability in the long run. (Ministry of Tourism and Environment of the republic of Albania, 2019)

As outlined in Ciro & Toska (2018), another reason behind this issue and also the ICT access factor, is the disconnection between the top-down tourism strategy and the inadequately skilled and equipped local governments. This gap results in a struggle to effectively translate the strategy into actionable plans. Moreover, the lack of trust and collaborative culture among stakeholders, along with insufficient institutional frameworks dedicated to tourism development and management, contributes significantly to the challenge. (Ciro & Toska, 2018)

2. Methodology

This study aims to investigate the correlation between access to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and the growth of the tourism industry, by using the Correlation Calculator by Statistics Kingdom (2023). The Correlation Calculator determines both the Pearson and Spearman's Rank correlation coefficients while assessing the significance of the outcomes. Furthermore, it computes the covariance between the variables.

$$S_{XY} = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{n - 1} \qquad r = \frac{S_{XY}}{S_x S_y}$$

Finally, by conducting a comprehensive review of existing literature, it seeks to uncover insights and provide recommendations for fostering the advancement of both ICT accessibility and the tourism sector. This research endeavors to offer actionable suggestions to bolster the symbiotic relationship between technological access and tourism development, thus contributing to their mutual progress and enhancement.

3. Results and Discussion

Results of the pearson correlation indicated that there is a significant large positive relationship between Individuals using the Internet and International inbound tourists, ($r(18) = .95, p < .001$).

Table 1: Individuals using the Internet (% of population) Albania

Table 2: International inbound tourists, Albania

Source: World Bank (2023)

Source: World Bank (2023) This paper has intentionally excluded the year 2020, because of the pandemic implications.

4. Conclusions & Recommendations

In Albania, the correlation between internet accessibility and international tourism is evident. Therefore, initiatives aimed at bolstering this industry should prioritize enhancing skills in digital marketing, promotion, and service strategies. In line with *Ciro & Toska (2018)*, this paper strongly advocates for leveraging bottom-up approaches to foster tourism innovation, empowering the efficient utilization of local strengths. This method nurtures trust, fostering confidence in the process, thereby fostering crucial partnerships essential for establishing a robust value chain. Finally, the author recommends a more disaggregated approach in data gathering when it comes to rural tourism, compared to tourism in general.

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Nation Branding Strategy: Focus on Albania Market

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Abstract

The scenarios of globalization have changed markets, lifestyles, traditions, and cultural customs, also creating confusion on the internal realities of almost all countries.

Consequently, the need emerged to reshape a more distinctive and authentic version of each country, giving life to the nation's branding strategy. Over the last two decades, the nation branding strategy has acquired particular importance in the daily life of developed countries, mainly in the tourism sector, becoming a guiding vector for emerging markets, where Albania is now part of this reality.

This research aims to offer a general picture of the main factors of this strategy and the advantages that can be obtained to distinguish the Albanian identity.

Keywords: nation branding, strategy, Albania market.

JEL code: M 31

STATISTICS & APPLIED INFORMATICS

Observation of the Employability Services Offered in Online Websites in Albania

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Abstract

Currently in Albania youth encounter challenges in their effort to seek a career that best matches their interests, skills, and professional background. Youth employment has a significant impact on our society, having an impact not only on the lives and well-being of young people but also on the macroeconomic prospects of societies. There is a long-term effect on a young person's professional life and prospects depending on how effortlessly or how hard they are able to transition from their education to the labor market. Young people can secure a solid career and a bright future by developing long-term employability skills. However, for people who have difficulty finding a good work, there is still a high risk of vulnerability and poverty. This group of job seekers primarily migrates to other nations in an effort to better their economic status. One of the factors contributing to Albania's population decline is migration. Young, highly educated, and skilled people are more willing to migrate. According to statistics, much more young people are leaving Albania than ever before, and the majority of those who travel in other countries to study, leave without returning. Potential migration is still strong, which means that a significant part of the Albanian population would like to relocate or has plans to do so in the near future. Therefore, current demographic data on youth, employment, and migration are analyzed in this paper, in order to better comprehend the difficulties that young people in Albania confront in the labor market.

In order to prevent this high rate of youth migration, recently there undertaken national measures such as policies and strategies from Albanian governmental institutions, to improve youth employability and further develop employability skills.

This paper aims to analyze and present current situation in Albania related national measures taken from Albanian Governmental Institutions to improve youth employability and further develop employability skills, in order to reduce high migration rates, which is one of the main social and economic wounds that Albania is currently suffering.

Keywords: National Measures, Governmental Institutions, Youth Employability, Demographic Data, Employability Skills Development

JEL codes: C42, E6, E24, E26

1. Introduction

Youth employment has a significant impact on our society, having an impact not only on the lives and well-being of young people but also on the macroeconomic prospects of societies. Young people can guarantee a respectable work and a prosperous future by finding sustainable forms of employment. However, for people who have difficulty finding a good work, there is still a high risk of vulnerability and poverty.

According to statistical data, a higher number of young people are leaving Albania than ever before, and the majority of those who travel in other countries to study do not return. Young people report low earnings, poor service quality, and a lack of meritocracy as their top three reasons for leaving Albania. In order to decrease this high level of emigration, young people

need to gain a variety of fundamental, transferrable, technical, and vocational skills in order to find, keep, and succeed in the workplace. Employers are increasingly looking for soft skills, such as the capacity to adjust to new situations, as well as digital skills. Employability skills are the expertise, skills, and knowledge that jobseekers must possess to enhance their capacity to obtain and maintain employment, advance professionally, deal with change, find new employment if they choose to leave their current position or are fired, and enter the labor market more quickly at various stages of their lives. Employability skills shape one's career by assisting in developing and enhancing their interpersonal, leadership, teambuilding, communication, and time management skills as well as their interviewing and interpersonal skills.

An effective national strategy ensures that a variety of skills are developed consistently over the course of a person's life and through a variety of means, including formal, informal, workplace, and community-based learning, and that these approaches are acknowledged in the educational system and advancement in employment.

Therefore, analysis of the structural framework relating to national initiatives implemented for this topic are very important. The national initiatives associated with the offer to improve youth employability by ensuring they have the necessary skills for work and assisting them to employment/self-employment opportunities is crucial to supporting young people develop their skills and be successful to the labor market. Programs and Strategies undertaken to promote productivity, competitiveness, and growth are examples of demand-related measures that encourage the development of new and better employability in the economy. These can be used to evaluate the effects of initiatives whose goal is to get youth ready for the workforce.

Therefore, the research questions that the present study intends to answer are:

RQ1: What are the current demographic data on youth, employment, and migration in Albania?

RQ2: Which are the national measures undertaken from governmental institutions to improve youth employability and further develop employability skills?

2. Methodology

For this study we have used observational, preliminary research and analysis in order to give an overview of the national measures undertaken to improve youth employability and further develop employability skills.

The approach is based on a preliminary research and analysis of the current literature and documents that already exist, including reports, official data of Albania, studies, national strategic documents and policies, as well as scientific articles and publications which address issues such as: demographic data on youth, employment, and migration, national measures undertaken to improve youth employability and further develop employability skills.

Based on the national demographic data, recently migration is one of the reasons for Albania's declining youth population and furthermore potential migration remains high even for the upcoming years.

In 2022, 13,963 people became immigrants, which is 51.9% more than in the year before. 46,460 people left the country; this represents a 10.5% increase over 2021. When compared to the prior year, net migration—the difference between immigrants and emigrants—saw an increase.

Table 1: Youth data

Age Group	January 2022			January 2023		
	M	F	Total	M	F	Total
15-19	93320	89877	183197	87761	84315	172076
20-24	101815	101448	203263	98353	97887	196240

25-29	113768	115124	228892	108705	110867	219572
Total	308903	306449	615352	294819	290907	587888

According to INSTAT data, all the age groups of youth have suffered decline from January 2022. This is mainly because of high level of migration.

Youth chose to migrate mainly because they are unemployed in Albania. The employment rate for those between the ages of 15 and 64 is 67.3 percent as of the second quarter of 2023.

Figure 1: Unemployment rates in Albania
Source: INSTAT, 2023

Therefore, Albania Employment Governmental Institutions have seen as a necessity to undertake measures in terms of national strategies, policies and programs to help youth increase their employability and further develop employability skills. Given the developments so far, Albania's vision reflected in the implementation of the National Youth Strategy and Action Plan 2022-2029 is to provide employability opportunities to youth and support them in becoming proactively involved in the country's development.

3. Results and Discussion

One of the pillars of Albania's governmental policies is working towards improving employability to keep young people work in Albania. There is still a high level of migration among qualified youth, who do not trust the labour market in Albania and choose to live and work worldwide. In order to decrease migration high rates, Albania has undertaken many national programs and policies to re-enforce employability and skills, especially among youth. The most important governmental initiatives will be highlighted in this paper. Hopefully this paper will serve to give a full panorama of what measures have taken the governmental institutions of Albania to strengthen the labor market in Albania and to help job seekers strengthen their employability skills. Also, we see this paper that many young people can refer to, so that they become aware of the governmental programs and initiatives they can use to get employed or self-employed in Albania and not migrate abroad.

Anyhow, we do believe that the migration and employability are two of the main social wounds that Albania currently is suffering and probably will suffer for a long period of time.

4. Conclusions

We can conclude that more effort must be done to strengthen, broaden, and consolidate policies that support youth employment and entrepreneurship as well as increase the employability of Albania's youth by evaluating the current state of conditions in relation to these policies, youth employment and entrepreneurship policies, training programs for unskilled youth, migrants

returning home, or marginalized groups, practice-based teaching, curriculum improvement through increased market connections, and the development of administrative capacities. We recommend that the only option to lower the high rate of youth migration is to combine and consolidate these national efforts so that young people would choose to live and work in Albania rather than go abroad.

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Significance of Data in the Tourism Industry

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Abstract

The tourism industry's historical reliance on manual record-keeping has evolved with the advent of technology, progressing from computerized systems to the current era of big data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT). This transition has enhanced decision-making, customer experiences, and overall industry efficiency. However, the digitalization has introduced challenges, notably in data security, privacy, and ethical aspects. This study implies a qualitative approach, conducting a comprehensive literature review to investigate the role of data in the tourism industry. The research question focuses on how the industry can effectively leverage data to enhance decision-making and customer experiences while addressing challenges related to privacy, security, and ethical considerations. The effective integration of data in the tourism industry offers insights into traveler behavior, preferences, and market trends. By analyzing large volumes of data from online bookings, social media, and customer feedback enables businesses to make informed decisions and adapt to market demands. Case studies, such as Disney's MagicBand system and Singapore's Tourism Analytics Network, illustrate successful data-driven initiatives in this direction. Despite the benefits, challenges in privacy, security, and ethics persist. Addressing these challenges is imperative for sustained success in this data-centric landscape. Stakeholders must prioritize the development of robust data governance frameworks and invest in cybersecurity measures to safeguard sensitive information, thereby maintaining the trust of the customers.

Keywords: tourism industry, decision-making, customer experiences, security, privacy and ethics.

JEL codes: Z32

1. Introduction

In the tourism industry, at the beginning, all records related to essential data such as tracking bookings, customer information, payments, etc were kept primarily manual, involving paper-based systems (Faulkner & Rusell, 1997). With the arrival of computers, the tourism industry has a transition towards the computerized systems. For example, processes including reservations, ticketing, and basic data storage were automated (Buhalis & Laws, 2012). The rise of the internet brought a significant upgrade on existing systems available in the tourism industry. Online booking platforms were implemented, enabling travellers to make reservations directly from the web. Also, in this phase, the collection of data through digital channels brought the foundation of e-commerce in tourism (Alford, 1999). In recent years, the tourism industry has entered in the era of big data. Advanced analytics tools and technologies enable the processing of large amounts of data, providing valuable insights into traveller behaviour, preferences, and market trends, which can be used to increase income in this industry (Xiang et al., 2017). Nowadays, the integration of innovative technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) into tourism operations enable predictive analytics, personalization, and automation of various processes, enhancing the overall

efficiency of the industry (Filiari et al., 2021; Egger, 2022). On the other hand, the advent of real-time data and the Internet of Things (IoT) in tourism involves the use of connected devices, providing instantaneous data for better decision-making and enhancing the overall tourist experience (Neuhofner et al., 2014).

However, this rapid integration of digital tools, technologies and platforms has led in a new set of challenges, prominently among them being data security and privacy concerns. As tourists traverse the globe, their digital footprint expands, leaving a trail of sensitive information susceptible to a variety of cyber threats. The tourism sector has the critical task of safeguarding a vast amount of personal data, including travel itineraries, financial transactions, and personal identifiers. The implications of a data breach in this context extend beyond financial losses, reaching into the realms of personal safety, trust, and the reputation of both individual businesses and the industry (Paraskevas, 2022). Also, the ethical aspects are important. For example, in data collection, obtaining informed consent from individuals whose data is being gathered is crucial. The principle of transparency and the right to know how one's data will be used underscore the importance of consent in preserving individual autonomy (Nissenbaum, 2010). Concerns related to "fairness" and "equity", arise when data collection practices disproportionately impact certain demographic groups. As shown by Barocas and Selbst (2016), striking a balance between the collection of relevant information, and avoiding discrimination is vital for upholding ethical standards. Regulatory frameworks, often established and enforced by governmental bodies, set the legal boundaries for data-related activities. For instance, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union establishes stringent rules regarding the processing and protection of personal data (EU, 2016). Compliance with such regulations is not only a legal imperative but also a key ethical consideration, as it protects individuals' rights to privacy and control over their data. Harmonizing these standards on a global scale poses a significant challenge, requiring ongoing collaboration between nations and industries as stated by Kuner's work (2018).

2. Methodology

The methodology employed in this study is designed to comprehensively investigate the role of data in the tourism industry, with a specific focus on enhancing decision-making and customer experiences while addressing challenges related to privacy, security, and ethical considerations. This research adopts a qualitative approach through a comprehensive review of scholarly articles, books, and reports related. The research question that this paper wants to address through an extended literature review is the following: "How can the tourism industry effectively embrace the importance of data to enhance decision-making, customer experiences, and overall competitiveness, while addressing challenges related to privacy, security, and ethical considerations?"

3. Results and Discussion

The research question of this study goes around the effective integration of data in the tourism industry to support decision-making, to boost customer experiences, and enhance overall competitiveness in the sector. In today's digital age, data has emerged as a powerful tool capable of transforming industries, and the tourism sector is no exception. The discussion will go through the multifaceted aspects of leveraging data in the tourism industry while recognizing and addressing challenges related to privacy, security, and ethical considerations. The tourism industry generates large amounts of data from various sources, including online bookings, social media, and customer feedback. Analyzing this data enables businesses to make more informed decisions. For instance, data analytics can provide insights into customer preferences, travel patterns, and emerging trends. These insights empower tourism professionals to adapt their services, marketing strategies, and operational decisions to meet

the evolving demands of the market (Sabou et al., 2012). Data-driven approaches allow tourism businesses to personalize customer experiences, creating more targeted and engaging interactions. From personalized recommendations based on past behaviour to streamlined booking processes, elaborated data can play a crucial role in optimizing every phase of the customer journey (Xu et al., 2019). For instance, Disney implemented the MagicBand system to enhance the overall experience for visitors at its theme parks. It collects data on visitor preferences, ride preferences, and behavior within the park and utilizes this data to personalize the visitor experience, offering personalized recommendations, targeted promotions, and minimizing wait times for popular attractions (Huddleston & Garlen, 2016). Singapore established a Tourism Analytics Network that integrates data from various sources, including visitor spending, demographics, and social media sentiment analysis. These data are used to understand visitor preferences, optimize marketing strategies, and tailor offerings to specific market segments, ultimately enhancing the overall tourism experience (Xiao et al., 2023). New Zealand in its "100% Pure New Zealand" campaign analyzed data on traveler preferences, online behavior, and market trends. By tailoring its marketing efforts based on data insights, the country successfully attracted specific segments of travelers, enhancing the overall perception of New Zealand as a tourist destination (Morgan et al., 2002).

While the benefits of data in the tourism industry are significant, there are inherent challenges associated with privacy, security, and ethical considerations. For instance, privacy challenges can arise when collecting extensive personal data for profiling purposes that can lead to potential privacy infringements, or the use IoT devices which can collect and share personal data without explicit user consent (Acquisti & Gross, 2006; Ziegeldorf et al., 2013). Security challenges are mostly related to cybersecurity including ransomware, phishing attacks, and malware, targeting individuals and organizations, and biometric data (e.g., fingerprints, facial recognition) used for theft or unauthorized access (Paraskevas, 2022; Neo & Teo, 2022).

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the effective integration of data in the tourism industry offers substantial benefits, ranging from improved decision-making and enhanced customer experiences to heightened competitiveness. However, the journey towards a data-driven tourism sector must navigate the ethical, privacy, and security challenges that accompany this transformation.

To succeed in this data-centric landscape, stakeholders in the tourism industry must prioritize the development of robust data governance frameworks, ensuring responsible and ethical use of customer data. Moreover, investing in cybersecurity measures is imperative to safeguard sensitive information and maintain the trust of tourists. By doing so, the industry can harness the power of data to not only meet but exceed customer expectations, driving innovation, and sustaining long-term success.

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Handling Data Imbalance in Text Classification

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Abstract

When dealing with classification problems using Machine Learning techniques one of many challenges faced, is the dataset imbalance. Dataset imbalance is caused by an imbalanced class distribution, which is prevalent in the field of data science and ML.

Real-world datasets are often imbalanced offering limited input for the training process. Some classes are represented more than others, leading to biased models that prioritize majority classes and neglect the minority ones, which are often of paramount interest due to their prevalence. Addressing class imbalance is crucial to achieving accurate and reliable predictions.

This paper will be focused on different balancing approaches and classification algorithms to derive models and evaluate those models by different metrics. The data that will be used is based on replies on open questions on the economic activity of enterprises collected through structural business survey. The results will identify balancing strategies for the training dataset and their impacts on the automatic text classification.

Keywords: Text classification, Machine learning, Balance, Metrics

JEL codes: C88

1. Introduction

Dataset preprocessing is one of the most important aspects of Machine Learning. The quality of the dataset that is used for training has a direct impact on the learning process of the machine. When dealing with classification problems, such as text classification, often in the preprocessing phase there is a need to deal with datasets imbalances, which are datasets that have severe skew in class distribution. The dataset imbalance can influence machine learning algorithms, leading to ignore the minority classes, which predictions sometimes are very important.

This paper is focused on handling imbalance of the dataset used for the automatic classification of the Economic Activity (NACE Rev.2). The dataset contains data collected over the years on open questions on the economic activity of the enterprises through structural business survey. There are several approaches to address the problem of dataset imbalance. One of these approaches is to randomly resample the training dataset, which is the one used in this paper. While resampling imbalanced datasets two different strategies are used: delete examples from the majority class, known as undersampling and duplicate examples from the minority class, known as oversampling. Python is used for data processing due to its vast number of libraries. The impact of dataset balancing will be measured by different metrics, in order to evaluate the different approaches used.

2. Methodology

Randomly resampling the training dataset is one way to solve the problem of class imbalance. Removing examples from the majority class (undersampling) and duplicating examples from the minority class (oversampling) are the two basic methods for randomly resampling an

unbalanced dataset. Resampling generates a modified version of the training dataset, resulting in a different distribution of classes. This is a straightforward and effective approach in addressing imbalanced classification challenges. It is also known as "naive resampling" due to the fact that these approaches make no assumptions about the data and do not employ any heuristics. For extremely huge and complicated datasets, this makes them easy to implement and quick to run. In this paper, the implementations provided by the imbalanced-learn Python library are used. This Python package provides several resampling methods that are frequently applied to datasets with significant between-class imbalances. It is included in the scikit-learn-contrib projects and compatible with scikit-learn.

SMOTE Oversampling

One of the most used methods for creating new examples of the minority classes is the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique, or SMOTE, described by Chawla et al. 2002. SMOTE synthesizes new minority cases by combining preexisting ones. For the minority class, it uses linear interpolation to create the virtual training records. For every example in the minority class, one or more of the k-nearest neighbors are arbitrarily chosen to create these synthetic training records.

Undersampling

Random selection of instances, from the majority class, to be removed from the training dataset until the desired class distribution is attained, is known as random undersampling (Hoens et al. 2013). As a result, the training dataset will contain fewer examples of the majority classes. The undersampling method can be obtained by using the RandomUnderSampler imbalanced-learn class. This class is useful in the context of datasets that have class imbalance but still the number of examples in the minority classes is sufficient to make good predictions.

SMOTE Tomek

SMOTE Tomek is a combination of oversampling and undersampling by using SMOTE and Tomek Links (Batista et al. 2004). While SMOTE generates synthetic data for minority class, Tomek Links removes the data from the majority class identified as Tomek Links. Tomek links are instances of data from the majority class which are closest to the minority one.

Metrics

According to Yanchen et al, (2023), it is crucial to assess classifier performance with proper metrics in a class imbalance problem, which can be considered an indicator of model performance. The performance of the classifiers may be different from the real performance, due to the small number of instances of the minority classes in the training dataset.

Accuracy is one of the most common metric to evaluate a model, but is sometimes misleading. It measures the correctness of the classifier across all classes. Precision takes into consideration the accuracy of positive predictions that the classifier made for a specific class.

Recall measures the ability of the classifier to capture all positive instances of a specific class.

F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It takes into consideration both precision and recall. In a multi-class setting, these metrics are calculated for each class separately.

Imbalanced-learn is used as a library which relies on scikit-learn. This library provides the tools to deal with classification and imbalanced classes.

The classification models are trained and tested using four different classifiers: Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest and Bagging. These classifiers can be used for the economic activity dataset as the data is already labeled. The dataset is partitioned in order not to overlap the instances used for model training and testing. The classifiers are based on supervised machine learning techniques. Three previously mentioned balancing methods are

applied in the training dataset (the testing dataset shall not be impacted) and evaluated based on different metric scores.

3. Results and Discussion

The available dataset contains 74 different classes, which correspond to different economic activities (the biggest class contains 2698 instances while the smallest one 202). Randomsampler, SMOTE and SMOTETomek are used during the balancing phase of the training dataset. In order to identify if the number of instances in a class has an impact on the performance of the models, top 10 classes with more instances are taken into consideration as well (the biggest one with 2698 instances while the smallest one with 880). The results of the models and the balancing strategies are based on the four different metrics (Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1) of the four models (NB, SVM, RF, Bag) on the original dataset for 74 different classes as well as on the one with top 10 bigger classes. Results vary considerably among classification algorithms, balancing approaches and number of classes used for the classification problem. Naïve Bayes has a lower performance than the other classifiers. It performs better after application of balancing methods and benefits more from balancing, than the other methods used. SMOTE is one of the best performing methods for balancing for the used datasets. Balancing has more impact on the scenario with classes with more instances. The biggest impact is in accuracy and precision, for all three balancing methods.

For the 74 classes dataset, SMOTE and SMOTETomek are the best methods for balancing. For all categories of data, accuracy and precision increases, while models start to deteriorate as far as recall is concerned.

The numbers of instances within the classes, as well as the total number of classes, have an impact on the classification performance. In the top 10 classes, SMOTE is the method with the most positive scores. The indicators show that the number of instances in the class affects the performance, when it increases, the performance improves.

4. Conclusions

This work provides practical insights for selecting appropriate classification algorithms and balancing methods based on the specific characteristics of the dataset. Existing classification algorithms typically misclassify the majority of members of the minority class because they concentrate on examples of the majority class, due to the way they are constructed. In the past years, a number of approaches have been put up to address this issue. The most effective ones are related to the balancing of the dataset in the preprocessing phase, specifically through bagging and sampling-based techniques. This demonstrates how well ensemble and sampling techniques work together. This research highlights the trade-offs and considerations when aiming to improve different performance metrics. It is critical to properly select and assess the balancing method, adjust hyper-parameters, and take into account the particulars of the dataset and the employed algorithm. The best strategy for handling the unbalanced nature of the data, while preserving or enhancing recall, can be found by further experimenting with various balancing techniques, algorithm selections, and parameter settings.

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AI's Reshaping of Tourism and Related Digital Services

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Abstract

This paper identifies the challenges that the rapid growth in tourism poses to a sustainable development and to the evaluation of the needs and reviews from the tourists. The body of knowledge is carefully analyzed, and the results indicate a digitalization of the services which could provide a tangible and long-lasting impact on the competitive advantages of the Albanian tourism in an international level. Also, the paper analysis the need for change in terms of the user experience of the main stakeholders from the tourism industry and proposed ai integrated services for a better targeting, reach and personalization of such experience.

Interviews with key stakeholders from the tourism sector are conducted in order to gather and analyze their requests, needs and difficulties while interacting with digital services, which then conduct the main pillars and characteristics of the proposed ai-integrated framework.

In the end a clear description of the outputs of the research is provided as well as the challenges and limitations of such output.

There are possible scenarios for the development of the current research work which are introduced in the last chapter of the paper.

Keywords: digital services, sustainable development, tourism, framework, design thinking.

JEL codes: O33, Q01, O35, L86.

1. Introduction

The tourism in Albania has experienced a rapid growth in the recent years due to important investments in transportation infrastructure, urban development and important marketing campaign on social-cultural activities in traditional and digital media. Yet, little investments have been made to digitalize solutions and use AI-powered services which could enhance the way tourists engage with Albanian's tourist destination and personalize their experience.

The scope of this paper is to analyze existing reference in the body of knowledge on how the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the digital services of the tourism sector can improve and enhance the satisfaction and impact in the indicating parameters of a sustainable and multicultural tourism. The facilitation of the sustainable tourism is mainly provided by the enhancement of the visitors experience and an effective promotion of the Albanian tourism aspects. The proposed framework grows upon a range of digital innovations such as digital records, microservices, Ai agents, chatbots and targeted marketing strategies. Such characteristics of the framework should be able to increase the tourist satisfaction as well as expand the reach of Albania's diverse tourist offerings.

The work in this paper analysis also how the user experience is very important on such digital services, that target a multicultural, multilingual and multiage group of tourists by carefully identifying that new means of communication, engagement and services should be provided in order to retain engagement and widen the reach of the target group.

2. Methodology

The research methodology for the proposal of such framework is based on design thinking, as we argue that a deep understanding of the problem should be provided by end users and a full engagement with the main stakeholder in the tourism industry.

This paper states clearly the two research questions on which the artefact of the framework is proposed and designed which are as following:

RQ1: What is the level of engagement that the end users of such digital services would consider as satisfying?

RQ2: What ai integrated services would form the core of the framework and guide the user experience?

In order to conduct the research work of this paper, interviews were conducted with stakeholders from the tourism industry with a focus on non-resident in Albania tourist and entrepreneurs/managers from the travel industry and hospitality industry.

3. Results and Discussion

The outcome of this the research work consists in identifying the design principles on the proposed prototype of the ai-integrated framework as well as an identification of the limitations it poses mainly on a governance perspective and compliancy with policies and regulations with the countries of residence of the tourists.

4. Conclusions

In this section will be analysed the design principles that contribute to the AI-integrated framework as well as the answer to the research questions is provided. At last we will address some limitations of the research work and a broad argument set of possible future works and of this contribution and their impact on the development of a sustainable tourism in Albania

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Blockchain for Tourism: Case Albania

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Abstract

Tourism is a multifaceted industry that plays a crucial role in Albania's economic development, cultural preservation, and international engagement. As the popularity of Albania as a tourist destination is on the rise and the country aims to set itself apart by promoting high-end ecotourism, the tourism industry and its operators must take active steps to improve the quality of their services and enhance customer experience. Integrating AI and blockchain technology in the tourism industry catalyzes transformative changes. This paper examines the nuanced benefits of implementing blockchain in tourism in the Albanian context, emphasizing its potential to significantly provide a competitive edge by enhancing efficiency, data integrity, and privacy and by upgrading the end-to-end experience of visitors. The decentralized nature of blockchain ensures secure and transparent transactions, while smart contracts streamline booking processes, reducing the risk of fraud. Moreover, blockchain implementation in supply chain management fosters traceability and accountability in the travel ecosystem. The wealth of data generated by blockchain transactions is a robust foundation for data analysis and supports AI models, empowering decision-making processes. This paper explores these dynamics through a literature review of blockchain for tourism and an analysis of the latest advancements in Albania's tourism. The paper provides insights into the innovative solutions arising from the convergence of AI and blockchain in the tourism sector.

Keywords: Blockchain, Tourism, AI, Albania

JEL codes: L8, L83, L86, Z3, Z32

1. Introduction

Blockchain technology is a decentralized, distributed ledger that stores transactional records of the public in several databases, known as the "chain," in a network connected through peer-to-peer nodes (Nakamoto 2008). A blockchain is a "digital, decentralized and distributed ledger in which transactions are logged and added in chronological order to create permanent and tamperproof records" (Treiblmaier 2018). The implementation of blockchain technology in the tourism industry has the potential to alter existing business relations, cause structural changes such as disintermediation, and have a substantial impact on organizational structures (Treiblmaier and Önder 2019).

The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) underscores Albania's remarkable resurgence in tourism. Albania experienced a 56% increase in tourist arrivals compared to pre-pandemic 2019 figures. Securing the third position globally for tourism sector growth during the first 7 months of 2023 and outperforming better-known European destinations (Tirana Times 2023). Although the tourism industry is an important sector in the Albanian economy, the research that has been conducted in the field is not extensive nor exhaustive. In particular, there is little research that has explored the extent of the diffusion of digital technologies among touristic enterprises operating in the industry. Furthermore, a lack of research is observed concerning qualitative aspects and topologies of digital technologies employed by the Albanian market tourism actors. IINSTAT (2022) has reported that in 2022,

100% of the enterprises that operate in the accommodation and food service industry use computer devices, 97.4% of these businesses have Internet access, and 29.8% of the employees of these enterprises use computer devices. Statistics from INSTAT (2023) have shown that 30.7% of the entire e-commerce sales volume has been realized by accommodation and food service enterprises. The same source also reports an increase in the percentage of Internet access in these businesses to 99.9%.

The authors in this paper aim to explore the potential impact of the implementation of blockchain technology in the Albanian tourism industry in the context of promoting sustainability in the sector. This paper provides an overview of the utilization of blockchain in the tourism sector in the literature review section. In the results and discussion section, the foundations of a blockchain-based solution are presented and particular areas of interest in terms of the added values are addressed. The key challenges that may affect the feasibility and the degree of success of the proposed solution are identified. In the conclusions section, the authors summarize the results of the conducted work and suggest future research.

2. Literature Review

An increased interest in the blockchain application and its impact on the tourism industry has emerged in recent years. Several recent studies have focused on the plausible issues that blockchain can address in the sector. Treiblamier and Önder (2019) used a multi-theoretical approach, focused on a supply chain management framework, to investigate blockchain's implications in the tourism industry. Analyzing data from 10 qualitative interviews, they anticipate blockchain's potential to reshape business relations by increasing transaction transparency, possibly diminishing the trust required for partnerships and initiating structural changes like disintermediation. The authors emphasize the substantial impact of anticipated changes in transaction costs on organizational structures, foreseeing simultaneous cost reductions and increases across domains, influencing market structures, revenue sharing, and B2B settlement. They consider blockchain as a new resource impacting both inter- and intra-organizational processes, ultimately influencing competitive advantage, but acknowledge that further research is required to assess blockchain's promises and benefits for system stakeholders (Treiblamier and Önder, 2019).

Blockchain technology is a viable solution for both hospitality operators (HTNG, 2018) and airlines (Goudarzi and Martin, 2018) regarding inventory management in the tourism industry. Utilizing blockchain in this context enables the sharing of information on the availability and the rate of inventory among stakeholders. Such capability of blockchain can lead to the replacement of proprietary property management systems (PMS) and central reservation systems (CRS) that connect various nodes in the tourism industry, thus directly connecting suppliers of inventory with customer-facing sales outlets, eliminating intermediaries (HTNG, 2018). Blockchain provides a means of automating the process of hotel check-in by triggering the assignment of rooms once the payment has been completed. This principle can be extended to other operators in the scope of rentals (apartments, office space, cars) by equipping the units with locks that can be controlled through a blockchain (Treiblmaier, 2020).

The supply chain is seen as one of the main application areas of blockchain technology (Treiblmaier, 2018). The approach includes tracking and tracing food to certify its origin and the handling procedures to mitigate the risk of health and hygiene issues. This element of the supply chain is essential for the sectors of food tourism that attain a competitive edge through the use of organic, local, authentic, or sustainable products (Nam et al., 2019). The blockchain application can be extended to other aspects of the food service industry, where smart contracts can be implemented to address inventory procurement standing orders, support devices, kitchen maintenance, and the purchase or lease of equipment (Willie, 2019). Other supply chain pertinent areas such as the tracking of the status and location of important assets both at

different levels of the chain can be addressed through blockchain. The applications are relevant to the airline industry and at a micro level, to tourists' assets or belongings by tracking and logging the location and every change in custody (Goudarzi and Martin, 2019). Additionally, it is possible to provide tourists with up-to-date information about the current location of their belongings on their devices (Ludeiro 2019). In airline operations, such blockchain-based solution is valid with regards to the avoidance of inconsistencies in the lifecycle documentation of an asset, guaranteeing uncorrupted credentials and verification of compliance with maintenance regulations (Irvin and Sullivan, 2018). Blockchain is also employable in the ambit of trip coordination across suppliers, leading to a reduction of inefficiencies, as in the case when a traveler fails to check in for a flight and the hotel, as well as the rental car supplier, can immediately release inventory for sale to others (HTNG 2018). Blockchain technology has the potential to function as a central location for storing in a content management setting for tourism enterprises, thus facilitating the process of keeping the company's web presence up to date (HTNG, 2018).

(Önder, 2018) suggested that blockchain could have a large impact on payments in the tourism industry. According to (Kwoh and Koh, 2018) certain small island destinations have already piloted the adoption of cryptocurrency payments for both residents and tourists in an attempt to gain a competitive advantage. The adoption of cryptocurrency payments provides a viable solution to the issues of cross-border remittances and foreign currency conversion. Smart contracts can trigger immediate payment after recording a transaction based on contractual terms, which can facilitate collaboration between hotels and travel agencies (Treiblmaier 2020). Due to its transparency and its immutable nature, blockchain is an adapted solution to address the complexities that may be encountered with taxation at multiple levels. In this scenario, it enables tax authorities to post structures and the taxes can be transferred through smart contracts, providing proof of compliance to the tax-paying entities (HTNG 2018).

Blockchain technology is relevant in the determination of a person's identity and a potential implementation could result in a global traveler identity across blockchain (Bell and Hollander, 2018). As a result, the work for hotels is facilitated as they store the arrival and departure dates on the blockchain instead of reporting to the authorities in charge (HTNG, 2018). Such an endeavor that helps with identity theft prevention requires cooperation with the governments as the IDs that enable this process should be equipped with cryptographically secured codes (Dogru et al., 2018).

Although blockchain in the tourism sector is not a widespread practice, blockchain-based tourism projects have already been piloted and deployed. Dubai, also known as the "Futuristic City" and an emerging hub for the Smart Tourism Dynamic Responsive System (STDRS) framework (Khan et al. 2017) has launched the Tourism 2.0 initiative to apply a B2B travel marketplace powered by blockchain. The marketplace enables hospitality operators and tour operators to administer smart contracts via blockchain and to supply offers directly to customers via customized social platform applications. It enhances tourists' experience by providing personalized itineraries and boosts the tourism sector (Bodkhe et al., 2019). In Croatia, the Rijeka Marketplace blockchain-based platform has been developed by the Rijeka Tourist Board to transform the city of Rijeka and the surrounding areas into a smart-tourism destination. The marketplace provides a platform where touristic operating entities can advertise and sell their offerings and where both citizens and tourists can browse and buy from a wide selection of city services via the user's digital wallet (ICTBusiness, 2019).

3. Methodology

This paper consists of exploratory research methods. The approach involves an analysis of existing literature on the latest advancements of blockchain technology in the tourism industry context. The literature review analyzes relevant studies and applications of blockchain

technology addressing tourism industry challenges. In the context of Albanian tourism, the methodology involves an analysis of the current situation of the tourism industry and the technologies that key stakeholders in Albanian tourism apply. The study is focused on identifying key issues that should be addressed in the Albanian tourism context and defining if blockchain has the potential to address them. This paper aims to explore blockchain technology and blockchain-based platform, that brings together key stakeholder in the tourism industry, and come to conclusions if those solutions are appropriate for addressing the challenges of Albanian tourism.

4. Results and Discussion

According to the UNWTO, sustainable development in tourism is “tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment, and host communities”. Under this prism, Albania has good premises for paving its way toward sustainable tourism development, powering this approach by the employment of blockchain technology. The country features great natural landscapes, a vast cultural inheritance, a great culinary tradition, local crafts and artisan work, and a lot more.

To date, there does not exist a platform that provides a common marketplace for the stakeholders. Therefore, the Albanian tourism industry would benefit from the creation of a blockchain-based single-source platform that brings together all the stakeholders. This marketplace has the potential to help enterprises that enable tourism-related services to grow by bringing them in direct communication with the demand for their services or products without any intermediary. On the other hand, such a marketplace promotes the enhancement of the tourists’ experience by providing them with a single source of information, where they can arrange their travel itinerary and browse a variety of offers. It has the potential to facilitate access to remote touristic areas by enabling the coordination of all the actors across the supply chain. The benefits extend beyond the tourist-focused industry, as the services and products can also be accessed and procured by the locals. This platform's implementation can transform Albania into a hub of smart destinations. Due to the features of blockchain technology, its employment will also result in the creation of datasets containing relevant tourism data across the industry. The creation of such datasets in combination with data analytics. ML models and other AI-based solutions can lay the foundations for better decision-making by the operators and the institutions in terms of their strategies and planning.

Blockchain technology can be used to create a transparent and secure record of ownership and transactions related to Albania’s cultural heritage sites. Another potential benefit of applying Blockchain technology in Albania’s tourism is the verification of the authenticity of local products and goods. This is particularly relevant in promoting local crafts, traditional foods, and souvenirs, and ensuring that tourists receive genuine high-quality products.

The Albanian tourism sector is predominantly comprised of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that cater to diverse offerings, including accommodation, food and beverages, travel guides, and travel packages. The size of the enterprises constrains the amounts of investments they can make in the implementation of innovative technologies. Due to the high number of stakeholders in the tourism industry, the interoperability between them is a significant challenge at a technical and business level. Agreements among the operators have to be reached and the interference of the institutions to provide a stimulus might be helpful. On the other hand, protocols to streamline the operational flow and the seamless integration of the services in the platform have to be addressed. Furthermore, a Blockchain regulatory framework has not been established regarding concerns about data privacy and information security that must be addressed from a legal standpoint. Resistance and skepticism may be encountered in the market of the operators because blockchain is a recent technology

and is still evolving. A strategy for building credibility in the given case is by proof of work and a small-scale implementation, focused on a limited area would provide such proof and establish the ground for further relevant analysis.

5. Conclusions

Blockchain technology is an emerging and evolving technology with the potential to disrupt the way that industries have operated to date. The tourism industry is not excluded from such disruption. Through this paper, the authors have come to evaluate that there are significant potential benefits that derive from the application of blockchain technology in the case of the Albanian industry of tourism. As no disruptive progress comes without any difficulty, in the Albanian case several challenges may be encountered. The challenges, however, can be addressed and resolved through the reach of consensus and possible incentives as part of a long-term strategy for the sustainable development of the tourism sector.

The benefits can be summarized as follows:

- The application of blockchain technology addresses the challenges associated with disparate systems, fostering collaboration and shared value creation.
- Increase transparency and mitigation of fraud risk
- Increase efficiency in inventory management
- Enhanced customer experience

The following challenges have been identified:

- Significant costs may be required for the implementation of the proposed platform
- Blockchain technology is not yet consolidated and widely adopted
- Lack of legal regulatory framework
- Resistance and skepticism due to the novelty of the technology
- Mandatory interoperability amongst all stakeholders

To conclude, further research focused on the Albanian case of blockchain implementation in the tourism industry is required. Blockchain implementation research in the context of the tourism industry will benefit from more in-depth relevant research about the sectors. The combination will provide more robust insights in addressing both the cases and the challenges that arise in the environment.

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A Review of the Gravity Model and its Applications in Migration Studies

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Abstract

Migration plays an increasingly important role in the transformation of national, regional and local populations. In order to study population movements and their impacts on the origin and destination areas, a study was made on the gravity model of migration, which is an interpretation of Newton's law of gravity in mechanics: the force of gravity between two physical bodies is proportional to the weight of each of the bodies divided by the square of the distance between the centers of gravity in meters.

Gravity models have long been popular for analyzing economic phenomena related to the movement of people, goods and services or capital. In the first studies there were data limitations regarding migration flows that have prevented their use in this context. During the last years, the use of gravity models for explaining international migration flows has significantly increased.

This model owes its success to, firstly, its intuitive consistency with migration theories; secondly, ease of estimation in its simplest form; and, thirdly, goodness of fit in most applications.

In this paper we review the gravity model, discuss for greater integration of migration modeling and how to relate it with labor forces and other economic or social factors.

By following through the development of the many forms of the gravity model in this way, the potential user is far better equipped to handle the particular situation with which he is confronted. He learns that the gravity model is a very flexible tool capable of almost infinite variation to suit the particular circumstances of his problem.

Keywords: Gravity model, migration, migration flows, labor forces.

JEL codes: J11, J21, R23, J61

1. Introduction

Migration is a phenomenon that has its own effects both in the demographic and economic aspects. For this reason, it is very important to study and reach results: Why do people migrate? What are the main reasons? How does it affect the workforce? What can be done to fix the structure of a country? etc. In recent years, there has been a high level of migration in Albania, especially among young people.

In this article, we will present a description of the models that study migration, which will serve us later (in other studies) to study migration in Albania in more detail, the reasons for migration and its impact on the labor force.

The gravity model for migration is one of the most used models by many other authors, and it has its bases from Newton's law of gravity. The work in this article consists in the presentation of different forms of the gravity model, how it has changed and expanded according to different authors. This will help us to have a clearer idea in choosing the model and variables that should be used to make a study analysis according to interest.

2. Methodology

This paper aims to examine the gravity model and the usefulness of this theoretical approach in migration studies. The methodology used follows a detailed historical analysis of the literature on the origin and chronological development of this model, beginning with Isaac Newton's gravity law in physics and concluding with its most current applications.

In the last 30 years, the topic has been extensively investigated and reviewed, by authors such as Philbrick (1973), Anderson (1979), Anderson (2011), Yotov et al. (2016), Head (2003), Carrothers (1956), Capoani (2023), etc. This research offers an updated and detailed analysis with a broader range of the existing applications of the model, especially in migration theory. Contributions applying the concept of gravity are examined, ranging from those describing the movement of people (Ravenstein 1885; Stewart 1947; among others) and those that determine the trade flows (Isard 1954; Tinbergen 1962) to more modern applications.

Ravenstein (1885) suggest that a population center attracts migrants from other centers in relation to its population size and inversely in proportion to its distance away, and that migrants leave according to the same principle. He postulated an equation of the form:

$$M_{ij} = \frac{f(P_i)}{D_{ij}} \quad [1]$$

where M_{ij} is the migration from origin i to a destination j , $f(P_i)$ is a function of population of i , D_{ij} is the distance between origin and destination.

The next development of the model occurred in the late 1920s when Young (1924) made a similar attempt to explain the patterns of migration. He came to the same conclusions as Ravenstein except that he claimed that migration varied inversely with the square of the distance between the source and the destination.

Reilly (1929) used the concepts of social gravitation to explain the way in which a city attracts trade from an individual in its surrounding territory. His Law of "Retail Gravitation" was of the same basic form as Young's equation. It states that a city attracts retail trade from a customer in its hinterland in proportion to its size (population) and in inverse proportion to the square of the distance separating the customer from the center of the city. The boundary separating the market areas of two cities i and j competing for customers in a hinterland is thus defined as the locus of points for which

$$P_i/D_{xi}^2 = P_j/D_{xj}^2 \quad [2]$$

where D_{xi} and D_{xj} are the distances of cities i and j respectively from any point x on the boundary.

During the 1940s Stewart and Zipf developed models which are apparently the origins of current models. Stewart based his theory on Boyle's investigation of gases and the study of matter as a mass. Stewart's expression describes demographic force as

$$F_{ij} = G \frac{P_i P_j}{D_{ij}} \quad [3]$$

where F_{ij} is the force of interaction between concentrations i and j , P_i is the population of area i , P_j is the population of area j , D_{ij} is the distance between areas i and j , and G is a constant.

Starting with the P/d relationship, Zipf expressed the theory that the number of persons that move between any two communities whose respective populations are P_i and P_j ; and which are separated by a shortest transportation distance, D_{ij} will be proportional to the ratio $P_i P_j / D_{ij}$, subject to the effect of modifying factors. While Stewart's and Zipf's expressions are basically the same, Zipf's relationship differs in that it raises the entire $P_i P_j / D_{ij}$ factor to a power.

$$F_{ij} = G \frac{P_i^\alpha P_j^\beta}{D_{ij}^\gamma} \quad [4]$$

After a transformation in logarithmic form equation is:

$$\ln F_{ij} = \delta + \alpha \ln P_i + \beta \ln P_j - \gamma \ln D_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij} \quad [5]$$

where $\delta = \ln G$ and ϵ_{ij} is a zero-mean error term added to the equation. This is the most common form used.

Zipf, Stewart and others have tested and applied these formulations of the gravity concept empirically, measuring the amount of interaction between pairs of cities by a variety of characteristics such as telephone calls, bus passenger movements and newspaper circulation.

The Swiss-American geographer Tobler (1970) was also inspired by the use of the gravitational model in social sciences. He formulated his first law of geography in the Journal Economic Geography and applied it to the study of international trade. In formal terms, the formula is:

$$T_{ij} = \frac{P_i P_j}{D_{ij}^\beta} \quad [6]$$

where T_{ij} is the degree of spatial interaction (migration, trade flows, air travel, etc) between place i and j . T_{ij} is proportionate to the size of the populations and inversely correlated to the distance. P_i is the population of the origin and P_j is the population of the destination. D_{ij} is the distance between these locations. The strength of the decline in interaction with increasing separation is estimated by β .

The basic gravity model of migration is as follows:

$$\ln M_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln P_i + \beta_2 \ln P_j + \beta_3 \ln D_{ij} + e_{ij} \quad [7]$$

where M_{ij} represents the migration flows from the origin i to the destination j , D_{ij} is the geographical distance between origin and destination, P is the population size and

The gravity model was extended to include the economic and other explanatory variables (Lowry, 1966; Lee, 1966). The modified gravity model widely used in the empirical investigations on migration determinants takes the following form:

$$\ln M_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln D_{ij} + \beta_2 \ln P_i + \beta_3 \ln P_j + \beta_4 \ln Y_i + \beta_5 \ln Y_j + \beta_6 \ln U_i + \beta_7 \ln U_j + e_{ij} \quad [8]$$

where Y is the income and U is the unemployment rate. This model is expressed in log-log form in order to obtain estimations for the parameters which can be interpreted as elasticities. A similar model is used from Jandová and Paleta (2011) in order to include wages and job vacancies of places origin and destination:

$$\ln M_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln D_{ij} + \beta_2 \ln P_i + \beta_3 \ln P_j + \beta_4 \ln \left(\frac{W_j}{W_i} \right) + \beta_5 \ln (FWP_j - FWP_i) + \beta_6 \ln U_i + \beta_7 \ln U_j \quad [9]$$

where $\frac{W_j}{W_i}$ is the ratio of wages and $FWP_j - FWP_i$ is a difference between job vacancies.

3. Results and Discussion

The gravity model of migration is the most common model used for migration studies, starting with the basic form of Ravenstein (1885):

$$M_{ij} = \frac{f(P_i)}{D_{ij}}$$

and then continuing with the models of Stewart and Zipf:

$$F_{ij} = G \frac{P_i P_j}{D_{ij}} \quad \text{and} \quad \ln F_{ij} = \delta + \alpha \ln P_i + \beta \ln P_j - \gamma \ln D_{ij} + \epsilon_{ij}$$

Applications of these models or the extended gravity models are used widely to study migration of population of a country.

4. Conclusions

In its most applied form, the law of gravity of population migration states that:

$$\ln M_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln P_i + \beta_2 \ln P_j + \beta_3 \ln D_{ij} + e_{ij}$$

This model provides us a more realistic description of the relationship between the variables, and using this basic model we can extend it adding other economic or social variables as it is done by Jandová and Paleta (2011) or Lowry (1966).

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E-Services Security: Navigating the Landscape of Electronic Public Services in Albania

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Abstract

Recent decades have witnessed that the global economy focus has changed from an industrial economy to a knowledge-based economy. At the heart of this economy lies the data, which in combination with the great and continuous development of technology and the increase of access and use of Internet, have become the main asset for the entities that own them. But, in this data- driven economy, personal data are an important part of the whole data set.

On one hand, individuals or users provide their data including personal ones and on the other hand, companies and public institutions assist them with various electronic services. So, this is a mutually beneficial relationship, but it should be guided by clear principles and policies of personal data protection, during collection, storage, processing, transfer and destruction. But does this always happen? Does the government always protect the data of its citizens? At the same time the benefits of data are growing, the risks are increasing as well and a lot of security and privacy issues and concerns arise.

The paper presents a general background of electronic public services offered by the government of Albania, specifically the case of the e-Albania portal. During the last 10 years, the access and use of the e-Albania portal has shown continuous growth. According to the statistics provided by National Agency for Information Society, 1,594,532 applications for electronic services have been registered in October 2023.

Taking into consideration that now 99% of public services in Albania are offered as digital services, this has further highlighted the security problem faced by the systems that offer these services. Beyond the positive developments of technology, these systems present some negative aspects, especially those that have to do with the security of personal data.

This paper emphasizes all positive and negative aspects of providing public services only through electronic means and examines the state of security of these services in Albania.

Keywords: knowledge-based economy, e-Albania, electronic services, personal data

Digital Innovation in the Development of Sustainable Tourism. The Case of Saranda, Albania

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Abstract

Tourism has become one of the most important and growing sectors of the Albanian economy. According to Minister of Tourism in Albania, till September 2023 the number of tourists in Albania was about 8,3 million. Saranda has a developed tourism sector, especially during the summer period for its natural beauty and cultural heritage. The number of foreign tourists visiting this city is constantly increasing.

In a time when digital technology is gaining rapid momentum and heading towards an increasingly global perspective, the promotion of tourism as a whole and cultural heritage through the development of various applications that connect people, communities, cultures, and markets worldwide is necessary. The aim of this paper is to present a sustainable tourism package that supports Immersive Experiential Tourism through innovative technology. The goal is to create opportunities for people to experience unique moments through a digital application, to virtually touch and live the full tourist potential that the area offers, and to encourage them to visit it in person. The app will be available on IOS and Android. The package will present all the information that a tourist needs about accommodation, restaurants, beaches, cultural sites, nightlife, transportation, events and tours in the city.

The development of an interactive digital application equipped with elements that ensures real-time information updates, contributes to the orientation of all stakeholders influencing tourism development to promote this innovation, which contributes to economic growth and community development. A comprehensive promotion that connects Saranda with the global tourism market is undoubtedly accompanied by economic growth, social networking, and cultural exchanges among different countries.

Keywords: Albania, Interactive, Smart Tourism, Platform, App.

1. Introduction

Cultural heritage has the capacity to enhance social capital, foster a sense of individual and communal belonging, and promote recognition and networking through cultural exchange. These factors contribute to the preservation of social and territorial coherence. However, cultural, archaeological, and natural heritage has now become commercially significant for the travel and tourism industry in many countries. The development of technology and innovation allows us to bring this cultural heritage closer to individuals, communities, countries, etc., in real-time.

Tourism has become one of the most important and growing sectors of the Albanian economy. According to Minister of Tourism in Albania, till September 2023 the number of tourists in Albania was about 8,3 million. In 2022 the total income from tourism was 2.8 Millard euro or 48.5% more than 2021¹. The total contribution is increasing from 10,7 % in 2020 to 24% of

¹ Ministry of Finance in Albania, <https://financa.gov.al/konventa-nderkombetare-e-turizmit-ibrahimaj-politika-fiskale-ka-nxitur-investimet-dhe-zhvillimin-e-sektorit-te-turizmit/>

GDP in 2022, with 250000 employed people in this sector as total number.² The UNWTO World Tourism Barometer, has positioned Albania in the third spot globally for the period spanning January to July 2023, Albania achieved an impressive 56% growth rate.³

The development of sustainable tourism is included in the national strategies for tourism development in our country, such as:

-The National Strategy for Sustainable Tourism Development 2019-2023 by the Ministry of Tourism and Environment.⁴ That aims to build instruments to increase added value, especially for families, the development of new tourist products, and the improvement of service sensitivity so that all together we promote an Albania with healthy values for a better future for us and our children.

-The National Strategy for Culture 2019-2025 by the Ministry of Culture.⁵ That aims to conceive a guide for the development of the cultural sector, cultural heritage, and the creative industry to create favorable conditions for individual, social, and state development.

Additionally, there is a significant number of EU policies related to the development of sustainable tourism:

-The resolution on the Work Plan for Culture 2023-2026, focuses on 4 priorities on of them being culture for people: enhancing cultural participation and the role of culture in society⁶. One of the actions of the work plan is stimulating the digital transformation of the cultural and creative sectors.⁷ The European tourism agenda 2030 covers five priorities areas: green transition, digital transition, resilience and inclusion, skills and support, and the enabling policy framework and governance.⁸ This agenda is based on European transition pathway for tourism that includes between others the digitalization of tourism service.

-The EU Youth Strategy within the framework of cooperation for EU youth policies for 2019-2027, focusing on three fundamental areas of action around three words: Commit, Connect, Empower. All this cultural heritage must be passed down through generations to ensure sustainability, preservation, and protection of national values.

The purpose of the paper is to promote sustainable tourism and economic growth through innovative technology and the concept of smart tourism.

The application that will be created aims to assist users in finding places and dedicated information for any attraction they seek. The novelty brought by this application is linked to the real-time update of information for all categories included, carried out by the application's maintainers, service providers, or other interested individuals. The application will be enriched with interactive maps, detailed itineraries to attractions offered by Saranda, along with photos and specific information. The development of an interactive digital application equipped with elements that ensures real-time information updates, contributes to the orientation of all stakeholders influencing tourism development to promote this innovation, which contributes to economic growth and community development.

A comprehensive promotion that connects Saranda with the global tourism market is undoubtedly accompanied by economic growth, social networking, and cultural exchanges among different countries.

² Tourism and Hospitality in Albania 2022, UNDP

³ UNWTO

⁴ <https://turizmi.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/National-Tourism-Strategy-2019-2023-EN.pdf>

⁵ <https://kultura.gov.al/ep-content/uploads/2021/02/finale-Strategjia-Kombe%CC%88tare-pe%CC%88r-Kulture%CC%88n-2019-2025-ne-Anglisht.pdf>

⁶ <https://culture.ec.europa.eu/news/council-of-ministers-agrees-on-new-eu-work-plan-for-culture-2023-2026>

⁷ [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022G1207\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022G1207(01))

⁸ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/news/european-tourism-agenda-2030-commission-welcomes-commitment-eu-countries-make-tourism-greener-more-2022-12-02_en

2. Methodology

The creation of this application for promoting cultural, archaeological, and natural attractions using digital tools will go through two phases as follows:

- Phase One: Project Setup

The creation of an admin panel in the backend that allows the administrator to add, modify, or delete information in the application, including posts, cultural sites, news, or any other application-related information. This admin panel is an essential tool for ensuring the quality and updated content of the application.

- Phase Two: Main Screen and App Flow

On the main screen, there will be user-published stories and a menu to navigate to other screens where it:

-Provides information about natural and cultural tourist attractions.

-Utilizes a map service to display the location of cultural sites on the map.

-Links each post to its location on the map.

-Enables searching and filtering of cultural sites.

-Users can view information about each attraction in Saranda, including the name, description, photos, and their location on the map.

-Users will have easy access to detailed information about each event, including date, time, location, description, and ticket details.

Figure 1. Application interface

3. Results and Discussion

The Municipality of Saranda is a rich area with tourist assets stemming from its culture, history, natural beauty, monuments, material and non-material heritage, food, and untapped social authenticity. This area represents a unique opportunity for implementing new, sustainable, and innovative development models based on its regional geographic position, natural resources, examples of national and international cultural and historical heritage, as well as vibrant folklore.

Therefore, the preservation and inheritance of national cultural and natural values are a national priority, but the integration with innovative and digital technology ensures long-term sustainability, effective management, and global promotion.

A dedicated application for the city of Saranda, aimed at promoting natural, cultural, and archaeological heritage, will provide:

- Rich information and interactivity about the details of cultural and natural heritage, allowing users to navigate and obtain information through photos, videos, and audio, as well as information about the history, culture, and characteristics of various heritage sites.
- Advanced technology to offer personalized information based on users' locations. This can assist in discovering important locations near the user's location.
- Education and awareness as this application also serves as an educational tool to increase awareness about the importance of cultural and natural heritage. Local actors and the targeted audience will deepen their knowledge about the use and promotion of the application as an innovation to help users learn more about a culture, place, tradition, and beyond.
- Opportunities for improving the tourist experience as it will assist users in exploring tourist attractions. They can provide detailed guidance, suggestions for activities and restaurants, and other practical information is needed.

4. Conclusions

Promoting cultural, archaeological, and natural attractions using digital tools (creating an application) aims to promote sustainable tourism and economic growth through innovative technology and the concept of SMART TOURISM. We offer a sustainable tourism package that supports Immersive Experiential Tourism through innovative technology. An application as a digital and interactive promotion novelty of cultural, natural, and archaeological attractions in Saranda is accessible to everyone and primarily provides an environment that enables sustainable tourism development.

Increasing the capacities of local government staff, tour guides, and local actors in the continuous use of technology as a steadily growing trend. Awareness, empowerment, and the rise of capacities within the target group as a consortium with complex interests in tourism promotion, joint tourist product development, and the need for coordination and mutual cooperation, recognizing and developing communication channels with service providers.

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Adapting AI Innovations for Chargeback Fraud Prevention in Albania's Hospitality Sector

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Abstract

In an era marked by the rapid evolution of technology and a corresponding rise in sophisticated fraudulent schemes, the tourism industry faces unique vulnerabilities.

This article examines the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies in combating chargeback fraud within the hospitality industry, with a specific focus on the Albanian context. Chargeback fraud, a significant concern in the global hospitality sector, presents unique challenges due to the increasing reliance on digital transactions and online bookings. In Albania, where tourism is a growing economic contributor, the adoption of AI for fraud prevention is both a necessity and a challenge, given the country's evolving digital infrastructure and payment practices.

Through a comprehensive literature review, the article explores global trends and innovations in AI-driven fraud prevention techniques, including customized fraud detection algorithms, guest behavior analysis, real-time transaction monitoring, and biometric verification systems. It then delves into a comparative analysis, drawing parallels between these global practices and the potential for their adaptation within the Albanian hospitality sector.

Given the scarcity of specific data on chargeback fraud in Albania, the article employs reasoning to highlight the urgency and feasibility of implementing AI solutions. It discusses the adaptation challenges and opportunities, considering Albania's unique technological, regulatory, and market conditions. The article concludes with strategic recommendations for stakeholders in Albania's tourism industry, emphasizing the need for investment in AI technologies as a strategic move to safeguard the sector's future against evolving fraudulent tactics.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Tourism Fraud, Chargeback fraud prevention, Machine Learning, Predictive Analytics, Data Security.

Online Privacy and Social Media: A Short Glimpse in Albania

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Abstract

During this ending year 2023 in Albania, online privacy has significantly evolved from its original conceptualization during the inception of data privacy. The cyber world inundates us with personal data while providing limited means to manage and safeguard this information. As Albanian citizen gain extensive access to the cyber realm encompassing e-commerce, portals, social media, and search engines, they become increasingly exposed to online privacy challenges and threats. Voluntarily feeding online portals with personal data that was once deemed private has become the norm. Despite the scarcity of laws governing privacy, which mainly focus on data processors within specific geographical boundaries, a growing concern arises: "Why is my personal data being used or misused by third parties?" Consequently, the ensuing debate revolves around questions such as, "Does data retain its privacy once voluntarily published on an online platform?", "What data should be considered private in the cyber world?" and "To what extent are online agreements, often presented in small fonts on small devices, valid?". Another critical point of discussion pertains to the blurred boundary between digital marketing and privacy infringement. The ethicality of online marketing practices has been under scrutiny, as companies invest vast sums in targeting specific customers via social networks. However, this practice often conflicts with protecting users' private data. This paper aims to redefine private data in the cyber domain and propose steps to establish new rules and regulations governing the conduct of all involved parties concerning private data.

Keywords: privacy, cyber world, threats, social media, intrusion.

JEL Codes: D8, M37

1. Introduction

The discourse surrounding online privacy has sparked numerous discussions, research papers, studies, and surveys. The advent of the digital era has revolutionized our world, inevitably giving rise to issues, challenges, and problems that demand attention and resolution. These issues, akin to the aftermath of the industrial revolution (such as pollution and global warming), will likely persist with us for some time—the contemporary digital issues.

Central to these concerns is privacy, a fact corroborated by research from the Boston Consulting Group indicating that 76 percent of global consumers and 83 percent of U.S. consumers prioritize the privacy of personal data.

There has been an increasing interest in user's privacy since it was out for public reach the news that Facebook gave Cambridge Analytica unfiltered and unauthorized access to PII (personal identifiable information) to more than 87 million of unaware and uninformed users. It gave a spark to the continuous debate over social networks' impact on individuals privacy. It is quite obvious of total lack of ability of national governments or governance institutions to prevent the impact of social media on the structure of society, and on the rights and duties of their citizens. The fact that data is gathered, stored and analyzed, in the aim of personalizing and customizing services offered and online experiences have been shaping the global economy and not only. These technological advancements in a frightful manner influence the

individual rights given by the constitution such as: freedom of expression, voting, equality in front of the law etc. In this paper we will treat only one of the many threats to privacy in the social media, not wanting to be prolonged in here and some other threats are correlated with other technology advancements and services offered widely to public such as cloud computing, smartphone app services, and Internet of Things, which are touched through the other sections in this paper.

Another critical point of discussion pertains to the blurred boundary between digital marketing and privacy infringement. The ethicality of online marketing practices has been under scrutiny, as companies invest vast sums in targeting specific customers via social networks. However, this practice often conflicts with protecting users' private data. Incidents like the infamous Cambridge Analytica case underscore the challenges faced by social networks in balancing the needs of paying customers and user privacy. Despite fines, regulations, updated agreements, and even Senate hearings, the damage caused by privacy breaches remains irreparable, exposing the dark side of social media networks where data is not only illegally collected but also manipulated to influence user decisions.

While some believe that laws and regulations such as COPPA, GDPR, and CFAA offer protection, limitations persist. GDPR, for instance, only applies to European citizens, leaving others excluded. Moreover, these regulations often result in mere financial penalties, allowing tech giants to recuperate losses. The legal battles between tech giants primarily revolve around securing adept attorneys rather than addressing the crux of privacy concerns.

2. Methodology

This paper consists of exploratory research methods. The approach involves an analysis of existing literature on the latest developments of cyber privacy issues, trends, as well as countermeasures and approaches by government to counter risks affecting citizens privacy in the digital environment. The literature review analyzes relevant studies, papers and legislative measures addressing cyber privacy challenges. In the context of Albanian citizens and their current risks to online privacy, the methodology involves an analysis of the current situation of the social media trends and exposure and the legislative approach that the government of Albania apply to protect citizen private data. The study is focused on identifying key issues that should be addressed in the Albanian social media exposure and defining possible measures to address them. This paper aims to analyze what are the lags, trends and risks to the Albanian citizens in the cyber world, what should be improved and some conclusions on possible solution for addressing the challenges of online privacy for Albanian cyber citizens.

3. Analysis & Discussion on Albania's current situation

Albanian citizens do contribute a fair share on the global content of data which is generated, gathered, elaborated and stored in cyberspace. A big number of the content generated constitutes of private data. These data are as prone to be affected by cyberthreats as that of any other citizen of the world. The privacy of their data is constantly under attack from both public and private organizations. Their online privacy is also questioned because of its existence in a world of cookies, big data, smart cities, smart gadgets, social networks, online marketing and government surveillance. In such circumstances there is a need of concern on regard of their privacy, as well as the constant monitoring of their communications from various parties.

The usage of social network as free services, because Albanian citizens, as modern online customers expect to pay for nothing, it sure does come with a price. And this is no secret their private data, which the moment that it is generated digitally loses its properties as private and becomes a valuable public currency. That becomes valuable asset for the social network that uses such to convert to financial transaction in whichever form the business profit is designed. Valuable to mention in here is that as the other citizens all over the world even Albanians are

obsessed with social networks and in order to impress their online friends and followers, do post all kind of personal data, from pictures of themselves, their families, friends even ultrasounds of unborn babies, as well as plans for weekends, holidays and travel destinations. These trends not only bring negative on the physical and psychological area but increase the level of threat to their own online privacy.

People have the fake security state and belief because “the site has already taken security measures”, and they proceed to click on acceptance of a written agreement, which is in most cases never even skimmed upon. The Albanian citizens are not the only ones to do so, they are part of the majority group that are totally oblivious on what they are offering in compare of free lunch.

The apps they download and use their services for “free” on their daily basis are constantly running in the background and doing what they are designed to do in the first place. Those mobile apps residing on their smartphones they do know well their location, their routine, where they live, which coffee shop they do frequent, their workplaces, their commute, their holiday destinations and so on. They do have a good deal of information regarding their work email, their private email, or even their “secret email”, their id, nicknames, contact list, close friends, call history, pictures, videos, wireless passcodes, IP’s, even browsing history and habits. Most of the apps behave the same way, they collect data directly from the smart phone, and send it back to their mother datacenters, where it is stored, elaborated and made ready to be sold to the next customer. All the other bunch of apps who do not do so, either have a very poor, or a non-existent security layer deployed in it. It is also no secret that one of the worst of privacy offenders is Google, one of the key service providers for Android users, who have a great share in the smart phone users in the Albanian smartphone market. One example which will be treated this paper is their mail app, which freely goes through what citizens think is their private email looking for keywords that would target ads towards them. Unfortunately, it will not stop there but will make full use of the potential on its big bouquet of services. The list goes on not only with the services that this company has to offer “free”, but to all the companies that do offer such services in exchange of private data and information. The citizens that think that they are covered by the Commissioner’s Office are just wrong. First because to be obliged by Albanian law, the company must be established or have a child company on the boundaries of the Republic of Albania, and secondly all the Commissioner can do is fine Google if it breaks the law, but Google clearly doesn’t think that it is bound by that law. And even if the Commissioner does succeed to fine Google – the fine would be just useless. Even if Google does pay the fine, for sure will earn more than the maximum fine defined by Albanian law in less than an hour. The question that follows this last sentence is: what about the private data? – Well guess everybody knows the answer to that question.

As all the citizens of the world Albanian citizens also sometimes do give online service operators permission for some of their activities, but they never really understand on what extension their information will be stored, mined, elaborated, exchanged, and sold. There are also many cases where even though the citizens do continuous denial of consent, their information is still used in order to be exchanged for financial benefit by the service providers. Albanian citizens do not have the habit to buy licensed software. According to a report published in 2018 from BSA (Business Software Alliance) [33] in Albania 74% of software in use were unlicensed. This high rate of piracy is also an indicator of poor security level which computers used by citizens to do their daily online routine activities. This broadens the spectrum of people, or companies getting hold of data and information which is created, processed and stored in these machines. From script kiddies, free keyloggers, spyware, trojan, rootkit, or any malware that its developer has included lines of code to steal data from the machine infected, to the very sophisticated elite hacker groups or gang can profit and make use of those unprotected data. When security professionals do approach and pursue the citizens to

buy the licensed software in order to make use of the latest security patched issued by the respective companies, so that the data doesn't get exposed to risks often do get a vague question as a reply : - Why would a hacker want my data for in the first place? – well the answer to that question is already there.

4. Conclusions

In summary, the online privacy issue is poised to persist, triggering ongoing debates, discussions, and breaches. The conventional wisdom of refraining from sharing information online to protect privacy no longer applies in a digital landscape dominated by extensive personal and private data exchange. In this era, the currency for personalized services is private data. The changing definition of privacy in 2023 raises the pertinent question: will these challenges prompt a redefinition of data privacy as we know it?

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Competition in Albania's e-Procurement: A Comparative Study of Supplies, Works and Services.

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Abstract

Public Procurement concerns to the acquisition of products, services, and works by government entities from private ventures. Earlier research has pointed out a decline in competitive dynamics. This study aims to pinpoint which among the three categories in Albania has experienced the most significant decrease in competition between 2010 and 2022, as they collectively represent an expenditure of 5.47 billion Euros. A quantitative methodology was used to examine data sourced from the Public Procurement Agency over a comprehensive 13-year period, encompassing 33,064 contracts that attracted 137,050 offers.

The level of competition in public procurement significantly influences the equitable and efficient utilization of taxpayers' funds. Essential metrics for all three categories, such as the number of contracts, allocation of funds, average number of bids per tender, disqualified bids, and the prevalence of single versus multiple bid contracts, are thoroughly evaluated. In spite of heightened funding and an expanded contract portfolio, this research indicates a simultaneous surge in disqualified bids, resulting in a worrisome decrease in competition. This trend presents hurdles to cost efficiency, especially in light of the prevalence of single-bid contracts. Throughout the study duration, single-bid contracts accounted for 3.27 billion Euros, whereas multiple-bid contracts totaled 2.2 billion Euros.

Significantly, the research finds that Public Works, which command the most substantial portion of public expenditure and have experienced the most pronounced decline in competition, exert the most substantial adverse impact on taxpayers' funds.

Keywords: Public Procurement; Competition, Comparative Studies, Efficiency.

1. Introduction

Public Procurement (PP) is the process via which government purchases from the private sector. In 2020, PP constitutes 14% of GDP. Although prior research in Albania have delved into the competitive dimension of PP for Goods, Works, and Services individually, a comprehensive comparative analysis across these three categories is notably absent and becoming the scope of this study. Since the funds subject of this research aggregate to 5.47 billion Euros (2010–2022), it is the objective of this paper to determine: In which of the three categories of PP competition has the largest impact.

Many advocate that a fair and competitive procurement process serve as a bulwark against favouritism and monopolies. Because PP endeavors to achieve integrity, accountability, efficiency, equal opportunities, and equitable treatment of providers (Arrowsmith, Butler, La Chimia, & Yukins, 2021) and its effects are thoroughly noted in economy (Ghossein, Islam, & Saliola, 2018). PP is structured to be a competitive process.

Studies consistently demonstrate that the correlation between the number of bidders and contract costs is negative (Shrestha & Pradhananga, 2010) (la Cour & Ølykke, 2017), highlighting the cost-efficiency, that open competition has on PP. It also indicates that cultivating an environment that inspires free and open competition can make a substantial

contribution to the overall cost-efficiency of PP projects. **Hypothesis:** Albania should focus in increasing the competition of Public Works, more than Supplies and Services.

2. Methodology

To juxtapose the three categories of PP in Albania over the extensive 13-year study period (2010 – 2022) we employed a quantitative approach to determine which category has the largest impact on competition of PP. Our primary source of data was the Public Procurement Agency (PPA). To gauge the competitiveness within each category of PP, we took into account several crucial variables (yearly and total) such as: the numbers of bids; allocated funds; the number contracts; average number of bids per tender; etc.

After data collection, we conducted a rigorous data analysis and employed linear regression as a key analytical tool to determine trends. In order to compare this statistical tool of each category per each variable we employed the angular coefficient, which helped determine which of the categories is experiencing the most increase or decrease per each variable. The findings were validated by the coefficient of determination, implemented in the framework of a statistical software, with the formula:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad [1]$$

3. Results and Discussion

Upon scrutinizing the total PP expenditure over the past 13 years, we observed that Public Works accounted for the largest share of PP funds (64% or € 3.84 Billion), followed by Supplies (20% or € 1.21 Billion), and Services (16% or € 1 Billion). Given the substantial allocation of funds in each category, we endeavor to discern meaningful trends. The linear regression of each category for the Average Number of Submitted Bids demonstrates a downturn in all three categories of PP (2010-2022), as shown in Figure 1. When comparing categories with each other we determined that Public Works has the steepest decline (-0.26), compared to Services (-0.12) and Supplies (-0.11). Vis-a-Vis, competition in Public Works is declining more than the other two categories.

Figure 1: Avg. No. of Submitted Bids per category per year.
 Source: Author’s elaboration on the bases of PPA data.

After public entities disqualify some bids, we studied the trend lines of the Average Number of Qualified Bids per each category in Figure 2. Linear regression demonstrates a decrease in

all categories. It is evident that disqualifications have the greatest impact on Public Works (-0.19), followed by Services (-0.10) and Supplies (-0.10).

Figure 2: Avg. No. of Qualified Bids per category per year.
Source: Author’s elaboration on the bases of PPA data.

After scrutinizing disqualification of bids after initial evaluation, now we will focus our attention to Single Bidding tenders. Data analysis also shows an increase in the usage of Single Bidding in all three categories throughout the study period. Figure 3 demonstrates that Single Bidding is much more dominant in Public Works when compared to Supplies and/or Services.

Figure 3: Single Bids per category
Source: Author’s elaboration on the bases of PPA data

After analyzing Single Bidding in all three categories of PP, now we are going to scrutinize its effect on savings. Figure 4 shows that savings in Single Bidding for Public Works are lower than Supplies and Services. In other words, although Single Bidding decreases savings in all categories, its effect is more predominant in the category of Public Works.

Figure 4: Percentage (%) of savings per category.
Source: Author's elaboration on the bases of PPA data

Prior studies have established that decreased competition is associated with lower savings. In order to determine the level of correlation between the percentage (%) of savings incurred and the average number of bids submitted per tender, for each of the three categories, we used the coefficient of determination. R^2 for each category resulted in: Works 0.496; Supplies 0.242; Services 0.229. It is evident that in Public Works there is a stronger correlation of competition with savings.

4. Conclusions

Our comprehensive analysis sheds light on a notable decrease in competition across all categories of PP throughout the extensive 13-year study period. When making comparisons between the categories, it becomes apparent that the decline is particularly pronounced in Public Works. As a result, the observed decline in competition directly influences the potential for cost savings, which may not reach the anticipated levels.

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Modelling and Forecasting Foreign Citizens Arrivals in Albania using the Holt-Winter Exponential Smoothing Method

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Abstract

This study aims to forecast seasonal time series data, taking into account the Holt Winters multiplicative and additive forecasting models. The historical dataset in this study is monthly data on the number of arrivals of foreign citizens in Albania in the years 2016–2019. Source of data obtained is the official site of INSTAT. The results show that the Holt-Winters exponential smoothing methods for the number of citizens entering Albania from 2016 to 2019 contain trend patterns and seasonal patterns by first defining the initial values and smoothing parameters. The focus of this study is to determine the optimal approach and which approach method is best.

Keywords: Forecasting method, seasonality, Holt Winters, additive model, multiplicative model.

JEL codes: C15, C61

The Impact of Digital Marketing On Small & Medium Businesses in Albania

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Abstract

Digital marketing is the newest field of research that always aims to present strategic importance to businesses that have increasingly directed their efforts towards the electronic market. For a business, an online presence is not enough to be translated into marketing. This is a continuous process which consists of different types of digital marketing as well as a series of strategies that will be further evidenced in this paper. The main focus of the paper is further knowledge of digital marketing and what this type of marketing consists of. More specifically, the paper will start with what researchers say about this topic, the evolution of this type of marketing over the years, then with the theoretical treatment of the topic, highlighting the key points that tell us more about digital marketing strategies. Then the authors will analyse the results that have come from the development of the survey regarding the impact of digital marketing on small and medium businesses in our country and concluding with recommendations and references.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Success, Business, Strategy Impact

Online Safety and Penetration Testing Methods

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Abstract

This paper examines the increasing threat of cybercrime within the framework of technological advancements and its implications for cybersecurity. This study aims to provide an in-depth look at cybersecurity techniques, with a specific emphasis on the concept of penetration testing, which is widely recognized as ethical hacking. This technique, utilized by organizations, aims to identify and address system vulnerabilities. This article explores the theoretical basis of penetration testing, including its simulation of hacker behaviors, the tools often used in this practice, and the many stages involved in its development. A practical demonstration is doing scans on a web application, simulating real-world situations in order to expose weaknesses in the system. The paper underscores the significant effect of cyber-attacks on information, finances, and reputation, highlighting the crucial significance of cybersecurity for companies. The main focus of this study is to provide a comprehensive examination of different cyber risks, explore the defensive measures used to mitigate these threats, and emphasize the crucial role of penetration testing in enhancing the security posture of major companies and organizations.

Keywords: cyber security, online attack, ethical hacking, penetration testing, web application.

JEL codes: O30, O31, O32, O33, O34

1. Introduction

Throughout history, technology has experienced significant developments and progress, establishing its dominance on a worldwide level. This influence has profoundly affected lifestyles, reshaping the way people conduct everyday life. The integration of computers and the internet has significantly improved several processes, especially in the domain of communication. The adoption of the internet has given rise to a virtual communication domain known as cyberspace, where data is transmitted through cables, fiber-optic networks, or wireless means. The transmission of information inside the digital world exposes it to vulnerabilities, hence increasing the likelihood of unauthorized access, manipulation, or misappropriation of data. Cyberattacks are often recognized as the primary sources of threats that compromise the security of cyberspace. The increasing severity and frequency of online attacks may be attributed to the continual emergence of innovative tools and strategies. These attacks serve to gain unauthorized access to sensitive or confidential information by engaging in activities such as hacking, theft of personal data, and financial manipulation.

The objective of this article is to raise awareness about the importance of cybersecurity and to develop understanding and engagement in this crucial domain within the field of technology. Various security mechanisms often used in information technology systems include firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and antivirus applications, among other methods. Certain businesses strive to get deeper insight by comprehensively assessing the vulnerabilities that exist inside their network infrastructure. This can be accomplished through penetration testing, conducted by a security specialist who infiltrates the network and connected systems to pinpoint existing vulnerabilities. Penetration testing functions as a simulated reproduction of hacker activities when unauthorized access to a system is attempted. The fundamental objective of this process is to uncover any shortcomings present within a given system. This enables the

testing team to develop effective strategies for addressing these vulnerabilities and strengthening the security architecture of the organization. The RoyalFit website operates as a platform for both theoretical and practical demonstrations of penetration testing, showcasing the operational mechanisms of this approach and its significance as a protective measure for computer systems.

2. Methodology

Ensuring the security of data is a vital mission, even though it is a demanding one nowadays. Protecting becomes more challenging considering the high number of attack types (**Table 1** - The classification of cyberattacks). Some of the most dangerous and common attacks are viruses, worms, DoS attacks, DDoS attacks, ransomware, trojans, spyware, phishing, SQL injection, cross-site scripting (XSS), man-in-the-middle attacks, etc.

Table 1. The classification of cyber attacks

BASED ON PURPOSE	LEGAL CLASSIFICATION	BASED ON THE LEVEL OF INTERACTION	BASED ON SCOPE AND INTENT OF THE ACTIONS
Reconnaissance Attack	Cybercrime	Active attacks	Malicious attacks
Access Attack	Cyber espionage	Passive attacks	Non-malicious attacks
Denial of Service Attack	Cyber terrorism		

Source: Own calculations

Some of the most common protective measures are: anti-virus programs, firewalls, Intrusion Detection Systems, Intrusion Prevention System, Pretty Good Privacy, Secure Shell, Secure Electronic Transmission, Secure Sockets Layer, Wired Equivalent Privacy, Wi-Fi Protected Access, Network Address Translation, penetration testing.

Penetration testing is a method used by organizations to attack their own systems, aiming to identify their weaknesses and improve them in the near future. This way, they can protect their system in case of a real attack. Pentesting is done by ethical hackers, also known as white-hat hackers. Ethical hackers have good intentions and take legitimate actions, but they use the same methods as real black-hat hackers. The pentesting process is interphased, including reconnaissance, scanning, exploitation, and reporting.

Anyone among us navigates daily on various websites, the security of which we may not be certain (**Figure 1** – Contact form). In this project, a web application has been created that can belong to a random business (**Figure 2** - User data collected by the form). It has the http header, which means it is not encrypted, so when the user types their data in the form, it might be stolen or modified. In this study, it is demonstrated, the reconnaissance phase of the pentesting process, that occurs when the ethical hacker tries to gain information and find the weaknesses of the web application.

Figure 1. Contact form
Source: Own research

Figure 2. User data collected by the form
Source: Own research

The tests are conducted utilizing automated methods employing Nmap and OWASP Zap.

3. Results and Discussion

The Nmap test is done using two commands: `nmap -T4 -A -v` and `nmap -p 1-65535 -T4 -A -v`. As a result, it is evidenced that the public key is of the EC type and has a length of 256 bits. In addition, the server utilizes the SHA256WithRSAEncryption algorithm, and the utilized hash value is SHA-1: 664a726e4e4d84d87f01e82e767f4120f5451a18. The open TCP ports are: 80, 443, 8887, and 8889.

The OWASP Zap test is a general vulnerability scan that detected the absence of anti-CSRF tokens (risk level: moderate) and the absence of the CSP header (risk level: moderate) (**Table 2** – Vulnerabilities of the system).

Table 2. Vulnerabilities of the system

Alert type	Risk	Count
Absence of Anti-CSRF Tokens	Medium	1 (11.1%)
Content Security Policy (CSP) Header Not Set	Medium	22 (244.4%)
Application Error Disclosure	Low	1 (11.1%)
Cookie No HttpOnly Flag	Low	1 (11.1%)
Private IP Disclosure	Low	1 (11.1%)
X-Content-Type-Options Header Missing	Low	28 (311.1%)
Content-Type Header Missing	Informational	1 (11.1%)
Modern Web Application	Informational	2 (22.2%)
User Agent Fuzzer	Informational	84 (933.3%)
Total		9

Source: OWASP Zap

4. Conclusions

Nowadays, technology is related to everything, so the risk of cyberattacks is higher. Penetration testing is a comprehensive methodology used to identify vulnerabilities in a system that combines manual methods with automated tools, so it should be performed by professionals in the field. The ethical hacker who performs the pentest process must adhere to the legal agreement established with the organization. The absence of encryption makes the corruption of information easier, and the risk is even higher for companies that might suffer financial damage.

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Utilizing Big Data and Social Network Analysis for Cultural Tourism Planning in the Berat Region

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Abstract

In an innovative approach to cultural tourism planning, this research utilizes big data analytics and social network analysis to explore the potential of Berat, Roshnik, Peshtan, and Osumi Canyons in Albania. Harnessing the power of Google Trends, the study analyzes search data over January 2022 – October 2023, focusing on tourist interest in local attractions and activities. This analysis is enriched by employing social network analysis to model the connections between various tourism nodes, revealing insights into tourist preferences and movement dynamics. The findings highlight a significant interest in Berat's historical architecture and the natural allure of Osumi Canyons, with distinct seasonal trends peaking during spring and summer. A notable connection emerged between Berat and Osumi Canyons, suggesting an intrinsic tourism corridor, while Roshnik and Peshtan offered unique, complementary experiences. Based on these results, the study proposes a diverse tourism circuit that integrates these areas, emphasizing sustainable tourism and local cultural engagement. This research demonstrates the efficacy of big data and social network analysis in developing a comprehensive tourism plan. It underscores the role of technology in enhancing tourism experiences and supports the development of tourism strategies that are both sustainable and community focused.

Keywords: Cultural Tourism Planning, Big Data Analytics, Social Network Analysis, Sustainable, Tourism Development, Albanian Heritage Sites

JEL codes: C55, Q01, Z32

1. Introduction

Tourism is considered one of the most significant and rapidly expanding industries globally, employing many individuals and catering to many tourists. As a result, it substantially contributes to the global gross domestic product (GDP) (Gao & Wu, 2017). The rapid growth of rural tourism has promoted sustainable tourism in rural villages, which has positive effects on the preservation and rejuvenation of rural society and culture. The burgeoning field of cultural tourism underscores the need for innovative and effective planning strategies that can adapt to diverse geographical and cultural contexts (Blanco et al., 2009) This study extends the pioneering work of (I.-L. Hu et al., 2020), which utilized big data and social network analysis for tourism planning in Taiwan's Hakka villages, to a new setting: the culturally and naturally rich regions of Berat, including villages like Roshnik, Peshtan, and Osumi Canyons in Albania. These areas, characterized by their unique historical, cultural, and natural landscapes, present an ideal backdrop for exploring the efficacy of data-driven tourism planning. The research aims to demonstrate how technology, massive data analytics, and social network analysis can revolutionize tourism planning by providing deeper insights into tourist behaviors and preferences. This approach is particularly pertinent in Albania, where tourism is a growing sector with the potential for significant economic and cultural impact.

2. Methodology

Regarding data gathering for social network analysis, researchers can use social media and social network websites to discover tourist experiences when visiting destinations that align with their interests (Bokelmann & Lessmann, 2019; Dergiades et al., 2018). The research employed a two-pronged approach. **Big Data Analytics Using Google Trends:**

Data Collection: Search query data from Google Trends was compiled for January 2022-October 2023, focusing on keywords related to cultural and natural attractions, events, and activities in the four areas.

Data Analysis: Trends in search queries were analyzed to determine the popularity and seasonal fluctuations in interest for specific attractions and activities. This involved examining the frequency of searches, geographic origin of interest, and correlating these trends with local events or natural phenomena.

Social network analysis is appropriate for tourism planning that incorporates a network component. Social network analysis can provide valuable insights for analyzing tourism locations and organizations. When using social network analysis for tourism planning, evaluating the degree centrality, specifically the in-degree, and out-degree, can help to find any network structural gaps among the nodes using the constraint index (Chang, 2018; J. Hu & Zhang, 2017). **Social Network Analysis:**

Data Modeling: Using the search data, a social network model was constructed to represent the connections between various tourism nodes (e.g., historical sites, local festivals, and natural attractions).

Network Analysis: This model was analyzed to uncover the strength of connections between nodes, identifying key attractions and potential pathways for tourist movement across the four areas.

3. Results and Discussion

The extensive data analysis revealed several key findings. **Popularity and Seasonal Trends:** Berat's architectural heritage and Osumi Canyons showed high search frequencies, indicating strong tourist interest.

Seasonal analysis highlighted a surge in searches during spring and summer, aligning with local festivals and favorable weather conditions for outdoor activities.

Social Network Insights:

The network analysis illuminated a robust connection between Berat and Osumi Canyons, suggesting a natural axis for a tourism corridor.

Roshnik and Peshtan, while less connected in the network, offered unique attractions that complemented the overall tourism experience.

Discussion:

Based on these results, the study proposes a tourism circuit connecting the cultural and natural attractions of the four areas. This circuit is designed to offer a diverse experience, balancing historical exploration in Berat, wine tourism in Roshnik, artisanal exposure in Peshtan, and adventure activities in Osumi Canyons. The findings from big data and social network analysis guide the development of this circuit, ensuring it aligns with tourist interests and seasonal preferences.

Sustainability and Cultural Integration:

The study underscores the importance of sustainable tourism practices and the integration of local culture into the tourism experience. It advocates for community participation in tourism development, ensuring local economic benefits and preservation of cultural authenticity.

4. Conclusions

This extended analysis substantiates the application of big data and social network analysis in cultural tourism planning, offering a pioneering approach tailored for Berat, Roshnik, Peshtan, and Osumi Canyons. This study highlights the value of technological tools in enhancing the effectiveness of tourism planning and underscores the potential for such methodologies to contribute to sustainable and community-centric development. The proposed tourism circuit, driven by data insights, paves the way for a balanced tourism experience that Honors these regions' cultural integrity and natural beauty. Furthermore, this research sets a foundation for future investigations in cultural tourism, particularly in areas where tourism is burgeoning yet underexplored. It invites further studies to validate and refine big data and social network analysis use in different cultural and geographical settings. Additionally, it underscores the need to integrate local community perspectives and sustainable practices in developing tourism strategies, ensuring long-term benefits for tourists and residents.

This study's implications extend beyond Albania's immediate context, offering insights and frameworks that can be adapted globally. It encourages tourism planners and policymakers to embrace data-driven approaches, fostering tourism that is not only economically beneficial but also culturally enriching and environmentally conscious.

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Unraveling the Impact of Service Quality on Hotel Ratings: A Comprehensive Study of Hotels and Aparthotels in Vlore County, Albania

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Abstract

This study explores the influence of customer satisfaction metrics on hotel and apart-hotel ratings in Vlore County, Albania, using data from Booking.com. It delves into how service dimensions like staff, facilities, cleanliness, and overall scores, along with location and review volume, impact these ratings in the context of the digital hospitality industry. A quantitative approach was adopted, with non-probability sampling of 373 hotels and apart-hotels from Booking.com. The research primarily involved Spearman's Rank and Kendall's Tau correlation analyses and Kruskal-Wallis tests to examine relationships between overall scores, specific service metrics, and customer satisfaction indicators. The findings indicate a strong positive correlation between overall scores and key service aspects, with staff service, facility quality, cleanliness, and comfort significantly influencing ratings. Interestingly, free Wi-Fi, while important, showed a lesser impact. Additionally, the study found that both the number of reviews and location considerably affect guest perceptions, suggesting geographical factors play a role in shaping customer experience. These outcomes highlight the crucial importance of specific service dimensions in enhancing guest satisfaction and emphasize the need for tailored service improvement strategies in the hospitality industry. The study contributes to the broader understanding of customer satisfaction dynamics in the digital era and offers practical insights for service optimization in hotels and apart-hotels. In conclusion, this research enriches the theoretical discourse on digital hospitality, offering valuable implications for industry stakeholders and setting a foundation for future explorations in diverse accommodation settings and locations.

Keywords: customer satisfaction in hospitality, hotel ratings analysis, digital hospitality, service quality metrics, Vlore County tourism.

JEL codes: M31, D12, C81, L86

1. Introduction

This paper investigates the impact of customer satisfaction metrics on hotel and apart-hotel ratings in Vlore County, Albania, with a focus on data from Booking.com. It centers on how service dimensions affect these ratings, taking into account factors like location and review volume. The study is crucial for understanding customer satisfaction in the digital realm of the hospitality industry and aims to offer insights for service improvement in Vlore County's evolving hospitality landscape. Hospitality is a key element in tourism industry. The expansion of digitalization in opinion-making and information sharing, facilitated by the Internet, allows for diverse perspectives in consumer behavior and decision-making in hospitality and tourism. Netnography (Gewinner, 2023) provides valuable insights in this domain. The significance of digital technology in Albanian tourism, particularly the growth of "smart tourism" features, is highlighted in the study (Gjika & Pano, 2020). Furthermore, an investigation (Anagnostopoulou, Buhalis, Kountouri, Manousakis, & Tsekrekos, 2020) examines the trends observed in online guest reviews on Booking.com. It sheds light on the association between

favorable review themes and improved financial performance of hotels, thereby making a valuable contribution to the body of knowledge regarding the influence of online reputation. Research (Ramosacaj & Kushta, 2023) evaluates statistics on the number of tourists and GDP in Albania from 2016 to 2022 and concludes that economic growth and tourism demand are favorably correlated. Seasonal variations in tourist lodging satisfaction are shown by differing levels of satisfaction between peak and off-peak months, according to an analysis of TripAdvisor data (Pjero & Gjermëni, 2020). This shows that the number of tourists has an impact on the quality of service provided. Moreover, a multitude of studies (Mariani & Borghi, 2020; Olorunsola, Saydam, Lasisi, & Eluwole, 2022; Anagnostopoulou, Buhalis, Kountouri, Manousakis, & Tsekrekos, 2020; Stefko, Fedorko, Bacik, & Rigelsky, 2020; Shabankareh, Nazarian, Seyyedamiri, Jandaghi, & Ranjbaran; Fu, Wei, Wang, & Kim, 2022; Egresi, Puiu, Zotic, & Alexandru, 2019) have examined data obtained from diverse hospitality platforms. These studies have examined a wide range of topics, including online reputation management, environmental discourse, customer experience management, factors that influence traveler loyalty, service quality assessment, and overall guest satisfaction. This study aims to thoroughly analyze customer satisfaction dynamics and their effect on hotel ratings in Vlore County. It examines the correlation between overall scores and specific satisfaction metrics—staff, facilities, cleanliness, comfort, value for money, location, and free Wi-Fi—and investigates how these are influenced by service quality dimensions, location, and review volume. The research addresses whether there is a significant correlation between overall scores and service aspects, how service quality dimensions impact ratings, and if ratings differ based on hotel location or review quantity.

2. Methodology

The present study utilized a quantitative research methodology to examine trends and characteristics of hotel ratings in Vlore County, Albania, with a specific emphasis on data obtained from Booking.com. The research was designed for statistical analysis of numerical data to identify patterns in customer satisfaction and service quality as reflected in Booking.com scores. A non-probability sampling method was used, utilizing administrative records from Booking.com. The sample consisted of hotels and aparthotels in Vlore County listed on the platform. These entities, forming the study's population, were evaluated based on user-provided scores. Data collection occurred on December 1, 2023, through specific filters on Booking.com, yielding information on 373 hotels and aparthotels. Each entity's hotel name, address, overall score (score number), number of reviews, and category ratings (staff, facilities, cleanliness, comfort, value for money, location, and free Wi-Fi) were recorded. The scoring system, on a scale of 1 to 10, is detailed on the booking platforms (Booking.com, How guest reviews work, n.d.) and (Booking.com, Everything You Need to Know About Guest Review Scores, n.d.). Twelve entities with incomplete ratings were excluded, resulting in a final sample of 361. Notably, 77 entities lacked free Wi-Fi scores. To maintain dataset integrity without discarding significant data, multiple imputation techniques were applied (Sterne, Carlin, Royston, & Carpenter, 2009), especially due to the non-normal distribution of data as indicated by the Shapiro-Wilk test (Royston, 1995). Data analysis was performed using R software (R Core Team, 2023), starting with descriptive statistics to understand the dataset's central tendency, dispersion, and shape. Relationships between overall scores and category ratings were examined using Spearman's rank and Kendall's tau correlation analyses (Sprent & Smeeton, 2007; Conover, 1999). Comparative analysis included location-based comparison and grouping by review count ('Low' (1–50 reviews), 'Medium' (51–200 reviews), and 'Very High' (501+ reviews)). Kruskal-Wallis tests (Hollander, Wolfe, & Chicken, 2015) determined if rating differences between groups were statistically significant. In all statistical tests, the level of statistical significance used is 0.05. The study acknowledges certain limitations. The

use of non-probability sampling from Booking.com may not fully represent all accommodations in Vlore County. Reliance on user-provided scores might introduce response bias, and employing multiple imputations for missing free Wi-Fi data, despite preserving data integrity, relies on assumptions that might not reflect actual values. The focus on Vlore County in a specific period limits the findings' applicability to other regions or timeframes, especially concerning location and review volume's impact on ratings.

3. Results and Discussion

The study's descriptive analysis (Table 1) indicates high guest satisfaction across various service categories, with data showing higher ratings and a concentration around the mean, especially in staff service. Review count distribution varied significantly, reflecting disparities in hotel visibility and popularity.

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of categories, and Shapiro-Wilk p-values.

Category	Mean	Median	SD	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Shapiro-Wilk p-value
Score Number	8.57	8.7	0.76	0.59	-2.09	11.14	2.39e-16
Reviews	199.89	135	217.67	47380.75	2.16	6.27	1.62e-21
Staff	9.03	9.2	0.73	0.53	-2.59	17.05	1.16e-18
Facilities	8.56	8.6	0.73	0.53	-0.64	0.36	1.12e-06
Cleanliness	8.94	9.1	0.68	0.47	-1.06	1.30	6.43e-12
Comfort	8.90	9.0	0.71	0.50	-1.07	1.14	3.12e-12
Value for money	8.62	8.8	0.72	0.52	-0.90	1.00	4.76e-10
Free Wi-Fi	8.80	9.0	1.24	1.54	-1.82	5.25	2.89e-19

Source: Own calculations

The analysis shows that staff performance, cleanliness, and comfort are strengths in the evaluated hospitality establishments, with room for improvement in facilities and value for money, reflecting high guest satisfaction and the need for maintaining service standards. The Shapiro-Wilk test results (Table 1) for each category non normality distribution.

Figure 1, The Spearman's Rank and Kendall's Tau correlation matrices.

Source: Own research

The Spearman's Rank and Kendall's Tau correlation analyses (see Figure 1) reveal significant insights into the interrelationships among various hotel service quality variables. The analysis, employing the Kruskal-Wallis test (Table 2), shed light on the nuances of service quality in hotels and aparthotels. This paper's data clearly indicates a strong positive correlation between overall scores and individual service aspects like staff service, facility quality, cleanliness, and comfort in hotels and aparthotels in Vlore County. This aligns with the findings of the study

(Stefko, Fedorko, Bacik, & Rigelsky, 2020), which underscores the significant impact of hotel equipment and cleanliness on sentiment polarity. However, this study reveals that free Wi-Fi, contrary to study's (Khan, Khan, Israr, & Zardari, 2020) indication of the non-significant impact of tangible elements (except Wi-Fi), exhibited a relatively lesser but still notable impact on overall evaluations. The high satisfaction levels across various service areas, as evidenced by the central tendencies and distribution shapes, highlight a strong guest experience in the establishments studied. This consistency is observed in the study (Chang, Liu, Xu, Li, & Hsu, 2020), which suggests that luxury hotels enhance customer satisfaction by prioritizing staff training, room cleanliness, and location selection. The authors' findings extend this understanding to a broader range of hotels and aparthotels, emphasizing the importance of these factors across different categories of accommodations. Notably, this study identified the influence of the number of reviews and location on guest perceptions and ratings, which was significant in certain service areas. This finding echoes the study (Gunasekar & Sudhakar, 2019), which discovered that location significantly boosts ratings, and further corroborates research (Ilieva & Ivanov, 2014), highlighting the growing importance of user-generated content in travel decision-making. Additionally, research in (Castro & Ferreira, 2018) indicates that factors like category, location, and facilities positively impact hotel rates, suggesting a complex interplay between service quality dimensions and economic aspects.

Table 2 Kruskal-Wallis's test results of ratings by review groups and location.

Category	Results by Review Groups			Results by Location		
	Kruskal-Wallis Chi-squared	df	p-value	Kruskal-Wallis Chi-Squared	df	p-value
Score Number	1.156	3	0.7636	28.731	15	0.01741
Staff	0.22779	3	0.973	32.627	15	0.005284
Facilities	2.2931	3	0.5139	20.269	15	0.1618
Cleanliness	1.3336	3	0.7212	26.971	15	0.02897
Comfort	1.6583	3	0.6462	19.742	15	0.1821
Value for money	0.67296	3	0.8795	37.304	15	0.001142
Free Wi-Fi	9.0374	3	0.0288	18.516	15	0.2365

Source: Own calculations

This study contributes to the theoretical understanding of customer satisfaction in the digital hospitality industry by highlighting the interconnected nature of service quality dimensions and the influence of location and review volume on guest experiences. For stakeholders in Vlore County's hospitality industry, the findings emphasize the importance of a holistic approach to improving service quality and tailoring strategies to regional-specific guest needs. However, limitations in sampling and data sources should be considered, and future research may explore a wider range of accommodations and causal relationships between service dimensions and satisfaction.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this investigation revealed a strong positive correlation between overall scores and individual service aspects like staff service, facility quality, cleanliness, and comfort. Surprisingly, Free Wi-Fi showed a lesser but significant impact on overall evaluations. High satisfaction levels across service areas indicate a robust guest experience. The study contributes to understanding customer satisfaction in the digital hospitality industry, bridging theoretical gaps and providing insights for service improvement in Vlore County's evolving hospitality landscape. It highlights the interconnected nature of service quality dimensions and the role of location and review volume in shaping guest perceptions. Acknowledging limitations, future

research can explore diverse accommodations, incorporate multiple platforms, and investigate causal relationships and cultural factors in different contexts.

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Investment Opportunities in Kosova Tourism

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Abstract

Kosovo as country with a favorable climate and situation, surrounded by high mountains, with many rivers and lakes, thermal water springs, and cultural and historical heritage, is among the countries with significant natural, cultural and human resources for development of tourism. Given that a sheer number of our compatriots live and work abroad who are also the supporters of family economies in Kosovo, there can be strategies for them to invest in their homeland. Their investments in Kosovo would be important for the development of Tourism, and also decreasing the rate of unemployment.

The purpose of this study is to compare the number of visitors during the first nine months of 2022 and 2023 and to point out various opportunities for direct investments in tourism, the identification and analysis of policies and strategies for foreign investments in tourism and setbacks that affect development of tourism in Kosovo. In this paper we used the quantity methodology, and an explorative and evaluative research. The results of this paper are very impressive after comparing the number of tourists who visited Kosovo during the last two years and can be of purpose to stir up investments in tourism.

Key words: investment, employment, tourism, compatriots, strategy

1. Introduction

“Tourists are those people who travel to foreign countries on holidays, out of curiosity, recreation, activities, business, etc., who travels to the countries where their organizers have previously visited”.¹

A place can be a tourist place if: tourists visit that place, if services intended for tourists are offered (guided tours) and if there is proper local infrastructure to welcome tourists (hotels, restaurants, night clubs, etc.) (Andreea Antonescu, 2018)

The Republic of Kosovo has an area of 10,905 km², situated in the center of Balkan Peninsula, with an inconstant Mediterranean climate, continental climate and mountain climate (Kastrati, Q. 2023, pg.62), surrounded on the North, South and West with high mountains, with many rivers and lakes, cultural-historical heritage and most importantly, with human resources (the youngest population in Europe), present superficial data for foreign investments in Tourism.

Hospitality is a distinguished quality of people in tourism (Musa Gashi, 1986). Kosovo is a tourist destination with two main particularities, very hospitable people, a hospitality which originates from our traditions and delicious traditional food. One of the direct impacts of tourism on the economic structure in touristic countries is also creating jobs in this sector (Doko, Dh, Draçi, Bilal, 2002).

The purpose of this paper is to point out the increase in the number of foreign and local visitors during the period from January to September in 2023 compared to the same period in 2022.

¹ From the definition for “tourist” in Émile Littré’s dictionary

Some of the reasons to invest in Kosovo in the field of tourism are: numerous investment opportunities, there is a law on tourism which defines the principles, standards and basic rules for the sustainable development and promotion of tourism, which is a good argument for all foreign investors, particularly investments from diaspora.

Since the remittances from Kosovo Albanian emigrants are increasing every year (about 3 billion euros for 2022)², there should be also more advantages so that investments from emigrants in tourism can increase.

2. Methodology

The methodology used in this paper is the quantity methodology; the research is an explorative and evaluative research. We used the most applicable software in statistics (Ms Excel and SPSS)

We have collected and analyzed data on foreign visitors in Kosovo and their overnight stays during 2022 (January-September 2022) (Table 1.)

Table 1. Comparison of foreign visitors during
2022 and 2023

Months	Visitors 2022	Visitors 2023	Percents2023/2022
January	16620	22743	36.8
February	15279	19723	29.1
March	18004	36066	100.3
April	18812	21208	12.7
May	20402	26138	28.1
June	25885	29317	13.3
July	38409	46566	21.2
August	42972	45711	6.4
September	25424	34038	33.9
Total	221807	281510	26.9

Source: ASK, Autors's calculations

Source: Autors's calculations

² Central Bank of Kosovo

Table 2. Comparison of nights of stay during
2022 and 2023

Months	Nights of stay 2022	Nights of stay 2023	Percents 2023/2022
January	29663	37069	25
February	23634	35505	50.2
March	30274	74035	144.5
April	31425	45556	45
May	34118	54370	59.4
June	47974	47974	0
July	91706	101755	11
August	82442	93083	12.9
September	44004	70850	61
Total	415240	560197	34.9

Source: ASK, Autors's calculations

Source: Autors's calculations

3. Results and discussion

We made a comparison of the visitors who visited Kosovo from January 2022 to the end of September 2022 and January 2023 to the end of September 2023. The results are: there were more foreign visitors in the first nine months of 2023 than in the same months in 2022 for 26.9%, while there were 34.9% more overnight stays in 2023 than in 2022.

4. Conclusion

Referring to the increased number of foreign visitors in 2023 compared to 2022 (this increase also includes local visitors and the increase started years ago), we can conclude that Kosovo has tourist resources and is a place where one can invest in tourism. Also, comparing the remittances of emigrants over the years, it is evident that they (remittances) are increasing; we can conclude that their investments can also be oriented to the tourism economy.

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Application: Think Kosova

Modeling and Forecasting Tourists' Arrivals in Albania

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Abstract

This article aims to accurately predict the number of tourists visiting Albania, recognising tourism's critical role in economic growth. Forecasting future tourism demand benefits governmental bodies and stakeholders, facilitating informed development strategies. This paper focuses on constructing the most reliable model for projecting Albania's tourist numbers for five years, employing and examining monthly data from 2016 onward.

We evaluated the outcomes of several fundamental seasonal forecasting methods, including naïve, Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA), and Exponential Smoothing, all implemented within the R programming language. The SARIMA model, which accounts for data seasonality, yielded the most precise forecasts.

Keywords: tourism, forecasting, time series, R, SARIMA

Navigating the Future: AI-Driven Transformations in Western Balkans Tourism

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Abstract

This paper explores the intersection of tourism and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Western Balkans (WB) region. It delves into the potential impact of AI on various facets of the tourism industry, from customer experiences to destination management. Through a comprehensive analysis, it aims to provide insights into how the integration of AI technologies can enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the WB as a tourist destination.

Keywords: AI-driven tourism, Western Balkans, Competitiveness, Sustainability.

JEL codes: Z32

1. Introduction

The Western Balkans (WB) is a region in Southeast Europe, consisting of countries with diverse cultural, historical, and natural attractions. The tourism landscape of this area can be considered multidimensional and include:

A rich historical and cultural heritage with influences from various civilizations, including Roman, Ottoman, and Austro-Hungarian mentioned in UNESCO World Heritage Sites (UNESCO, 2023), such as Butrint's archaeological site and Historic Centres of Berat and Gjirokastra in Albania, the Medieval Monuments in Kosovo, Dubrovnik Old Town in Croatia, the Historic Centre of Ohrid in North Macedonia, and the Mehmed Paša Sokolović Bridge in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Natural beauty with diverse landscapes ranging from pristine Adriatic and Ionian coastlines to mountainous terrains with national parks and lakes. Some of the most notable natural attractions in this area include the Glacial Lakes and Lush Forests of Rrajca in Albania, Plitvice Lakes National Park in Croatia, Tara National Park in Serbia, and the Bay of Kotor in Montenegro.

A growing popularity of adventure tourism activities, including hiking, rafting, and zip-lining in the mountainous regions, such as adventure parks in Peja and Rugova (Kosovo), rafting activities in Osum and Vjosa rivers (Albania), and hiking paths from Valbona to Theth (Albania). Another much-loved destination is the Tara River Canyon in Montenegro, which is one of the deepest canyons in Europe and attracts adventure enthusiasts.

Coastal Tourism with picturesque coastal areas along the Adriatic and Ionian Seas offering beach resorts, historical towns, and vibrant nightlife, such as the following prominent coastal destinations of Dubrovnik (Croatia), Budva (Montenegro), and Saranda (Albania).

Numerous cultural events, music festivals, and traditional celebrations that attract both local and international visitors, such as the noteworthy examples of Sunny Hill Festival in Pristina (Kosovo), Exit Festival in Novi Sad (Serbia), and the Sarajevo Film Festival in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

A hospitality culture known for warmth and friendliness, and culinary delights with diverse and delicious cuisine influenced by Mediterranean, Ottoman, and Central European flavors.

While the region has immense tourism potential, challenges such as infrastructure development, marketing, and regional cooperation persist. Efforts to overcome these challenges and capitalize on the unique offerings of each country are essential for sustainable tourism growth. As emerging trends, WB has an increasing interest in sustainable and responsible tourism practices and the adoption of digital technologies, including online booking platforms and destination marketing through social media.

The global tourism industry is undergoing a profound transformation fueled by advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI). In an era characterized by unprecedented technological innovation, AI is emerging as a pivotal force shaping the way travelers plan, experience, and reflect on their journeys. This paradigm shift is not only altering the dynamics of customer engagement but also revolutionizing operational efficiency for businesses within the tourism sector. AI, a branch of computer science that enables machines to simulate human intelligence, has found multifaceted applications in the tourism industry. From personalized customer interactions to optimizing backend operations, AI technologies are redefining the entire travel ecosystem. As we delve into the intricate intersection of AI and tourism, it becomes evident that the adoption of these technologies is not merely a trend but a strategic imperative for businesses seeking to stay competitive and responsive to the evolving needs of modern travelers. While witnessing the global tourism industry undergo a radical adoption of cutting-edge technologies, the WB stands out as a region ready for a nuanced exploration of the diverse implications of AI. The convergence of rich cultural heritage, varied landscapes, and a flourishing tourism sector calls for a closer look at the intricate relationship between traditional allure and the innovative potential inherent in AI applications. As destinations worldwide incorporate AI into their tourism strategies and frameworks, understanding its unique impact on the WB becomes essential.

This study seeks to unravel the rationale behind delving into the AI landscape within the WB tourism sector, exploring how this fusion of tradition and technology can shape the region's competitiveness and sustainability. Through an in-depth analysis, we aim to navigate the complexities, challenges, and opportunities arising at the intersection of AI and the distinctive tourism offerings of this area. The comprehensive review of the literature highlights the multifaceted applications of AI within the tourism domain, providing insights into the transformative potential and key trends that characterize this dynamic intersection.

One prominent domain of AI influence lies in enhancing customer experiences throughout the tourism journey. Personalization, facilitated by machine learning algorithms, has become a cornerstone of AI applications. Studies by Xiang et al. (2017) and Li et al. (2017) underscore the role of AI in tailoring travel recommendations, optimizing user interfaces, and elevating overall satisfaction. The incorporation of chatbots and virtual assistants further exemplifies the commitment of the industry to provide seamless, AI-driven interactions (Buhalis & Leung, 2018).

Beyond customer interactions, AI contributes significantly to destination management and operational efficiency. Neuhofer et al. (2015) emphasize the role of AI in optimizing resource allocation, crowd management, and predictive analytics for sustainable tourism practices. This dimension is particularly pertinent for the WB, where balancing preservation and accessibility is a critical consideration.

The literature also delves into the broader societal implications of AI integration in tourism. Discussions by Gretzel et al. (2015) shed light on the necessity of robust policy frameworks to govern the responsible adoption of AI technologies. Additionally, ethical considerations, including privacy concerns and societal impacts, have been highlighted as critical dimensions requiring attention in the era of AI-driven tourism.

While AI is gaining momentum globally, regional disparities in adoption rates and strategies are evident. The WB, with its distinctive cultural and economic landscape, necessitates a nuanced understanding of these disparities.

2. Methodology

The methodology adopted for this paper involves a comprehensive and iterative approach that synthesizes existing knowledge, draws on best practices in AI governance and incorporates insights from academic literature and industry reports. The primary goal is to provide a foundation for policymakers, industry leaders, and stakeholders to navigate the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the tourism sector of the WB responsibly. The methodology encompasses an extensive literature review of academic literature, reports, and case studies related to AI applications in the global tourism industry for understanding the current state of AI in tourism and identifying best practices and challenges, to emphasize ethical considerations, sustainable practices, and the role of AI in enhancing destination competitiveness by giving recommendations tailored to the WB context.

3. Results and Discussion

Through the analysis of the existing literature, we identified key trends and advancements in AI relevant to the tourism industry such as:

1. **Personalization and User-Centric AI:** Studies by Wang et al. (2018) and Sun et al. (2020) elaborate on AI algorithms facilitating tailored travel recommendations and user interfaces. This trend revolutionizes how tourists engage with services, delivering a more personalized and enriching travel experience.
2. **Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Conversational AI:** The utilization of NLP in chatbots and virtual assistants is highlighted by Li et al. (2018) as integral to enhancing customer interactions. This capability improves customer engagement, making communication more streamlined and user-friendly in the tourism sector.
3. **Predictive Analytics for Smart Destination Management:** Research by Gao et al. (2019) demonstrates how AI-driven predictive models optimize resource allocation and enhance overall operational efficiency, contributing to a more proactive and adaptive tourism experience.
4. **Integration of AI in Sustainable Tourism Practices:** Zhang et al. (2021) highlight how AI's analytical capabilities contribute to minimizing the environmental impact of tourism activities. This trend aligns with the global shift towards responsible tourism, positioning AI as a key enabler for sustainability in the tourism sector.
5. **Emerging Technologies: Blockchain and AI Synergy:** Yasin et al. (2020) discuss the complementary nature of blockchain's transparency and security with AI applications, addressing concerns related to data privacy and security in the tourism sector. This intersection represents a promising avenue for future research and development.

To explore how the WB measures up against other global destinations we did a comparative analysis, and the results show while some regions are swiftly embracing AI to revolutionize their tourism sectors, the WB stands at a unique crossroads, blending traditional charm with technological innovation. In destinations like Singapore and Dubai, renowned for their avant-garde approaches to tourism, AI has become integral to smart city initiatives and visitor experiences. Singapore employs AI in waste management and urban planning, optimizing the overall tourist experience (Yeoh & Zhang, 2020). Dubai, on the other hand, utilizes AI to enhance visitor engagement and streamline energy consumption in hotels and attractions (Ali et al., 2019). In the WB, where historical and cultural richness meets a burgeoning tourism industry, AI adoption appears to be gaining momentum. As exemplified by initiatives in

Barcelona and Amsterdam, where AI is employed for crowd management and sustainable tourism practices, the WB has the opportunity to leverage AI for both cultural preservation and sustainable tourism growth (Díaz et al., 2018; Gretzel et al., 2015). An AI-powered platform can be used to analyze users' past travel behavior, preferences, and real-time data to curate personalized itineraries for the region. Factors considered can include historical sites, cultural events, and outdoor activities. Furthermore, a conversational AI chatbot, accessible through mobile apps and websites, can provide instant information on local attractions, dining recommendations, and travel tips. It can use NLP to understand user queries and deliver contextually relevant responses. Another step can be the Augmented Reality (AR) Integration, which can offer immersive experiences to bring historical sites to life. This kind of AI-driven tourism results in enhanced user satisfaction and improved operational efficiency, with tourists feeling more connected to the regions offerings and human resources freed up from routine queries handled by AI assistants.

4. Conclusions

Overall, the WB offers a mosaic of experiences for travelers, combining history, natural beauty, and vibrant cultural traditions. The region is working to position itself as a competitive and sustainable tourist destination in the global market. By contextualizing the incorporation of AI within the unique tourism landscape of the WB, this research endeavors to contribute valuable insights to both academia and industry stakeholders, fostering a holistic understanding of the region's trajectory in the ever-evolving realm of AI-driven tourism.

As we reflect on the prospects that lie ahead, it becomes clear that the transformative impact of AI has the capacity to reshape the tourism sector, offering a path toward sustainability, resilience, and global competitiveness. The promise of AI in WB tourism lies in its ability to create personalized and memorable experiences for visitors while optimizing destination management practices. Through predictive analytics, smart resource allocation, and the promotion of sustainable tourism initiatives, AI becomes a catalyst for positive change. It has the potential to elevate the region as a forward-thinking and technologically advanced destination, attracting a new generation of conscious travelers seeking immersive, authentic, and responsibly curated experiences.

However, this transformative journey is not a solitary endeavor. It requires a collective commitment from all stakeholders involved in the tourism ecosystem of the WB. A call to action resonates across governmental bodies, private enterprises, local communities, and technology innovators to collaborate in harnessing the benefits of AI for sustainable and competitive tourism.

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Interaction Design Component in E-Government and M-Government Systems

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Abstract

E-government has become the primary tool through which governments deliver services to their citizens. These systems have become part of the society structure and a communication norm between the government and citizens. In developing countries, e-government systems are a central part of the digitalization strategy to fast-track economic development. M-Government is a subcategory of E-Government systems that is concerned with providing services through the use of mobile devices, mainly smartphones. The objective is to deliver services regardless of time and place as long as the citizens can access the platform. The adoption of E-Government and M-Government Systems in developing countries has faced many issues that have delayed the process of digital transformation. Through an exploratory literature review, this paper will explore if usability is one of the challenges that developing countries face and evaluate the impact of the Interaction Design discipline during system development.

Keywords: interaction design, usability, e-government, m-government, developing countries

1. Introduction

E-government can be described as providing government services from state and local institutions through information and communication technology. OECD (2003) defines *e-government* as the use of information and communication technologies, particularly the Internet, as a tool to achieve better government. E-government focuses on service delivery through ICT and should be distinct from e-governance, which focuses on encouraging, empowering, and engaging citizens. (Calista & Melitski, 2007).

During the years, E-government systems have had to adapt to the continuous change in ICT. The introduction of smartphones as a more convenient computing device, together with the increase in their computing power, created the conditions for expanding m-government as a sub-channel that provides e-government services through mobile technologies.

Interaction Design (ID) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) are two related disciplines that study how users use digital products but are concerned with different aspects. NASA defines HCI as combining computer science, psychology, and design. Dix (2009) describes it as studying how computer technology influences human work and activities.

For Sharp et al. (2019), ID is the practice of designing interactive products to support the way people communicate and interact in their everyday and working lives. Both fields are interrelated, but while the former is a broader field concerned with the impact of digital products, the latter focuses more on creating artifacts and interfaces to use. An essential element of both the HCI and ID field is the concept of "usability."

The efforts to define usability started many years ago, during the beginning of the HCI discipline. One of the first propositions was that "usability" should be described as a

combination of two elements: a product's ease of use and acceptability. (Bevan et al., 1991). Furthermore, the proposition emphasizes that it should be defined for a particular class of users, carrying out specific tasks and in specific environments. (Bevan et al., 1991)

Sharp et al. (2019, pp. 19-20) break down usability into six goals: effectiveness, efficiency, safety, utility, learnability, and memorability. These goals serve as questions when a product is in development and turn into usability criteria once it starts to be implemented.

The scope of this paper is to understand the challenges that developing countries face during the implementation of E-Government and M-Government systems and identify if usability is among this group. Furthermore, the study intends to identify components of the Interaction Design discipline that are related to usability and its impact during the development of E-Government/M-Government systems. For this paper, it is used an exploratory review. The methodology is described in detail in the following section.

2. Methodology

In this study it is used an exploratory literature review to answer the question: Is usability one of the challenges developing countries face when implementing e-government and m-government systems? What impact can the Interaction Design discipline have during system development to mitigate the usability problem?

For this exploratory review, the authors have determined five primary keywords to select publications for review: e-government, m-government, usability, interaction design, and developing countries. In addition, five secondary keywords closely related to the first ones were used to broaden the scope of the research: e-services, mobile systems, applicability, human-computer interaction, and emerging economies.

Google Scholar and Research Gate were the leading search engines, combined with affiliate institution scientific databases on related fields. The sources used included academic journals, conference proceedings, books, and online resources. For further investigation, based on relevance to research questions, only publications in the last five years were selected, except for publications regarding definitions and terminology.

Furthermore, the selected publications needed to focus on case studies for developing countries. For categorizing a country as developing, the Human Development Index (HDI) developed by UNDP was considered indicative.

3. Results and Discussion

Changes in technology will always create challenges regarding usability. Implementing E-government / M-government in developing countries has had several challenges, including (but not limited to) Technological Development, Available Budgeting, Privacy Concerns, Digital Literacy, and Legal Framework. The term usability does not appear often in selected publications but is inferred by its relation to readiness, training, education, and accessibility. Interaction Design as a research field has identified potential issues and solutions regarding the usability of E-Government systems. Possible solutions include (but are not limited to) progressing design, single page interface, task-oriented design, learning interface, and limitations of features on mobile screens.

The research has its limitations primarily due to the selected approach. Exploratory literature review is a rigid methodology compared to other alternative approaches and the selected sample is relatively narrow. Furthermore, there was a variability in the digital products

mentioned in publications regarding time and technology. A systematic literature review with a more significant sample should be more appropriate for future research, combined with user analysis of selected digital products for further investigation on the Interaction Design discipline.

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Dynamics of Retrieval Augmented Generative Techniques in Tourism-Oriented Search Engine Information Queries

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Abstract

The field of tourism is rapidly growing and presents unique challenges in managing its data. This article explores these challenges and reviews the use of advanced language processing models, particularly focusing on a customized model named 'TourBERT'. TourBERT is tailored for understanding and handling the specific types of data found in tourism, such as customer preferences and trend analyses. It showcases how adaptable these language models can be, especially in processing and interpreting large and diverse sets of data in tourism.

Alongside TourBERT, we also examine a method known as 'Retrieval Augmented Generation' (RAG). This method blends powerful language generation models with techniques to efficiently find and use relevant information. It is especially useful in situations where the available data is plentiful and varied, which is often the case in the tourism industry.

The purpose of our article is to highlight how these advanced language models, like TourBERT and the RAG method, can be valuable tools in analyzing and utilizing data in tourism. We provide a detailed look at both these approaches, aiming to guide future research and practice in tourism data management, and to underline the significant benefits these models can bring to the field.

Keywords: Tourism Data, Language Large Models, TourBERT, BERT Models, Retrieval Augmented Generation, Data Challenges in Tourism.

1. Introduction

In today's world, where data is as common as the many travel destinations it describes, the tourism industry faces both great opportunities and significant challenges. Our paper, "Challenges for Data Analysis in the Tourism Sector," dives into this industry to understand its complexities better. We look at the various challenges related to data and how advanced technology can help overcome these.

The tourism sector deals with a lot of different types of data, like customer preferences, feedback, booking details, as well as the latest market trends and economic conditions. There's a lot of data to manage and analyze, and it's important to use this information to grow the business and improve the experiences offered to customers.

One major challenge is just how much data there is, and how varied it can be – from social media posts to customer inquiries. To really benefit from this wealth of information, we need advanced tools that can sort through it all and find useful insights that can help shape business strategies and make operations more efficient.

Another key issue is the need for quick data processing. The tourism industry is always changing, with trends, preferences, and market conditions that can shift rapidly. Being able to quickly process and act on this information is essential to stay competitive and meet customer expectations.

Understanding and predicting what customers will want is also a big challenge. The industry needs to not only serve a global audience with different tastes but also predict their needs in

advance. This often means analyzing lots of customer interactions and feedback, which can be difficult to do.

There are also challenges in bringing together data from different sources. The tourism industry involves many different players – like hotels, travel agencies, airlines, and attractions – and it's challenging to create a single, unified view of all this data.

Concerns about data privacy and security are extremely important, especially in a time when data breaches are uncommon, and protecting client information is a top priority. The global nature of tourism and different data protection laws around the world add to these challenges. Language and cultural differences also pose challenges in providing services that are both linguistically accurate and culturally sensitive.

Finally, there's an increasing need to focus on sustainable and responsible tourism. This means monitoring data related to environmental impacts, benefits to local communities, and ethical practices to promote sustainable tourism.

In this paper, we will explore how advanced technologies, like tailored Language Large Models (LLMs) such as TourBERT and Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) methods, offer promising ways to address these complex data challenges. Using these technologies, the tourism industry can better navigate and succeed in this data-rich environment.

2. Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative methodology, exploring the multifaceted data challenges in the tourism sector and the potential of advanced computational models to address these issues. The methodology is based in an extensive review of existing literature and case studies, coupled with an in-depth analysis of technological advancements in data processing and analysis. The primary research question guiding this study is: "How can fine-tuned Language Large Models (LLMs) and Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) approaches effectively address the data analysis challenges in the tourism sector?"

3. Results and Discussion

The implementation of Language Large Models (LLMs) in the tourism sector has demonstrated substantial potential in managing the complex data landscape. These models have shown proficiency in processing and interpreting large volumes of diverse data sources prevalent in tourism. For example, the analysis of customer reviews and social media posts through LLMs can bring valuable insights into customer preferences and market trends, significantly aiding businesses in understanding and adapting to dynamic market conditions. Moreover, the ability of LLMs to process data in multiple languages and dialects can be specifically addressed in LLMs in bridging language barriers, enhancing customer engagement across different regions. This multilingual capability is especially beneficial in the globally interconnected tourism industry.

However, our research identified challenges in the application of LLMs, such as the risk of model bias and the general nature of these models. The potential for these biases, if not taken care of, could hinder the effectiveness of LLMs in providing culturally sensitive and accurate insights.

Enhancing Effectiveness through Fine-Tuning

In response to the limitations of general LLMs, the research explored the impact of fine-tuning these models for the tourism sector. Fine-tuned models, such as TourBERT, have shown a marked improvement in understanding the unique nuances of the tourism industry. These models have been more effective in analyzing industry-specific patterns, leading to more accurate predictions and insights.

The training of TourBERT on a large, domain-specific corpus is a testament to the effectiveness of fine-tuning. This approach has allowed for a more nuanced understanding of linguistic features and cultural contexts in tourism-related texts, which general language models may overlook.

Challenges in Fine-Tuning and the Introduction of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)

Despite the advancements with fine-tuned LLMs, challenges in data collection, owning data and the need for continuous updates emerged. To address these challenges, our research presents a well-known approach to data augmentation, the concept of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG). RAG combines the generative capabilities of LLMs with advanced retrieval techniques, providing a more contextually aware and responsive solution.

The implementation of RAG in document processing and knowledge search has shown promising results, especially in improving the relevance and timeliness of responses. However, challenges such as low precision in retrieval and the potential for biased responses remain concerns that need to be addressed for effective implementation.

Integrated Approach: Combining fine-tuning with RAG

Our proposal of an integrated approach combining the strengths of fine-tuned models (notably following the example of TourBERT) and RAG aims to leverage the deep contextual understanding of fine-tuned LLMs with the dynamic data retrieval capabilities of RAG. This solution is designed to address the multifaceted data challenges in the tourism sector comprehensively.

The integration allows for the continuous updating of insights processed by the LLMs with real-time data from RAG. This ensures that user interactions are not only contextually rich but also reflect the most current information. Personalization and content generation can significantly benefit from this integrated approach, offering highly tailored customer experiences and industry-specific content that is both current and factually accurate.

Furthermore, this approach effectively handles multilingual and cultural nuances, a critical requirement in the global tourism industry. The combination of TourBERT's language capabilities with RAG's access to culturally specific, up-to-date information forms a culturally aware response system.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the integration of fine-tuned LLMs with RAG presents a potent solution to the complex data challenges in the tourism industry. This integrated approach promises to enhance real-time data processing, personalization, and crisis management, making it an invaluable tool in the rapidly evolving tourism sector. However, implementing this approach involves addressing challenges in integration complexity, resource optimization, data privacy, and continuous learning. Future research and development in this area will be crucial for realizing the full potential of this innovative approach in transforming data analysis and decision-making in tourism.

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The role of Artificial Intelligence in Cyber Security

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Abstract

This research paper is dedicated to the role of artificial intelligence in cyber security. The development of technology, in the last decades in an exponential manner, has been accompanied in parallel with cyber security risks and threats. The evolution of Artificial Intelligence, integrated as a crucial component among smart devices or technological equipment's has increased the exposure against malicious activities.

The role of cyber security, to guarantee security through defense mechanisms against cyber threats, now faces a new challenge as threat actors will try to take advantage of Artificial Intelligence. The objective of this research is to analyze the role of AI in cyber security and to identify the number of cyber incidents closed by AI investigation and decisions through automation in Albanian government cyber space.

Quantitative methodology is used for this research, focused on collecting, testing, and measuring numerical data. All the data that has been analyzed it is correlated from governmental cyber space, where the combination of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence it is used by Security Operations Centre team and Cyber Incident Response team in order to mitigate cyber-attacks.

Analyzing all the information gathered, data coming from devices, computers, networks, user behaviors and malicious activities by threat actors, more than 60% of cyber incidents are being closed by AI.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Cyber Security, Machine Learning, Government Cyber-Space, Cyber Incidents

1. Introduction

The scope of this research, referring to the extent of the study, falls under Albanian government cyber space boundaries. Albanian government it is constantly targeted by adversaries which tend to gain access in the systems. All the actors, from cyber espionage to the last year destructive cyber-attack¹, use the latest techniques and sophisticated tools to reach their objectives. In order to defend against complex and highly skilled hackers, Artificial Intelligence helps with automation and mitigation. AI is used by hackers and cyber-security teams for different purposes.

Data is correlated and digested into a single platform, Sentinel SIEM (Security Information Event Manager), analyzing all the logs that come from computers, users, software's, security platforms etc. Sentinel as the centralized platform for all the data, through Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence records specific patterns for each event that is created. If abnormal activity or unusual logs rise, it immediately triggers an alert or incident based on the customized playbooks and notebooks created from NAIS cyber incident response team. As the objective was to identify the percentage of actions and incidents solved by AI, it was seen that after

¹ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/security/blog/2022/09/08/microsoft-investigates-iranian-attacks-against-the-albanian-government/>
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analyzing the data provided through Sentinel, more than 60% of incidents were closed automatically.

Quantitative methodology was used for the research, focused on collecting, millions of signal and numerical data. As per the status quo of 60%, with the improvement of AI code and ML, the objective on the upcoming year would be to reach at 80-90% to at least have an investigation done by Artificial Intelligence and actions to be taken by human interaction.

2. Methodology

In this research was used Quantitative methodology, focused on collecting, testing, and measuring numerical data. All the data that has been analyzed it is correlated from governmental cyber space, where the combination of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence it is used by Security Operations Centre team and Cyber Incident Response team in order to mitigate cyber-attacks.

Incidents created by severity over time

Events and alerts over time

3. Results and Discussion

Several techniques already implemented into the playbooks and notebooks which are tailored by AKSHI-s Security Operation Team and Incident Response team are detected from Artificial Intelligence. Immediately a certain malicious pattern is detected, the user session is revoked and he or her is forced to log out. In the photo below an illustration of anomalous token technique was revoked, this technique is one of the latest that threat actors use to bypass advanced security solutions.

NAIS-Sentinel, automated actions

After filtering all the events and incidents which were responded and mitigated by automation as a pillar of AI, it was stated that more than 60% of all cyber incidents are treated and successfully closed by AI.

4. Conclusions

Artificial intelligence now is already present in many fields including government, education, health, cars industry and transportation.

Cyber incident response, led by humans it is no longer possible to keep up with the speed, scale and sophistication of automated cyber-attacks.

The need for more sophisticated technologies is emerging with defenders turning their efforts to

guarding against AI-powered attacks and by enabling AI integrated in their defenses.

As a need to handle and react to sophisticated attacks, Albanian government uses AI to react to more than 60% of incidents.